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Solutions of Nonlinear PDEs: Variational and Topological Approaches

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- [CS2] Anna Maria Candela, Kanishka Perera and Caterina Sportelli, On a class of supercritical N -Laplacian problems, *Nonlinear Anal. Real World Appl.* **71** (2023), article 103817
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- [CS10] Addolorata Salvatore and Caterina Sportelli, On existence and multiplicity of solutions for generalized (p, q) -Laplacian equations on unbounded domains (*submitted for publication*)
- [CS11] Flavia Esposito, Laura Selicato and Caterina Sportelli, Theoretical aspects in penalty hyperparameters optimization, (*submitted for publication*)
- [CS12] Giovanni Molica Bisci, Kanishka Perera, Raffaella Servadei and Caterina Sportelli, Nonlocal critical problems with jumping nonlinearities, (*preprint*)

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Abstract

This thesis collects many new results obtained via variational and topological techniques for different types of nonlinear partial differential equations which present quite challenging structures. The relevance of the problems handled here relies upon the fact that they outline the mathematical wording which many significant physical, chemical and biological phenomena are governed by.

More precisely, not only we state new existence and multiplicity results for partial differential equations and/or systems which are semilinear, quasilinear (local and non-local) or of relativistic type, but also we provide several new abstract theorems which turn out that cannot be fit in proper tangible models or physical situations, but are of significant interest in current pure mathematical research.

Questa tesi contiene diversi nuovi risultati di esistenza e molteplicità per diverse tipologie di equazioni alle derivate parziali nonlineari. I teoremi qui presentati sono dimostrati mediante l'utilizzo di argomenti variazionali e tecniche topologiche. La rilevanza dei risultati conseguiti risiede anche nel fatto che molti dei problemi affrontati rappresentano la corretta formulazione matematica di fenomeni e processi fisici, chimici e biologici.

Più precisamente, l'obiettivo raggiunto è duplice: da un lato proviamo nuovi risultati di esistenza e molteplicità per equazioni alle derivate parziali semilineari, quasilineari (sia di tipo locale che non-locale) e relativistiche; dall'altro dimostriamo anche nuovi risultati di natura puramente astratta che, anche se non si collocano in alcun modello o situazione fisica, sono di rilevante interesse per la moderna pura ricerca matematica.

Introduction

This thesis collects many new results obtained via variational and topological techniques for different types of nonlinear partial differential equations which present quite challenging structures. As will be detailed in a little while, this work deals with partial differential equations and/or systems which are semilinear, quasilinear (local and nonlocal) or of relativistic type.

As the large number of problems taken into account here may seem untied at a first glance, it is worth to emphasize how they are linked together. In fact, the common thread of this thesis is not only to gather new existence and multiplicity results for the aforementioned kinds of PDEs availing of the proficiency of variational and topological methods, but also place them into a proper applicative perspective. Indeed, besides the purely mathematical interest, our choice in the study of a so wide range of problems is significantly motivated by their applications. In fact, the relevance of the problems handled here relies upon the fact that they outline the mathematical wording which many significant physical, chemical and biological phenomena are governed by. Nonetheless, we warn the reader that also many results presented here rely upon several new abstract theorems which turn out that cannot be fit in proper tangible models or physical situations, but are of significant interest in current pure mathematical research.

To shed light on the different models of PDEs we deal with, on the difficulties they are affected by and the different employed strategies, we have preferred to present all the results in three separate parts, for an entirety of twelve chapters.

Up to a few exceptions imposed by the need to introduce at first some already known theorems or theories (we refer to Chapters 1 and 9), the results exhibited here are entirely new and are mainly outlined in the twelve papers listed before this introduction. Nonetheless, with the idea of a constant improvement of our results, in Chapter 1 we choose to present the needed abstracts results in a way which differs from the published papers, providing actually a new abstract theorem which could be valuable for our investigations to come.

This thesis consists of three parts. Here we just point out the main topics of each argument while, in order not to weigh down this introduction with too many details, we refer the interested reader to the brief discussions which come with each chapter.

In Part I we study the existence of one or more solutions for quasilinear elliptic problems whose principal part is affected by the occurrence of some coefficients depending on the solution and its gradient themselves.

The close bond between existence of critical points and solvability of Euler–Lagrange equations is now a fact and for functionals defined as

$$J(u) = \int_{\Omega} \mathcal{A}(x, u, \nabla u) dx \quad u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega),$$

with Ω open bounded subset in \mathbb{R}^N , a wide number of papers can be referenced about critical points which are minimizers (see e.g [79, 121, 144]). Besides variational problems whose solutions correspond to minima, there is a broad variety of cases of differentiable functionals where one looks for critical points different from minima. This can happen either because the functional is not bounded from below (or from above), or because the minimum exists, but it corresponds to a trivial solution so it is not relevant for the problem, or because other critical points may exist besides the minimum (see e.g. [7, 83, 160, 177]). In those cases, one of the most used tools is the Ambrosetti–Rabinowitz Mountain Pass Theorem (see [12]). Besides geometrical assumptions, it demands also the well known Palais–Smale condition. Unluckily, the differentiability fails to hold even in very simple cases. For example, the functional

$$J(u) = \int_{\Omega} A(x, u) |\nabla u|^2 dx, \quad u \in H_0^1(\Omega),$$

with $0 < \alpha \leq A(x, t)$, $|\partial_t A(x, t)| \leq \beta < \infty$ is not Gâteaux differentiable in its domain but is differentiable only along the directions of $H_0^1(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ even for a smooth function $A(x, t)$. In order to solve both the lack of regularity and some difficulties linked to the Palais–Smale condition which occur in this case, different approaches have been used. For instance, Arcoya and Boccardo have introduced in [20, 21] the definition according to which $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ is a critical point of J if

$$\langle J'(u), v \rangle = 0 \quad \forall v \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$$

and have derived a general min–max result applicable to functionals which are not differentiable in all directions.

Here, following the ideas developed in the pioneering papers [52, 53], we take into account the case in which the functional J is restricted to the intersection space

$$W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega).$$

It is a Banach space equipped with the norm given by the sum of the usual norms of $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and $L^\infty(\Omega)$ and it is continuously embedded in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Our choice is motivated by the fact that some classical growth hypotheses make quite natural to prove that our functional is of class C^1 in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$. Moreover, in this setting

the Palais–Smale condition or its Cerami variant, requires also the L^∞ –convergence. Actually, such a claim is too much, so a weaker condition has been introduced in [53], which we recall here in Chapter 1.

Several previous works (see e.g. [52–55]) deals with existence and multiplicity results for single equations whose principal part involves coefficients depending on the solution and its gradient themselves. But, in many applications of interest there may be two or more interacting quantities (for instance, populations of two or more species, parts of a whole and so on) which depend upon each other. When the amount or size of one quantity depends in part on the amount of another, and vice versa, they are said to be *coupled* and it is not possible or appropriate to model each one separately. In these cases we write models which consist of systems of partial differential equations.

For that reason, we investigate the existence of one or more weak bounded solutions for the class of coupled gradient–type quasilinear elliptic systems with homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions given by

$$(S) \begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(a_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i)) + A_{i,t}(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) = G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) & \text{in } \Omega, i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \\ \mathbf{u} = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases}$$

with $m \geq 2$ and $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_m) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ an unknown vector function, where $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ is an open bounded domain and some functions $A_i : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, and $G : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exist such that

$$A_{i,t}(x, t, \xi) = \frac{\partial A_i}{\partial t}(x, t, \xi), \quad a_i(x, t, \xi) = \left(\frac{\partial A_i}{\partial \xi_1}(x, t, \xi), \dots, \frac{\partial A_i}{\partial \xi_N}(x, t, \xi) \right)$$

if $1 \leq i \leq m$ and $\nabla_{\mathbf{u}}G(x, \mathbf{u}) = (G_1(x, \mathbf{u}), \dots, G_m(x, \mathbf{u}))$, i.e.,

$$G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial u_i}(x, \mathbf{u}) \quad \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq m.$$

Also, we consider the particular model derived by taking $m = 2$, $A_1(x, t, \xi) = \frac{1}{p_1}A(x, t)|\xi|^{p_1}$ and $A_2(x, t, \xi) = \frac{1}{p_2}B(x, t)|\xi|^{p_2}$ with $p_1, p_2 > 1$. So, (S) reduces to the coupled quasilinear elliptic system

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p_1-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p_1}A_u(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p_1} = G_u(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ -\operatorname{div}(B(x, v)|\nabla v|^{p_2-2}\nabla v) + \frac{1}{p_2}B_v(x, v)|\nabla v|^{p_2} = G_v(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = v = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases}$$

As pointed out before, in our setting classical abstract theorems such as the statements in [12, 27] cannot be applied, since the functional related to problem (S) (as well as to the model one) satisfies neither the classical Palais–Smale condition nor its Cerami’s variant (see, for example, [54, Example 4.3]). Hence, using the arguments introduced in [53], we apply the abstract Theorems 1.2, 1.3 and 1.4 by taking advantage of the interaction between two different norms. Then, we prove the existence of at

least one solution (see Theorems 2.1, 2.3, 3.1 and 3.4) of infinitely many distinct ones under the additional assumption that our functional is even (see Theorems 2.2, 2.3, 3.2, 3.3 and Corollaries 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 3.1).

With respect to the coefficients introduced, roughly speaking we assume that $A(x, u)$ and $B(x, v)$ are C^1 -Carathéodory, bounded on bounded sets, greater than a strictly positive constant and interact properly with their partial derivatives. Here, $G(x, u, v)$ is assumed to be a C^1 -Carathéodory function and satisfies an Ambrosetti-Rabinowitz type condition. We point out that we address those problems not only in the case in which $G(x, u, v)$ has a suitable subcritical growth, but we can manage also the definitely more challenging cases in which $G(x, u, v)$ has a supercritical growth, in the sense described in Remarks 3.7 and 3.8. On this matter, we point out that we provided an existence result also in the even more mild case of a N -Laplacian problem with a nonlinear term governed by the Trudinger-Moser inequality. We refer the interested reader to Chapter 3 for a wider and detailed discussion of this challenging case.

The remaining chapter tabled in Part I is devoted to the study of

$$-\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}A_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p + V(x)|u|^{p-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N,$$

and its more comprehensive formulation leads by the generalized (p, q) -Laplacian equation

$$\begin{aligned} & -\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}A_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p - \operatorname{div}(B(x, u)|\nabla u|^{q-2}\nabla u) \\ & + \frac{1}{q}B_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^q + V(x)|u|^{p-2}u + W(x)|u|^{q-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \end{aligned}$$

where $1 < q \leq p \leq N$, $A, B : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are C^1 -Carathéodory functions with $A_t(x, u) = \frac{\partial A}{\partial t}(x, u)$, $B_t(x, u) = \frac{\partial B}{\partial t}(x, u)$, $V, W : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are suitable potentials in the sense discussed in Chapter 4 and $g : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Carathéodory function.

Our study is motivated by the fact that many examples of the aforementioned problems are related to the existence of solitary waves for the quasilinear Schrödinger equation

$$iz_t = -\Delta z + V(x)z - h(|z|^2)z - \Delta(l(|z|^2))l'(|z|^2)z \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (0.0.1)$$

where $V : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a given potential, $l, h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are real functions and the solution $z = z(x, t)$ is a complex function in $\mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R}$ which portrays several physical phenomena such as the self-channeling of a high-power ultrashort laser, or also some problems which arise in Plasma Physics, Fluid Mechanics, Mechanics and in the Condensed Matter Theory (see the introduction at Sections 4.1 and 4.3 for a deeper discussion about the physical situations covered by those considered equations). By means of approximation arguments on bounded sets, we prove the existence of a nontrivial weak bounded solution, while the multiplicity result, which is completely new also even in the simplest case $q = p$, is gained under symmetry assumptions and a sharp decomposition of the ambient space.

The relevance of those latter results leans on the fact that, for the first time, we are

able to provide existence and multiplicity results for those challenging problems in the whole \mathbb{R}^N , without limiting ourselves to the search of radial solution as done in [58]. This brings new problems closer to those arising from real-world situations applications, which we aim to formulate and investigate.

On the other hand, Part II deals with the study of some local and nonlocal (and mixed local and nonlocal) critical elliptic problems. The first chapters are related to the study of critical elliptic problems with jumping nonlinearities

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = bu^+ - au^- + |u|^{2^*-2}u & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases}$$

where Ω is a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 4$, $2^* = 2N/(N-2)$ is the critical Sobolev exponent, $a, b > 0$, and $u^\pm = \max\{\pm u, 0\}$ are the positive and negative part of u , respectively.

The notion of a jumping nonlinearity introduced and studied by Fučík is one of the most important tools in dealing with, for instance, the mathematical models of suspension bridges proposed by Lazer and McKenna (see [109]) and investigated by Drábek in [96]. In fact, in [96], boundary value problem with jumping nonlinearities are provided to explain large oscillations of the bridge in the following simplifying assumptions: the bridge is assumed to be one-dimensional, vibrating beam, supported above by cables whose restoring force due to elasticity is proportional to u^+ . Also, the model does not concern with a critical growth.

Back to our problem, to start we observe that when $a = b = \lambda$, this problem reduces to the well-known Brézis-Nirenberg problem (see [48]). It is worth noting that the arguments given in [48, 64] (see also [13, 77]) cannot be used to obtain nontrivial solutions for our problem. In fact, the asymptotic problem associated with our problem is nonlinear and therefore its solution set is not a linear subspace of $H_0^1(\Omega)$ when it has nontrivial solutions (we refer the interested reader to the introduction of Chapter 5 for a deeper discussion). In order to overcome this difficulty, we prove that the variational functional associated with our problem admits, depending on the location of the point (a, b) in the plane, certain linking structures based on a splitting of $H_0^1(\Omega)$ into nonlinear submanifolds. In order to capture these linking geometries, we prove several generalizations of the classical linking theorem of Rabinowitz [160] that are not based on linear subspaces. Then we will use these new linking theorems to obtain nontrivial solutions of our problem when (a, b) lies in certain regions of the plane.

The developed abstract results are of independent interest and can be applied to investigate the existence of nontrivial solutions for more general problems with jumping nonlinearities involving nonlocal operators like the fractional Laplacian. In fact, we employ them also to investigate the existence of nontrivial solutions to the nonlocal critical growth elliptic problem with a jumping nonlinearity

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = bu^+ - au^- + |u|^{2_s^*-2}u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases}$$

where Ω is a bounded Lipschitz domain in \mathbb{R}^N satisfying the exterior ball condition, $(-\Delta)^s$ is the fractional Laplacian operator defined on smooth functions by

$$(-\Delta)^s u(x) = 2 \lim_{\varepsilon \searrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_\varepsilon(x)} \frac{u(x) - u(y)}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dy, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N,$$

$s \in (0, 1)$, $N > 2s$, $2_s^* = 2N/(N - 2s)$ is the fractional critical Sobolev exponent, $a, b > 0$, and $u^\pm = \max\{\pm u, 0\}$ are the positive and negative parts of u , respectively. It is worth noting that the nonlocal case is more challenging than the local one. In fact, unlike what happens in the local case, many technical difficulties due to the nonlocal nature of our problem arise in the proofs. For that reason, we can establish so far the existence of nontrivial solutions in the nonlocal case only when (a, b) is below the lower curve and $N \geq 4s$. Nonetheless, we are confident we can obtain a similar result as in the local case when (a, b) are above the upper curve (see Theorem 5.2) but when $N > 2(\sqrt{2} + 1)s$. Moreover, we think we can provide the existence of a nontrivial solution also when $2s < N < 4s$, widening the results obtained by Servadei and Valdinoci in [169–172].

We conclude Part II tying up to the ending chapter of Part I, but this once studying a problem involving the fractional (p, q) -Laplacian operator. To be more precise, we prove a multiplicity result for the critical non local problem

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)_p^s u - \mu (-\Delta)_q^t u = \lambda |u|^{p-2} u + |u|^{p_s^*-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases}$$

where Ω is a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N with Lipschitz boundary, $0 < t < s < 1$, $1 < q < p < N/s$, $(-\Delta)_p^s$ is the fractional p -Laplacian operator defined on smooth functions by

$$(-\Delta)_p^s u(x) = 2 \lim_{\varepsilon \searrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_\varepsilon(x)} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^{p-2} (u(x) - u(y))}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dy, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N,$$

$p_s^* = Np/(N - sp)$ is the fractional critical Sobolev exponent, and $\lambda, \mu > 0$ are parameters. Our multiplicity result also holds in the limiting case $s = 1$, where the previous problem reduces to a mixed local and nonlocal problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta_p u - \mu (-\Delta)_q^t u = \lambda |u|^{p-2} u + |u|^{p^*-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases}$$

where $0 < t < 1$, $1 < q < p < N$, $\Delta_p u = \operatorname{div}(|\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u)$ is the p -Laplacian of u , $p^* = Np/(N - p)$ is the critical Sobolev exponent, and $\lambda, \mu > 0$ are parameters. Mixed local and nonlocal problems are a subject of recent intensive investigation as local and nonlocal interactions are ubiquitous in many physical and biological systems. Recent results by Biagi, Dipierro, Valdinoci, and Vecchi [40–42] have given many new inquiries into problems involving mixed operators, resulting in several results related to qualitative behaviour of solutions, their regularity and related variational principles.

The main result we provide concerns the existence of two nontrivial weak solutions. Here, a new phenomenon emerges: there exist two nontrivial weak solutions, one with negative energy and the other with positive energy, for all sufficiently small values of a parameter. Our proof is based on an abstract result obtained in [151].

Finally, following our study of non-differentiable functionals addressed in Part I, we study in Part III the T -periodic solutions both of the relativistic Lorentz force equation

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1-|q'|^2}} \right)' = E(t, q) + q' \times B(t, q), \quad (0.0.2)$$

with the electric and magnetic fields, respectively E and B given by

$$E = -\nabla_q V - \frac{\partial W}{\partial t}, \quad B = \text{curl}_q W,$$

and of the relativistic scalar pendulum-type equation

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1-(q')^2}} \right)' + q = G'(q) + h(t), \quad (0.0.3)$$

when they involve singular terms. In fact, we assume that $V : [0, T] \times (\mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{0\}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $W : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$, $G : \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $h \in L^1(0, T)$.

Lorentz force equation models the motion, in a relativistic regime, of a slowly accelerated charged particle under the influence of an electromagnetic field. The relativistic nature of equation (0.0.2) turns out in its left hand side, which involves the relativistic momentum introduced by Poincaré in [156], with the velocity of light in the vacuum and the charge-to-mass ratio normalized to one, for simplicity. Instead, the presence of an electromagnetic field is emphasized by the Lorentz force $E(t, q) + q' \times B(t, q)$ in its right hand side.

By introducing the diffeomorphism

$$\phi : B(0, 1) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3, \quad \phi(v) = \frac{v}{\sqrt{1-|v|^2}},$$

in a more geared mathematical literature, left-hand side of (0.0.2) is entitled as singular ϕ -Laplacian (see [37]).

It is well known that (0.0.2) represents one of the most significant equation of Mathematical Physics (see e.g., [102]) and it is a topic of several classical textbooks concerning Physics and Electrodynamics (see e.g. [112, Chapters 5, 12]), [117, Chapter 12] and [123, Chapter 3]. One of the main reasons is that the proper mathematical framework for it was established only recently and their applications to (0.0.2) scarcely occur in the last decades.

In fact, a rigorous mathematical variational approach for its study was developed recently in [18, 19] (see also [36] for the case $B \equiv 0$) where the maps V and W are assumed to be of class C^1 . We point out that these interesting mentioned results cannot handle the open problems of the relevant cases including configurations of electric

fields coming from the physical models and consisting of singular electric potential. Motivated by these arguments, we develop the variational framework needed to address equation (0.0.2) and other relativistic singular problems as well, establishing the landmark for future investigations related on these topics. To be more precise, we show not only that equation (0.0.2) can be studied using a variational approach even when the electric field E is singular, widening the range of possible choices of V and covering the case untreated in [18, 19]; but also, we prove that the topological argument carried on in [107] can be employed in such a way to handle other kinds of relativistic problems in which appears a singular term.

As a first step to study (0.0.2) variationally, we derive a new version of the Mountain Pass Theorem, which has its own interest and allows one to identify critical points of functionals which possess singularities (see Theorem 9.1). Anyway, we refer the interested reader to Chapters 9 and 10 for a detailed discussion about our approach. Finally, the last Chapter 11 is motivated by the study of the spherical pendulum addressed in [9]. We employ again Theorem 9.1 to derive the existence of a T -periodic solution of (0.0.3). To be more precise, we improve the results in [9] and derive new existence results both in the case $h \neq 0$ (see Theorem 11.1) and $h \equiv 0$ (see Theorem 11.2). Finally, we use the global continuation theorem to address equation (0.0.3) but assuming that there exists $c_0 > 0$ such that $G'(q)q$ is bounded from below by the function $c_0/|q|$ when q is in a neighborhood of the origin.

Lastly, it is worth pointing out that our research has taken a further direction, too. In fact, we have recently investigated the chance to employ some abstract variational tools to handle machine learning algorithms. As reporting the results achieved would have demanded also the introduction of prerequisites arising from numerical analysis and machine learning, in order not to overload this thesis too much, we made the choice not to include here the paper [CS11]. Also, as the presented result finds some of its strengths in the blending between pure and numerical analysis, it is worth highlight that our contribution in this project clearly comes with the abstract variational part. However, we limit ourselves to a brief discussion concerning our motivations and the ideas developed in [CS11].

Training a Machine Learning (ML) algorithm is quite important to produce data-driven models, which can be successfully applied in real life applications. These processes often require to specify several variables by the users, namely hyperparameters, which must be set before the learning procedure starts. Hyperparameters govern the whole learning process and play a crucial role in guaranteeing good model performances. As previously mentioned, they are often manually specified, and the lack of an automatic tuning procedure makes the field of Hyperparameter Optimization (HPO) an ever-evolving topic. In a supervised learning scenario, HPO can be addressed through a bi-level formulation. This approach looks for the hyperparameters such that the minimization of the regularized training leads to the best performance of the trained data-driven model on a validation set. The best hyperparameters for a data learning task can be selected as the solution of a suitable minimum problem (see [103, 183] for more details). To overcome the difficulties in ensuring the theoretical assumptions when real data domains are considered, our work extends existence and uniqueness theorems for the solution of the hyperparameters bi-level problem to the more general

framework of infinite dimensional Hilbert space. Some theoretical results applicable in all those situations when it is unnecessary or not possible obtaining an exact minimizer are outlined. Then, an iterative algorithmic strategy is considered, equipped with a stopping criterion via Ekeland's variational principle, which allows us to build an approach based on solid mathematical foundations useful for future extensions and generalizations to other problems, too.

All the results in this thesis are not selfcontained and we are pretty confident that they can be enhanced and expanded, as well as our new abstract results will be the starting point for many of the investigations to come, some of which are already underway.

Notation

- $\mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, \dots\}$ the set of the strictly positive integers;
- Ω open subset of \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 2$;
- $B_R(x) = \{y \in \mathbb{R}^N : |y - x| < R\}$ the open ball with center in $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and radius $R > 0$;
- $B_R = B_R(0)$ the open ball with center in the origin and radius $R > 0$;
- $|D|$ the usual N -dimensional Lebesgue measure of a measurable set D in \mathbb{R}^N ;
- c_i and/or d_i any strictly positive and each time different constant;
- ω_{N-1} the area of the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^N ;
- $\alpha_N = N\omega_{N-1}^{1/(N-1)}$ the best constant for the Trudinger–Moser inequality;
- $N' = N/(N - 1)$ the Hölder conjugate of N ;
- $|\cdot|$ the standard norm on any Euclidean space;
- $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_m)$, $\mathbf{u}_n = (u_1^n, \dots, u_m^n)$, $\mathbf{0} = (0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{R}^m$;
- $\{\mathbf{e}_j : 1 \leq j \leq m\}$ the standard basis of the Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^m , i.e., \mathbf{e}_j has components $e_i^j = \delta_i^j$;
- for $m \in \mathbb{N}$, $m \geq 2$, for short we replace

$$\sum_{i=1}^m \quad \text{with} \quad \sum_i \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^m \quad \text{with} \quad \sum_{j \neq i}.$$

- $(L^r(\Omega), |\cdot|_{\Omega,r})$ the classical Lebesgue space with norm

$$|u|_{\Omega,r} = \left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^r dx \right)^{1/r} \quad \text{if } 1 \leq r < +\infty;$$

- $(L^\infty(\Omega), |\cdot|_{\Omega,\infty})$ the space of Lebesgue-measurable essentially bounded functions endowed with norm

$$|u|_{\Omega,\infty} = \operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} |u|;$$

- $W^{1,p}(\Omega)$ the classical Sobolev space equipped with the standard norm

$$\|u\|_{\Omega} = (|\nabla u|_{\Omega,p}^p + |u|_{\Omega,p}^p)^{\frac{1}{p}} \quad \text{if } 1 \leq p < +\infty;$$

- $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ the classical Sobolev space equipped with

$$\|u\|_{\Omega} = (|\nabla u|_{\Omega,p}^p + |u|_{\Omega,p}^p)^{\frac{1}{p}}$$

if Ω is unbounded while with the norm

$$\|u\|_{\Omega} = (|\nabla u|_{\Omega,p})$$

if Ω is bounded, $1 \leq p < +\infty$;

- $H_0^1(\Omega) = W_0^{1,2}(\Omega)$;
- if $U : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a measurable function such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} U(x) > 0,$$

we denote by

$$(L_U^r(\Omega), |\cdot|_{\Omega,U,r}), \quad 1 \leq r < +\infty$$

the weighted Lebesgue space with

$$\begin{aligned} L_U^r(\Omega) &= \left\{ u \in L^r(\Omega) : \int_{\Omega} U(x)|u|^r dx < +\infty \right\}, \\ |u|_{\Omega,U,r} &= \left(\int_{\Omega} U(x)|u|^r dx \right)^{\frac{1}{r}}; \end{aligned} \tag{0.0.4}$$

- $W_U^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and $W_{0,U}^{1,p}(\Omega)$, if $1 \leq p < +\infty$, the weighted Sobolev spaces

$$\begin{aligned} W_U^{1,p}(\Omega) &= \left\{ u \in W^{1,p}(\Omega) : \int_{\Omega} U(x)|u|^p dx < +\infty \right\}, \\ W_{0,U}^{1,p}(\Omega) &= \left\{ u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) : \int_{\Omega} U(x)|u|^p dx < +\infty \right\} \end{aligned}$$

endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_{\Omega,U} = (|\nabla u|_{\Omega,p}^p + |u|_{\Omega,U,p}^p)^{\frac{1}{p}}; \tag{0.0.5}$$

- $H_{0,U}^1(\Omega) = W_{0,U}^{1,2}(\Omega)$;
- $|\cdot|_r = |\cdot|_{\mathbb{R}^N, r}$ the norm in $L^r(\mathbb{R}^N)$, for all $1 \leq r \leq +\infty$;
- $|\cdot|_{U,r} = |\cdot|_{\mathbb{R}^N, U, r}$ the norm in $L_U^r(\mathbb{R}^N)$, for all $1 \leq r < +\infty$;
- $\|\cdot\| = \|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{R}^N}$ the norm in $W^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) = W_0^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$;
- $\|\cdot\|_U = \|\cdot\|_{\mathbb{R}^N, U}$ the norm in $W_U^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) = W_{0,U}^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$;
- the Gagliardo seminorm of a measurable function $u : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$[u]_{s,p} = \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \right)^{1/p}$$

and

$$W^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{u \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^N) : [u]_{s,p} < \infty\}$$

the fractional Sobolev space endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_{s,p} = \left(|u|_p^p + [u]_{s,p}^p \right)^{1/p};$$

- $W_0^{s,p}(\Omega) = \{u \in W^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) : u = 0 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega\}$, equivalently renormed by setting $\|\cdot\| = [\cdot]_{s,p}$;
- the Gagliardo seminorm of a measurable function $u : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

$$[u]_s = \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \right)^{1/2}$$

and

$$H^s(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{u \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^N) : [u]_s < \infty\}$$

the fractional Sobolev space endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_s = \left(|u|_2^2 + [u]_s^2 \right)^{1/2},$$

where $|\cdot|_2$ denotes the norm in $L^2(\mathbb{R}^N)$;

- $H_0^s(\Omega) = \{u \in H^s(\mathbb{R}^N) : u = 0 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega\}$, equivalently renormed by setting $\|\cdot\| = [\cdot]_s$;
- $\dot{H}^s(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{u \in L^{2^*}(\mathbb{R}^N) : [u]_s < \infty\}$.

PART I

**Existence and multiplicity results for
quasilinear elliptic problems**

Mountain Pass Theorem

An intriguing circumstance which arises when handling nonlinear problems through variational techniques is that the energy functional tied to the problem (whose critical points are the weak solutions) is indefinite, i.e. it is bounded neither from below nor from above. As absolute minima or maxima does not exist in that situation, the direct methods of calculus of variations cease to perform. If the energy functional also fails to have local extrema, thus the existence of critical points with different nature than those (Mountain Pass points, for example) has to be investigated.

One of the most celebrated results in critical point theory when not searching for local minima or maxima is the Mountain Pass Theorem by Ambrosetti and Rabinowitz (see [12]). On the contrary, it provides to characterize a critical value of the functional by a minimax argument. As early as it appeared, it attracted attention by raising up a lot of theoretical developments and by serving to solve a very large number of problems in many areas of Nonlinear Analysis. As it has been widely inquired over the years, now we handle a plenty amount of its variants.

In this first chapter we provide a revised version of the Mountain Pass Theorem suited for functionals which are not differentiable in all directions, as they will be the subject of investigation of the Part I of this thesis.

It is worth nothing that here we do not adhere closely the trail outlined in [CS3, CS4, CS5, CS6, CS7] and [53]. In fact, we choice to give the needed version of the Mountain Pass Theorem not as stated in [53] but as a general min–max theorem from which a version of the Mountain Pass Theorem as well as new versions of other min–max theorems can be inferred. The relevance of this result relies upon its “easy” proof, which does not require neither a deformation lemma (unlike in [53]) nor other particular technical issues, but takes advantage only on the Ekeland Variational Principle and the Mean Value Theorem.

Existence and multiplicity of nonnegative critical points are also studied through the use of our theorem.

Throughout this chapter we assume that:

- $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ is a Banach space with dual $(X', \|\cdot\|_{X'})$;
- $(W, \|\cdot\|_W)$ is a Banach space such that $X \hookrightarrow W$ continuously, i.e. $X \subset W$ and a constant $\sigma_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$\|\xi\|_W \leq \sigma_0 \|\xi\|_X \quad \text{for all } \xi \in X;$$

- $J : \mathcal{D} \subset W \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $J \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$ with $X \subset \mathcal{D}$.

Furthermore, we recall the following definition.

Definition 1.1. Taking $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$, we say that a sequence $(\xi_n)_n \subset X$ is a *Cerami–Palais–Smale sequence at level β* , briefly $(CPS)_\beta$ -sequence, if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} J(\xi_n) = \beta \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \|dJ(\xi_n)\|_{X'}(1 + \|\xi_n\|_X) = 0.$$

Moreover, β is a *Cerami–Palais–Smale level*, briefly (CPS) -level, if there exists a $(CPS)_\beta$ -sequence.

Now, we provide the aforementioned general min–max theorem. Although we follow the ideas developed in [184, Theorem 2.8] and in the more general framework considered in [22], we point out that at the best of our knowledge this theorem is new and contains extra information with respect to the previous mentioned results. For that reason, we provide it with all the details.

Theorem 1.1. Let $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ be Banach space and $J \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$. Let K be a compact metric space, $K_0 \subset K$ a closed subset and $\gamma_0 : K_0 \rightarrow X$ a continuous map. Consider the set

$$\Gamma = \{\gamma \in C(K, X) \text{ such that } \gamma|_{K_0} = \gamma_0\}.$$

and let

$$c = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \max_{t \in K} J(\gamma(t)) > c_1 = \max_{t \in K_0} J(\gamma_0(t)). \quad (1.0.1)$$

If

$$0 < \varepsilon < \min\{c - c_1, 1\}, \quad (1.0.2)$$

then for all $\gamma \in \Gamma$ such that

$$c \leq \max_{t \in K} J(\gamma(t)) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \quad (1.0.3)$$

there exist $\bar{\gamma} \in \Gamma$ and $u \in \bar{\gamma}(K) \subset X$ satisfying

$$c \leq \max_{t \in K} J(\bar{\gamma}(t)) \leq \max_{t \in K} J(\gamma(t)) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \quad \frac{\max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t) - \gamma(t)\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon},$$

$$c - \varepsilon \leq J(u) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \quad |\langle dJ(u), v \rangle| \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon}(1 + \sqrt{\varepsilon}) \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \|u\|_X} \quad \forall v \in X.$$

Proof. To start, we observe that taking γ and ε as in (1.0.2) and (1.0.3), we have that Γ is a complete metric space endowed with the distance

$$d_\gamma(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) = \frac{\max_{t \in K} \|\gamma_1(t) - \gamma_2(t)\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X}, \quad \gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \Gamma.$$

Consider the functional $\Upsilon : \Gamma \rightarrow (-\infty, +\infty]$ defined as

$$\Upsilon(\gamma) = \sup_{t \in K} J(\gamma(t)), \quad \gamma \in \Gamma.$$

By (1.0.1), Υ is proper and bounded from below by c_1 . In addition, Υ is lower semi-continuous by [178, Lemma 3.1]. Applying the Ekeland variational principle [99], we deduce that there exists $\bar{\gamma} \in \Gamma$ such that

$$c \leq \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}) \leq \Upsilon(\gamma) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2},$$

$$d_\gamma(\bar{\gamma}, \gamma) = \frac{\max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t) - \gamma(t)\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon}, \quad (1.0.4)$$

and

$$\Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}) < \Upsilon(\vartheta) + \sqrt{\varepsilon} d_\gamma(\bar{\gamma}, \vartheta) \quad \text{for all } \vartheta \in \Gamma \setminus \bar{\gamma}. \quad (1.0.5)$$

Now we prove the existence of $t \in \mathcal{T} := \{t \in K : c - \sqrt{\varepsilon} \leq J(\bar{\gamma}(t))\}$ such that, if $u = \bar{\gamma}(t)$, then

$$|\langle dJ(u), v \rangle| \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \quad \forall v \in X.$$

Assume by contradiction that the previous inequality is false. Then, for each $t \in \mathcal{T}$ either there exists $v_t \in X$ such that

$$\langle dJ(\bar{\gamma}(t)), v_t \rangle < -\sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|v_t\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X}.$$

or there exists $w_t \in X$ such that

$$\langle dJ(\bar{\gamma}(t)), w_t \rangle > \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|w_t\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X}.$$

Without loss of generality, we assume that the first inequality holds and $\|v_t\|_X = 1$. By continuity, for any $t \in \mathcal{T}$ there exists $\delta_t > 0$ and an open ball B_t in K with $t \in B_t$, such that

$$\langle dJ(\bar{\gamma}(s) + u), v_t \rangle \leq -\frac{\sqrt{\varepsilon}}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \quad (1.0.6)$$

for every $s \in B_t$ and $u \in X$ satisfying $\|u\|_X < \delta_t$. Now, since \mathcal{T} is compact, there exists a finite family of neighborhoods B_{t_1}, \dots, B_{t_k} such that

$$\mathcal{T} \subset \bigcup_{j=1}^k B_{t_j}.$$

Taking $\delta = \min\{\delta_{t_1}, \dots, \delta_{t_k}\}$ and choosing $\psi, \psi_j \in C(K, [0, 1])$ satisfying

$$\psi(s) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } c \leq J(\bar{\gamma}(s)), \\ 0 & \text{if } J(\bar{\gamma}(s)) \leq c - \varepsilon \end{cases}$$

and

$$\psi_j(s) = \begin{cases} \frac{\text{dist}(s, K \setminus B_{t_j})}{\sum_{i=1}^k \text{dist}(s, K \setminus B_{t_i})} & \text{if } s \in \bigcup_{i=1}^k B_{t_i} \\ 0 & \text{if } s \in K \setminus \bigcup_{i=1}^k B_{t_i}. \end{cases}$$

Thus, taking

$$\gamma^* := \bar{\gamma} + \delta \psi \sum_{j=1}^k \psi_j v_{t_j}$$

and using that $\varepsilon < c - c_1$, it can be easily check that $\gamma^* \in \Gamma$. Moreover, for every $s \in K \setminus \mathcal{T}$, as $\psi(s) = 0$, it is $\gamma^*(s) = \bar{\gamma}(s)$ and then $J(\gamma^*(s)) = J(\bar{\gamma}(s)) < c - \varepsilon$. On the other hand, if $s \in \mathcal{T}$, the Mean Value Theorem implies that there exists $\tau \in (0, 1)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} J(\gamma^*(s)) - J(\bar{\gamma}(s)) &= \left\langle J' \left(\bar{\gamma}(s) + \tau \delta \psi(s) \sum_{j=1}^k \psi_j(s) v_{t_j} \right), \delta \psi(s) \sum_{j=1}^k \psi_j(s) v_{t_j} \right\rangle \\ &= \delta \psi(s) \sum_{j=1}^k \psi_j(s) \left\langle J' \left(\bar{\gamma}(s) + \tau \delta \psi(s) \sum_{j=1}^k \psi_j(s) v_{t_j} \right), v_{t_j} \right\rangle. \end{aligned}$$

By (1.0.6) we have

$$\begin{aligned} J(\gamma^*(s)) - J(\bar{\gamma}(s)) &\leq -\frac{\sqrt{\varepsilon}}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \delta \psi(s) \sum_{j=1}^k \psi_j(s) \\ &= -\frac{\sqrt{\varepsilon}}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \delta \psi(s). \end{aligned}$$

Then, if $s \in K$ is the point in which $J \circ \gamma^*$ attains its maximum, i.e. $J(\gamma^*(s)) = \Upsilon(\gamma^*) \geq c$, we infer that it necessarily has to be $\psi(s) = 1, s \in \mathcal{T}$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \Upsilon(\gamma^*) &= J(\gamma^*(s)) \leq J(\bar{\gamma}(s)) - \frac{\delta\sqrt{\varepsilon}}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \\ &\leq \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}) - \frac{\delta\sqrt{\varepsilon}}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \\ &\leq \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}) - \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\max_{t \in K} \|\gamma^*(t) - \bar{\gamma}(t)\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} = \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}) - \sqrt{\varepsilon} \mathbf{d}_\gamma(\gamma^*, \bar{\gamma}), \end{aligned}$$

which contradicts (1.0.5). Hence, we have proved that

$$|\langle dJ(u), v \rangle| \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \quad \forall v \in X.$$

Thus, by (1.0.4) and direct computations we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} |\langle dJ(u), v \rangle| &\leq \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t)\|_X} \frac{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t)\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \\ &\leq \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t)\|_X} \frac{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X + \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t) - \gamma(t)\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \\ &\leq \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t)\|_X} \left[1 + \frac{\max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t) - \gamma(t)\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma(t)\|_X} \right] \\ &\leq \sqrt{\varepsilon} \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t)\|_X} [1 + \mathbf{d}_\gamma(\bar{\gamma}, \gamma)] \\ &\leq \sqrt{\varepsilon}(1 + \sqrt{\varepsilon}) \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}(t)\|_X} \end{aligned}$$

and since u is in the graph of $\bar{\gamma}$, we infer that

$$|\langle dJ(u), v \rangle| \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon}(1 + \sqrt{\varepsilon}) \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \|u\|_X}$$

completing the proof. \square

Remark 1.1. Observe that, if $X \hookrightarrow W$ where W is a Banach space itself, the previous Theorem still holds if we replace the hypothesis $J \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$ with the lighter ones assumed in [20, Theorem 2.1], i.e.

- a) J has a directional derivative $\langle J'(u), v \rangle$ at each $u \in W$ through any direction $v \in X$;
- b) For fixed $u \in W$, the function $\langle J'(u), v \rangle$ is linear in $v \in X$, and, for fixed $v \in X$, the function $\langle J'(u), v \rangle$ is continuous in $u \in W$.

Anyway, as in the following we will avail of some techniques adopted in [52, 53], for the reader convenience, we preferred to state Theorem 1.1 in our case of interest.

From Theorem 1.1 we infer that there exists a sequence $(u_n)_n \subset X$ such that, if $(\varepsilon_n)_n$ is an infinitesimal sequence, it follows that

$$(J(u_n))_n \text{ is bounded} \quad \text{and} \quad |\langle dJ(u_n), v \rangle| \leq \xi_n \frac{\|v\|_X}{1 + \|u_n\|_X} \quad \forall v \in X, \quad (1.0.7)$$

with

$$\xi_n = \sqrt{\varepsilon_n}(1 + \sqrt{\varepsilon_n}) \rightarrow 0.$$

Now it remains to derive a suitable compactness condition on the functional J which guarantees the existence of a subsequence (u_{n_k}) converging to a critical point of J ; such a condition must be inferred from (1.0.7). Observe that here, as we will assume that $X \hookrightarrow W$, the classical Palais–Smale condition (which comes inherently when $X = W$), can not be enforced. Hence a weaker compactness condition is required. To be more precise, it should be

“Any sequence $(u_n)_n \subset X$ satisfying (1.0.7) admits a converging subsequence in W .”

Summing up, the natural compactness condition which comes from these argument is the following one.

Definition 1.2. The functional J satisfies the *weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition at level β* ($\beta \in \mathbb{R}$), briefly *(wCPS) $_{\beta}$ condition*, if for every *(CPS) $_{\beta}$ -sequence* $(\xi_n)_n$, a point $\xi \in X$ exists, such that

$$(i) \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \|\xi_n - \xi\|_W = 0 \quad (\text{up to subsequences}),$$

$$(ii) \quad J(\xi) = \beta, \quad dJ(\xi) = 0.$$

If J satisfies the *(wCPS) $_{\beta}$ condition* at each level $\beta \in I$, I real interval, we say that J satisfies the *(wCPS) condition in I* .

From Theorem 1.1 and the previous arguments, we can state this generalized version of Mountain Pass Theorem.

Theorem 1.2. *Let $J \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$ be such that $J(0) = 0$ and the (wCPS) condition holds in \mathbb{R}_+ .*

Moreover, assume that there exist some constants $R_0, \varrho_0 > 0$, and a point $e \in X$ such that

- (i) $y \in X, \quad \|y\|_W = R_0 \quad \implies \quad J(y) \geq \varrho_0;$
(ii) $\|e\|_W > R_0 \quad \text{and} \quad J(e) < \varrho_0.$

Then, J has a critical point $y \in X$ such that

$$J(y) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \sup_{s \in [0,1]} J(\gamma(s)) \geq \varrho_0$$

with

$$\Gamma = \{\gamma \in C([0, 1], X) : \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = e\}.$$

Proof. Taking $e \in X$ and

$$K = [0, 1], \quad K_0 = \{0, 1\}, \quad \gamma_0 : K_0 \rightarrow X \text{ such that } \gamma_0(0) = 0, \gamma_0(1) = e.$$

thus (1.0.1) turns into

$$c = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \max_{t \in [0,1]} J(\gamma(t)) > c_1 = \max\{J(0), J(e)\}$$

with

$$\Gamma = \{\gamma \in C([0, 1], X) \text{ such that } \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = e\}.$$

□

As useful in the incoming results, we observe that the previous result remains true if we replace $\|\cdot\|_W$ with any continuous map $\ell : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, as has been showed in [56]. For the reader convenience, we state the result here.

Theorem 1.3. *Let $J \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$ be such that $J(0) = 0$ and the (wCPS) condition holds in \mathbb{R}_+ .*

Moreover, assume that there exist a continuous map $\ell : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, some constants $r_0, \varrho_0 > 0$, and $e \in X$ such that

- (i) $\ell(0) = 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \ell(y) \geq \|y\|_W \quad \text{for all } y \in X;$
(ii) $y \in X, \quad \ell(y) = r_0 \quad \implies \quad J(y) \geq \varrho_0;$
(iii) $\|e\|_W > r_0 \quad \text{and} \quad J(e) < \varrho_0.$

Then, J has a Mountain Pass critical point $y^* \in X$ such that

$$J(y^*) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \sup_{s \in [0,1]} J(\gamma(s)) \geq \varrho_0$$

with

$$\Gamma = \{\gamma \in C([0, 1], X) : \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = e\}.$$

If, in addition, we require that J is symmetric, then a more general version of the Symmetric Mountain Pass Theorem in [12] can be stated, too (for the proof, see [160, Theorem 2.4] and [27, Theorem 2.4]).

Theorem 1.4. *Let $J \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$ be an even functional such that $J(0) = 0$ and the (wCPS) condition holds in \mathbb{R}_+ . Moreover, assume that $\varrho > 0$ exists so that:*

(\mathcal{H}_ϱ) *three closed subsets V_ϱ, Z_ϱ and \mathcal{M}_ϱ of X and a constant $R_\varrho > 0$ exist which satisfy the following conditions:*

(i) V_ϱ and Z_ϱ are subspaces of X such that

$$V_\varrho + Z_\varrho = X, \quad \text{codim } Z_\varrho < \dim V_\varrho < +\infty;$$

(ii) $\mathcal{M}_\varrho = \partial\mathcal{N}$, where $\mathcal{N} \subset X$ is a neighborhood of the origin which is symmetric and bounded with respect to $\|\cdot\|_W$;

(iii) $y \in \mathcal{M}_\varrho \cap Z_\varrho \implies J(y) \geq \varrho$;

(iv) $y \in V_\varrho, \|y\|_X \geq R_\varrho \implies J(y) \leq 0$.

Then, if we put

$$\beta_\varrho = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma_\varrho} \sup_{y \in V_\varrho} J(\gamma(y)),$$

with

$$\Gamma_\varrho = \{\gamma : X \rightarrow X : \gamma \text{ odd homeomorphism, } \gamma(y) = y \text{ if } y \in V_\varrho \text{ with } \|y\|_X \geq R_\varrho\},$$

the functional J possesses at least a pair of symmetric critical points in X with corresponding critical level β_ϱ which belongs to $[\varrho, \varrho_1]$, where $\varrho_1 \geq \sup_{y \in V_\varrho} J(y) > \varrho$.

Remark 1.2. Since the vector space V_ϱ in Theorem 1.4 has finite dimension, then condition $(\mathcal{H}_\varrho)(iv)$ implies that $\sup_{y \in V_\varrho} J(y) < +\infty$. Moreover, such hypothesis still holds if we replace $\|\cdot\|_X$ with $\|\cdot\|_W$.

We point out that if condition (\mathcal{H}_ϱ) is satisfied for any $\varrho > 0$, then Theorem 1.4 can be applied to any $\varrho > 0$. Hence, it is possible to establish an increasing sequence of critical levels $(\varrho_n)_n$ of the functional J such that the following multiplicity abstract result holds, too.

Corollary 1.1. *Let $J \in C^1(X, \mathbb{R})$ be an even functional such that $J(0) = 0$, the (wCPS) condition holds in \mathbb{R}_+ and assumption (\mathcal{H}_ϱ) holds for all $\varrho > 0$.*

Then, the functional J possesses a sequence of critical points $(y_n)_n \subset X$ such that $J(y_n) \nearrow +\infty$ as $n \nearrow +\infty$.

Coupled quasilinear elliptic systems of gradient type

Here we investigate the existence of one or more weak bounded solutions for the following class of gradient-type quasilinear elliptic systems with homogeneous Dirichlet boundary conditions

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(a_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i)) + A_{i,t}(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) = G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) & \text{in } \Omega, i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \\ \mathbf{u} = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (2.0.1)$$

with $m \geq 2$ and $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_m) : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ an unknown vector function, where $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ is an open bounded domain and some functions $A_i : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, and $G : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exist such that

$$A_{i,t}(x, t, \xi) = \frac{\partial A_i}{\partial t}(x, t, \xi), \quad a_i(x, t, \xi) = \left(\frac{\partial A_i}{\partial \xi_1}(x, t, \xi), \dots, \frac{\partial A_i}{\partial \xi_N}(x, t, \xi) \right) \quad (2.0.2)$$

if $1 \leq i \leq m$ and $\nabla_{\mathbf{u}} G(x, \mathbf{u}) = (G_1(x, \mathbf{u}), \dots, G_m(x, \mathbf{u}))$, i.e.,

$$G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial u_i}(x, \mathbf{u}) \quad \text{if } 1 \leq i \leq m. \quad (2.0.3)$$

A particular model of system (2.0.1) can be obtained taking $m = 2$, $A_1(x, t, \xi) = \frac{1}{p_1} A(x, t) |\xi|^{p_1}$ and $A_2(x, t, \xi) = \frac{1}{p_2} B(x, t) |\xi|^{p_2}$ with $p_1, p_2 > 1$. So, (2.0.1) reduces to the coupled quasilinear elliptic system

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u) + \frac{1}{p_1} A_u(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p_1} = G_u(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ -\operatorname{div}(B(x, v) |\nabla v|^{p_2-2} \nabla v) + \frac{1}{p_2} B_v(x, v) |\nabla v|^{p_2} = G_v(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = v = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (2.0.4)$$

where Ω is an open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 2$, $p_1, p_2 > 1$, functions $A, B : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ admit partial derivatives

$$A_u(x, u) = \frac{\partial A}{\partial u}(x, u), \quad B_v(x, v) = \frac{\partial B}{\partial v}(x, v) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } u, v \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.0.5)$$

and a function $G : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exists such that

$$\nabla G(x, u, v) = (G_u(x, u, v), G_v(x, u, v)),$$

i.e.

$$\frac{\partial G}{\partial u}(x, u, v) = G_u(x, u, v), \quad \frac{\partial G}{\partial v}(x, u, v) = G_v(x, u, v) \quad (2.0.6)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. In the even more particular setting $A(x, u) = A^*(x)$ and $B(x, v) = B^*(x)$, problem (2.0.4) reduces to

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(A^*(x)|\nabla u|^{p_1-2}\nabla u) = G_u(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ -\operatorname{div}(B^*(x)|\nabla v|^{p_2-2}\nabla v) = G_v(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = v = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (2.0.7)$$

with $A^*, B^* : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$. If $A^*(x), B^*(x)$ are measurable, bounded and strictly positive functions, then (2.0.7) generalizes the classical (p_1, p_2) -Laplacian system

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta_{p_1} u = G_u(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ -\Delta_{p_2} v = G_v(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = v = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases} \quad (2.0.8)$$

The recent literature provides many works concerning the study of coupled elliptic systems of gradient type. In fact, many authors have studied problem (2.0.8) and have obtained several existence results under hypotheses of sublinear, superlinear, and resonant type on the nonlinearity $G(x, u, v)$ (see, e.g., [6, 43, 97, 152, 182] and, if $p_1 = p_2 = p$, eventually $p = 2$, the survey [85] and references therein).

On the other hand, a generalization of system (2.0.7) has been studied in [50] by using a cohomological local splitting while quasilinear elliptic systems similar to (2.0.4) are studied in [35] by means of an approximation approach and in [23, 176] via nonsmooth techniques.

As discussed extensively in the introduction, the presence of some coefficients depending on the solution and its gradient themselves makes the variational approach tougher. Nonetheless, here we extend the existence result in [43, Theorem 3] to our quasilinear problem (2.0.4), but with stronger subcritical growth conditions which allow us to find bounded solutions. Moreover, we want also to state a multiplicity result under hypothesis of symmetry.

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS7, CS6].

2.1 Variational setting and first properties

In this section, we highlight the variational nature of problems (2.0.1) and (2.0.4), then we prove some early properties of the associated functionals. As they share some features, here we prefer to carry on their study simultaneously.

To start, we recall the following definition.

Definition 2.1. A function $f : \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^l \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $l \in \mathbb{N}$, is a \mathcal{C}^k -Carathéodory function, $k \in \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}$, if

- $f(\cdot, \omega) : x \in \Omega \mapsto f(x, \omega) \in \mathbb{R}$ is measurable for all $\omega \in \mathbb{R}^l$,
- $f(x, \cdot) : \omega \in \mathbb{R}^l \mapsto f(x, \omega) \in \mathbb{R}$ is \mathcal{C}^k for a.e. $x \in \Omega$.

For each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, let $A_i : (x, t, \xi) \in \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \mapsto A_i(x, t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R}$ be a given function such that the following conditions hold:

(2h₀) $A_i(x, t, \xi)$ is a \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function with partial derivatives $A_{i,t}(x, t, \xi)$, $a_i(x, t, \xi)$ as in (2.0.2);

(2h₁) a power $p_i > 1$ and some positive continuous functions $\Phi_0^i, \phi_0^i, \Phi_1^i, \phi_1^i, \Phi_2^i, \phi_2^i : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exist such that

$$|A_i(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Phi_0^i(t) + \phi_0^i(t)|\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (2.1.1)$$

$$|A_{i,t}(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Phi_1^i(t) + \phi_1^i(t)|\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (2.1.2)$$

$$|a_i(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Phi_2^i(t) + \phi_2^i(t)|\xi|^{p_i-1} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (2.1.3)$$

So, taking $p_i > 1$ as in (h₁), we consider the related Sobolev space

$$W_i = W_0^{1,p_i}(\Omega) \quad \text{with norm } \|\cdot\|_{W_i} = \|\cdot\|_{W_0^{1,p_i}}.$$

From the Sobolev Embedding Theorem, W_i is continuously embedded in $L^r(\Omega)$ for any $r \in [1, p_i^*]$ with $p_i^* = \frac{Np_i}{N-p_i}$ if $N > p_i$, or $r \in [1, +\infty[$ with $p_i^* = +\infty$ if $p_i \geq N$, i.e., for such an r a positive constant $\tau_{i,r}$ exists such that

$$|u|_r \leq \tau_{i,r} \|u\|_{W_i} \quad \text{for all } u \in W_i. \quad (2.1.4)$$

For simplicity, we put

$$\frac{1}{p_i^*} = 0 \quad \text{if } p_i^* = +\infty. \quad (2.1.5)$$

Now, assume that a function $G : (x, \mathbf{u}) \in \Omega \times \mathbb{R}^m \mapsto G(x, \mathbf{u}) \in \mathbb{R}$ exists such that

(2g₀) $G(x, \mathbf{u})$ is a \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function with partial derivatives $G_i(x, \mathbf{u})$ as in (2.0.3) such that

$$G(\cdot, \mathbf{0}) \in L^\infty(\Omega)$$

and

$$G_i(x, \mathbf{0}) = 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for each } i \in \{1, \dots, m\};$$

(2g₁) for every $i, j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, $j \neq i$, some real numbers $q_i \geq 1$, $s_{i,j} \geq 0$ and a constant $\sigma > 0$ exist such that

$$|G_i(x, \mathbf{u})| \leq \sigma \left(1 + |u_i|^{q_i-1} + \sum_{j \neq i} |u_j|^{s_{i,j}} \right) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (2.1.6)$$

with

$$1 \leq q_i < p_i^* \quad (2.1.7)$$

and

$$0 \leq s_{i,j} < \frac{p_i}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^*} \right) p_j^*. \quad (2.1.8)$$

Remark 2.1. We note that the subcritical growth assumptions (2.1.7) and (2.1.8) are required in order to prove the (*wCPS*) condition (see Proposition 2.3) but not the variational principle stated in Proposition 2.1.

Moreover, for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ and all $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m$, condition (2g₀) together with Mean Value Theorem implies that $t \in]0, 1[$ exists such that

$$|G(x, \mathbf{u})| \leq |G(\cdot, \mathbf{0})|_\infty + \sum_i |G_i(x, t\mathbf{u})| |u_i|,$$

then from (2.1.6) it follows that

$$|G(x, \mathbf{u})| \leq \sigma_1 \sum_i \left(1 + |u_i|^{q_i} + \sum_{j \neq i} |u_i| |u_j|^{s_{i,j}} \right) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (2.1.9)$$

with $\sigma_1 > 0$ which depends on σ , m and $|G(\cdot, \mathbf{0})|_\infty$.

To investigate the existence of weak solutions of the nonlinear problem (2.0.1) as critical points of a suitable functional, we have to introduce the “right” Banach space. To this aim, the notation introduced in Chapter 1 is referred to

$$W = W_1 \times \dots \times W_m \quad (2.1.10)$$

with norm

$$\|\mathbf{u}\|_W = \|(u_1, \dots, u_m)\|_W = \sum_i \|u_i\|_{W_i} \quad \text{if } \mathbf{u} \in W, \quad (2.1.11)$$

while the Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ is defined as

$$X = X_1 \times \dots \times X_m \quad (2.1.12)$$

with norm

$$\|\mathbf{u}\|_X = \|(u_1, \dots, u_m)\|_X = \sum_i \|u_i\|_{X_i} \quad \text{if } \mathbf{u} \in X,$$

where, for any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, it is

$$X_i := W_i \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$$

equipped with norm

$$\|u\|_{X_i} = \|u\|_{W_i} + |u|_\infty \quad \text{if } u \in X_i. \quad (2.1.13)$$

We note that, setting

$$L = L^\infty(\Omega) \times \dots \times L^\infty(\Omega)$$

with norm

$$\|\mathbf{u}\|_L = \|(u_1, \dots, u_m)\|_L = \sum_i |u_i|_\infty \quad \text{if } \mathbf{u} \in L,$$

we have that X in (2.1.12) can also be written as

$$X = W \cap L \quad \text{with} \quad \|\mathbf{u}\|_X = \|\mathbf{u}\|_W + \|\mathbf{u}\|_L.$$

For every $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we have that $(W_i, \|\cdot\|_{W_i})$ is a reflexive Banach space and, by definition, it is $X_i \hookrightarrow W_i$ and $X_i \hookrightarrow L^\infty(\Omega)$ with continuous embeddings. Thus, also $(W, \|\cdot\|_W)$ is a reflexive Banach space and, obviously, $X \hookrightarrow W$ and $X \hookrightarrow L$ with continuous embeddings, too.

Remark 2.2. If $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ is such that $p_i > N$, then $X_i = W_i$, as $W_i \hookrightarrow L^\infty(\Omega)$. So, in general, if an $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ exists such that $p_i \leq N$ then $X \neq W$, but if for all $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ it is $p_i > N$, then $X = W$ and the classical Mountain Pass Theorems in [12] can be used, if required.

If conditions $(2h_0)$ – $(2h_1)$, $(2g_0)$ and (2.1.6) hold, by (2.1.9) and direct computations it follows that the functional

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) = \sum_{i=1}^m \int_{\Omega} A_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) dx - \int_{\Omega} G(x, \mathbf{u}) dx \quad (2.1.14)$$

is well defined for all $\mathbf{u} \in X$. Moreover, taking any $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in X$, the Gâteaux differential of functional \mathcal{J} in \mathbf{u} along the direction \mathbf{v} is well defined as

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})[\mathbf{v}] = & \sum_i \left(\int_{\Omega} a_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) \cdot \nabla v_i dx + \int_{\Omega} A_{i,t}(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) v_i dx \right. \\ & \left. - \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) v_i dx \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.15)$$

We note that, since $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in X$ imply that $\mathbf{u}, \mathbf{v} \in L$, no critical growth upper bound on the powers q_i and $s_{i,j}$ is required in order to have $d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})[\mathbf{v}] \in \mathbb{R}$.

For simplicity, for every $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ we introduce the i -th partial derivative of \mathcal{J} in $\mathbf{u} \in X$ as

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}) : v \in X_i \mapsto \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u})[v] = d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})[ve_i] \in \mathbb{R},$$

where from (2.1.15) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u})[v] &= \int_{\Omega} a_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) \cdot \nabla v \, dx + \int_{\Omega} A_{i,t}(x, u_i, \nabla u_i)v \, dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u})v \, dx. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.16)$$

Remark 2.3. Taking $\mathbf{u} \in X$, since $d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \in X'$, then

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}) \in X'_i \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$$

and

$$d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})[\mathbf{v}] = \sum_i \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u})[v_i] \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{v} = (v_1, \dots, v_m) \in X. \quad (2.1.17)$$

Moreover, direct computations imply that

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}) \right\|_{X'_i} \leq \|d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})\|_{X'} \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\} \quad (2.1.18)$$

and

$$\|d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})\|_{X'} \leq \sum_i \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}) \right\|_{X'_i}. \quad (2.1.19)$$

Clearly, we have

$$d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) = 0 \text{ in } X \quad \iff \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}) = 0 \text{ in } X_i \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

Now, we can state a regularity result.

Proposition 2.1. *Suppose that conditions (2h₀)–(2h₁), (2g₀) and (2.1.6) hold. Let $(\mathbf{u}_n)_n \subset X$ and $\mathbf{u} \in X$ be such that*

$$\mathbf{u}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{u} \text{ strongly in } W \quad \mathbf{u}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{u} \text{ a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (2.1.20)$$

If $M > 0$ exists such that

$$|\mathbf{u}_n|_{\infty} \leq M \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (2.1.21)$$

then

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) - d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence, \mathcal{J} is a C^1 functional on X with Fréchet differential defined as in (2.1.15).

Proof. Let $(\mathbf{u}_n)_n \subset X$ and $\mathbf{u} \in X$ be such that (2.1.20) and (2.1.21) hold. Taking any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, from hypotheses (2h₀)–(2h₁), (2.1.20) and (2.1.21), by reasoning as in the proof of [52, Proposition 3.1], it follows that the “partial” functional

$$\mathcal{A}_i : u \in X_i \mapsto \int_{\Omega} A_i(x, u, \nabla u) dx \in \mathbb{R}$$

is such that

$$\mathcal{A}_i(u_i^n) \rightarrow \mathcal{A}_i(u_i).$$

Moreover, by means of Dominated Convergence Theorem, conditions (2g₀), (2.1.9), (2.1.20) and (2.1.21) imply that

$$\int_{\Omega} G(x, \mathbf{u}_n) dx \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} G(x, \mathbf{u}) dx.$$

Thus, summing up, we have

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Now, we observe that (2.1.17) gives

$$\|d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) - d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})\|_{X'} \leq \sum_i \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}) \right\|_{X'_i},$$

so, in order to prove that $\|d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) - d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0$, it is enough to verify that

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}) \right\|_{X'_i} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (2.1.22)$$

To this aim, fixing $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and taking $v \in X_i$ such that $\|v\|_{X_i} \leq 1$, from (2.1.16) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[v] - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u})[v] \right| &\leq \int_{\Omega} |a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) - a_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i)| |\nabla v| dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} |A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) - A_{i,t}(x, u_i, \nabla u_i)| dx + \int_{\Omega} |G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G_i(x, \mathbf{u})| dx, \end{aligned}$$

where, by reasoning as in [52, Proposition 3.1], it can be proved that

$$\int_{\Omega} |a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) - a_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i)| |\nabla v| dx \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{uniformly with respect to } v$$

and

$$\int_{\Omega} |A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) - A_{i,t}(x, u_i, \nabla u_i)| dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Moreover, (2.1.20), (2.1.21), hypotheses (2g₀), (2.1.6) and, again, Dominated Convergence Theorem, imply that

$$\int_{\Omega} |G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G_i(x, \mathbf{u})| dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Hence, summing up, we conclude that

$$\left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[v] - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u})[v] \right| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{uniformly with respect to } v \in X_i, \|v\|_{X_i} \leq 1,$$

and, by the arbitrariness of $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, it follows that (2.1.22) is satisfied, too. \square

Remark 2.4. Differently from the Sobolev Embedding Theorem, in our setting we have

$$X_i \hookrightarrow L^r(\Omega) \quad \forall r \geq 1 \text{ and } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

Hence, in the proof of Proposition 2.1 no sub-critical growth is required for $G_i(x, \mathbf{u})$, as it was already pointed out in Remark 2.1.

We conclude this section providing an analogous regularity result as Proposition 2.1 for the model problem (2.0.4).

Let $A : (x, u) \in \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto A(x, u) \in \mathbb{R}$, $B : (x, v) \in \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto B(x, v) \in \mathbb{R}$ and $G : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be given functions. To start, we observe that assumptions (2h₁), (2h₂), (2g₀), (2g₁) specialize in this way:

(2 \tilde{h}_0) A and B are \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory functions with partial derivatives as in (2.0.5);

(2 \tilde{h}_1) for any $\rho > 0$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{|u| \leq \rho} |A(\cdot, u)| &\in L^\infty(\Omega), & \sup_{|v| \leq \rho} |B(\cdot, v)| &\in L^\infty(\Omega), \\ \sup_{|u| \leq \rho} |A_u(\cdot, u)| &\in L^\infty(\Omega), & \sup_{|v| \leq \rho} |B_v(\cdot, v)| &\in L^\infty(\Omega); \end{aligned}$$

(2 \tilde{g}_0) G is a \mathcal{C}^1 -Caratheodory function with partial derivatives as in (2.0.6) such that

$$G(\cdot, 0, 0) \in L^\infty(\Omega)$$

and

$$G_u(x, 0, 0) = G_v(x, 0, 0) = 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega;$$

(2 \tilde{g}_1) some real numbers $q_i \geq 1$, $s_i \geq 0$ if $i \in \{1, 2\}$, and $\sigma > 0$ exist such that

$$|G_u(x, u, v)| \leq \sigma(1 + |u|^{q_1-1} + |v|^{s_1}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (2.1.23)$$

$$|G_v(x, u, v)| \leq \sigma(1 + |u|^{s_2} + |v|^{q_2-1}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (2.1.24)$$

with

$$1 \leq q_1 < p_1^*, \quad 1 \leq q_2 < p_2^*, \quad (2.1.25)$$

and

$$0 \leq s_1 < \frac{p_1}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_1^*}\right) p_2^*, \quad 0 \leq s_2 < \frac{p_2}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_2^*}\right) p_1^*. \quad (2.1.26)$$

Similar arguments as in Remark 2.1 holds, which imply that conditions $(2\tilde{g}_0)$, (2.1.23) and (2.1.24) suggest the existence of a constant $\sigma_1 > 0$ such that

$$|G(x, u, v)| \leq \sigma_1 (1 + |u| + |u|^{q_1} + |u||v|^{s_1} + |v| + |u|^{s_2}|v| + |v|^{q_2}) \quad (2.1.27)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ and with $\sigma_1 = \max\{\sigma, |G(\cdot, 0, 0)|_\infty\}$.

Moreover, the notations introduced in (2.1.10)–(2.1.13) simplify with

$$W = W_1 \times W_2 \quad (2.1.28)$$

while the Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ is defined as

$$X = X_1 \times X_2, \quad (2.1.29)$$

where

$$X_1 := W_1 \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad X_2 := W_2 \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$$

with the norms

$$\|u\|_{X_1} = \|u\|_{W_1} + |u|_\infty \quad \text{if } u \in X_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \|v\|_{X_2} = \|v\|_{W_2} + |v|_\infty \quad \text{if } v \in X_2. \quad (2.1.30)$$

Since $(W_i, \|\cdot\|_{W_i})$ is a reflexive Banach space for both $i = 1$ and $i = 2$, so is $(W, \|\cdot\|_W)$ where, for $(u, v) \in W$ it is

$$\|(u, v)\|_W = \|u\|_{W_1} + \|v\|_{W_2}.$$

Setting

$$L := L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{with} \quad \|(u, v)\|_L = |u|_\infty + |v|_\infty,$$

we have that X in (2.1.29) can also be written as

$$X = W \cap L$$

and can be equipped with the norm

$$\|(u, v)\|_X = \|(u, v)\|_W + \|(u, v)\|_L = \|u\|_{X_1} + \|v\|_{X_2}.$$

Now, if conditions $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_1)$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$, (2.1.23) and (2.1.24) hold, by direct computations it follows that the functional

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) = \frac{1}{p_1} \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \frac{1}{p_2} \int_\Omega B(x, v) |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx - \int_\Omega G(x, u, v) dx \quad (2.1.31)$$

is well defined for all $(u, v) \in X$. Moreover, taking any $(u, v), (w, z) \in X$, the Gâteaux differential of functional \mathcal{J} in (u, v) along the direction (w, z) is

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathcal{J}(u, v)[(w, z)] &= \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla w \, dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{p_1} \int_\Omega A_u(x, u) w |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \int_\Omega B(x, v) |\nabla v|^{p_2-2} \nabla v \cdot \nabla z \, dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{p_2} \int_\Omega B_v(x, v) z |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx - \int_\Omega G_u(x, u, v) w \, dx \\ &- \int_\Omega G_v(x, u, v) z \, dx. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.32)$$

As done in the previous case, for simplicity we put

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v) : w \in X_1 &\mapsto \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v)[w] = d\mathcal{J}(u, v)[(w, 0)] \in \mathbb{R}, \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v) : z \in X_2 &\mapsto \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v)[z] = d\mathcal{J}(u, v)[(0, z)] \in \mathbb{R}.\end{aligned}$$

Thus, from (2.1.32), it follows that (2.1.16) specializes as

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v)[w] &= \int_{\Omega} A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla w \, dx + \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} A_u(x, u) w |\nabla u|^{p_1} \, dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u, v) w \, dx\end{aligned}\tag{2.1.33}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v)[z] &= \int_{\Omega} B(x, v) |\nabla v|^{p_2-2} \nabla v \cdot \nabla z \, dx + \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} B_v(x, v) z |\nabla v|^{p_2} \, dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} G_v(x, u, v) z \, dx.\end{aligned}\tag{2.1.34}$$

On the other hand the arguments in Remark 2.3 clearly remains true. We proceed providing an analogous regularity result as in Proposition 2.1.

Proposition 2.2. *Assume that conditions $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_1)$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$, (2.1.23) and (2.1.24) hold. Let $((u_n, v_n))_n \subset X$ and $(u, v) \in X$ be such that*

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ in } W_1, \quad u_n \rightarrow u \text{ a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow \infty,\tag{2.1.35}$$

$$v_n \rightarrow v \text{ in } W_2, \quad v_n \rightarrow v \text{ a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow \infty,\tag{2.1.36}$$

and, moreover, $M > 0$ exists such that

$$|u_n|_{\infty} \leq M \quad \text{and} \quad |v_n|_{\infty} \leq M \quad \forall n \in \mathbb{N}.\tag{2.1.37}$$

Then,

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(u, v) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - d\mathcal{J}(u, v)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty.$$

Hence, \mathcal{J} is a C^1 functional on X with Fréchet differential defined as in (2.1.32).

Even if Proposition 2.2 follows from Proposition 2.1, some ad hoc arguments can be employed to turn the proof of that result “faster”. Hence, we prefer to provide it here with all the details. We start recalling this technical lemma (see [110]).

Lemma 2.1. *A constant $C > 0$ exists such that for any $\xi, \eta \in \mathbb{R}^N$, $N \geq 1$, it results*

$$\|\xi|^{r-2}\xi - |\eta|^{r-2}\eta\| \leq C|\xi - \eta| (|\xi| + |\eta|)^{r-2} \quad \text{if } r > 2,\tag{2.1.38}$$

$$\|\xi|^{r-2}\xi - |\eta|^{r-2}\eta\| \leq C|\xi - \eta|^{r-1} \quad \text{if } 1 < r \leq 2.\tag{2.1.39}$$

From Lemma 2.1 and reasoning as in [58, Lemma 3.4], we have the following estimate.

Lemma 2.2. *If $p > 1$, a constant $C = C(p) > 0$ exists such that*

$$\int_{\Omega} \left| |\nabla w|^p - |\nabla z|^p \right| dx \leq C \|w - z\|_{W_0^{1,p}} \left(\|w\|_{W_0^{1,p}}^{p-1} + \|z\|_{W_0^{1,p}}^{p-1} \right) \quad \forall w, z \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Proof of Proposition 2.2. Let $((u_n, v_n))_n \subset X$ and $(u, v) \in X$ be such that conditions (2.1.35)–(2.1.37) hold. Firstly, we prove that

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(u, v) \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (2.1.40)$$

To this aim, we note that

$$\begin{aligned} |\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - \mathcal{J}(u, v)| &\leq \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n)| \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} - |\nabla u|^{p_1} \right| dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} |B(x, v_n)| \left| |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} - |\nabla v|^{p_2} \right| dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} |B(x, v_n) - B(x, v)| |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx + \int_{\Omega} |G(x, u_n, v_n) - G(x, u, v)| dx. \end{aligned}$$

From (2.1.35), (2.1.37) and Lemma 2.2 it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n)| \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} - |\nabla u|^{p_1} \right| dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.1.41)$$

On the other hand, from Dominated Convergence Theorem we have that

$$\int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \rightarrow 0, \quad (2.1.42)$$

as (2.1.35) and (2.1.37) imply that

$$|A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega$$

and from (2.1.37) and (2.1.37) it results

$$|A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1} \leq C |\nabla u|^{p_1} \in L^1(\Omega).$$

Similarly, by assumptions (2.1.36)–(2.1.37), (2.1.36), (2.1.37) and again Lemma 2.2, we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega} |B(x, v_n)| \left| |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} - |\nabla v|^{p_2} \right| dx \rightarrow 0, \quad \int_{\Omega} |B(x, v_n) - B(x, v)| |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Finally, (2.1.35), (2.1.36) and (2.1.37) imply that

$$G(x, u_n, v_n) \rightarrow G(x, u, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega,$$

while, by conditions (2.1.27) and (2.1.37), a constant $C > 0$ exists such that

$$|G(x, u_n, v_n)| \leq C \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega,$$

thus, by Dominated Convergence Theorem we conclude that

$$\int_{\Omega} G(x, u_n, v_n) dx \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} G(x, u, v) dx$$

and (2.1.40) holds.

Now, in order to prove that

$$\|d\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - d\mathcal{J}(u, v)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0,$$

we note that it is enough to prove that

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v) \right\|_{X'_1} \rightarrow 0, \quad (2.1.43)$$

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v) \right\|_{X'_2} \rightarrow 0, \quad (2.1.44)$$

as from (2.1.17) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - d\mathcal{J}(u, v)\|_{X'} &\leq \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v) \right\|_{X'_1} \\ &\quad + \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n) - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v) \right\|_{X'_2}. \end{aligned}$$

To this aim, firstly let $w \in X_1$ be such that $\|w\|_{X_1} \leq 1$. So, from (2.1.33), condition $|w|_{\infty} \leq 1$ implies that

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[w] - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v)[w] \right| \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n)| \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \right| |\nabla w| dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1-1} |\nabla w| dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} |A_u(x, u_n)| \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} - |\nabla u|^{p_1} \right| dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} |A_u(x, u_n) - A_u(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \int_{\Omega} |G_u(x, u_n, v_n) - G_u(x, u, v)| dx. \end{aligned}$$

From assumptions $(2\tilde{g}_0)$, (2.1.23), (2.1.24), conditions (2.1.35)–(2.1.37) and again Dominated Convergence Theorem it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} |G_u(x, u_n, v_n) - G_u(x, u, v)| dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Moreover, with arguments which are similar to those ones used previously up for proving (2.1.41), respectively (2.1.42), we have that

$$\int_{\Omega} |A_u(x, u_n)| \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} - |\nabla u|^{p_1} \right| dx \rightarrow 0,$$

respectively

$$\int_{\Omega} |A_u(x, u_n) - A_u(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Furthermore, since $\|w\|_{W_1} \leq 1$, by using Hölder inequality we have that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)| |\nabla u|^{p_1-1} |\nabla w| dx \\ & \leq \left(\int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1-1}{p_1}}, \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \rightarrow 0$$

as (2.1.35) and hypothesis $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ imply

$$|A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} |\nabla u|^{p_1} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega$$

while from (2.1.37) and $(2\tilde{h}_1)$ it follows that

$$|A(x, u_n) - A(x, u)|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} |\nabla u|^{p_1} \leq C |\nabla u|^{p_1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega$$

so Dominated Convergence Theorem applies.

At last, hypothesis $(2h_1)$, (2.1.37) and Hölder inequality imply that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n)| \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \right| |\nabla w| dx \\ & \leq C \left(\int_{\Omega} \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \right|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1-1}{p_1}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.45)$$

We note that if $p_1 > 2$, then Lemma 2.1 and again Hölder inequality, with conjugate exponents $p_1 - 1$ and $\frac{p_1-1}{p_1-2}$, give

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\int_{\Omega} \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \right|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1-1}{p_1}} \\ & \leq C \left(\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n - \nabla u|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} (|\nabla u_n| + |\nabla u|)^{\frac{p_1(p_1-2)}{p_1-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1-1}{p_1}} \\ & \leq C \left(\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_n - \nabla u|^{p_1} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p_1}} \left(\int_{\Omega} (|\nabla u_n| + |\nabla u|)^{p_1} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1-2}{p_1}} \\ & \leq C \|u_n - u\|_{W_1} \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.46)$$

as (2.1.35) implies that $(\|u_n\|_{W_1})_n$ is bounded.

On the other hand, if $1 < p_1 \leq 2$, from Lemma 2.1 we have

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \right|^{\frac{p_1}{p_1-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1-1}{p_1}} \leq C \|u_n - u\|_{W_1}^{p_1-1}. \quad (2.1.47)$$

Hence, from (2.1.35) and (2.1.45)–(2.1.47) it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} |A(x, u_n)| \left| |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n - |\nabla u|^{p_1-2} \nabla u \right| |\nabla w| dx \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{uniformly with respect to } w.$$

Thus, summing up, we have that

$$\left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[w] - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v)[w] \right| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{uniformly with respect to } w \in W_1, \|w\|_{X_1} \leq 1,$$

and (2.1.43) holds.

Finally, similar arguments allow us to prove that

$$\left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[z] - \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v)[z] \right| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{uniformly with respect to } z \in X_2, \|z\|_{X_2} \leq 1;$$

hence, (2.1.44) is satisfied, too. \square

2.2 The weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition

To prove some more properties of functional $\mathcal{J} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined as in (2.1.14), we require that not only (2h₀)–(2h₁) hold, but also $R \geq 1$ exists such that for each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ function $A_i(x, t, \xi)$ and its partial derivatives in (2.0.2) satisfy the following conditions:

(2h₂) a constant $\lambda > 0$ exists such that

$$a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \geq \lambda |\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$$

with $p_i > 1$ as in (2h₁);

(2h₃) some constants $\eta_1, \eta_2 > 0$ exist such that

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_1 a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \quad (2.2.1)$$

$$\sup_{|(t, \xi)| \leq R} |A_i(x, t, \xi)| \leq \eta_2 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega; \quad (2.2.2)$$

(2h₄) a constant $\mu_1 > 0$ exists such that

$$a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi + A_{i,t}(x, t, \xi)t \geq \mu_1 a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R;$$

(2h₅) taking $p_i > 1$ as in (2h₁), some positive constants $\theta_i, \mu_2 > 0$ exist such that

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) - \theta_i a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi - \theta_i A_{i,t}(x, t, \xi)t \geq \mu_2 a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R$$

with

$$\theta_i < \frac{1}{p_i}; \quad (2.2.3)$$

(2h₆) for all $\xi, \xi' \in \mathbb{R}^N$, with $\xi \neq \xi'$, it is

$$[a_i(x, t, \xi) - a_i(x, t, \xi')] \cdot [\xi - \xi'] > 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Moreover, let us assume that function $G(x, \mathbf{u})$ satisfies not only hypotheses (2g₀)–(2g₁) but also the following Ambrosetti–Rabinowitz type condition:

(2g₂) taking θ_i as in (2h₅) for all $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we have that

$$0 < G(x, \mathbf{u}) \leq \sum_i \theta_i G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) u_i \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \text{if } |\mathbf{u}| \geq R, \quad \mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_m),$$

with $R > 0$ as in the previous set of hypotheses (2h₃)–(2h₅).

Remark 2.5. We note that hypothesis (2h₄) is satisfied also if $t = 0$ and $|\xi| \geq R$, then from (2h₂) we have $\mu_1 \leq 1$. Furthermore, hypotheses (2h₄) and (2h₅) give

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) \geq (\theta_i \mu_1 + \mu_2) a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \quad (2.2.4)$$

whence, from (2h₂) we have that

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) \geq (\theta_i \mu_1 + \mu_2) \lambda |\xi|^{p_i} \geq 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R. \quad (2.2.5)$$

Summing up, from (2.2.5) and assumption (2.2.2) it follows that a positive constant η_3 exists such that

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) \geq (\theta_i \mu_1 + \mu_2) \lambda |\xi|^{p_i} - \eta_3 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (2.2.6)$$

Remark 2.6. Taking $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we note that (2.1.1) in (2h₁) is not required as hypothesis if (2h₂)–(2h₅) and (2.1.3) hold. In fact, in these assumptions not only (2.2.6) is satisfied but also direct computations imply that

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_1 \Phi_2^i(t) + \eta_2 + \eta_1 (\Phi_2^i(t) + \phi_2^i(t)) |\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \text{for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N.$$

Hence, (2h₁) can be replaced by the weaker condition

(2h'₁) assumptions (2.1.2) and (2.1.3) hold.

Furthermore, taking $t = 0$ and $|\xi| \geq R$ in both (2.2.1) and (2h₅), from (2h₂) it follows $\eta_1 \geq \mu_2 + \theta_i$ so, without loss of generality, we can assume that μ_2 is so that

$$\eta_1 - \mu_2 - \theta_i > 0.$$

Thus, in order to give better growth conditions on function $A_i(x, t, \xi)$, hypotheses (2.2.1) and (2h₅) give

$$\left(\frac{\eta_1 - \mu_2 - \theta_i}{\eta_1 \theta_i} \right) A_i(x, t, \xi) \geq A_{i,t}(x, t, \xi) t \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R. \quad (2.2.7)$$

Hence, (2.2.5), (2.2.7) with hypotheses (2.1.3), (2.2.1) and direct computations imply that $\eta_4 > 0$ exists such that

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_4 |t|^{\frac{\eta_1 - \mu_2 - \theta_i}{\eta_1 \theta_i}} |\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |t| \geq 1, |\xi| \geq R,$$

then (2.2.4) gives

$$a_i(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \leq \frac{\eta_4}{\theta_i \mu_1 + \mu_2} |t|^{\frac{\eta_1 - \mu_2 - \theta_i}{\eta_1 \theta_i}} |\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |t| \geq 1, |\xi| \geq R.$$

Remark 2.7. Taking $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, from (2g₂) we have that

$$0 < G(x, u \mathbf{e}_i) \leq \theta_i G_i(x, u \mathbf{e}_i) u \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } u \in \mathbb{R}, |u| \geq R.$$

Hence, (2g₀) and direct computations imply that $h_i \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, $h_i(x) > 0$ for a.a. $x \in \Omega$, exists such that

$$G(x, u \mathbf{e}_i) \geq h_i(x) |u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} \quad \text{for a.a. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } u \in \mathbb{R}, |u| \geq R. \quad (2.2.8)$$

Thus, if also (2.1.6) holds, from (2.1.9), (2.2.3) and (2.2.8) not only we obtain that

$$1 < p_i < \frac{1}{\theta_i} \leq q_i \quad (2.2.9)$$

but also

$$G(x, u \mathbf{e}_i) \geq h_i(x) |u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} - \sigma_i \quad \text{for a.a. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } u \in \mathbb{R} \quad (2.2.10)$$

for a suitable $\sigma_i > 0$.

Example 2.1. Let us consider

$$G(x, \mathbf{u}) = \sum_i c_i |u_i|^{q_i} + c_* \prod_{i=1}^m |u_i|^{\gamma_i},$$

where we assume that

$$q_i > 1, \quad \gamma_i > 1 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

Then, (2g₀) is verified and for any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ we have

$$G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) = c_i q_i |u_i|^{q_i - 2} u_i + c_* \gamma_i |u_i|^{\gamma_i - 2} u_i \prod_{\substack{j=1 \\ j \neq i}}^m |u_j|^{\gamma_j} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega.$$

If, in addition, we suppose that

$$\gamma_i < q_i \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\},$$

then the generalized Young inequality and direct computations allow us to conclude that also (2.1.6) holds by taking

$$s_{i,j} = (m-1) \gamma_j \frac{q_i - 1}{q_i - \gamma_i} \quad \text{for all } i, j \in \{1, \dots, m\}, j \neq i.$$

Finally, if we have that

$$\sum_i \frac{\gamma_i}{q_i} \geq 1,$$

then hypothesis $(2g_2)$ is verified, too, by taking each $\theta_i \geq \frac{1}{q_i}$.

Up to now, no upper bound is required for the growth of the nonlinear term $G(x, \mathbf{u})$. Anyway, the subcritical assumptions (2.1.7) and (2.1.8) are required for proving the weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition.

Remark 2.8. Let $i, j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, $j \neq i$, be such that $s_{i,j}$ verifies condition (2.1.8). Then $\tilde{q}_i > 0$ exists such that

$$1 < \tilde{q}_i < p_i^*, \quad 0 \leq \tilde{s}_{i,j} := \frac{s_{i,j}\tilde{q}_i}{\tilde{q}_i - 1} < p_j^*. \quad (2.2.11)$$

In fact, if both $p_i < N$ and $p_j < N$, then (2.1.8) implies that

$$p_i p_j^* - N s_{i,j} > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 1 \leq \frac{p_j^*}{p_j^* - s_{i,j}} \leq \frac{p_i p_j^*}{p_i p_j^* - N s_{i,j}} < p_i^*,$$

hence, \tilde{q}_i exists such that

$$\frac{p_i p_j^*}{p_i p_j^* - N s_{i,j}} < \tilde{q}_i < p_i^* \quad (2.2.12)$$

so that both estimates in (2.2.11) hold. On the other hand if $p_i \geq N$, respectively $p_j \geq N$, with $p_i^* = +\infty$ and (2.1.5), respectively $p_j^* = +\infty$, implies that the conditions in (2.2.11) are less restrictive and the existence of \tilde{q}_i and $\tilde{s}_{i,j}$ is easier to prove.

Remark 2.9. Assume that $(2g_0)$ and $(2g_1)$ hold. If for every $i, j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, $j \neq i$, by using the same notations in Remark 2.8, from (2.2.11) and Young inequality it follows that

$$|u_i| |u_j|^{s_{i,j}} \leq \frac{|u_i|^{\tilde{q}_i}}{\tilde{q}_i} + \frac{\tilde{q}_i - 1}{\tilde{q}_i} |u_j|^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}} \leq |u_i|^{\tilde{q}_i} + |u_j|^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}} \quad \text{for any } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m. \quad (2.2.13)$$

Thus, from (2.1.9) and (2.2.13) we obtain that

$$|G(x, \mathbf{u})| \leq \sigma_1 \sum_i \left(1 + |u_i|^{q_i} + \sum_{j \neq i} (|u_i|^{\tilde{q}_i} + |u_j|^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}}) \right) \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m.$$

Hence, setting

$$\bar{q}_i = \max\{q_i, \tilde{q}_i, \tilde{s}_{j,i} : 1 \leq j \leq m, j \neq i\} \quad \text{for any } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (2.2.14)$$

it follows that

$$|G(x, \mathbf{u})| \leq \sigma_0 \sum_i (1 + |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i}) \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m \quad (2.2.15)$$

for a suitable constant $\sigma_0 \geq \sigma_1$.

At last, if $(2g_2)$ is verified too, then from (2.2.9) and (2.2.11) we obtain

$$1 < p_i < \frac{1}{\theta_i} \leq \bar{q}_i < p_i^* \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (2.2.16)$$

Now, we show that the $(wCPS)$ -condition holds. To this aim, the following boundedness result is required (for its proof, see [121, Theorem II.5.1]).

Lemma 2.3. *Let Ω be an open bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^N and consider $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ with $p \leq N$. Suppose that $\gamma > 0$ and $k_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ exist such that*

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \leq \gamma \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} (u-k)^r dx \right)^{\frac{p}{r}} + \gamma \sum_{l=1}^{\nu} k^{\alpha_l} [\text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)]^{1-\frac{p}{N}+\varepsilon_l} \quad \text{for all } k \geq k_0,$$

with $\Omega_k^+ := \{x \in \Omega : u(x) > k\}$ and $r, \nu, \alpha_l, \varepsilon_l$ are positive constants such that

$$1 \leq r < p^*, \quad \varepsilon_l > 0, \quad p \leq \alpha_l < \varepsilon_l p^* + p.$$

Then, $\text{ess sup}_{\Omega} u$ is bounded from above by a positive constant which can be chosen so that it depends only on $\text{meas}(\Omega), N, p, \gamma, k_0, r, \nu, \varepsilon_l, \alpha_l, |u|_{p^*}$ (eventually $|u|_q$ for some $q > r$ if $p^* = +\infty$).

Proposition 2.3. *Assume that hypotheses $(2h_0)$ – $(2h_6)$ and $(2g_0)$ – $(2g_2)$ hold. Then functional \mathcal{J} in (2.1.14) satisfies condition $(wCPS)$ in \mathbb{R} .*

Proof. Taking $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$, let $(\mathbf{u}_n)_n \subset X$, with $\mathbf{u}_n = (u_1^n, \dots, u_m^n)$, be a sequence such that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow \beta \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n)\|_{X'} (1 + \|\mathbf{u}_n\|_X) \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.17)$$

We have to prove that $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_m) \in X$ exists such that

- (i) $\mathbf{u}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{u}$ strongly in W ;
- (ii) $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) = \beta, d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) = 0$.

To this aim, our proof is divided in the following steps:

1. $(\mathbf{u}_n)_n$ is bounded in W ; hence, up to subsequences, $\mathbf{u} \in W$ exists such that

$$\mathbf{u}_n \rightharpoonup \mathbf{u} \quad \text{weakly in } W, \quad \text{i.e., } u_i^n \rightharpoonup u_i \quad \text{weakly in } W_i \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (2.2.18)$$

$$u_i^n \rightarrow u_i \quad \text{strongly in } L^{r_i}(\Omega) \quad \text{if } r_i \in [1, p_i^*[, \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (2.2.19)$$

$$\mathbf{u}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{u} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega; \quad (2.2.20)$$

2. $\mathbf{u} \in L$, then $\mathbf{u} \in X$;

3. for any $k > 0$, let $T_k : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathcal{T}_k : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ be defined as

$$T_k t := \begin{cases} t & \text{if } |t| \leq k \\ k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k \end{cases}$$

and

$$\mathcal{T}_k(t_1, \dots, t_m) := (T_k t_1, \dots, T_k t_m), \quad (2.2.21)$$

then, taking any $k \geq \max\{|\mathbf{u}|_L, R\} + 1$ (with $R \geq 1$ as in our set of hypotheses), we have

$$\|d\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad (2.2.22)$$

and

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow \beta; \quad (2.2.23)$$

4. $\|\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n - \mathbf{u}\|_W \rightarrow 0$, then (i) holds;
5. (ii) is satisfied.

For simplicity, here and in the following we will use the notation $(\varepsilon_n)_n$ for any infinitesimal sequence depending only on sequence $(\mathbf{u}_n)_n$, $(\varepsilon_{k,n})_n$ for any infinitesimal sequence depending not only on $(\mathbf{u}_n)_n$ but also on a fixed integer k . Moreover, b_l will denote any strictly positive constant independent of n .

Step 1. Firstly, we observe that (2.1.18) and (2.2.17) imply that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[u_i^n] = \varepsilon_n \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (2.2.24)$$

Thus, taking $\theta_i, i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, as in hypotheses (2h₅) and (2g₂), and fixing $n \in \mathbb{N}$, from (2.1.14), (2.1.16), (2.2.17) and (2.2.24) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \beta + \varepsilon_n &= \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) - \sum_i \theta_i \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[u_i^n] \\ &= \sum_i \int_{\Omega} (A_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) - \theta_i a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n - \theta_i A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) u_i^n) dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} \left(\sum_i (\theta_i G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) u_i^n) - G(x, \mathbf{u}_n) \right) dx. \end{aligned}$$

Now, fix $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and set

$$\Omega_{n,R}^i = \{x \in \Omega : |(u_i^n(x), \nabla u_i^n(x))| > R\}.$$

Then, we have that

$$\int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_{n,R}^i} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx \leq R^{p_i} \text{meas}(\Omega). \quad (2.2.25)$$

On the other hand, hypothesis (2h₁) implies that

$$\sum_i \int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_{n,R}^i} |A_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) - \theta_i a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n - \theta_i A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) u_i^n| dx \leq b_1,$$

while from assumptions (2h₂) and (2h₅) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_i \int_{\Omega_{n,R}^i} (A_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) u_i^n - \theta_i a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n - \theta_i A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) u_i^n) dx \\ & \geq \mu_2 \sum_i \int_{\Omega_{n,R}^i} a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n dx \geq \mu_2 \lambda \sum_i \int_{\Omega_{n,R}^i} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx. \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, from hypotheses (2.1.6), (2g₂) with (2.1.9) and direct computations we have

$$\int_{\Omega} \left(\sum_i (\theta_i G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) u_i^n) - G(x, \mathbf{u}_n) \right) dx \geq -b_2.$$

Thus, summing up, from the previous estimates and (2.2.25), we obtain that

$$\beta + \varepsilon_n \geq \mu_2 \lambda \sum_i \int_{\Omega_{n,R}^i} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx - b_3 \geq \mu_2 \lambda \sum_i \|u_i^n\|_{W_i}^{p_i} - b_4.$$

Hence, $(\mathbf{u}_n)_n$ is bounded in W and so $\mathbf{u} \in W$ exists such that, up to subsequences, (2.2.18)–(2.2.20) hold.

Step 2. In order to prove that $\mathbf{u} \in L$, arguing by contradiction, we assume that $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ exists such that $p_i < N$ (the proof if $p_i = N$ is simpler) and $u_i \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$, then either

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} u_i = +\infty \tag{2.2.26}$$

or

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} (-u_i) = +\infty. \tag{2.2.27}$$

If (2.2.26) holds, then for any fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we have that

$$\operatorname{meas}(\Omega_k^{i,+}) > 0, \quad \text{with } \Omega_k^{i,+} = \{x \in \Omega : u_i(x) > k\}. \tag{2.2.28}$$

Defining $R_k^+ : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as

$$R_k^+ t := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \leq k \\ t - k & \text{if } t > k \end{cases}, \tag{2.2.29}$$

from (2.2.18) it follows that

$$R_k^+ u_i^n \rightharpoonup R_k^+ u_i \quad \text{weakly in } W_i,$$

whence the sequentially weakly lower semicontinuity of $\|\cdot\|_{W_i}$ gives

$$\int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} |\nabla u_i|^{p_i} dx \leq \liminf_n \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^{i,+}} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx, \quad \text{with } \Omega_{n,k}^{i,+} = \{x \in \Omega : u_i^n(x) > k\}. \tag{2.2.30}$$

On the other hand, from (2.1.18), (2.2.17) and definition (2.2.29) we have that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[R_k^+ u_i^n] \rightarrow 0,$$

so, from (2.2.28) an integer $n_k \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[R_k^+ u_i^n] < \text{meas}(\Omega_k^{i,+}) \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (2.2.31)$$

Now, taking $k > R$ (R as in our set of hypotheses) and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, as $\mu_1 \leq 1$ (see Remark 2.5) from (2.1.16), (2h₂), (2h₄) and direct calculations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[R_k^+ u_i^n] &= \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^{i,+}} \left(1 - \frac{k}{u_i^n}\right) (a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n + A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) u_i^n) dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^{i,+}} \frac{k}{u_i^n} a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n dx - \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k^+ u_i^n dx \\ &\geq \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^{i,+}} a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n dx - \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k^+ u_i^n dx \\ &\geq \mu_1 \lambda \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^{i,+}} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx - \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k^+ u_i^n dx, \end{aligned}$$

which, together with (2.2.31), implies that

$$\mu_1 \lambda \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^{i,+}} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx \leq \text{meas}(\Omega_k^{i,+}) + \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k^+ u_i^n dx \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (2.2.32)$$

We note that

$$\int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k^+ u_i^n dx \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) R_k^+ u_i dx. \quad (2.2.33)$$

In fact, from (2g₀) and (2.2.20) we obtain that

$$G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k^+ u_i^n \rightarrow G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) R_k^+ u_i \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega,$$

while, since (2.1.8) implies that suitable exponents can be chosen so that (2.2.11) holds, from (2.1.6), (2.2.13) and also (2.1.7), (2.2.11), (2.2.19), [46, Theorem 4.9] it follows that a function $h \in L^1(\Omega)$ exists such that

$$|G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k^+ u_i^n| \leq \sigma \left(|u_i^n| + |u_i^n|^{q_i} + \sum_{j \neq i} (|u_i^n|^{\bar{q}_i} + |u_j^n|^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}}) \right) \leq h(x) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega,$$

then Dominated Convergence Theorem applies.

Thus, summing up, from (2.2.30), (2.2.32), (2.2.33) and, again, (2.1.6) and (2.2.13) we have that (2.1.8) and direct computations imply that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} |\nabla u_i|^{p_i} dx \leq b_5 \left(\text{meas}(\Omega_k^{i,+}) + \int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i} dx + \sum_{j \neq i} \int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} |u_j|^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}} dx \right), \quad (2.2.34)$$

with \bar{q}_i as in (2.2.14) and $\tilde{s}_{i,j}$ as in (2.2.11).

At last, Hölder inequality and (2.2.11) imply that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} |u_j|^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}} dx \leq |u_j|_{p_j^*}^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}} [\text{meas}(\Omega_k^{i,+})]^{1 - \frac{\tilde{s}_{i,j}}{p_j^*}} \quad \text{for each } j \neq i,$$

while (2.2.16) and direct computations give

$$\int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i} dx \leq 2^{\bar{q}_i-1} |u_i|^{\frac{\bar{q}_i}{\bar{q}_i} - p_i} \left(\int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} (u_i - k)^{\bar{q}_i} dx \right)^{\frac{p_i}{\bar{q}_i}} + 2^{\bar{q}_i-1} k^{\bar{q}_i} \text{meas}(\Omega_k^{i,+}),$$

so from (2.2.34), Sobolev Embedding Theorems and direct computations we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} |\nabla u_i|^{p_i} dx \leq b_6 \left(\left(\int_{\Omega_k^{i,+}} (u_i - k)^{\bar{q}_i} dx \right)^{\frac{p_i}{\bar{q}_i}} + \sum_j k^{\alpha_j} [\text{meas}(\Omega_k^{i,+})]^{1 - \frac{p_i}{N} + \varepsilon_j} \right) \quad (2.2.35)$$

with $b_6 = b_6(\|\mathbf{u}\|_W) > 0$, where we set

$$\alpha_j = \begin{cases} \bar{q}_i & \text{if } j = i \\ 0 & \text{if } j \neq i \end{cases}, \quad \varepsilon_j = \begin{cases} \frac{p_i}{N} & \text{if } j = i \\ \frac{p_i}{N} - \frac{\bar{s}_{i,j}}{p_j^*} & \text{if } j \neq i \end{cases}.$$

From (2.2.12) it follows that $\varepsilon_j > 0$ for each $j \neq i$, so (2.2.35) with (2.2.16) (here, $\varepsilon_i p_i^* + p_i = p_i^*$) allow us to apply Lemma 2.3 and u_i is essentially bounded from above in contradiction with (2.2.26).

Similar arguments make us to rule out also (2.2.27); hence, it has to be $u_i \in L^\infty(\Omega)$.

Step 3. In order to prove this statement, we extend the main arguments used in the corresponding *Step 3* in the proof of [CS7, Proposition 4.6] to our setting but introducing some technical changes as in [52, Proposition 4.6]. Anyway, for the sake of completeness, here we give the main tools.

Taking $k \geq \max\{\|\mathbf{u}\|_L, R\} + 1$, we define $R_k : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $\mathcal{R}_k : \mathbb{R}^m \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m$ as

$$R_k t = t - T_k t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |t| \leq k \\ t - k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k \end{cases},$$

$$\mathcal{R}_k(t_1, \dots, t_m) = (R_k t_1, \dots, R_k t_m),$$

and denote

$$\Omega_{n,k}^i := \{x \in \Omega : |u_i^n(x)| > k\} \quad \text{for any } n \in \mathbb{N}, i \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

By definition, it follows that

$$\|\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n\|_X \leq \|\mathbf{u}_n\|_X \quad \text{and} \quad \|\mathcal{R}_k \mathbf{u}_n\|_X \leq \|\mathbf{u}_n\|_X \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (2.2.36)$$

Moreover, we have that $\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{u}$ and $\mathcal{R}_k \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{0}$ a.e. in Ω , so from (2.2.18)–(2.2.20), in particular, it follows that

$$\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{u} \text{ a.e. in } \Omega, \quad (2.2.37)$$

$$\mathcal{R}_k \mathbf{u}_n \rightarrow \mathbf{0} \text{ in } L^{r_1}(\Omega) \times \dots \times L^{r_m}(\Omega), \quad \forall (r_1, \dots, r_m) \in [1, p_1^*[\times \dots \times [1, p_m^*[\quad (2.2.38)$$

$$\text{meas}(\Omega_{n,k}^i) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (2.2.39)$$

Fixing any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, from (2.1.18), (2.2.17) and (2.2.36) we have that

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n) \right\|_{X_i'} \|R_k u_i^n\|_{X_i} \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.40)$$

Then, reasoning as in the previous *Step 2* but replacing $R_k^+ u_i$ with $R_k u_i$, from (2.2.40) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_n + \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k u_i^n dx &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[R_k u_i^n] + \int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k u_i^n dx \\ &\geq \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n dx \geq \lambda \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.41)$$

Since arguments similar to those ones used for proving (2.2.33) apply, from (2.2.38) we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega} G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) R_k u_i^n dx \rightarrow 0,$$

then (2.2.41) implies both

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} |\nabla u_i^n|^{p_i} dx \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{i.e.} \quad \|R_k u_i^n\|_{W_i} \rightarrow 0, \quad (2.2.42)$$

and

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla u_i^n dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.43)$$

By means of (2.1.19), if we prove that

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n) \right\|_{X_i'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\},$$

then (2.2.22) holds. To this aim, fixing any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we take $v \in X_i$ such that $\|v\|_{X_i} = 1$. Direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)[v] &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathbf{u}_n)[v] - \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla v dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) v dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} (a_i(x, T_k u_i^n, 0) \cdot \nabla v + A_{i,t}(x, T_k u_i^n, 0) v) dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} (G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G_i(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)) v dx. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.44)$$

We observe that $(2h_1)$ with $\xi = 0$ and $|T_k u_i^n| \leq k$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ imply the boundness of both $A_{i,t}(x, T_k u_i^n, 0)$ and $a_i(x, T_k u_i^n, 0)$ in set $\Omega_{n,k}^i$; hence, from (2.2.39) and direct computations so to “erase” v from the limit, we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} (a_i(x, T_k u_i^n, 0) \cdot \nabla v + A_{i,t}(x, T_k u_i^n, 0) v) dx \rightarrow 0 \quad (2.2.45)$$

uniformly with respect to v . On the other hand, Dominated Convergence Theorem implies that

$$\int_{\Omega} |G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G_i(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)| dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.46)$$

In fact, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} |G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G_i(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)| dx &\leq \int_{\Omega} |G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G_i(x, \mathbf{u})| dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} |G_i(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n) - G_i(x, \mathbf{u})| dx, \end{aligned}$$

where (2g₀) together with (2.2.20), respectively (2.2.37), give

$$G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) \quad \text{and} \quad G_i(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow G_i(x, \mathbf{u}) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega,$$

and from (2.1.6), Young inequality, (2.1.7), (2.2.11), (2.2.19) and [46, Theorem 4.9] we obtain that

$$|G_i(x, \mathbf{u}_n)| \leq b_7 \left(1 + |u_i^n|^{q_i} + \sum_{j \neq i} |u_j^n|^{\tilde{s}_{i,j}} \right) \leq \bar{h}(x) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega$$

for a suitable $\bar{h} \in L^1(\Omega)$, while, again, (2.1.6) and the boundedness of $(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)_n$ in L give

$$|G_i(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)| \leq b_8 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega,$$

so Dominated Convergence Theorem applies and (2.2.46) holds.

Thus, summing up, from (2.2.44)–(2.2.46) we obtain that

$$\left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)[v] \right| \leq \varepsilon_{k,n} + \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} (a_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) \cdot \nabla v + A_{i,t}(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n)v) dx \right|, \quad (2.2.47)$$

where $\varepsilon_{k,n}$ is independent of v . At last, the estimate of the last integral in (2.2.47) can be obtained as in the corresponding *Step 3* in the proof of [52, Proposition 4.6] but testing $\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)$ on the new test functions $v R_k^+ u_i^n$ and $v R_k^- u_i^n$, with $R_k^- : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$R_k^- t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \geq -k \\ t + k & \text{if } t < -k \end{cases}.$$

Then, (2.2.22) holds.

Finally, we have to prove (2.2.23). From (2.1.14), (2.2.21) and direct computations, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n) &= \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_n) - \sum_i \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} (A_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) - A_i(x, \mathcal{T}_k u_i^n, 0)) dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} (G(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)) dx, \end{aligned}$$

where (2.2.1), (2.2.5), (2.2.43), respectively the boundness of $A_i(x, T_k u_i^n, 0)$ and (2.2.39), imply that

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} A_i(x, u_i^n, \nabla u_i^n) dx \rightarrow 0, \quad \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^i} A_i(x, T_k u_i^n, 0) dx \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

On the other hand, from (2.2.15), (2.2.16), (2.2.19), (2.2.20), (2.2.37) and, again, Dominated Convergence Theorem, we have that

$$\int_{\Omega} (G(x, \mathbf{u}_n) - G(x, \mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)) dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Thus, (2.2.23) follows from (2.2.17).

Step 4. For each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, by using the same arguments as in *Step 4* in the proof of [52, Proposition 4.6] but applied to the partial derivative $\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u_i}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)$, we prove that

$$\|T_k u_i^n - u_i\|_{W_i} \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.48)$$

So, condition (i) follows from (2.2.42) and (2.2.48).

Step 5. By applying Proposition 2.1 to the uniformly bounded sequence $(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n)_n$, from (i) and (2.2.37) we have that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k \mathbf{u}_n) - d\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0,$$

which, together with (2.2.22) and (2.2.23), implies (ii). \square

Following the structure of the Section 2.1, we prove that the crucial compactness property stated in Proposition 2.1 holds also for the functional (2.1.31) associated with the model problem (2.0.4). To this aim, we start specializing the conditions furnished at the beginning of this section. More precisely, we require that $R \geq 1$ exists such that the following conditions hold:

($2\tilde{h}_2$) a constant $\mu_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$A(x, u) \geq \mu_0 \quad \text{and} \quad B(x, v) \geq \mu_0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \text{for all } u, v \in \mathbb{R};$$

($2\tilde{h}_3$) there exists $\mu_1 > 0$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} A(x, u) + \frac{1}{p_1} A_u(x, u)u &\geq \mu_1 A(x, u) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |u| \geq R, \\ B(x, v) + \frac{1}{p_2} B_v(x, v)v &\geq \mu_1 B(x, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |v| \geq R; \end{aligned}$$

($2\tilde{h}_4$) there exist $\theta_1, \theta_2, \mu_2 > 0$ such that

$$\theta_1 < \frac{1}{p_1}, \quad \theta_2 < \frac{1}{p_2}, \quad (2.2.49)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - p_1 \theta_1)A(x, u) - \theta_1 A_u(x, u)u &\geq \mu_2 A(x, u) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } u \in \mathbb{R}, \\ (1 - p_2 \theta_2)B(x, v) - \theta_2 B_v(x, v)v &\geq \mu_2 B(x, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } v \in \mathbb{R}; \end{aligned}$$

($2\tilde{g}_2$) taking θ_1, θ_2 as in ($2\tilde{h}_4$), we have

$$0 < G(x, u, v) \leq \theta_1 G_u(x, u, v)u + \theta_2 G_v(x, u, v)v \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(u, v)| \geq R.$$

Remark 2.10. In ($2\tilde{h}_3$), respectively ($2\tilde{h}_4$), we can always assume that

$$\mu_1 < 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_2 < \min \{1 - p_1\theta_1, 1 - p_2\theta_2\}.$$

Hence, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} -p_1(1 - \mu_1)A(x, u) &\leq A_u(x, u)u \leq \frac{1}{\theta_1}(1 - p_1\theta_1 - \mu_2)A(x, u) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |u| \geq R \\ -p_2(1 - \mu_1)B(x, v) &\leq B_v(x, v)v \leq \frac{1}{\theta_2}(1 - p_2\theta_2 - \mu_2)B(x, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |v| \geq R \end{aligned}$$

which imply

$$\begin{aligned} |A_u(x, u)u| &\leq \gamma_1 A(x, u) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |u| \geq R, \\ |B_v(x, v)v| &\leq \gamma_2 B(x, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |v| \geq R, \end{aligned}$$

where $\gamma_i = \max\{p_i(1 - \mu_1), \frac{1}{\theta_i}(1 - p_i\theta_i - \mu_2)\}$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$. Then, it results

$$\begin{aligned} |A_u(x, u)| &\leq \frac{\gamma_1}{R} A(x, u) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |u| \geq R, \\ |B_v(x, v)| &\leq \frac{\gamma_2}{R} B(x, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |v| \geq R. \end{aligned} \tag{2.2.50}$$

On the other hand, from hypotheses ($2\tilde{h}_0$)–($2\tilde{h}_2$), ($2\tilde{h}_4$) and standard computations it follows that

$$A(x, u) \leq a_1 + a_2 |u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1 - p_1\theta_1 - \mu_2)} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } u \in \mathbb{R}, \tag{2.2.51}$$

$$B(x, v) \leq b_1 + b_2 |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}(1 - p_2\theta_2 - \mu_2)} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } v \in \mathbb{R}, \tag{2.2.52}$$

for suitable constants $a_1, a_2, b_1, b_2 > 0$.

Remark 2.11. Arguing as in Remark 2.7, from assumptions ($2\tilde{g}_0$), ($2\tilde{g}_2$) and direct computations we infer the existence of $h_i \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, $h_i(x) > 0$ for a.a. $x \in \Omega$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$, such that

$$G(x, u, 0) \geq h_1(x) |u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } |u| \geq R, \tag{2.2.53}$$

$$G(x, 0, v) \geq h_2(x) |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } |v| \geq R.$$

Thus, if also (2.1.23) and (2.1.24) hold, from (2.2.49) and (2.1.27) it follows that

$$p_1 < \frac{1}{\theta_1} \leq q_1, \quad p_2 < \frac{1}{\theta_2} \leq q_2. \tag{2.2.54}$$

As crucial for the incoming results, here we specialize Remark 2.8 for the exponents (2.1.23) and (2.1.24) in order to obtain, besides the already assumed conditions (2.1.25) and (2.1.26), a proper subcritical growth. For the reader convenience, we provide all the details of the computations.

Remark 2.12. Consider $1 < p_1 < N$ and $1 < p_2 < N$. If $s_1 \in \mathbb{R}$ is as in (2.1.26), then $s_3 > 0$ exists such that

$$1 < s_3 < p_1^*, \quad 0 \leq s_4 := \frac{s_1 s_3}{s_3 - 1} < \frac{p_1}{N} p_2^* < p_2^*. \quad (2.2.55)$$

In fact, (2.1.26) implies that

$$p_1 p_2^* - N s_1 > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 1 < \frac{p_1 p_2^*}{p_1 p_2^* - N s_1} < p_1^*,$$

so $s_3 \in]\frac{p_1 p_2^*}{p_1 p_2^* - N s_1}, p_1^*[$ exists such that (2.2.55) holds.

Thus, from (2.2.55) and Young inequality it follows that

$$|u| |v|^{s_1} \leq \frac{|u|^{s_3}}{s_3} + \frac{s_3 - 1}{s_3} |v|^{s_4} \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2. \quad (2.2.56)$$

Similarly, if $s_2 \in \mathbb{R}$ is as in (2.1.26), then $s_5 > 0$ exists such that

$$1 < s_5 < p_2^*, \quad 0 \leq s_6 := \frac{s_2 s_5}{s_5 - 1} < \frac{p_2}{N} p_1^* < p_1^*, \quad (2.2.57)$$

and

$$|u|^{s_2} |v| \leq \frac{s_5 - 1}{s_5} |u|^{s_6} + \frac{|v|^{s_5}}{s_5} \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2.$$

Remark 2.13. Taking $1 < p_1 < N$ and $1 < p_2 < N$, if $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{g}_1)$ hold, then from (2.1.27) and Remark 2.12 it follows that

$$|G(x, u, v)| \leq C(1 + |u| + |v| + |u|^{\bar{q}_1} + |v|^{\bar{q}_2}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (2.2.58)$$

where we set

$$\bar{q}_1 = \max\{q_1, s_3, s_6\} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{q}_2 = \max\{q_2, s_4, s_5\}. \quad (2.2.59)$$

If also $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ holds, then from (2.2.54), (2.2.55) and (2.2.57) it follows that

$$p_1 < \frac{1}{\theta_1} \leq \bar{q}_1 < p_1^*, \quad p_2 < \frac{1}{\theta_2} \leq \bar{q}_2 < p_2^*. \quad (2.2.60)$$

As in the previous Section, the compactness condition for functional (2.1.31) can be deduced by Proposition 2.3. Nonetheless, as its proof can be performed by using a more direct approach, we prefer to give it here with all the details.

Proposition 2.4. *Assume hypotheses $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_4)$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ hold. Then, functional \mathcal{J} in (2.1.31) satisfies condition (wCPS) in \mathbb{R} .*

Proof. Let $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$ be fixed. We have to prove that if $((u_n, v_n))_n \subset X$ is a sequence such that

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow \beta, \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n)\|_{X'}(1 + \|(u_n, v_n)\|_X) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow +\infty, \quad (2.2.61)$$

then $(u, v) \in X$ exists such that

- (i) $(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v)$ in W (up to subsequences),
 (ii) $\mathcal{J}(u, v) = \beta$, $d\mathcal{J}(u, v) = 0$.

To this aim, our proof is divided in several steps; more precisely, we will prove that:

1. $((u_n, v_n))_n$ is bounded in W ; hence, there exists $(u, v) \in W$ such that, up to subsequences, we have that

$$(u_n, v_n) \rightharpoonup (u, v) \text{ weakly in } W, \quad (2.2.62)$$

$$(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v) \text{ in } L^{r_1}(\Omega) \times L^{r_2}(\Omega) \text{ for any } (r_1, r_2) \in [1, p_1^*] \times [1, p_2^*], \quad (2.2.63)$$

$$(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v) \text{ a.e. in } \Omega; \quad (2.2.64)$$

2. $(u, v) \in L$;
 3. for any $k > 0$, defining $T_k : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$T_k t := \begin{cases} t & \text{if } |t| \leq k \\ k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k \end{cases}$$

and

$$\mathcal{T}_k : (t_1, t_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mapsto \mathcal{T}_k(t_1, t_2) = (T_k t_1, T_k t_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2,$$

then, if $k \geq \max\{|(u, v)|_L, R\} + 1$ (with $R \geq 1$ as in our set of hypotheses), we have

$$\|d\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad (2.2.65)$$

and

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n)) \rightarrow \beta; \quad (2.2.66)$$

4. $\|(T_k u_n - u, T_k v_n - v)\|_W \rightarrow 0$ and then (i) holds;
 5. (ii) is satisfied.

For simplicity, here and in the following we use the notation $(\varepsilon_n)_n$ for any infinitesimal sequence depending only on $((u_n, v_n))_n$, while $(\varepsilon_{k,n})_n$ for any infinitesimal sequence depending also on some fixed integer k . Moreover, we assume that $1 < p_i < N$ for both $i \in \{1, 2\}$, otherwise the proof is simpler.

Step 1. Firstly, we note that (2.1.18) and (2.2.61) imply that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[u_n] = \varepsilon_n, \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[v_n] = \varepsilon_n.$$

Then, taking θ_1, θ_2 as in $(2\tilde{h}_4)$ and $(2\tilde{g}_2)$, and fixing any $n \in \mathbb{N}$, from (2.1.31), (2.1.33), (2.1.34), (2.2.61) and conditions $(2\tilde{h}_2), (2\tilde{h}_4)$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \beta + \varepsilon_n &= \mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - \theta_1 \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[u_n] - \theta_2 \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[v_n] \\ &= \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} [(1 - \theta_1 p_1)A(x, u_n) - \theta_1 A_u(x, u_n)u_n] |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} [(1 - \theta_2 p_2)B(x, v_n) - \theta_2 B_v(x, v_n)v_n] |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} (\theta_1 G_u(x, u_n, v_n)u_n + \theta_2 G_v(x, u_n, v_n)v_n - G(x, u_n, v_n)) dx \\ &\geq \frac{\mu_0 \mu_2}{p_1} \|u_n\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + \frac{\mu_0 \mu_2}{p_2} \|v_n\|_{W_2}^{p_2} - C \end{aligned}$$

as (2.1.23), (2.1.24), $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ and (2.1.27) imply

$$\int_{\Omega} (\theta_1 G_u(x, u_n, v_n)u_n + \theta_2 G_v(x, u_n, v_n)v_n - G(x, u_n, v_n)) dx \geq -C.$$

Hence, $(u, v) \in W$ exist such that (2.2.62)–(2.2.64) hold, up to subsequences.

Step 2. As we want to prove that $(u, v) \in L$, arguing by contradiction we assume that either $u \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$ or $v \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$. If $u \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$, either

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} u = +\infty \tag{2.2.67}$$

or

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} (-u) = +\infty. \tag{2.2.68}$$

For example, suppose that (2.2.67) holds. Then, for any fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k > R$ (with $R \geq 1$ as in the hypotheses), we have

$$\operatorname{meas}(\Omega_k^+) > 0, \tag{2.2.69}$$

with $\Omega_k^+ := \{x \in \Omega \mid u(x) > k\}$. Now, we consider the new function $R_k^+ : t \in \mathbb{R} \mapsto R_k^+ t \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$R_k^+ t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \leq k \\ t - k & \text{if } t > k \end{cases}.$$

From (2.2.62), we have

$$R_k^+ u_n \rightharpoonup R_k^+ u \quad \text{in } W_1.$$

Thus, by the sequentially weakly lower semicontinuity of $\|\cdot\|_{W_1}$, it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla R_k^+ u|^{p_1} dx \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla R_k^+ u_n|^{p_1} dx,$$

i.e.,

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx, \quad (2.2.70)$$

with $\Omega_{n,k}^+ := \{x \in \Omega \mid u_n(x) > k\}$.

On the other hand, by definition, we have

$$\|R_k^+ u_n\|_{X_1} \leq \|u_n\|_{X_1}.$$

Hence, (2.1.18) and (2.2.61) imply that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[R_k^+ u_n] \rightarrow 0;$$

thus, from (2.2.69) an integer $n_k \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[R_k^+ u_n] < \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+) \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (2.2.71)$$

Taking any $k > R$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, from (2.1.33), hypothesis (2 \tilde{h}_3) with $\mu_1 < 1$ (see Remark 2.10) and condition (2 \tilde{h}_2) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[R_k^+ u_n] &= \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \left(1 - \frac{k}{u_n}\right) \left(A(x, u_n) + \frac{1}{p_1} A_u(x, u_n) u_n\right) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \frac{k}{u_n} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx - \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \\ &\geq \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx - \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \\ &\geq \mu_0 \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx - \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n dx, \end{aligned}$$

which, together with (2.2.71), implies that

$$\mu_0 \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \leq \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+) + \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (2.2.72)$$

We note that, from (2.2.64) and (2 \tilde{g}_0), we have

$$G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n \rightarrow G_u(x, u, v) R_k^+ u \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega.$$

Moreover, hypothesis (2.1.26) implies that suitable exponents can be chosen so that (2.2.55) holds. Thus, since $|R_k^+ u_n(x)| \leq |u_n(x)|$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, by using (2.2.56) in (2.1.23), from (2.1.25), (2.2.55) and (2.2.63) we have that a function $h \in L^1(\Omega)$ exists such that

$$|G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n| \leq C(|u_n| + |u_n|^{q_1} + |u_n|^{s_3} + |v_n|^{s_4}) \leq h(x) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega,$$

up to subsequences (see, e.g., [46, Theorem 4.9]). So, by using the Dominated Convergence Theorem, we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n dx = \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u, v) R_k^+ u dx. \quad (2.2.73)$$

Hence, summing up, from (2.2.70), (2.2.72) and (2.2.73) we obtain

$$\mu_0 \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \leq \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+) + \int_{\Omega_k^+} G_u(x, u, v) R_k^+ u dx,$$

which implies, by using again (2.1.23), that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \leq C \left(\text{meas}(\Omega_k^+) + \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u| dx + \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{q_1} dx + \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u| |v|^{s_1} dx \right). \quad (2.2.74)$$

Since (2.1.26) holds, taking s_3, s_4 as in (2.2.55), from (2.2.56), Hölder inequality with conjugate exponents $\frac{p_2^*}{s_4} > 1$ (see (2.2.55)) and $\frac{p_2^*}{p_2^* - s_4}$, and direct computations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u| |v|^{s_1} dx &\leq \frac{1}{s_3} \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{s_3} dx + \frac{s_3 - 1}{s_3} \int_{\Omega_k^+} |v|^{s_4} dx \\ &\leq \frac{1}{s_3} \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{s_3} dx + \frac{s_3 - 1}{s_3} |v|_{p_2^*}^{s_4} [\text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)]^{1 - \frac{s_4}{p_2^*}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.75)$$

Taking \bar{q}_1 as in (2.2.59), in our setting of hypotheses the estimates in (2.2.60) hold, so

$$u \in W_1 \hookrightarrow L^{\bar{q}_1}(\Omega),$$

and, since $k \geq 1$, we have that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |u| dx \leq \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx, \quad \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{q_1} dx \leq \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx, \quad \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{s_3} dx \leq \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx.$$

Thus, (2.2.74) and (2.2.75) imply that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \leq C \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx + \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+) + [\text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)]^{1 - \frac{s_4}{p_2^*}} \right) \quad (2.2.76)$$

with $C = C(\|v\|_{W_2}) > 0$. At last, from (2.2.60) and direct computations we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx &\leq 2^{\bar{q}_1 - 1} \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u - k|^{\bar{q}_1} dx + 2^{\bar{q}_1 - 1} k^{\bar{q}_1} \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+) \\ &\leq 2^{\bar{q}_1 - 1} |u|_{\bar{q}_1}^{\bar{q}_1 - p_1} \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} |u - k|^{\bar{q}_1} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1}{\bar{q}_1}} + 2^{\bar{q}_1 - 1} k^{\bar{q}_1} \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+); \end{aligned}$$

while, as $p_1 < N$, from (2.2.55) it results

$$\begin{aligned} \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+) &= \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)^{1 - \frac{p_1}{N} + \varepsilon_1}, \quad \varepsilon_1 = \frac{p_1}{N} > 0, \\ \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)^{1 - \frac{s_4}{p_2^*}} &= \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)^{1 - \frac{p_1}{N} + \varepsilon_2}, \quad \varepsilon_2 = \frac{p_1}{N} - \frac{s_4}{p_2^*} > 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, summing up, from (2.2.76) we have that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \leq C \left(\left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} |u - k|^{\bar{q}_1} dx \right)^{\frac{p_1}{\bar{q}_1}} + \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)^{1 - \frac{p_1}{N} + \varepsilon_1} + \text{meas}(\Omega_k^+)^{1 - \frac{p_1}{N} + \varepsilon_2} \right),$$

with $C = C(\|u\|_{W_1}, \|v\|_{W_2}) > 0$; so, as $k \geq 1$ implies $1 \leq k^{p_1}$, Lemma 2.3 applies and yields a contradiction to (2.2.67).

Now, suppose that (2.2.68) holds which implies that, fixing any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k \geq R$, it is

$$\text{meas}(\Omega_k^-) > 0 \quad \text{with } \Omega_k^- = \{x \in \Omega : u(x) < -k\}.$$

In this case, by replacing function R_k^+ with $R_k^- : t \in \mathbb{R} \mapsto R_k^- t \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$R_k^- t := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \geq -k \\ t + k & \text{if } t < -k \end{cases},$$

we can reason as above so to apply again Lemma 2.3 which yields a contradiction to (2.2.68). Then, it has to be $u \in L^\infty(\Omega)$.

Similar arguments but considering $\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)$ and $R_k^+ v_n$, respectively $R_k^- v_n$, and the related sets, allow us to prove that it has to be also $v \in L^\infty(\Omega)$.

Step 3. Fixing k as required in this step, define the functions

$$R_k : t \in \mathbb{R} \mapsto R_k t = t - T_k t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |t| \leq k \\ t - k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k \end{cases} \in \mathbb{R},$$

$$\mathcal{R}_k : (t_1, t_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mapsto \mathcal{R}_k(t_1, t_2) = (R_k t_1, R_k t_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2,$$

and the sets

$$\Omega_{n,k}^u := \{x \in \Omega : |u_n(x)| > k\}, \quad \Omega_{n,k}^v := \{x \in \Omega : |v_n(x)| > k\} \quad \text{for any } n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

By definition, we have that

$$\|\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n)\|_X \leq \|(u_n, v_n)\|_X, \quad \|\mathcal{R}_k(u_n, v_n)\|_X \leq \|(u_n, v_n)\|_X \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}; \quad (2.2.77)$$

furthermore, we note that

$$\mathcal{T}_k(u, v) = (u, v) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{R}_k(u, v) = (0, 0) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega.$$

Then, from (2.2.62)–(2.2.64) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n) &\rightharpoonup (u, v) \quad \text{weakly in } W, \\ \mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n) &\rightarrow (u, v) \quad \text{in } L^{r_1}(\Omega) \times L^{r_2}(\Omega) \quad \text{for any } (r_1, r_2) \in [1, p_1^*] \times [1, p_2^*], \\ \mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n) &\rightarrow (u, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.78)$$

and also, again from (2.2.63) and (2.2.64), we have that

$$\mathcal{R}_k(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (0, 0) \quad \text{in } L^{r_1}(\Omega) \times L^{r_2}(\Omega) \quad \text{for any } (r_1, r_2) \in [1, p_1^*] \times [1, p_2^*], \quad (2.2.79)$$

$$\text{meas}(\Omega_{n,k}^u) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{meas}(\Omega_{n,k}^v) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Furthermore, (2.1.18), (2.2.61) and (2.2.77) imply that

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n) \right\|_{X'_1} \|R_k u_n\|_{X_1} \rightarrow 0, \quad \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n) \right\|_{X'_2} \|R_k v_n\|_{X_2} \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.80)$$

Now, by reasonig as in the proof of *Step 2* but replacing $R_k^+ u_n$ and $R_k^+ v_n$ with $R_k u_n$, respectively $R_k v_n$, from (2.2.80) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_n &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[R_k u_n] + \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k u_n dx \\ &\geq \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \geq \mu_0 \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.81)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_n &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[R_k v_n] + \int_{\Omega} G_v(x, u_n, v_n) R_k v_n dx \\ &\geq \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B(x, v_n) |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx \geq \mu_0 \mu_1 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.82)$$

as the same arguments used for proving (2.2.73) apply so that from (2.2.79) we obtain

$$\int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k u_n dx \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\Omega} G_v(x, u_n, v_n) R_k v_n dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Whence, (2.2.81) and (2.2.82) imply not only that

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx \rightarrow 0,$$

i.e.

$$\|R_k u_n\|_{W_1} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \|R_k v_n\|_{W_2} \rightarrow 0, \quad (2.2.83)$$

but also

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B(x, v_n) |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.84)$$

Now, in order to prove (2.2.65), from (2.1.19) it is enough to verify that

$$\left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n)) \right\|_{X'_1} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n)) \right\|_{X'_2} \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.85)$$

To this aim, let $w \in X_1$, $z \in X_2$ be such that $\|w\|_{X_1} = 1$, $\|z\|_{X_2} = 1$. Then, direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[w] &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[w] - \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n \cdot \nabla w dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A_u(x, u_n) w |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} (G_u(x, u_n, v_n) - G_u(x, \mathcal{T}_k u_n, \mathcal{T}_k v_n)) w dx \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.86)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[z] &= \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[z] - \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B(x, v_n) |\nabla v_n|^{p_2-2} \nabla v_n \cdot \nabla z dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B_v(x, v_n) z |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} (G_v(x, u_n, v_n) - G_v(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n)) z dx. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.87)$$

From (2.1.18) and (2.2.61) we have that

$$\left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[w] \right| \leq \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n) \right\|_{X_1'} \rightarrow 0, \quad \left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[z] \right| \leq \left\| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n) \right\|_{X_2'} \rightarrow 0.$$

Moreover, (2.2.50) and (2.2.84) imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A_u(x, u_n) w |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \right| &\leq \frac{\gamma_1}{R} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \rightarrow 0, \\ \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B_v(x, v_n) z |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx \right| &\leq \frac{\gamma_2}{R} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B(x, v_n) |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, it results

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\Omega} (G_u(x, u_n, v_n) - G_u(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n)) w dx \right| &\leq \int_{\Omega} |G_u(x, u_n, v_n) - G_u(x, u, v)| dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} |G_u(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n) - G_u(x, u, v)| dx, \\ \left| \int_{\Omega} (G_v(x, u_n, v_n) - G_v(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n)) z dx \right| &\leq \int_{\Omega} |G_v(x, u_n, v_n) - G_v(x, u, v)| dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} |G_v(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n) - G_v(x, u, v)| dx. \end{aligned}$$

We note that from (2.2.70) and (2.2.64), respectively (2.2.78), we have

$$\begin{aligned} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) &\rightarrow G_u(x, u, v) & \text{and} & \quad G_v(x, u_n, v_n) \rightarrow G_v(x, u, v) & \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \\ G_u(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n) &\rightarrow G_u(x, u, v) & \text{and} & \quad G_v(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n) \rightarrow G_v(x, u, v) & \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \end{aligned}$$

while from (2.2.71) and Young inequality, direct computations imply that

$$|G_u(x, u_n, v_n)| \leq C(1 + |u_n|^{q_1} + |v_n|^{s_4}), \quad |G_v(x, u_n, v_n)| \leq C(1 + |u_n|^{s_6} + |v_n|^{q_2})$$

a.e. in Ω , with s_4 as in (2.2.55) and s_6 as in (2.2.57), and

$$|G_u(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n)| \leq C \quad \text{and} \quad |G_v(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n)| \leq C \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega;$$

thus, (2.2.55), (2.2.57), (2.2.63) and [46, Theorem 4.9] allow us to apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem so that we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} |G_u(x, u_n, v_n) - G_u(x, u, v)| dx &\rightarrow 0, \quad \int_{\Omega} |G_u(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n) - G_u(x, u, v)| dx \rightarrow 0, \\ \int_{\Omega} |G_v(x, u_n, v_n) - G_v(x, u, v)| dx &\rightarrow 0, \quad \int_{\Omega} |G_v(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n) - G_v(x, u, v)| dx \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

So, summing up, from (2.2.86) and (2.2.87), all the previous limits imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[w] \right| &\leq \varepsilon_{k,n} + \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1-2} \nabla u_n \cdot \nabla w dx \right|, \\ \left| \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[z] \right| &\leq \varepsilon_{k,n} + \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B(x, v_n) |\nabla v_n|^{p_2-2} \nabla v_n \cdot \nabla z dx \right|, \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.88)$$

where both $(\varepsilon_{k,n})_n$ represent suitable infinitesimal sequences independent of w , respectively z .

Using the same notation introduced in *Step 2*, we evaluate the last integrals in (2.2.88) by reasoning as in the proof of *Step 3* in [52, Proposition 4.6] but taking new test functions and passing to the limit in

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[wR_k^+ u_n], & \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[wR_{k-1}^+ u_n], \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[wR_k^- u_n], & \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[wR_{k-1}^- u_n], \end{aligned}$$

respectively

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[zR_k^+ v_n], & \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[zR_{k-1}^+ v_n], \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[zR_k^- v_n], & \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[zR_{k-1}^- v_n]. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, we are able to claim that (2.2.85) hold.

At last, direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n)) &= \mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^u} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^v} B(x, v_n) |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx + \int_{\Omega} (G(x, u_n, v_n) - G(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n)) dx, \end{aligned}$$

where from (2.2.58), (2.2.60), (2.2.63), (2.2.64), (2.2.78), and again the Dominated Convergence Theorem we have

$$\int_{\Omega} (G(x, u_n, v_n) - G(x, T_k u_n, T_k v_n)) dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Thus, (2.2.66) follows from (2.2.61) and (2.2.84).

Step 4. By following some ideas introduced in [20] and considering the real map $\psi(t) = te^{\eta t^2}$, where η can be fixed in a suitable way, in particular by applying the same arguments developed in the proof of [55, Proposition 3.6] in order to estimate $\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[\psi(T_k u_n - u)]$, we prove that

$$\|T_k u_n - u\|_{W_1} \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.89)$$

Moreover, reasoning in the same way but considering $\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))[\psi(T_k v_n - v)]$, we have also

$$\|T_k v_n - v\|_{W_2} \rightarrow 0. \quad (2.2.90)$$

Then, condition (i) follows from (2.2.83), (2.2.89) and (2.2.90).

Step 5. By means of Proposition 2.2 applied to the uniformly bounded sequence $(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n))_n$, from (2.2.78), (2.2.89) and (2.2.90) it follows that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n)) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(u, v) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(\mathcal{T}_k(u_n, v_n)) - d\mathcal{J}(u, v)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0.$$

Hence, (ii) follows from (2.2.65) and (2.2.66). \square

2.3 Existence and multiplicity result for the general system

To introduce a suitable decomposition of the space X , we recall that, if $p > 1$ but $p \neq 2$, the spectral properties of the operator $-\Delta_p$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ are still mostly unknown. In fact, in the particular case $p = 2$, $H_0^1(\Omega)$ is a Hilbert space so the classical choice is to consider the sequence of the eigenvalues of $-\Delta$ on Ω , with homogeneous Dirichlet data and their eigenfunctions. In that case, for each $n \geq 1$, the Banach space X can be splitted into the closed subspace spanned by the first n of such eigenfunctions and the matching complementary. If $p \neq 2$ that approach cannot be used as $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ is a Banach space; hence, a different decomposition is required which does not come out from the known sequences of eigenvalues of $-\Delta_p$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

Here, we consider the sequence of pseudo-eigenvalues of the operator $-\Delta_p$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ as introduced in [52, Section 5] which realizes a suitable decomposition of the Sobolev space $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$.

For the reader convenience, we prefer to recall these notions. To start, we recall that if $V \subseteq X$ is a closed subspace of a Banach space X , a subspace $Y \subseteq X$ is a *topological complement* of V , briefly $X = V \oplus Y$, if Y is closed and every $x \in X$ can be uniquely written as $w + y$, with $w \in V$ and $y \in Y$; furthermore, the projection operators onto V and Y are (linear and) continuous (see, e.g., [46, p. 38]). When $X = V \oplus Y$ and V has finite dimension, we say that Y has finite codimension, with $\text{codim } Y = \dim V$.

Let us consider

$$\mathcal{S} = \left\{ v \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) : \int_{\Omega} |v|^p dx = 1 \right\}$$

and

$$I : v \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \mapsto \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^p dx \in \mathbb{R},$$

with

$$\langle dI(v), w \rangle = p \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^{p-2} \nabla v \cdot \nabla w dx \quad \text{for all } v, w \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

We define the first eigenvalue of $-\Delta_p$ in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ as

$$\lambda_1 = \inf_{v \in \mathcal{S}} I(v).$$

It is well known (see [127]) that $\lambda_1 > 0$ and, up to constants, it is attained by a unique $\varphi_1 \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ satisfying

$$\varphi_1 > 0, \quad \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_1|^p dx = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\Omega} |\nabla \varphi_1|^p dx = \lambda_1.$$

In addition, it is $\varphi_1 \in L^\infty(\Omega)$ (particularly $\varphi_1 \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$) and

$$\int_{\Omega} |v|^p dx \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_1} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^p dx \quad \text{for all } v \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Now, consider the linear operator

$$\mathcal{L}_1 : L^p(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad \text{such that} \quad \mathcal{L}_1 v = \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_1|^{p-2} \varphi_1 v dx.$$

Denoted by $L^{p'} = (L^p(\Omega))'$ the dual space of $L^p(\Omega)$, by the previous relations we infer that $\mathcal{L}_1 \in L^{p'}$ and

$$\mathcal{L}_1 \varphi_1 = 1, \quad \|\mathcal{L}_1\|_{L^{p'}} = 1.$$

Furthermore, denoting by \mathcal{L}_1 also its restriction to $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, it follows that $\mathcal{L}_1 \in W^{-1,p}(\Omega)$ and

$$\|\mathcal{L}_1\|_{W^{-1,p}} \leq \sqrt[p]{\frac{1}{\lambda_1}}.$$

The latter relations allow us to establish a new constraint

$$\mathcal{S}_1 = \{v \in \mathcal{S} : \mathcal{L}_1 v = 0\} = \ker(\mathcal{L}_1|_{\mathcal{S}})$$

where the corresponding constrained infimum of I is given by

$$\lambda_2 = \inf_{v \in \mathcal{S}_1} I(v).$$

By definition, it is $\lambda_2 > \lambda_1$ and the infimum is achieved (see [52, Lemma 5.1]). In fact, there exists $\varphi_2 \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ satisfying

$$\int_{\Omega} |\varphi_2|^p dx = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\Omega} |\nabla \varphi_2|^p dx = \lambda_2.$$

Thus, one can define a new linear operator (this time related to φ_2) such that

$$\mathcal{L}_2 : L^p(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad \text{such that} \quad \mathcal{L}_2 v = \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_2|^{p-2} \varphi_2 v dx$$

and a new constraint given by

$$\mathcal{S}_2 = \{v \in \mathcal{S} : \mathcal{L}_1 v = \mathcal{L}_2 v = 0\} = \ker(\mathcal{L}_1|_{\mathcal{S}}) \cap \ker(\mathcal{L}_2|_{\mathcal{S}})$$

with related constrained infimum of I given by

$$\lambda_3 = \inf_{v \in \mathcal{S}_2} I(v).$$

We proceed by iterating this construction. Thus, taken an index $j \geq 2$ and assuming to have defined the positive numbers

$$\lambda_1 < \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_j$$

and the functions

$$\varphi_1, \dots, \varphi_j \in \mathcal{S} \cap L^\infty(\Omega),$$

for any $i \in \{1, \dots, j\}$ one can consider the linear operator associated to each φ_i as

$$\mathcal{L}_i : L^p(\Omega) \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \quad \text{such that} \quad \mathcal{L}_i v = \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_i|^{p-2} \varphi_i v dx,$$

verifying

$$\mathcal{L}_i \in L^{p'}, \quad \|\mathcal{L}_i\|_{L^{p'}} = 1$$

and

$$\mathcal{L}_i \in W^{-1,p}(\Omega), \quad \|\mathcal{L}_i\|_{W^{-1,p}(\Omega)} = (\lambda_i^{p-1} \lambda_1)^{-1/p}.$$

Moreover, it is

$$\varphi_i \in L^\infty(\Omega), \quad \mathcal{L}_i \varphi_i = \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_i|^p dx = 1, \quad \int_{\Omega} |\nabla \varphi_i|^p dx = \lambda_i, \quad \varphi_i \in \bigcap_{l=1}^{i-1} \ker(\mathcal{L}_l|_{\mathcal{S}}), \quad i \geq 2.$$

A further constraint can be defined as

$$\mathcal{S}_j = \{v \in \mathcal{S} : \mathcal{L}_1 v = \dots = \mathcal{L}_j v = 0\} = \bigcap_{i=1}^j \ker(\mathcal{L}_i|_{\mathcal{S}})$$

and the related constrained infimum of I as

$$\lambda_{j+1} = \inf_{v \in \mathcal{S}_j} I(v).$$

Thus, back to our problem, by means of the results stated in [52, Lemmas 5.1-5.4], for $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we define $\lambda_{i,1}$, the first eigenvalue of $-\Delta_{p_i}$ in W_i , which is characterized as

$$\lambda_{i,1} := \inf_{u \in W_i \setminus \{0\}} \frac{\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p_i} dx}{\int_{\Omega} |u|^{p_i} dx}. \quad (2.3.1)$$

It is simple, positive and isolated and has a unique eigenfunction $\varphi_{i,1}$ such that

$$\varphi_{i,1} > 0 \text{ a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \varphi_{i,1} \in L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad |\varphi_{i,1}|_{p_i} = 1. \quad (2.3.2)$$

Then, a sequence of positive real numbers $(\lambda_{i,n})_n$ and a corresponding sequence of pseudo-eigenfunctions $(\psi_{i,n})_n \subset W_i$ exist such that

$$0 < \lambda_{i,1} < \lambda_{i,2} \leq \dots \leq \lambda_{i,n} \leq \dots, \quad \text{with } \lambda_{i,n} \nearrow +\infty \text{ as } n \rightarrow +\infty, \quad (2.3.3)$$

and for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ we have that $\psi_{i,n} \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, hence $\psi_{i,n} \in X_i$. Moreover, taking $k \in \mathbb{N}$ and

$$V_{i,k} := \text{span}\{\psi_{i,1}, \dots, \psi_{i,k}\},$$

a suitable (infinite dimensional) topological complement $Y_{i,k}$ can be found in W_i such that

$$W_i = V_{i,k} \oplus Y_{i,k}$$

and the following inequality holds:

$$\lambda_{i,k+1} \int_{\Omega} |w|^{p_i} dx \leq \int_{\Omega} |\nabla w|^{p_i} dx \quad \text{for all } w \in Y_{i,k} \quad (2.3.4)$$

(cf. [52, Proposition 5.4]). Hence, defining $Y_k^{X_i} := Y_{i,k} \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \subset X_i$, from the boundedness of each $\psi_{i,n}$ we have that $V_{i,k}$ is a subspace of X_i , too, and then

$$X_i = V_{i,k} \oplus Y_k^{X_i},$$

with

$$\dim(V_{i,k}) = k \quad \text{and} \quad \text{codim}(Y_k^{X_i}) = k.$$

Thus, by means of (2.1.10) we have that

$$W = (V_{1,k} \times \dots \times V_{m,k}) \oplus (Y_{1,k} \times \dots \times Y_{m,k})$$

and then from (2.1.29) it follows that

$$X = V_k \oplus Y_k^X$$

with

$$V_k = V_{1,k} \times \dots \times V_{m,k}, \quad Y_k^X = Y_k^{X_1} \times \dots \times Y_k^{X_m}, \quad \dim V_k = \text{codim} Y_k^X < +\infty. \quad (2.3.5)$$

Now, we are able to state our main results.

Theorem 2.1. *For each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ let $p_i > 1$ and assume that $A_i(x, t, \xi)$ satisfies hypotheses $(2h_0)$ – $(2h_6)$. Moreover, suppose that a given function $G(x, \mathbf{u})$ verifies $(2g_0)$ – $(2g_2)$. If, in addition, $\mu_3 > 0$ exists such that*

$(2h_7)$ for every $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ it is

$$A_i(x, t, \xi) \geq \mu_3 |\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \text{for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N;$$

(2g₃) taking $\lambda_1^* := \min \{ \lambda_{i,1} : 1 \leq i \leq m \}$, with $\lambda_{i,1}$ as in (2.3.1), assume that

$$\limsup_{\mathbf{u} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}} \frac{G(x, \mathbf{u})}{\sum_i |u_i|^{p_i}} < \mu_3 \lambda_1^* \quad \text{uniformly a.e. } \Omega;$$

then functional \mathcal{J} in (2.1.14) possesses at least one nontrivial critical point in X ; hence, problem (2.0.1) admits a nontrivial weak bounded solution.

Theorem 2.2. For each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ let $p_i > 1$ and assume that $A_i(x, t, \xi)$ and $G(x, \mathbf{u})$ satisfy hypotheses (2h₀)–(2h₆), (2g₀)–(2g₂). If we also suppose that

(2h₈) for each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ function $A_i(x, \cdot, \cdot)$ is even in $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$;

$$(2g_4) \liminf_{|\mathbf{u}| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{G(x, \mathbf{u})}{\sum_i |u_i|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}}} > 0 \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega;$$

(2g₅) $G(x, \cdot)$ is even in \mathbb{R}^m for a.e. $x \in \Omega$;

then functional \mathcal{J} in (2.1.14) has an unbounded sequence of critical points $(\mathbf{u}_k)_k \subset X$ such that $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}_k) \nearrow +\infty$; hence, problem (2.0.1) admits infinitely many distinct weak bounded solutions.

From now on, assume that for each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ function $A_i(x, t, \xi)$ satisfies (2h₀)–(2h₆) while $G(x, \mathbf{u})$ verifies (2g₀)–(2g₂). Moreover, let $1 < p_i < N$ for each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ (otherwise, the proof is simpler) and, for simplicity, suppose that

$$\int_{\Omega} A_i(x, 0, \mathbf{0}_N) dx = 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}, \quad (2.3.6)$$

with $\mathbf{0}_N = (0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{R}^N$, and

$$\int_{\Omega} G(x, \mathbf{0}) dx = 0 \quad (2.3.7)$$

(otherwise, we replace $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u})$ with $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) - \sum_i \int_{\Omega} A_i(x, 0, \mathbf{0}_N) dx + \int_{\Omega} G(x, \mathbf{0}) dx$ which has the same differential on X).

Firstly, we state the following preliminary result (for the proof, see [52, Proposition 6.5]).

Proposition 2.5. Let $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ be fixed. Then, for any $(t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$ with $|(t, \xi)| \geq R$ we have that

$$A_i(x, st, s\xi) \leq s^{\frac{1}{\theta_i} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1}\right)} A_i(x, t, \xi) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } s \geq 1,$$

with R , θ_i , μ_2 and η_1 as in our set of hypotheses. Moreover, some constants b_1^* , $b_2^* > 0$ exist, independent of i , such that for all $(t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$ it is

$$|A_i(x, t, \xi)| \leq b_1^* \left(1 + |t|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1}\right)}\right) + b_2^* \left(1 + |t|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1}\right) - p_i}\right) |\xi|^{p_i} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \quad (2.3.8)$$

with $\frac{1}{\theta_i} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1}\right) - p_i > 0$ (without loss of generality, as we can take, a priori, either μ_2 small enough or η_1 large enough).

Now, we are able to prove our main results.

Proof of Theorem 2.1. We note that, being $\mu_3\lambda_1^* > 0$, then from hypothesis (2g₃) a constant $\bar{\lambda} \in \mathbb{R}$ exists such that

$$\bar{\lambda} > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \limsup_{\mathbf{u} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}} \frac{G(x, \mathbf{u})}{\sum_i |u_i|^{p_i}} < \bar{\lambda} < \mu_3\lambda_1^* \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega. \quad (2.3.9)$$

Thus, a radius $\rho^* > 0$ exists such that

$$G(x, \mathbf{u}) \leq \bar{\lambda} \sum_i |u_i|^{p_i} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega \text{ if } |\mathbf{u}| \leq \rho^*. \quad (2.3.10)$$

Now, let $\mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m$ be such that $|\mathbf{u}| > \rho^*$, $\mathbf{u} = (u_1, \dots, u_m)$. Then, an integer $i^* \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ exists such that $|u_{i^*}| \geq \frac{\rho^*}{m}$; hence, $1 \leq \left(\frac{m}{\rho^*}\right)^{\bar{q}_{i^*}} |u_{i^*}|^{\bar{q}_{i^*}}$. Thus, from (2.2.15) direct computations allow us to prove the existence of a constant $\sigma^* > 0$ such that

$$|G(x, \mathbf{u})| \leq \sigma^* \sum_i |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega \text{ if } |\mathbf{u}| > \rho^*. \quad (2.3.11)$$

Summing up, from (2.3.10) and (2.3.11), we have that

$$G(x, \mathbf{u}) \leq \bar{\lambda} \sum_i |u_i|^{p_i} + \sigma^* \sum_i |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m. \quad (2.3.12)$$

Then, taking $\mathbf{u} \in X$, from (2.1.14), assumption (2h₇) and inequality (2.3.12) we have that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \sum_i \left(\mu_3 \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_i|^{p_i} dx - \bar{\lambda} \int_{\Omega} |u_i|^{p_i} dx - \sigma^* \int_{\Omega} |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i} dx \right),$$

or better, (2.1.4), (2.2.16), (2.3.1), the definition of λ_1^* and also (2.1.11) imply that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \sum_i \left(\left(\mu_3 - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{i,1}} \right) \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{p_i} - \bar{\sigma} \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{\bar{q}_i} \right) \geq \sum_i \left(\|u_i\|_{W_i}^{p_i} \left(\mu_3 - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_1^*} - \bar{\sigma} \|\mathbf{u}\|_W^{\bar{q}_i - p_i} \right) \right) \quad (2.3.13)$$

for a suitable $\bar{\sigma} > 0$. Thus, from (2.2.16) and (2.3.9) it follows that some constants R_0, ρ_1 exist such that

$$0 < R_0 < 2m \quad \text{and} \quad \mu_3 - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_1^*} - \bar{\sigma} R_0^{\bar{q}_i - p_i} \geq \rho_1 > 0 \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (2.3.14)$$

Since (2.1.11) and $\|\mathbf{u}\|_W = R_0$ imply that $\|u_j\|_{W_j} \geq \frac{R_0}{2m}$ for some $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, from (2.3.13) and (2.3.14) we have that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \rho_1 \sum_i \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{p_i} \geq \rho_1 \|u_j\|_{W_j}^{p_j} \geq \rho_1 \left(\frac{R_0}{2m} \right)^{\bar{p}}$$

with $\bar{p} = \max\{p_i : 1 \leq i \leq m\}$. So, a constant $\rho_0 > 0$ can be found so that

$$\mathbf{u} \in X, \quad \|\mathbf{u}\|_W = R_0 \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \rho_0. \quad (2.3.15)$$

Finally, to prove that also the geometric condition (ii) in Theorem 1.2 is satisfied, fixing any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, we take $\varphi_{i,1} \in X_i$ as in (2.3.2). Then, from (2.1.14), (2.2.10), (2.3.6), (2.3.8) and direct computations, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(t\varphi_{i,1}\mathbf{e}_i) &= \int_{\Omega} A_i(x, t\varphi_{i,1}, t\nabla\varphi_{i,1})dx + \sum_{j \neq i} \int_{\Omega} A_j(x, 0, \mathbf{0}_N)dx - \int_{\Omega} G(x, t\varphi_{i,1}\mathbf{e}_i)dx \\ &\leq b_1^* \text{meas}(\Omega) + b_1^* t^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_{i,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} dx + b_2^* t^{p_i} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla\varphi_{i,1}|^{p_i} dx \\ &\quad + b_2^* t^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_{i,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})-p_i} |\nabla\varphi_{i,1}|^{p_i} dx - t^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} \int_{\Omega} h_i(x) |\varphi_{i,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} dx + \sigma_i \text{meas}(\Omega), \end{aligned}$$

where (2.3.2) and Remark 2.7 imply that all the integrals are finite and $\int_{\Omega} h_i(x) |\varphi_{i,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} dx > 0$. Thus, since $\eta_1, \mu_2 > 0$, from (2.2.9) it follows that

$$\mathcal{J}(t\varphi_{i,1}\mathbf{e}_i) \rightarrow -\infty \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence, $v \in X_i$ exists such that

$$\|v\mathbf{e}_i\|_W > R_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}(v\mathbf{e}_i) < \varrho_0, \quad (2.3.16)$$

R_0 and ϱ_0 as in (2.3.15).

So, since (2.1.14), (2.3.6) and (2.3.7) imply that $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{0}) = 0$, by means of Theorem 1.2 we have that Propositions 2.1 and 2.3 together with (2.3.15) and (2.3.16) imply the existence of a critical point $\mathbf{u}^* \in X$ such that $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}^*) \geq \varrho_0 > \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{0})$. \square

Proof of Theorem 2.2. Since (2h₈) and (2g₅) imply that \mathcal{J} is an even functional on X , in order to apply Corollary 1.1 we have to prove that assumption (\mathcal{H}_{ϱ}) holds for infinitely many ϱ .

For simplicity, here and in the following, b_l will denote any strictly positive constant independent of the index $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$.

Firstly, we prove that, taking any finite dimensional subspace V of X , a radius $R_V > 0$ exists such that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \leq 0 \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{u} \in V, \|\mathbf{u}\|_X \geq R_V. \quad (2.3.17)$$

To this aim, for any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ and $u_i \in X_i$, from (2.3.8), and, then, (2.1.13), direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} A_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) dx &\leq b_1^* \text{meas}(\Omega) \left(1 + |u_i|_{\infty}^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} \right) \\ &\quad + b_2^* \left(1 + |u_i|_{\infty}^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})-p_i} \right) \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{p_i} \\ &\leq b_1 + b_2 \|u_i\|_{X_i}^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} + b_2^* \|u_i\|_{X_i}^{p_i}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.18)$$

On the other hand, from hypothesis $(2g_4)$ it follows that $\bar{\lambda}$ exists such that

$$\liminf_{|\mathbf{u}| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{G(x, \mathbf{u})}{\sum_i |u_i|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}}} > \bar{\lambda} > 0 \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega,$$

so $R_1 > 0$ exists so that

$$G(x, \mathbf{u}) \geq \bar{\lambda} \sum_i |u_i|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } |\mathbf{u}| \geq R_1,$$

while from (2.1.9) we obtain

$$|G(x, \mathbf{u}) - \bar{\lambda} \sum_i |u_i|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}}| \leq \bar{\sigma} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } |\mathbf{u}| \leq R_1.$$

Hence, we have that

$$G(x, \mathbf{u}) \geq \bar{\lambda} \sum_i |u_i|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} - \bar{\sigma} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for all } \mathbf{u} \in \mathbb{R}^m. \quad (2.3.19)$$

Thus, from (2.1.14), (2.3.18) and (2.3.19) we obtain that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \leq \sum_i \left(b_3 + b_2 \|u_i\|_{X_i}^{\frac{1}{\theta_i} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1}\right)} + b_2^* \|u_i\|_{X_i}^{p_i} - \bar{\lambda} \int_{\Omega} |u_i|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} dx \right) \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{u} \in X. \quad (2.3.20)$$

Now, if V is a finite dimensional subspace of X , $V = V_1 \times \cdots \times V_m$, for any $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ also the projection V_i onto X_i is a finite dimensional subspace, so all the norms are equivalent and in particular $\nu_i > 0$ exists such that

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} |u_i|^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} dx \right)^{\theta_i} \geq \nu_i \|u_i\|_{X_i} \quad \text{for all } u_i \in V_i.$$

So, from (2.3.20) it follows that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \leq \sum_i \left(b_3 + b_2 \|u_i\|_{X_i}^{\frac{1}{\theta_i} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1}\right)} + b_2^* \|u_i\|_{X_i}^{p_i} - b_4 \|u_i\|_{X_i}^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} \right) \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{u} \in V, \quad (2.3.21)$$

or better, taking

$$\zeta_i : s \in [0, +\infty[\mapsto \zeta_i(s) = b_3 + b_2 s^{\frac{1}{\theta_i} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1}\right)} + b_2^* s^{p_i} - b_4 s^{\frac{1}{\theta_i}} \in \mathbb{R}, \quad i \in \{1, \dots, m\},$$

estimate (2.3.21) reduces to

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \leq \sum_i \zeta_i(\|u_i\|_{X_i}) \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{u} \in V. \quad (2.3.22)$$

We note that for each $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$ the continuous function ζ_i is such that $\zeta_i(0) = b_3 > 0$ and $\zeta_i(s) \rightarrow -\infty$ as $s \rightarrow +\infty$. Hence, a constant $b_5 > 0$ and a radius $\bar{R} > 0$ exist such that

$$\max_{s \geq 0} \zeta_i(s) \leq b_5 \quad \text{and} \quad \zeta_i(s) < -mb_5 \quad \text{if } s \geq \bar{R} \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}. \quad (2.3.23)$$

Thus, if $(s_1, \dots, s_m) \in (\mathbb{R}_+)^m$ is such that $\sum_i s_i > m\bar{R}$, we have that $s_j \geq \bar{R}$ for some index $j \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, then (2.3.23) and direct computations allow one to prove that

$$\sum_i \zeta_i(s_i) < 0 \quad \text{if} \quad \sum_i s_i > m\bar{R}.$$

Whence, (2.3.17) holds from (2.3.22) with $R_V \geq m\bar{R}$, $s_i = \|u_i\|_{X_i}$.

Now, we want to prove that for any fixed $\varrho > 0$ there exists $k = k(\varrho) \geq 1$ and $R_k > 1$ such that

$$\mathbf{u} \in Y_k^X, \quad \|\mathbf{u}\|_W = R_k \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \varrho \quad (2.3.24)$$

with Y_k^X as in (2.3.5).

To this aim, we note that if $\mathbf{u} \in X$ estimate (2.2.6) gives

$$\int_{\Omega} A_i(x, u_i, \nabla u_i) dx \geq \lambda(\theta_i \mu_1 + \mu_2) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_i|^{p_i} dx - \eta_3 \text{meas}(\Omega) \quad \text{for each } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$$

then (2.1.14) and (2.2.15) imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \sum_i \left(\lambda(\theta_i \mu_1 + \mu_2) \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_i|^{p_i} dx - \eta_3 \text{meas}(\Omega) \right. \\ \left. - \sigma_0 \int_{\Omega} |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i} dx - \sigma_0 \text{meas}(\Omega) \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.3.25)$$

We note that, for every $i \in \{1, \dots, m\}$, inequality (2.2.16) allows us to take $0 < r_i < p_i$ such that

$$\frac{r_i}{p_i} + \frac{\bar{q}_i - r_i}{p_i^*} = 1, \quad \text{i.e.} \quad r_i = p_i \frac{p_i^* - \bar{q}_i}{p_i^* - p_i},$$

so that from (2.1.4), standard interpolation arguments and, fixing any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, condition (2.3.4), it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} |u_i|^{\bar{q}_i} dx \leq \tau_{i, p_i^*}^{\bar{q}_i - r_i} \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{i, k+1}} \right)^{\frac{r_i}{p_i}} \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{\bar{q}_i} \quad \text{for all } u_i \in Y_k^{X_i}. \quad (2.3.26)$$

Thus, from (2.3.25) and (2.3.26), taking $b_6, b_7, b_8 > 0$ such that

$$b_6 = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} \lambda(\theta_i \mu_1 + \mu_2), \quad b_7 = \max_{1 \leq i \leq m} \tau_{i, p_i^*}^{\bar{q}_i - r_i} \sigma_0, \quad b_8 = m(\eta_3 + \sigma_0) \text{meas}(\Omega),$$

we obtain that

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \sum_i \left(\|u_i\|_{W_i}^{p_i} \left(b_6 - \frac{b_7}{\bar{\lambda}_k} \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{\bar{q}_i - p_i} \right) \right) - b_8 \quad \text{for all } \mathbf{u} \in Y_k^X, \quad (2.3.27)$$

with

$$\bar{\lambda}_k = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} (\lambda_{i, k+1})^{\frac{r_i}{p_i}}.$$

We note that (2.3.3) implies

$$\bar{\lambda}_k \rightarrow +\infty \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty, \quad (2.3.28)$$

then, if we assume

$$R_k = \left(\frac{b_6}{2b_7} \bar{\lambda}_k \right)^{\frac{1}{\bar{q}-p}}$$

with

$$p = \min_{1 \leq i \leq m} p_i, \quad \bar{q} = \max_{1 \leq i \leq m} \bar{q}_i,$$

$\bar{q} > p > 1$ from (2.2.16). As limit (2.3.28) gives

$$R_k \rightarrow +\infty \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty, \quad (2.3.29)$$

an integer $k_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that for all $k \geq k_1$ it is $R_k \geq 1$ and

$$R_k^{\bar{q}_i - p_i} \leq R_k^{\bar{q} - p} \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\}.$$

Or better, if $k_2 \geq k_1$ is such that for all $k \geq k_2$ we have $R_k \geq 2m$, taking $k \geq k_2$ and $\mathbf{u} \in Y_k^X$ such that $\|\mathbf{u}\|_W = R_k$, direct computations imply not only that

$$b_6 - \frac{b_7}{\bar{\lambda}_k} \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{\bar{q}_i - p_i} \geq b_6 - \frac{b_7}{\bar{\lambda}_k} R_k^{\bar{q}_i - p_i} \geq \frac{b_6}{2} \quad \text{for all } i \in \{1, \dots, m\},$$

but also

$$\sum_i \|u_i\|_{W_i}^{p_i} \geq \left(\frac{R_k}{2m} \right)^p.$$

Hence, (2.3.27) gives

$$\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{u}) \geq \frac{b_6}{2} \left(\frac{R_k}{2m} \right)^p - b_8 \quad \text{if } \mathbf{u} \in Y_k^X \text{ is such that } \|\mathbf{u}\|_W = R_k.$$

Thus, taking any $\varrho > 0$, (2.3.24) follows from (2.3.29) if $k = k(\varrho) \in \mathbb{N}$ is large enough. Moreover, taking $\bar{k} > k$, the \bar{k} -dimensional space $V_{\bar{k}}$, defined as in (2.3.5), is such that not only $\text{codim} Y_{\bar{k}} < \dim V_{\bar{k}}$ but also (2.3.17) holds. Whence, assumption (\mathcal{H}_ϱ) is verified with $\mathcal{M}_\varrho = \{\mathbf{u} \in X : \|\mathbf{u}\|_W = R_k\}$.

Finally, since (2.3.6) and (2.3.7) give $\mathcal{J}(\mathbf{0}) = 0$, from Propositions 2.1, 2.3 and the arbitrariness of ϱ for condition (\mathcal{H}_ϱ) , we have that Corollary 1.1 applies to \mathcal{J} in X and a sequence of diverging critical levels exists. \square

2.4 Existence and multiplicity results for the model system

In order to prove a multiplicity result, for each $i \in \{1, 2\}$ we make use of the decomposition of W_i as introduced in the previous Section.

Thus, for all $m \in \mathbb{N}$, in our setting (2.1.28) we have

$$W = (V_{1,m} \times V_{2,m}) \oplus (Y_{1,m} \times Y_{2,m})$$

and then, since $V_{i,m}$ is also a finite dimensional subspace of X_i ,

$$X = (V_{1,m} \times V_{2,m}) \oplus (Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}),$$

with

$$Y_m^{X_i} = Y_{i,m} \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \subset X_i \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2\}.$$

We note that it results $X_i = V_{i,m} \oplus Y_m^{X_i}$ with

$$\dim V_{i,m} = m \quad \text{and} \quad \text{codim} Y_m^{X_i} = m.$$

Now, we can state our main results.

Theorem 2.3. *Taking $p_1, p_2 > 1$, let $A(x, u)$ and $B(x, v)$ be two given real functions defined in $\Omega \times \mathbb{R}$ such that conditions $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_4)$ hold. Moreover, suppose that the real function $G(x, u, v)$, defined in $\Omega \times \mathbb{R}^2$, satisfies hypotheses $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{g}_2)$. In addition, we assume that*

$$(2\tilde{g}_3) \quad \limsup_{(u,v) \rightarrow 0} \frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{p_1} + |v|^{p_2}} < \mu_0 \min \left\{ \frac{\lambda_{1,1}}{p_1}, \frac{\lambda_{2,1}}{p_2} \right\} \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega,$$

with $\lambda_{i,1}, i \in \{1, 2\}$, as in (2.3.1). Then, functional \mathcal{J} in (2.1.31) possesses at least one nontrivial critical point in X ; hence, problem (2.0.4) admits a nontrivial weak bounded solution.

Theorem 2.4. *Taking $p_1, p_2 > 1$, suppose that $A(x, u)$, $B(x, v)$ and $G(x, u, v)$ satisfy hypotheses $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_4)$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{g}_2)$. Moreover, assume also that*

$$(2\tilde{h}_5) \quad A(x, \cdot), B(x, \cdot) \text{ are even in } \mathbb{R} \text{ for a.e. } x \in \Omega;$$

$$(2\tilde{g}_4) \quad \liminf_{|(u,v)| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}} > 0 \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega;$$

$$(2\tilde{g}_5) \quad G(x, \cdot, \cdot) \text{ is even in } \mathbb{R}^2 \text{ for a.e. } x \in \Omega.$$

Then, the even functional \mathcal{J} in (2.1.31) possesses a sequence of critical points $((u_m, v_m))_m \subset X$ such that $\mathcal{J}(u_m, v_m) \nearrow +\infty$; hence, problem (2.0.4) admits infinitely many distinct weak bounded solutions.

Remark 2.14. Subcritical growth conditions (2.1.26) are stronger than the “classical” ones required for Laplacian coupled systems in [43]. In our setting, we need it for proving that weak limits of (CPS) -sequences in the product Sobolev space W belong also to L , i.e. they are bounded functions (see *Step 2* in the proof of Proposition 2.4).

Before turning to the proof of Theorems 2.3, 2.4, we provide some examples.

Example 2.2. Let $p_i > 1$, with $i \in \{1, 2\}$, and consider

$$A(x, u) = A_1(x) + A_2(x)|u|^{\gamma_1}, \quad B(x, v) = B_1(x) + B_2(x)|v|^{\gamma_2} \quad (2.4.1)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $u, v \in \mathbb{R}$, where

$$\gamma_i > 1 \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (2.4.2)$$

and

$$A_i \in L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad B_i \in L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2\}. \quad (2.4.3)$$

If we assume that a constant $\mu_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$A_1(x), B_1(x) \geq \mu_0, \quad A_2(x), B_2(x) \geq 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \quad (2.4.4)$$

then conditions $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_3)$ are satisfied with

$$A_u(x, u) = \gamma_1 A_2(x)|u|^{\gamma_1-2}u, \quad B_v(x, v) = \gamma_2 B_2(x)|v|^{\gamma_2-2}v$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $u, v \in \mathbb{R}$. Moreover, if we take

$$0 < \theta_i < \frac{1}{p_i + \gamma_i} \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (2.4.5)$$

also $(2\tilde{h}_4)$ holds with $\mu_2 = \min\{1 - p_1\theta_1 - \gamma_1\theta_1, 1 - p_2\theta_2 - \gamma_2\theta_2\} > 0$.

Example 2.3. Consider

$$G(x, u, v) = |u|^{q_1} + c_*|u|^{\gamma_3}|v|^{\gamma_4} + |v|^{q_2} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } u, v \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.4.6)$$

with $c_* \in \mathbb{R}$ and

$$q_1 > 1, \quad q_2 > 1, \quad \gamma_3 > 1, \quad \gamma_4 > 1. \quad (2.4.7)$$

Then, condition $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ is satisfied with

$$\begin{aligned} G_u(x, u, v) &= q_1|u|^{q_1-2}u + \gamma_3 c_*|u|^{\gamma_3-2}u|v|^{\gamma_4}, \\ G_v(x, u, v) &= \gamma_4 c_*|u|^{\gamma_3}|v|^{\gamma_4-2}v + q_2|v|^{q_2-2}v \end{aligned}$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $u, v \in \mathbb{R}$. Moreover, if also

$$\gamma_3 < q_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_4 < q_2, \quad (2.4.8)$$

then from Young inequality and direct computations it follows that (2.1.23) and (2.1.24) hold with

$$\begin{aligned} s_1 = \gamma_4 \alpha_1, \quad \text{with } \alpha_1 = \frac{q_1 - 1}{q_1 - \gamma_3} > 1 &\iff q_1 - 1 = (\gamma_3 - 1) \frac{\alpha_1}{\alpha_1 - 1}, \\ s_2 = \gamma_3 \alpha_2, \quad \text{with } \alpha_2 = \frac{q_2 - 1}{q_2 - \gamma_4} > 1 &\iff q_2 - 1 = (\gamma_4 - 1) \frac{\alpha_2}{\alpha_2 - 1}, \end{aligned} \quad (2.4.9)$$

for a suitable $\sigma > 0$. At last, if

$$c_* \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\gamma_3}{q_1} + \frac{\gamma_4}{q_2} \geq 1, \quad (2.4.10)$$

taking

$$\theta_i \geq \frac{1}{q_i} \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (2.4.11)$$

we have that also (\tilde{g}_2) is verified.

We note that if $G(x, u, v)$ in (2.4.6) has $c_* = 0$, then problem (2.0.4) with such a nonlinear term reduces to an *uncoupled system*.

Example 2.4. Consider

$$G(x, u, v) = |u|^{q_1} + |u|^{\gamma_3} \log(v^2 + 1) + \log(u^2 + 1) |v|^{\gamma_4} + |v|^{q_2} \quad (2.4.12)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $u, v \in \mathbb{R}$, with

$$q_1 > 1, \quad q_2 > 1, \quad \gamma_3 > 1, \quad \gamma_4 > 1. \quad (2.4.13)$$

Then, condition $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ is satisfied with

$$\begin{aligned} G_u(x, u, v) &= q_1 |u|^{q_1-2} u + \gamma_3 |u|^{\gamma_3-2} u \log(v^2 + 1) + \frac{2u}{u^2 + 1} |v|^{\gamma_4}, \\ G_v(x, u, v) &= |u|^{\gamma_3} \frac{2v}{v^2 + 1} + \gamma_4 \log(1 + u^2) |v|^{\gamma_4-2} v + q_2 |v|^{q_2-2} v \end{aligned}$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $u, v \in \mathbb{R}$. Moreover, assume also that

$$\gamma_3 < q_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \gamma_4 < q_2. \quad (2.4.14)$$

From (2.4.13) and (2.4.14), taking any $\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$\varepsilon < \gamma_4 \frac{q_1 - \gamma_3}{q_1 - 1} \implies \varepsilon < \gamma_4 \quad \text{and} \quad 0 < \frac{\gamma_3 \gamma_4 - \varepsilon}{\gamma_4 - \varepsilon} \leq q_1 \quad (2.4.15)$$

direct computations imply that a suitable constant $C > 0$ exists such that

$$0 \leq \log(v^2 + 1) \leq |v|^\varepsilon + C \quad \text{for all } v \in \mathbb{R},$$

then from Young inequality applied to $\frac{\gamma_4}{\varepsilon} > 1$ and (2.4.14), (2.4.15) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} ||u|^{\gamma_3-2} u \log(v^2 + 1)| &\leq |u|^{\gamma_3-1} |v|^\varepsilon + C |u|^{\gamma_3-1} \\ &\leq C (|u|^{\frac{\gamma_3 \gamma_4 - \varepsilon}{\gamma_4 - \varepsilon} - 1} + |v|^{\gamma_4} + |u|^{\gamma_3-1}) \leq C (1 + |u|^{q_1-1} + |v|^{\gamma_4}). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, by applying similar arguments also in order to estimate $\log(1 + u^2)|v|^{\gamma_4-2}v$ we prove that (2.1.23) and (2.1.24) hold with

$$s_1 = \gamma_4 \quad \text{and} \quad s_2 = \gamma_3, \quad (2.4.16)$$

for a suitable $\sigma > 0$. At last, taking

$$\theta_1 \geq \frac{1}{\gamma_3} \quad \text{and} \quad \theta_2 \geq \frac{1}{\gamma_4} \quad (2.4.17)$$

we have that also $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ is verified as (2.4.14) implies $\theta_i q_i \geq 1$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$.

Some corollaries to previous Theorem 2.4 can be stated, both when condition $(2\tilde{g}_4)$ is replaced by a stronger assumption, which is easier to verify, and when such a theorem is applied to the special cases obtained by coupling Example 2.2 with Example 2.3, respectively Example 2.4.

Corollary 2.1. *Taking $p_1, p_2 > 1$, suppose that $A(x, u)$, $B(x, v)$ and $G(x, u, v)$ satisfy hypotheses $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_5)$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ and $(2\tilde{g}_5)$. Moreover, assume also that*

$$(2\tilde{g}_6) \quad \inf\{G(x, w, z) : x \in \Omega, (w, z) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \text{ such that } |(w, z)| = R\} > 0, \text{ with } R \text{ as in } (g_2);$$

$$(2\tilde{g}_7) \quad \theta_1 = \theta_2, \text{ with } \theta_1, \theta_2 \text{ as in } (2\tilde{h}_4) \text{ and } (2\tilde{g}_2).$$

Then, the even functional \mathcal{J} in (2.1.31) possesses a sequence of critical points $((u_m, v_m))_m \subset X$ such that $\mathcal{J}(u_m, v_m) \nearrow +\infty$; hence, problem (2.0.4) admits infinitely many distinct weak bounded solutions.

Corollary 2.2. *Let us consider problem (2.0.4) with $p_1, p_2 > 1$, and $A(x, u)$, $B(x, v)$ as in (2.4.1) such that conditions (2.4.2)–(2.4.4) hold. Moreover, consider $G(x, u, v)$ defined as in (2.4.6) and such that (2.4.7)–(2.4.8), (2.4.10) are satisfied. If*

$$p_1 + \gamma_1 < q_1 < p_1^*, \quad p_2 + \gamma_2 < q_2 < p_2^*, \quad (2.4.18)$$

$$\gamma_4 \frac{q_1 - 1}{q_1 - \gamma_3} < \frac{p_1}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_1^*}\right) p_2^*, \quad \gamma_3 \frac{q_2 - 1}{q_2 - \gamma_4} < \frac{p_2}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_2^*}\right) p_1^*, \quad (2.4.19)$$

then functional

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_1(u, v) = & \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} (A_1(x) + A_2(x)|u|^{\gamma_1}) |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} (B_1(x) + B_2(x)|v|^{\gamma_2}) |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx \\ & - \int_{\Omega} (|u|^{q_1} + c_* |u|^{\gamma_3} |v|^{\gamma_4} + |v|^{q_2}) dx \end{aligned}$$

has infinitely many critical points in X .

Corollary 2.3. *Let us consider problem (2.0.4) with $p_1, p_2 > 1$, and $A(x, u), B(x, v)$ as in (2.4.1) such that conditions (2.4.2)–(2.4.4) hold. Moreover, consider $G(x, u, v)$ defined as in (2.4.12) and such that (2.4.13) is satisfied. If*

$$p_1 + \gamma_1 < \gamma_3 < q_1 < p_1^*, \quad p_2 + \gamma_2 < \gamma_4 < q_2 < p_2^*, \quad (2.4.20)$$

$$\gamma_3 < \frac{p_2}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_2^*}\right) p_1^*, \quad \gamma_4 < \frac{p_1}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_1^*}\right) p_2^*, \quad (2.4.21)$$

then functional

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_2(u, v) &= \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} (A_1(x) + A_2(x)|u|^{\gamma_1}) |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} (B_1(x) + B_2(x)|v|^{\gamma_2}) |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} (|u|^{q_1} + |u|^{\gamma_3} \log(v^2 + 1) + \log(u^2 + 1)|v|^{\gamma_4} + |v|^{q_2}) dx \end{aligned}$$

has infinitely many critical points in X .

Now, we can prove our main results. To this aim, for simplicity we assume that

$$\int_{\Omega} G(x, 0, 0) dx = 0, \quad (2.4.22)$$

otherwise we can replace functional $\mathcal{J}(u, v)$ in (2.1.31) with $\mathcal{J}(u, v) + \int_{\Omega} G(x, 0, 0) dx$ which has the same differential $d\mathcal{J}(u, v)$ in (2.1.32).

Proof of Theorem 2.3. Without loss of generality, we suppose $1 < p_i < N$ for both $i \in \{1, 2\}$, otherwise the proof is simpler.

Moreover, as $\mu_0 \min \left\{ \frac{\lambda_{1,1}}{p_1}, \frac{\lambda_{2,1}}{p_2} \right\} > 0$, from (2.7.3) we can take $\bar{\lambda} > 0$ such that

$$\limsup_{(u,v) \rightarrow 0} \frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{p_1} + |v|^{p_2}} < \bar{\lambda} < \mu_0 \min \left\{ \frac{\lambda_{1,1}}{p_1}, \frac{\lambda_{2,1}}{p_2} \right\}. \quad (2.4.23)$$

We claim that (2.2.58) and (2.4.23) imply the existence of a suitable constant $\sigma^* > 0$ such that

$$G(x, u, v) \leq \bar{\lambda}(|u|^{p_1} + |v|^{p_2}) + \sigma^*(|u|^{\bar{q}_1} + |v|^{\bar{q}_2}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2. \quad (2.4.24)$$

In fact, from one hand inequality (2.4.23) implies that a radius $\varrho^* > 0$ exists such that

$$G(x, u, v) \leq \bar{\lambda}(|u|^{p_1} + |v|^{p_2}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega \text{ if } |(u, v)| < \varrho^*.$$

On the other hand, if $|(u, v)| \geq \varrho^*$, then either $|u| \geq \frac{\varrho^*}{2}$, hence $1 \leq \frac{2}{\varrho^*}|u|$ and $|u| \leq \left(\frac{2}{\varrho^*}\right)^{\bar{q}_1-1} |u|^{\bar{q}_1}$, or $|v| \geq \frac{\varrho^*}{2}$, hence $1 \leq \frac{2}{\varrho^*}|v|$ and $|v| \leq \left(\frac{2}{\varrho^*}\right)^{\bar{q}_2-1} |v|^{\bar{q}_2}$. So, analyzing all the possible cases, direct computations imply that

$$1 \leq \frac{2}{\varrho^*}(|u| + |v|), \quad |u| + |v| \leq 2 \left(\frac{2}{\varrho^*}\right)^{\bar{q}_1-1} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} + 2 \left(\frac{2}{\varrho^*}\right)^{\bar{q}_2-1} |v|^{\bar{q}_2} \quad \text{if } |(u, v)| \geq \varrho^*.$$

Whence, (2.4.24) follows from (2.2.58).

Now, from definition (2.1.31), hypothesis ($2\tilde{h}_2$) and estimate (2.4.24), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq \frac{\mu_0}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \frac{\mu_0}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx - \bar{\lambda} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p_1} dx - \bar{\lambda} \int_{\Omega} |v|^{p_2} dx \\ &\quad - \sigma^* \int_{\Omega} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx - \sigma^* \int_{\Omega} |v|^{\bar{q}_2} dx, \end{aligned}$$

or better, from (2.1.4), (2.2.60) and (2.3.1) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq \|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{p_1} - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{1,1}} - \sigma^* \tau_{1, \bar{q}_1} \|u\|_{W_1}^{\bar{q}_1 - p_1} \right) \\ &\quad + \|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{p_2} - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{2,1}} - \sigma^* \tau_{2, \bar{q}_2} \|v\|_{W_2}^{\bar{q}_2 - p_2} \right) \\ &\geq \|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{p_1} - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{1,1}} - \sigma^* \tau_{1, \bar{q}_1} \|(u, v)\|_W^{\bar{q}_1 - p_1} \right) \\ &\quad + \|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2} \left(\frac{\mu_0}{p_2} - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{2,1}} - \sigma^* \tau_{2, \bar{q}_2} \|(u, v)\|_W^{\bar{q}_2 - p_2} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (2.4.25)$$

for all $(u, v) \in X$. Thus, from (2.2.60) and (2.4.23) we have that a radius $R_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$\frac{\mu_0}{p_1} - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{1,1}} - \sigma^* \tau_{1, \bar{q}_1} R_0^{\bar{q}_1 - p_1} > 0, \quad \frac{\mu_0}{p_2} - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{2,1}} - \sigma^* \tau_{2, \bar{q}_2} R_0^{\bar{q}_2 - p_2} > 0; \quad (2.4.26)$$

hence, (2.4.25), (2.4.26) and direct computations imply the existence of a constant $\varrho_0 > 0$ such that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \varrho_0 \quad \text{if } \|(u, v)\|_W = R_0. \quad (2.4.27)$$

At last, taking for example $\varphi_{1,1} \in X_1$, with $\varphi_{1,1}$ first eigenvalue of $-\Delta_{p_1}$ in W_1 so that (2.3.2) holds with $i = 1$, and $R \geq 1$ as in (2.2.53), we can consider

$$\bar{u}(x) = R \frac{\varphi_{1,1}(x)}{|\varphi_{1,1}(x)|} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega. \quad (2.4.28)$$

Then, fixing any $t \geq 1$, from (2.1.31), (2.2.51), (2.2.53) and direct computations it follows that

$$\mathcal{J}(t\bar{u}, 0) \leq t^{p_1} \frac{a_1}{p_1} \|\bar{u}\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + t^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\mu_2)} \frac{a_2}{p_1} |\bar{u}|_{\infty}^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\theta_1 p_1 - \mu_2)} \|\bar{u}\|_{W_1}^{p_1} - t^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} \int_{\Omega} h_1(x) |\bar{u}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} dx,$$

with $0 < \int_{\Omega} h_1(x) |\bar{u}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} dx < +\infty$ as $\bar{u}, h_1 \in L^{\infty}(\Omega)$ with both $h_1(x) > 0$ (see Remark 2.11) and $\bar{u}(x) > 0$ (from (2.3.1) and (2.4.28)) for a.e. $x \in \Omega$. Hence, (2.2.49) implies that

$$\mathcal{J}(t\bar{u}, 0) \rightarrow -\infty \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Thus, $\bar{e}_1 \in X_1$ exists such that

$$\|(\bar{e}_1, 0)\|_W > R_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}(\bar{e}_1, 0) < \varrho_0. \quad (2.4.29)$$

Finally, from (2.4.22) we have that $\mathcal{J}(0, 0) = 0$ and, summing up, Propositions 2.2 and 2.4 together with (2.4.27), (2.4.29) allow us to apply Theorem 1.2. So, a critical point $(u^*, v^*) \in X$ exists such that $\mathcal{J}(u^*, v^*) \geq \varrho_0 > 0$. \square

Now, we want to prove Theorem 2.4 by applying Corollary 1.1. To this aim, we need the following ‘‘geometric’’ estimates.

Proposition 2.6. *Assume that hypotheses $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_2)$, $(2\tilde{h}_4)$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ and $(2\tilde{g}_4)$ hold. Then, taking any finite dimensional subspace V of X , there exists $R_V > 0$ such that*

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \leq 0 \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in V, \|(u, v)\|_X \geq R_V.$$

In particular, \mathcal{J} is bounded from above in V .

Proof. Considering (2.1.30), from (2.1.31), (2.2.51), (2.2.52) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\leq \frac{a_1}{p_1} \|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + \frac{a_2}{p_1} |u|_{\infty}^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-p_1\theta_1-\mu_2)} \|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + \frac{b_1}{p_2} \|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2} \\ &\quad + \frac{b_2}{p_2} |v|_{\infty}^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}(1-p_2\theta_2-\mu_2)} \|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2} - \int_{\Omega} G(x, u, v) dx \\ &\leq \frac{a_1}{p_1} \|u\|_{X_1}^{p_1} + \frac{a_2}{p_1} \|u\|_{X_1}^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\mu_2)} + \frac{b_1}{p_2} \|v\|_{X_2}^{p_2} + \frac{b_2}{p_2} \|v\|_{X_2}^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}(1-\mu_2)} - \int_{\Omega} G(x, u, v) dx \end{aligned}$$

for all $(u, v) \in X$. Now, from $(2\tilde{g}_4)$ we can take $\bar{\lambda} \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\liminf_{|(u,v)| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}} > \bar{\lambda} > 0 \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega,$$

then $R_1 > 0$ exists such that

$$G(x, u, v) \geq \bar{\lambda} (|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega \text{ if } |(u, v)| \geq R_1. \quad (2.4.30)$$

Thus, taking $(u, v) \in V$ such that

$$|(u, v)|_{\infty} > R_1 \quad \implies \quad \text{meas}(\Omega_{R_1}) > 0 \quad (2.4.31)$$

with $\Omega_{R_1} = \{x \in \Omega : |(u(x), v(x))| > R_1\}$. Then, since (2.1.27) implies

$$\int_{\Omega \setminus \Omega_{R_1}} |G(x, u, v)| dx \leq C_1$$

for a suitable $C_1 > 0$, from (2.4.30), (2.4.31) and direct computations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} G(x, u, v) dx &\geq \bar{\lambda} \int_{\Omega_{R_1}} (|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}) dx - C_1 \\ &\geq \bar{\lambda} \left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} dx + \int_{\Omega} |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}} dx \right) - C_2 \end{aligned}$$

for a suitable $C_2 > 0$. At last, summing up, as all the norms are equivalent in the finite dimensional space $V = V_1 \times V_2$ and the same is in both the projections V_1 in X_1 and V_2 in X_2 , if $\|(u, v)\|_X$ is large enough then (2.4.31) holds and we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\leq \frac{a_1}{p_1} \|u\|_{X_1}^{p_1} + \frac{a_2}{p_1} \|u\|_{X_1}^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\mu_2)} \\ &\quad + \frac{b_1}{p_2} \|v\|_{X_2}^{p_2} + \frac{b_2}{p_2} \|v\|_{X_2}^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}(1-\mu_2)} - C_3 \|u\|_{X_1}^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} - C_4 \|v\|_{X_2}^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}} + C_5 \end{aligned}$$

for suitable constants $C_j > 0$; hence, condition (2.2.49) implies that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \rightarrow -\infty \quad \text{as } \|(u, v)\|_X \rightarrow +\infty$$

which completes the proof. \square

Proposition 2.7. *Assume that hypotheses $(2\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{h}_2)$, $(2\tilde{h}_4)$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ – $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ hold. Then, for any fixed $\varrho \in \mathbb{R}$ there exists $m = m(\varrho) \geq 1$ and $r_m > 0$ such that*

$$(u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}, \quad \|(u, v)\|_W = r_m \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \varrho.$$

Proof. The proof is essentially as in [52, Proposition 6.4], carefully extended to a system. For completeness, we give here all the details and, without loss of generality, we suppose $1 < p_i < N$ for both $i \in \{1, 2\}$ (otherwise, the proof is simpler).

Taking any $(u, v) \in X$, from (2.1.31), hypothesis $(2\tilde{h}_2)$, (2.2.58) and direct computations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq \frac{\mu_0}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \frac{\mu_0}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx \\ &\quad - C_1 \int_{\Omega} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx - C_1 \int_{\Omega} |v|^{\bar{q}_2} dx - C_2 \end{aligned} \tag{2.4.32}$$

for suitable constants $C_1, C_2 > 0$. Moreover, (2.2.60) allows us to take $r_1, r_2 > 0$ such that

$$\frac{r_1}{p_1} + \frac{\bar{q}_1 - r_1}{p_1^*} = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{r_2}{p_2} + \frac{\bar{q}_2 - r_2}{p_2^*} = 1;$$

so, by using a standard interpolation argument and (2.1.4), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} |u|_{\bar{q}_1} &\leq |u|_{p_1^*}^{\bar{q}_1 - r_1} |u|_{p_1}^{r_1} \leq \tau_{1, p_1^*}^{\bar{q}_1 - r_1} \|u\|_{W_1}^{\bar{q}_1 - r_1} |u|_{p_1}^{r_1} \quad \text{for all } u \in X_1, \\ |v|_{\bar{q}_2} &\leq |v|_{p_2^*}^{\bar{q}_2 - r_2} |v|_{p_2}^{r_2} \leq \tau_{2, p_2^*}^{\bar{q}_2 - r_2} \|v\|_{W_2}^{\bar{q}_2 - r_2} |v|_{p_2}^{r_2} \quad \text{for all } v \in X_2, \end{aligned}$$

or better, fixing $m \geq 1$, from (2.3.4) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} |u|_{\bar{q}_1} &\leq \tau_{1, p_1^*}^{\bar{q}_1 - r_1} (\lambda_{1, m+1})^{-\frac{r_1}{p_1}} \|u\|_{W_1}^{\bar{q}_1} \quad \text{for all } u \in Y_m^{X_1}, \\ |v|_{\bar{q}_2} &\leq \tau_{2, p_2^*}^{\bar{q}_2 - r_2} (\lambda_{2, m+1})^{-\frac{r_2}{p_2}} \|v\|_{W_2}^{\bar{q}_2} \quad \text{for all } v \in Y_m^{X_2}. \end{aligned} \tag{2.4.33}$$

Then, (2.4.32), (2.4.33) and direct computations imply that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \bar{\mu}_0 (\|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + \|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2}) - \frac{C_3}{\lambda_m} (\|u\|_{W_1}^{\bar{q}_1} + \|v\|_{W_2}^{\bar{q}_2}) - C_2 \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}$$

for a suitable constant $C_3 > 0$ independent of m , where we assume

$$\bar{\mu}_0 = \min \left\{ \frac{\mu_0}{p_1}, \frac{\mu_0}{p_2} \right\}, \quad \bar{\lambda}_m = \min \left\{ (\lambda_{1,m+1})^{\frac{r_1}{p_1}}, (\lambda_{2,m+1})^{\frac{r_2}{p_2}} \right\}. \quad (2.4.34)$$

On the other hand, taking

$$p = \min\{p_1, p_2\} \quad \text{and} \quad q = \max\{\bar{q}_1, \bar{q}_2\},$$

direct computations allow us to prove that

$$\|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + \|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2} \geq \frac{1}{2^{p-1}} \|(u, v)\|_W^p - 1, \quad \|u\|_{W_1}^{\bar{q}_1} + \|v\|_{W_2}^{\bar{q}_2} \leq 2 \|(u, v)\|_W^q \text{ if } \|(u, v)\|_W \geq 2.$$

Thus, summing up, for all $(u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}$ such that $\|(u, v)\|_W \geq 2$ we obtain that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \|(u, v)\|_W^p \left(\frac{\bar{\mu}_0}{2^{p-1}} - \frac{2C_3}{\bar{\lambda}_m} \|(u, v)\|_W^{q-p} \right) - C_4$$

with $C_4 = C_2 + \bar{\mu}_0$.

Now, consider $\|(u, v)\|_W = r_m$ with

$$r_m = \left(\frac{\bar{\mu}_0 \bar{\lambda}_m}{2^{p+1} C_3} \right)^{\frac{1}{q-p}} \quad (2.4.35)$$

(from (2.2.60) it is $p < q$). We note that (2.4.35) implies

$$\frac{\bar{\mu}_0}{2^{p-1}} - \frac{2C_3}{\bar{\lambda}_m} r_m^{q-p} = \frac{\bar{\mu}_0}{2^p},$$

furthermore again from (2.4.35) and (2.3.3), (2.4.34) we have

$$r_m \rightarrow +\infty \quad \text{if } m \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Then, if $r_m \geq 2$, we obtain that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \frac{\bar{\mu}_0}{2^p} r_m^p - C_4 \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}, \text{ with } \|(u, v)\|_W = r_m$$

which gives the thesis if $\varrho > 0$ is fixed and m is large enough. \square

Proof of Theorem 2.4. From (2.4.22) it is $\mathcal{J}(0, 0) = 0$. Then, fixing any $\varrho > 0$, from Proposition 2.7 it follows that $m_\varrho \geq 1$ and $r_{m_\varrho} > 0$ exist such that

$$(u, v) \in Y_{m_\varrho}^{X_1} \times Y_{m_\varrho}^{X_2}, \quad \|(u, v)\|_W = r_{m_\varrho} \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \varrho;$$

moreover, taking $m > m_\varrho$, the m -dimensional space V_m is such that $\text{codim} Y_{m_\varrho} < \dim V_m$, thus, Proposition 2.6 implies that assumption (\mathcal{H}_ϱ) is verified with

$$\mathcal{M}_\varrho = \{(u, v) \in X : \|(u, v)\|_W = r_{m_\varrho}\}.$$

Hence, from Propositions 2.2 and 2.4 we have that Corollary 1.1 applies to \mathcal{J} in X and a sequence of diverging critical levels exists. \square

In order to prove Corollary 2.1, the following lemma is useful.

Lemma 2.4. *If hypotheses $(2\tilde{g}_0)$ and $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ hold, then, taking any $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $|(u, v)| \geq R$ we have that*

$$G(x, t^{\theta_1}u, t^{\theta_2}v) \geq t G(x, u, v) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ all } t \geq 1. \quad (2.4.36)$$

Proof. Taking $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $|(u, v)| \geq R$ and any $t \geq 1$, $(2\tilde{g}_0)$, $(2\tilde{g}_2)$ and direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d}{dt}G(x, t^{\theta_1}u, t^{\theta_2}v) &= \frac{1}{t}(\theta_1 G_u(x, t^{\theta_1}u, t^{\theta_2}v)t^{\theta_1}u + \theta_2 G_v(x, t^{\theta_1}u, t^{\theta_2}v)t^{\theta_2}v) \\ &\geq \frac{1}{t}G(x, t^{\theta_1}u, t^{\theta_2}v) > 0 \end{aligned}$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$. Hence, fixing $t \geq 1$ and by integration in $[1, t]$ we obtain that

$$\log \left(\frac{G(x, t^{\theta_1}u, t^{\theta_2}v)}{G(x, u, v)} \right) \geq \log t$$

which gives (2.4.36). \square

Proof of Corollary 2.1. The proof is a direct consequence of Theorem 2.4 if we prove that $(2\tilde{g}_4)$, with $\theta = \theta_1 = \theta_2$ due to $(2\tilde{g}_7)$, follows from $(2\tilde{g}_6)$.

To this aim, since $(2\tilde{g}_6)$ holds, we denote

$$C_R = \inf \{ G(x, w, z) : \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, (w, z) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \text{ such that } |(w, z)| = R \} > 0$$

with $R > 0$ as in $(2\tilde{g}_2)$. Then, fixing any $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ such that $|(u, v)| \geq R$, by applying (2.4.36) with

$$t = \left(\frac{|(u, v)|}{R} \right)^{\frac{1}{\theta}} \geq 1,$$

direct computations imply

$$G(x, u, v) \geq \left(\frac{|(u, v)|}{R} \right)^{\frac{1}{\theta}} G \left(x, \frac{Ru}{|(u, v)|}, \frac{Rv}{|(u, v)|} \right) \geq \frac{C_R}{R^{\frac{1}{\theta}}} |(u, v)|^{\frac{1}{\theta}} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega.$$

Hence, we obtain

$$\frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta}}} \geq \frac{C_R}{R^{\frac{1}{\theta}}} \frac{|(u, v)|^{\frac{1}{\theta}}}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta}}} \geq \frac{C_R}{2R^{\frac{1}{\theta}}} > 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega \text{ if } |(u, v)| \geq R,$$

which implies $(2\tilde{g}_4)$. \square

Proof of Corollary 2.2. From (2.4.18), taking $\theta_i > 0$ such that

$$p_i + \gamma_i < \frac{1}{\theta_i} \leq q_i, \quad i \in \{1, 2\},$$

we have that (2.4.5) and (2.4.11) hold. Moreover, (2.4.18) implies (2.1.25) while from (2.4.9) and (2.4.19) it follows (2.1.26). At last, we note that (2.4.10) gives

$$\frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}} \geq \frac{|u|^{q_1} + |v|^{q_2}}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}} \quad \text{if } (u, v) \neq 0.$$

Then, $(2\tilde{g}_4)$ holds as direct computations imply

$$\frac{|u|^{q_1} + |v|^{q_2}}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}} \geq \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{if } |(u, v)| \geq 2. \quad (2.4.37)$$

Thus, from Examples 2.2 and 2.3, it follows that Theorem 2.4 applies to \mathcal{J}_1 in X . \square

Proof of Corollary 2.3. From (2.4.20), taking $\theta_1, \theta_2 > 0$ such that

$$p_1 + \gamma_1 < \frac{1}{\theta_1} \leq \gamma_3, \quad p_2 + \gamma_2 < \frac{1}{\theta_2} \leq \gamma_4, \quad (2.4.38)$$

we have that (2.4.5) and (2.4.17) hold. Moreover, (2.4.20) implies (2.1.25) while from (2.4.16) and (2.4.21) it follows (2.1.26). At last, from (2.4.20) and (2.4.38), since (2.4.37) is satisfied, we have that $(2\tilde{g}_4)$ holds. Then, from Examples 2.2 and 2.4, Theorem 2.4 applies to \mathcal{J}_2 in X . \square

New threshold for some critical systems

The study of partial differential equations involving nonlinearities with critical or supercritical growths, is a very complex matter and for many critical and supercritical problems some basic issues are mostly unknown or undiscovered. For example, let us consider the quasilinear elliptic problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta_p u = \lambda |u|^{p-2} u + |u|^{q-2} u & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (3.0.1)$$

where Ω is an open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 2$, and $1 < p < N$. In spite of the simple looking structure of the problem, if we ask q to be critical or supercritical from the viewpoint of the Sobolev Embedding Theorem, namely $q \geq p^* = \frac{Np}{N-p}$, some significant difficulties arise. Among other problems, in general the lack of compactness which occurs, does not guarantee even the existence of solutions, which has been derived only in few cases and frequently under assumptions on the shape of the domain Ω (for the classical nonexistence result due to the Pohožaev's identity see [155], or also [177, Theorem III.1.3]).

The existence of positive solutions of (3.0.1) has been successfully addressed either by adding some lower order term to the critical nonlinearity (see [48]) or by considering domains which are not starshaped (see, e.g., [26, 75]) if $p = 2$, $q = 2^*$ and $\lambda = 0$, while the existence of sign-changing solutions of (3.0.1) have been obtained if $p = 2$, $q = 2^*$ but $\lambda \neq 0$ (see, e.g., [67, 165]). To our knowledge, all the results carried over so far, are built on the key assertion that the functional associated to the critical problem (3.0.1) satisfies the Palais–Smale condition even if only in certain ranges of energy.

On the other hand, taking $p \neq 2$, due to the hardship in handling a quasilinear operator, very few results of existence have been derived so far, not even under assumptions of symmetry on the domain (we refer to [139] for a wider discussion). We limit ourselves to point out that, as derived in [142], a Pohožaev type nonexistence

result is not yet available for sign-changing solutions of (3.0.1), as the unique continuation principle for the p -Laplacian is not known, while it has been proved for nonnegative solutions (see [113]). However, the existence of a positive solution in a domain with a sufficiently small hole has been shown for $\frac{2N}{N+2} \leq p \leq 2$, as well as an existence and multiplicity result has been proved under further assumptions of symmetry (see [73, 139, 140, 142, 151] and references therein). Also, the regularity of solutions has been investigated e.g. in [65].

In spite of the mentioned difficulties, in recent years there has been a marked increase of research in critical and supercritical problems. The interest in these problems is related to their similarity to some variational problems which arise in Geometry and Physics where the lack of compactness also occurs. In this sense, one of the best known challenges is the so called Yamabe's problem, but also some examples related to the existence of extremal functions for isoperimetric inequalities, Hardy–Littlewood–Sobolev inequalities and trace inequalities can be addressed (see, e.g., [118, 126, 128]). However, in general, also in the “simplest” cases some problems are still open and some classical variational tools, largely used in the subcritical case, do not work in the critical and supercritical ones.

In this Chapter we study the existence of solutions for two challenging supercritical problems. The first one is related to the systems already studied in Chapters 2, but in the case when the coefficients are allowed to fulfill a “supercritical” growth; roughly speaking, taking $m = 2$ and $A_1(x, u_1, \nabla u_1) = A(x, u, \nabla u)$, $A_2(x, u_2, \nabla u_2) = B(x, v, \nabla v)$ in (2.0.1), here we assume that $A(x, u, \nabla u)$ grows at least as $(1 + |u|^{s_1 p_1})|\nabla u|^{p_1}$, $p_1 > 1$, $s_1 \geq 0$, while $B(x, v, \nabla v)$ grows at least as $(1 + |v|^{s_2 p_2})|\nabla v|^{p_2}$, $p_2 > 1$, $s_2 \geq 0$ (see Remark 3.3 and assumption (3h₇)), and that $G(x, u, v)$ can also have a supercritical growth depending on s_1 and s_2 (see hypothesis (3g₂)).

The second one is a generalized version of N -Laplacian problem which involves the coefficient $A_0(x) + A(x) |u|^{Ns}$, for $A_0, A \in L^\infty(\Omega)$ and the nonlinear term is given by $h(t)e^{\alpha|u|^\gamma}$, where $\alpha, \gamma > 0$ are given constants, $h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function which has a “subexponential” growth at infinity and $e^{\alpha|u|^\gamma}$ is governed by the Trudinger–Moser inequality. In spite of the above mentioned difficulties, in both cases we provide the existence of weak bounded solutions. The relevance of the results presented here relies upon the fact that we are able to move a little forward the “usual” critical exponent, providing an existence (and multiplicity for the system (3.1.1)) result also in a wider range than usual (see (3.1.46)).

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS5, CS2].

3.1 Quasilinear elliptic systems with a supercritical growth

Here, following the ideas introduced in [56], we look for solutions of the family of coupled gradient-type quasilinear elliptic systems

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(a(x, u, \nabla u)) + A_t(x, u, \nabla u) = G_u(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ -\operatorname{div}(b(x, v, \nabla v)) + B_t(x, v, \nabla v) = G_v(x, u, v) & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = v = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (3.1.1)$$

where Ω is an open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 2$, and $A, B : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given functions with partial derivatives

$$A_t(x, t, \xi) = \frac{\partial A}{\partial t}(x, t, \xi), \quad a(x, t, \xi) = \left(\frac{\partial A}{\partial \xi_1}(x, t, \xi), \dots, \frac{\partial A}{\partial \xi_N}(x, t, \xi) \right), \quad (3.1.2)$$

$$B_t(x, t, \xi) = \frac{\partial B}{\partial t}(x, t, \xi), \quad b(x, t, \xi) = \left(\frac{\partial B}{\partial \xi_1}(x, t, \xi), \dots, \frac{\partial B}{\partial \xi_N}(x, t, \xi) \right), \quad (3.1.3)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, for all $(t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$. Moreover, a nonlinear function $G : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exists so that

$$G_u(x, u, v) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial u}(x, u, v), \quad G_v(x, u, v) = \frac{\partial G}{\partial v}(x, u, v) \quad (3.1.4)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, all $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$.

While subcritical quasilinear systems have been handled through several techniques (see, e.g., [CS7, CS6, 23, 43, 50]), as far as we know very few existence results have been determined for supercritical quasilinear elliptic systems (see, for example, [60, 114] and references therein), even though no result occurs for supercritical systems with coefficients depending on the solution and its gradient themselves, as that one in (3.1.1). Moreover, as in [56], even if a supercritical growth occurs, the domain Ω is only open and bounded as we consider homogeneous Dirichlet boundary condition and the solutions we are looking for, are weak.

3.1.1 Variational framework

To recall some features shared with the subcritical systems in Chapter 2, if needed, here we introduce similar notations. For the reader convenience, we prefer to recall them here.

Let $A, B : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be such that the following conditions hold:

(3h₀) $A(x, t, \xi)$ and $B(x, t, \xi)$ are \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory functions with partial derivatives as in (3.1.2), respectively (3.1.3);

(3h₁) two exponents $p_1 > 1$, $p_2 > 1$, and some positive functions $\Phi_i, \phi_i, \Psi_i, \psi_i \in C^0(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$, if $i \in \{0, 1, 2\}$, exist such that

$$|A(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Phi_0(t) + \phi_0(t)|\xi|^{p_1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (3.1.5)$$

$$|A_t(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Phi_1(t) + \phi_1(t)|\xi|^{p_1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N,$$

$$|a(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Phi_2(t) + \phi_2(t)|\xi|^{p_1-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (3.1.6)$$

and

$$|B(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Psi_0(t) + \psi_0(t)|\xi|^{p_2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (3.1.7)$$

$$|B_t(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Psi_1(t) + \psi_1(t)|\xi|^{p_2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N,$$

$$|b(x, t, \xi)| \leq \Psi_2(t) + \psi_2(t)|\xi|^{p_2-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (3.1.8)$$

Furthermore, let $G : \Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a map which satisfies the following hypotheses:

(3g₀) $G(x, u, v)$ is a C^1 -Caratheodory function with partial derivatives as in (3.1.4), such that

$$G(\cdot, 0, 0) \in L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad G_u(x, 0, 0) = G_v(x, 0, 0) = 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega;$$

(3g₁) a constant $\sigma > 0$ and some exponents $q_i \geq 1$, $t_i \geq 0$, if $i \in \{1, 2\}$, exist such that

$$|G_u(x, u, v)| \leq \sigma(1 + |u|^{q_1-1} + |v|^{t_1}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (3.1.9)$$

$$|G_v(x, u, v)| \leq \sigma(1 + |u|^{t_2} + |v|^{q_2-1}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2.$$

Remark 3.1. Hypotheses (3g₀)-(3g₁), the Mean Value Theorem and direct computations ensure the existence of a positive constant $\sigma_1 > 0$ such that

$$|G(x, u, v)| \leq \sigma_1 (1 + |u|^{q_1} + |v|^{t_1}|u| + |u|^{t_2}|v| + |v|^{q_2}) \quad (3.1.10)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, for all $(u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2$. Now, taking any couple of real numbers $t_3, t_5 > 1$, from Young inequality we obtain

$$|v|^{t_1}|u| \leq |u|^{t_3} + |v|^{t_4}, \quad |u|^{t_2}|v| \leq |u|^{t_6} + |v|^{t_5} \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (3.1.11)$$

where, for simplicity, we set

$$t_4 := \frac{t_1 t_3}{t_3 - 1} \geq t_1 \quad \text{and} \quad t_6 := \frac{t_2 t_5}{t_5 - 1} \geq t_2. \quad (3.1.12)$$

Thus, from (3.1.10) and (3.1.11) we infer that

$$|G(x, u, v)| \leq \sigma_2 (1 + |u|^{\bar{q}_1} + |v|^{\bar{q}_2}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (3.1.13)$$

with

$$\bar{q}_1 := \max\{q_1, t_3, t_6\} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{q}_2 := \max\{q_2, t_4, t_5\}, \quad (3.1.14)$$

for a suitable constant $\sigma_2 > 0$.

For each $i \in \{1, 2\}$ let $p_i > 1$ be as in assumption $(3h_1)$ and let us consider the related Sobolev space

$$W_i = W_0^{1,p_i}(\Omega) \quad \text{with norm } \|\cdot\|_{W_i} = \|\cdot\|_{W_0^{1,p_i}}.$$

Here, the notation $(W, \|\cdot\|_W)$, introduced for the abstract setting at the beginning of this section, is referred to our problem with

$$W = W_1 \times W_2 \quad \text{and} \quad \|(u, v)\|_W = \|u\|_{W_1} + \|v\|_{W_2} \quad \text{if } (u, v) \in W. \quad (3.1.15)$$

Since $(W_i, \|\cdot\|_{W_i})$ is a reflexive Banach space for both $i \in \{1, 2\}$, so is $(W, \|\cdot\|_W)$ in (3.1.15).

Moreover, we consider the Banach space $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$ defined as

$$X = X_1 \times X_2 \quad \text{with} \quad \|(u, v)\|_X = \|u\|_{X_1} + \|v\|_{X_2} \quad \text{if } (u, v) \in X, \quad (3.1.16)$$

where

$$X_1 := W_1 \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad X_2 := W_2 \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \quad (3.1.17)$$

are endowed with the norms

$$\|u\|_{X_1} = \|u\|_{W_1} + |u|_\infty \quad \text{if } u \in X_1 \quad \text{and} \quad \|v\|_{X_2} = \|v\|_{W_2} + |v|_\infty \quad \text{if } v \in X_2.$$

Setting

$$L := L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega) \quad \text{with} \quad \|(u, v)\|_L = |u|_\infty + |v|_\infty,$$

we have that X in (3.1.16) can also be written as

$$X = W \cap L \quad (3.1.18)$$

and its norm is such that

$$\|(u, v)\|_X = \|(u, v)\|_W + \|(u, v)\|_L.$$

Clearly, from (3.1.17), for both $i \in \{1, 2\}$ we have that the continuous embeddings $X_i \hookrightarrow W_i$ and $X_i \hookrightarrow L^\infty(\Omega)$ hold.

Firstly, we note that if conditions $(3h_0)$ – $(3h_1)$, $(3g_0)$ – $(3g_1)$ hold, then direct computations imply that the functional

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) = \int_{\Omega} A(x, u, \nabla u) dx + \int_{\Omega} B(x, v, \nabla v) dx - \int_{\Omega} G(x, u, v) dx \quad (3.1.19)$$

is well defined for all $(u, v) \in X$. Moreover, taking any $(u, v), (w, z) \in X$, the Gâteaux differential of functional \mathcal{J} in (u, v) along the direction (w, z) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} d\mathcal{J}(u, v)[(w, z)] &= \int_{\Omega} a(x, u, \nabla u) \cdot \nabla w \, dx + \int_{\Omega} A_u(x, u, \nabla u) w \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega} b(x, v, \nabla v) \cdot \nabla z \, dx + \int_{\Omega} B_v(x, v, \nabla v) z \, dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u, v) w \, dx - \int_{\Omega} G_v(x, u, v) z \, dx. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.20)$$

Observe that the supercritical nature of problem (3.1.1) hasn't turned out so far and (2.1.14), (3.1.19) have the same shape, as well as (2.1.15), (3.1.20). Thus, for simplicity, here we use the same notations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v) : w \in X_1 &\mapsto \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u, v)[w] = d\mathcal{J}(u, v)[(w, 0)] \in \mathbb{R}, \\ \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v) : z \in X_2 &\mapsto \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u, v)[z] = d\mathcal{J}(u, v)[(0, z)] \in \mathbb{R}; \end{aligned}$$

introduced in Chapter 2 (see (2.1.16)–(2.1.19) and Remark 2.3).

Moreover, we can state the regularity of functional \mathcal{J} defined in (3.1.19) (for the proof, see [CS6, Proposition 3.5] or Proposition 2.1).

Proposition 3.1. *Assume that conditions $(3h_0)$ – $(3h_1)$, $(3g_0)$ – $(3g_1)$ hold. Let $((u_n, v_n))_n \subset X$ and $(u, v) \in X$ be such that*

$$(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v) \text{ in } W \quad \text{and} \quad (u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v) \text{ a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

If $M > 0$ exists such that

$$|u_n|_\infty \leq M \quad \text{and} \quad |v_n|_\infty \leq M \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N},$$

then

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(u, v) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - d\mathcal{J}(u, v)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence, \mathcal{J} is a \mathcal{C}^1 functional on X with Fréchet differential defined as in (3.1.20).

3.1.2 The weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition

To prove some more properties of functional \mathcal{J} in (3.1.19), let $p_1 > 1$ and $p_2 > 1$ as in the earlier hypothesis $(3h_1)$. Then, assume that $R \geq 1$ exists such that the following conditions hold:

$(3h_2)$ some constants $\eta_1, \eta_2 > 0$ exist such that

$$A(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_1 a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \quad (3.1.21)$$

$$B(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_1 b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \quad (3.1.22)$$

and

$$\sup_{|(t, \xi)| \leq R} |A(x, t, \xi)| \leq \eta_2, \quad \sup_{|(t, \xi)| \leq R} |B(x, t, \xi)| \leq \eta_2 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega; \quad (3.1.23)$$

$(3h_3)$ some exponents $s_1, s_2 \geq 0$ and a constant $\mu_0 > 0$ exist so that

$$a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \geq \mu_0(1 + |t|^{s_1 p_1})|\xi|^{p_1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N,$$

$$b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \geq \mu_0(1 + |t|^{s_2 p_2})|\xi|^{p_2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N;$$

(3h₄) a constant $\mu_1 > 0$ exists such that

$$\begin{aligned} a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi + A_t(x, t, \xi)t &\geq \mu_1 a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi & \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \\ b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi + B_t(x, t, \xi)t &\geq \mu_1 b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi & \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R; \end{aligned}$$

(3h₅) some constants $\theta_1, \theta_2, \mu_2 > 0$ exist such that

$$\theta_1 < \frac{1}{p_1}, \quad \theta_2 < \frac{1}{p_2}, \quad (3.1.24)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} A(x, t, \xi) - \theta_1 a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi - \theta_1 A_t(x, t, \xi)t &\geq \mu_2 a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi & \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \\ B(x, t, \xi) - \theta_2 b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi - \theta_2 B_t(x, t, \xi)t &\geq \mu_2 b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi & \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R; \end{aligned}$$

(3h₆) for all $\xi, \xi' \in \mathbb{R}^N$, with $\xi \neq \xi'$, it is

$$\begin{aligned} [a(x, t, \xi) - a(x, t, \xi')] \cdot [\xi - \xi'] &> 0 & \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \\ [b(x, t, \xi) - b(x, t, \xi')] \cdot [\xi - \xi'] &> 0 & \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}; \end{aligned}$$

(3g₂) for $i \in \{1, 2\}$, taking p_i as in hypothesis (3h₁), q_i, t_i as in assumption (3g₁) and s_i as in (3h₃), we assume that

$$1 \leq q_1 < p_1^*(s_1 + 1), \quad 1 \leq q_2 < p_2^*(s_2 + 1), \quad (3.1.25)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} 0 \leq t_1 &< \frac{p_1}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_1^*(s_1 + 1)} \right) p_2^*(s_2 + 1), \\ 0 \leq t_2 &< \frac{p_2}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_2^*(s_2 + 1)} \right) p_1^*(s_1 + 1); \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.26)$$

(3g₃) taking θ_1, θ_2 as in (3h₅), we assume that

$$0 < G(x, u, v) \leq \theta_1 G_u(x, u, v)u + \theta_2 G_v(x, u, v)v \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ if } |(u, v)| \geq R.$$

Remark 3.2. Assumption (3.1.25) shows up the supercritical nature of our problem which vanishes if $s_1 = s_2 = 0$ as it reduces exactly to the subcritical condition (3g₁) in [CS7, CS6]. However, in general, if one or both $s_1 > 0, s_2 > 0$ hold, then a supercritical growth on the nonlinear term $G(x, u, v)$ is allowed. Moreover, we emphasize that the growth hypothesis (3g₂) is needed to prove that the functional \mathcal{J} satisfies the (*wCPS*) condition, but has not been required for the variational principle stated in Proposition 3.1.

Remark 3.3. If we consider hypothesis (3h₄) with $t = 0$ and $|\xi| \geq R$, then assumption (3h₃) gives $\mu_1 \leq 1$. Moreover, we note that (3h₄) and (3h₅) yield

$$A(x, t, \xi) \geq (\theta_1 \mu_1 + \mu_2) a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \quad (3.1.27)$$

$$B(x, t, \xi) \geq (\theta_2 \mu_1 + \mu_2) b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R \quad (3.1.28)$$

which, together with condition $(3h_3)$, imply that

$$A(x, t, \xi) \geq \mu_0(\theta_1\mu_1 + \mu_2)(1 + |t|^{s_1 p_1})|\xi|^{p_1} \geq 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R, \quad (3.1.29)$$

$$B(x, t, \xi) \geq \mu_0(\theta_2\mu_1 + \mu_2)(1 + |t|^{s_2 p_2})|\xi|^{p_2} \geq 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R. \quad (3.1.30)$$

Hence, from (3.1.23) and (3.1.29), respectively (3.1.30), and direct computations we have that

$$A(x, t, \xi) \geq \mu_0(\theta_1\mu_1 + \mu_2)(1 + |t|^{s_1 p_1})|\xi|^{p_1} - \eta_3 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \quad \forall (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \quad (3.1.31)$$

$$B(x, t, \xi) \geq \mu_0(\theta_2\mu_1 + \mu_2)(1 + |t|^{s_2 p_2})|\xi|^{p_2} - \eta_3 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \quad \forall (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N \quad (3.1.32)$$

for a suitable constant $\eta_3 > 0$. On the other hand, from $(3h_2)$ and (3.1.6), respectively (3.1.8), direct computations imply that

$$A(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_1\Phi_2(t) + \eta_1(\Phi_2(t) + \phi_2(t))|\xi|^{p_1} + \eta_4 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \forall (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (3.1.33)$$

$$B(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_1\Psi_2(t) + \eta_1(\Psi_2(t) + \psi_2(t))|\xi|^{p_2} + \eta_4 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \forall (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (3.1.34)$$

for a suitable constant $\eta_4 > 0$. Then, if hypotheses $(3h_2)$ – $(3h_5)$ hold, the growth conditions on $A(x, t, \xi)$ and $B(x, t, \xi)$ stated in (3.1.5) and (3.1.7) are a direct consequence of (3.1.6), respectively (3.1.8), as (3.1.5) follows from (3.1.31) and (3.1.33) while (3.1.7) follows from (3.1.32) and (3.1.34). Hence, even if (3.1.5) and (3.1.7) are part of assumption $(3h_1)$, they can be ruled-out from the hypotheses if $(3h_2)$ – $(3h_5)$ hold, too.

Remark 3.4. In the set of hypotheses $(3h_2)$ and $(3h_5)$ a more precise growth condition on both the functions $A(x, t, \xi)$ and $B(x, t, \xi)$ can be pointed out. In fact, (3.1.21), respectively (3.1.22), $(3h_5)$ and direct calculations imply that

$$\left(\frac{\eta_1 - \theta_1 - \mu_2}{\eta_1\theta_1} \right) A(x, t, \xi) \geq A_t(x, t, \xi)t \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R \quad (3.1.35)$$

$$\left(\frac{\eta_1 - \theta_2 - \mu_2}{\eta_1\theta_2} \right) B(x, t, \xi) \geq B_t(x, t, \xi)t \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |(t, \xi)| \geq R. \quad (3.1.36)$$

Now, taking $t = 0$ and $|\xi| \geq R$ in both $(3h_2)$ and $(3h_5)$, without loss of generality we can choose μ_2 small enough so that

$$\eta_1 - \theta_1 - \mu_2 > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \eta_1 - \theta_2 - \mu_2 > 0.$$

Thus, from (3.1.5), (3.1.29), (3.1.35), respectively (3.1.7), (3.1.30), (3.1.36), and direct computations we obtain that

$$A(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_5 |t|^{\frac{\eta_1 - \theta_1 - \mu_2}{\eta_1\theta_1}} |\xi|^{p_1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |t| \geq 1 \text{ and } |\xi| \geq R,$$

$$B(x, t, \xi) \leq \eta_5 |t|^{\frac{\eta_1 - \theta_2 - \mu_2}{\eta_1\theta_2}} |\xi|^{p_2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |t| \geq 1 \text{ and } |\xi| \geq R,$$

for a suitable $\eta_5 > 0$, and then from (3.1.27), respectively (3.1.28), we have that

$$a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \leq \frac{\eta_5}{\theta_1 \mu_1 + \mu_2} |t|^{\frac{\eta_1 - \theta_1 - \mu_2}{\eta_1 \theta_1}} |\xi|^{p_1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |t| \geq 1 \text{ and } |\xi| \geq R, \quad (3.1.37)$$

$$b(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \leq \frac{\eta_5}{\theta_2 \mu_1 + \mu_2} |t|^{\frac{\eta_1 - \theta_2 - \mu_2}{\eta_1 \theta_2}} |\xi|^{p_2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega \text{ if } |t| \geq 1 \text{ and } |\xi| \geq R. \quad (3.1.38)$$

Finally, from (3.1.37), (3.1.38) and assumption (3h₃), we infer that

$$0 \leq p_1 s_1 \leq \frac{1}{\theta_1} - \frac{\theta_1 + \mu_2}{\eta_1 \theta_1} \quad \text{and} \quad 0 \leq p_2 s_2 \leq \frac{1}{\theta_2} - \frac{\theta_2 + \mu_2}{\eta_1 \theta_2}. \quad (3.1.39)$$

We note that, if

$$0 \leq s_1 < \frac{1}{\theta_1 p_1} \quad \text{and} \quad 0 \leq s_2 < \frac{1}{\theta_2 p_2}, \quad (3.1.40)$$

then we can always choose η_1 in (3h₂) large enough so that (3.1.39) is satisfied.

Remark 3.5. Conditions in (3.1.40) not only relate the exponents s_1, s_2 provided in assumption (3h₃) with the powers $p_1, p_2 > 1$ used in the growth conditions (3h₁) and θ_1, θ_2 claimed in (3.1.24), but also they tell us how far we can take it. In particular, it implies that in our set of hypotheses, a supercritical growth is allowed as long as s_1, s_2 cover the whole range stated in (3.1.40).

Remark 3.6. Assumptions (3g₀)–(3g₁), (3g₃) and direct calculations imply that for each $i \in \{1, 2\}$ a function $h_i \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, $h_i(x) > 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, exists such that

$$\begin{aligned} G(x, u, 0) &\geq h_1(x) |u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } |u| \geq R, \\ G(x, 0, v) &\geq h_2(x) |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ if } |v| \geq R. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, from (3.1.10) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} h_1(x) |u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} - \sigma_3 &\leq G(x, u, 0) \leq \sigma_1 (1 + |u|^{q_1}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for all } u \in \mathbb{R}, \\ h_2(x) |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}} - \sigma_3 &\leq G(x, 0, v) \leq \sigma_1 (1 + |v|^{q_2}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for all } v \in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.41)$$

for a positive constant $\sigma_3 > 0$. Then, (3.1.40) and (3.1.41) imply that

$$p_1 s_1 < \frac{1}{\theta_1} \leq q_1, \quad p_2 s_2 < \frac{1}{\theta_2} \leq q_2,$$

while from (3.1.24) it is

$$p_1 < \frac{1}{\theta_1}, \quad p_2 < \frac{1}{\theta_2}.$$

So, if condition (3.1.25) holds, without loss of generality we can take q_1, q_2 in (3g₁) large enough so that

$$p_1(s_1 + 1) < q_1 < p_1^*(s_1 + 1) \quad \text{and} \quad p_2(s_2 + 1) < q_2 < p_2^*(s_2 + 1). \quad (3.1.42)$$

To show that the (*wCPS*) condition holds also in our supercritical setting, we need some preliminary results.

Firstly, we note that, taking $p > 1$ and $s \geq 0$, then straightforward computations give

$$|\nabla(|y|^s y)|^p = (s+1)^p |y|^{sp} |\nabla y|^p \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad \text{for all } y \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega). \quad (3.1.43)$$

Such an equality allows us to prove the following Rellich–type embedding theorem (for the proof, see [56, Lemma 3.8]).

Lemma 3.1. *Taking $1 < p < N$ and $s > 0$, let $(y_n)_n \subset W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$ be a sequence such that*

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} (1 + |y_n|^{sp}) |\nabla y_n|^p dx \right)_n \quad \text{is bounded.}$$

Then, $y \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ exists such that $|y|^s y \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, too, and, up to subsequences, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} y_n &\rightharpoonup y \quad \text{weakly in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega), \\ |y_n|^s y_n &\rightharpoonup |y|^s y \quad \text{weakly in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega), \\ y_n &\rightarrow y \quad \text{strongly in } L^r(\Omega) \quad \text{for each } r \in [1, p^*(s+1)[, \\ y_n &\rightarrow y \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega. \end{aligned}$$

As pointed out in Remark 3.2, the upper bounds in (3g₂) were not required so far, but will be essential in the incoming results. Therefore, some consequences of the estimates in (3.1.25) and (3.1.26) are needed.

Remark 3.7. Suppose $1 < p_1 < N$, $1 < p_2 < N$ and take t_1, t_2 as in (3.1.26). Following the ideas in Remark 3.1, we can choose t_3 and t_5 in (3.1.11) so that

$$\begin{aligned} 1 &< \frac{p_1 p_2^*(s_2 + 1)}{p_1 p_2^*(s_2 + 1) - N t_1} < t_3 < p_1^*(s_1 + 1), \\ 1 &< \frac{p_2 p_1^*(s_1 + 1)}{p_2 p_1^*(s_1 + 1) - N t_2} < t_5 < p_2^*(s_2 + 1), \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.44)$$

as (3.1.26) implies that

$$p_1 p_2^*(s_2 + 1) - N t_1 > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 1 < \frac{p_1 p_2^*(s_2 + 1)}{p_1 p_2^*(s_2 + 1) - N t_1} < p_1^*(s_1 + 1),$$

and also

$$p_2 p_1^*(s_1 + 1) - N t_2 > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad 1 < \frac{p_2 p_1^*(s_1 + 1)}{p_2 p_1^*(s_1 + 1) - N t_2} < p_2^*(s_2 + 1).$$

Then, t_4 and t_6 in (3.1.12) are such that

$$\begin{aligned} t_1 &\leq t_4 < \frac{p_1}{N} p_2^*(s_2 + 1) \leq p_2^*(s_2 + 1), \\ t_2 &\leq t_6 < \frac{p_2}{N} p_1^*(s_1 + 1) \leq p_1^*(s_1 + 1). \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.45)$$

Clearly, (3.1.44) and (3.1.45) still hold if $p_1 = N$ and/or $p_2 = N$.

Remark 3.8. In the set of hypotheses $(3g_0)$ – $(3g_3)$, by reasoning as in Remark 3.1 we can consider estimate (3.1.13) with \bar{q}_1 and \bar{q}_2 as in (3.1.14) but taking $t_j, j \in \{3, 4, 5, 6\}$, as in Remark 3.7. Hence, from (3.1.25), (3.1.42), (3.1.44) and (3.1.45) we infer that

$$1 < p_1 < \frac{\bar{q}_1}{s_1 + 1} < p_1^* \quad \text{and} \quad 1 < p_2 < \frac{\bar{q}_2}{s_2 + 1} < p_2^*. \quad (3.1.46)$$

Finally, we are able to prove that the weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition holds.

Proposition 3.2. *Under assumptions $(3h_0)$ – $(3h_6)$ and $(3g_0)$ – $(3g_3)$ functional $\mathcal{J} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, defined as in (3.1.19), satisfies (wCPS) condition in \mathbb{R} .*

As relevant differences occur in Steps 1, 2 with respect to the correspondings ones in the proofs of Propositions 2.3, 2.4, we prefer to provide all the details of the proof even here.

Proof. Taking any $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$, let $((u_n, v_n))_n \subset X$ be a sequence such that

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow \beta \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n)\|_{X'}(1 + \|(u_n, v_n)\|_X) \rightarrow 0 \quad (3.1.47)$$

as $n \rightarrow +\infty$. We want to prove that a couple $(u, v) \in X$ exists such that

- (i) $(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v)$ in W (up to subsequences),
- (ii) $\mathcal{J}(u, v) = \beta, \quad d\mathcal{J}(u, v) = 0$.

To this aim, for simplicity, we organize our proof in the following steps:

1. both the sequences

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} (1 + |u_n|^{s_1 p_1}) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx \right)_n, \quad \left(\int_{\Omega} (1 + |v_n|^{s_2 p_2}) |v_n|^{p_2} dx \right)_n \quad \text{are bounded,} \quad (3.1.48)$$

so, by applying Lemma 3.1 a couple $(u, v) \in W$ exists such that also $(|u|^{s_1} u, |v|^{s_2} v) \in W$ and, up to subsequences, we have:

$$(u_n, v_n) \rightharpoonup (u, v) \quad \text{weakly in } W \quad (3.1.49)$$

$$(|u_n|^{s_1} u_n, |v_n|^{s_2} v_n) \rightharpoonup (|u|^{s_1} u, |v|^{s_2} v) \quad \text{weakly in } W \quad (3.1.50)$$

$$(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v) \quad \text{in } L^{r_1}(\Omega) \times L^{r_2}(\Omega) \quad \text{if } 1 \leq r_i < p_i^*(s_i + 1), \quad i \in \{1, 2\} \quad (3.1.51)$$

$$(u_n, v_n) \rightarrow (u, v) \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega; \quad (3.1.52)$$

2. $(u, v) \in L^\infty(\Omega) \times L^\infty(\Omega)$;

3. for any $k > 0$, define $T_k : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$T_k t := \begin{cases} t & \text{if } |t| \leq k \\ k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k \end{cases}$$

and

$$\mathbb{T}_k : (y_1, y_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mapsto \mathbb{T}_k(y_1, y_2) = (T_k y_1, T_k y_2) \in \mathbb{R}^2,$$

then, if $k \geq \max\{\|(u, v)\|_L, R\} + 1$ (with $R \geq 1$ as in our set of hypotheses), it is

$$\|d\mathcal{J}(\mathbb{T}_k(u_n, v_n))\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}(\mathbb{T}_k(u_n, v_n)) \rightarrow \beta;$$

4. $\|\mathbb{T}_k(u_n, v_n) - (u, v)\|_W \rightarrow 0$ and then (i) holds;

5. (ii) is satisfied.

For simplicity, here and in the following we will use the notation $(\varepsilon_n)_n$ for any infinitesimal sequence depending only on $((u_n, v_n))_n$. Moreover, we denote by c_i every positive constant which arises during our computations.

Step 1. Firstly, we note that (2.1.18) and (3.1.47) imply

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[u_n] = \varepsilon_n \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[v_n] = \varepsilon_n. \quad (3.1.53)$$

Thus, if we take θ_1, θ_2 as in (3h₅), (3g₃), and s_1, s_2 as in (3h₃), by reasoning as in [CS6, Step 1 in Proposition 4.8], from (3.1.19), (2.1.16), (3.1.47), (3.1.53), assumptions (3h₁), (3h₃), (3h₅), (3g₃) together with estimate (3.1.13), and direct computations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \beta + \varepsilon_n &= \mathcal{J}(u_n, v_n) - \theta_1 \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n)[u_n] - \theta_2 \frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial v}(u_n, v_n)[v_n] \\ &\geq \mu_0 \mu_2 \int_{\Omega} (1 + |u_n|^{s_1 p_1}) |\nabla u_n|^{p_1} dx + \mu_0 \mu_2 \int_{\Omega} (1 + |v_n|^{s_2 p_2}) |\nabla v_n|^{p_2} dx - c_1, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that (3.1.48) is satisfied and, up to subsequences, $(u, v) \in W$ exists such that (3.1.49)–(3.1.52) hold.

Step 2. Due to the Sobolev Embedding Theorem, this step requires a proof only if either $p_1 \leq N$ or $p_2 \leq N$. So, if $p_1 < N$ (when $p_1 = N$ the arguments can be simplified) we want to prove that $u \in L^\infty(\Omega)$. Arguing by contradiction, we assume that $u \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$ as either

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} u = +\infty \quad (3.1.54)$$

or

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} (-u) = +\infty. \quad (3.1.55)$$

If (3.1.54) holds, then for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we have that

$$\operatorname{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) > 0 \quad \text{with} \quad \Omega_{u,k}^+ = \{x \in \Omega : u(x) > k\}, \quad (3.1.56)$$

and for an integer $\tilde{k} > 0$ we consider the function $R_{\tilde{k}}^+ : t \in \mathbb{R} \mapsto R_{\tilde{k}}^+ t \in \mathbb{R}$ defined as

$$R_{\tilde{k}}^+ t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \leq \tilde{k} \\ t - \tilde{k} & \text{if } t > \tilde{k} \end{cases}. \quad (3.1.57)$$

Now, we consider condition (3.1.56) for a fixed integer $k > R$ (with $R \geq 1$ as in our setting of hypotheses) and, taking $\tilde{k} = k^{s_1+1}$, for simplicity we put

$$w_n = |u_n|^{s_1} u_n, \quad w = |u|^{s_1} u, \quad (3.1.58)$$

and, as $|t|^{s_1} t > \tilde{k} \iff t > k$, we have that

$$\Omega_{u,k}^+ = \{x \in \Omega : w(x) > \tilde{k}\}. \quad (3.1.59)$$

Thus, from condition (3.1.50) and the sequentially weakly lower semicontinuity of $\|\cdot\|_{W_1}$ we have that

$$\|R_{\tilde{k}}^+ w\|_{W_1} \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \|R_{\tilde{k}}^+ w_n\|_{W_1},$$

i.e.,

$$\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |\nabla w|^{p_1} dx \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla w_n|^{p_1} dx, \quad (3.1.60)$$

with

$$\Omega_{n,k}^+ = \{x \in \Omega : u_n(x) > k\} = \{x \in \Omega : w_n(x) > \tilde{k}\}.$$

On the other hand, by definition (3.1.57) with \tilde{k} replaced with k , it is $\|R_k^+ u_n\|_{X_1} \leq \|u_n\|_{X_1}$, so from (2.1.18), (3.1.47) and (3.1.56), an integer $n_k \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{J}}{\partial u}(u_n, v_n) [R_k^+ u_n] < \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (3.1.61)$$

Then, by reasoning as in [CS6, Step 2 in Proposition 4.8], from (2.1.16), hypotheses (3h₃), (3h₄) with $\mu_1 \leq 1$ (see Remark 3.3), equality (3.1.43) and estimate (3.1.61) we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla w_n|^{p_1} dx &\leq \frac{(s_1 + 1)^{p_1}}{\mu_0 \mu_1} \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) \\ &+ \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.62)$$

We claim that

$$\int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \rightarrow \int_{\Omega} G_u(x, u, v) R_k^+ u dx. \quad (3.1.63)$$

In fact, from (3.1.52) and (3g₀) we have that

$$G_u(x, u_n, v_n) R_k^+ u_n \rightarrow G_u(x, u, v) R_k^+ u \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega,$$

while, thanks to assumption $(3g_2)$, formulae (3.1.9), (3.1.11), (3.1.44), (3.1.45) and (3.1.51) ensure the existence of $h \in L^1(\Omega)$ such that

$$|G_u(x, u_n, v_n)R_k^+u_n| \leq \sigma(|u_n| + |u_n|^{q_1} + |u_n|^{t_3} + |v_n|^{t_4}) \leq h(x) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega,$$

so the Dominated Convergence Theorem implies (3.1.63).

Thus, summing up, via (3.1.60), (3.1.62), (3.1.63) and again (3.1.9), from definition (3.1.57) (\tilde{k} replaced with k) we infer that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |\nabla w|^{p_1} dx &\leq c_2 \left(\int_{\Omega} |R_k^+ u| dx + \int_{\Omega} |u|^{q_1-1} |R_k^+ u| dx \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \int_{\Omega} |v|^{t_1} |R_k^+ u| dx + \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) \right) \\ &\leq c_2 \left(\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |u| dx + \int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |u|^{q_1} dx + \int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |u||v|^{t_1} dx + \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) \right), \end{aligned}$$

or better, from (3.1.11) but according to the choices in Remark 3.7, by taking $\bar{q}_1 > 1$ as in (3.1.14) and being $u > 1$ in $\Omega_{u,k}^+$, definition (3.1.58) implies that

$$\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |\nabla w|^{p_1} dx \leq c_3 \left(\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |w|^{\frac{\bar{q}_1}{s_1+1}} dx + \int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |v|^{t_4} dx + \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) \right). \quad (3.1.64)$$

We claim that

$$\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |v|^{t_4} dx \leq (\tau_{2,p_2^*} \| |v|^{s_2} v \|_{W_2})^{\frac{t_4}{s_2+1}} [\text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+)]^{1 - \frac{t_4}{p_2^*(s_2+1)}}. \quad (3.1.65)$$

In fact, if $t_4 = 0$ then (3.1.65) reduces to

$$\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |v|^{t_4} dx = \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+),$$

while if $t_4 > 0$ from Step 1 we have that $z = |v|^{s_2} v \in W_2$, so (3.1.45) gives $\frac{p_2^*(s_2+1)}{t_4} > 1$ and the Hölder inequality with such an exponent, together with (2.1.4), implies that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |v|^{t_4} dx &= \int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |z|^{\frac{t_4}{s_2+1}} dx \leq |z|_{p_2^*}^{\frac{t_4}{s_2+1}} [\text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+)]^{1 - \frac{t_4}{p_2^*(s_2+1)}} \\ &\leq (\tau_{2,p_2^*} \|z\|_{W_2})^{\frac{t_4}{s_2+1}} [\text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+)]^{1 - \frac{t_4}{p_2^*(s_2+1)}}. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, if, for simplicity we put $r = \frac{\bar{q}_1}{s_1+1}$, from (3.1.46), direct computations and, again, (2.1.4) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |w|^{\frac{\bar{q}_1}{s_1+1}} dx &\leq 2^{r-1} \left(\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |w - \tilde{k}|^r dx + \tilde{k}^r \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) \right) \\ &\leq 2^{r-1} \left((\tau_{1,r} \|w\|_{W_1})^{r-p_1} \left(\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |w - \tilde{k}|^r dx \right)^{\frac{p_1}{r}} + \tilde{k}^r \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) \right), \end{aligned}$$

which, together with (3.1.65), allows us to reduce (3.1.64) to the estimate

$$\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |\nabla w|^{p_1} dx \leq c_4 \left(\left(\int_{\Omega_{u,k}^+} |w - \tilde{k}|^r dx \right)^{\frac{p_1}{r}} + \tilde{k}^r \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) + [\text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+)]^{1 - \frac{t_4}{p_2^*(s_2+1)}} \right) \quad (3.1.66)$$

with $c_4 = c_4(\|w\|_{W_1}, \|z\|_{W_2}) > 0$.

At last, as $p_1 < N$, from (3.1.45) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+) &= \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+)^{1 - \frac{p_1}{N} + \varepsilon_1}, \quad \text{with } \varepsilon_1 = \frac{p_1}{N} > 0, \quad \varepsilon_1 p_1^* + p_1 = p_1^*, \\ \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+)^{1 - \frac{t_4}{p_2^*(s_2+1)}} &= \text{meas}(\Omega_{u,k}^+)^{1 - \frac{p_1}{N} + \varepsilon_2}, \quad \varepsilon_2 = \frac{p_1}{N} - \frac{t_4}{p_2^*(s_2+1)} > 0, \end{aligned}$$

so, from (3.1.46) and (3.1.59), since (3.1.66) holds for all \tilde{k} large enough, we have that Lemma 2.3 applies and $\text{ess sup}_\Omega w < +\infty$ in contradiction to (3.1.54).

Similar arguments, but modified in a suitable way, ensures that even (3.1.55) cannot occur, then it has to be $u \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, and also that it has to be $v \in L^\infty(\Omega)$.

Step 3 The proof can be obtained by reasoning as in the proof of [CS6, Step 3 in Proposition 4.8] but with $m = 2$ and by replacing the estimates in [CS6, Remark 4.5] with those ones in Remark 3.7 together with (3.1.46), and also by using (3.1.51) at the place of [CS6, (4.19)].

Steps 4 and 5. The proofs are as in the corresponding steps of [CS6, Proposition 4.8] (see also [52, Proposition 4.6]). \square

3.1.3 Existence and multiplicity results

To prove a multiplicity result, for each $i \in \{1, 2\}$ we make use of the decomposition of W_i as introduced in Section 2.3.

Here we state our main existence and multiplicity results.

Theorem 3.1. *Suppose that $A(x, t, \xi)$, $B(x, t, \xi)$ comply with assumptions $(3h_0)$ – $(3h_6)$ and that a given function $G(x, u, v)$ satisfies hypotheses $(3g_0)$ – $(3g_3)$. Furthermore, assume that a constant $\alpha_2 > 0$ exists such that the following conditions hold:*

$(3h_7)$ *taking p_1, p_2 as in hypothesis $(3h_1)$ and $s_1, s_2 \geq 0$ as in assumption $(3h_3)$, we have that*

$$\begin{aligned} A(x, t, \xi) &\geq \alpha_2(1 + |t|^{s_1 p_1})|\xi|^{p_1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N, \\ B(x, t, \xi) &\geq \alpha_2(1 + |t|^{s_2 p_2})|\xi|^{p_2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \text{ for all } (t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N; \end{aligned}$$

$(3g_4)$ *taking $\lambda_{1,1}$ and $\lambda_{2,1}$ as in (2.3.1), we have that*

$$\limsup_{(u,v) \rightarrow (0,0)} \frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{p_1} + |v|^{p_2}} < \alpha_2 \min\{\lambda_{1,1}, \lambda_{2,1}\} \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega.$$

Thus, functional \mathcal{J} in (3.1.19) possesses at least one nontrivial critical point in X ; hence, problem (3.1.1) admits a nontrivial weak bounded solution.

Theorem 3.2. *Suppose that $A(x, t, \xi)$, $B(x, t, \xi)$ and $G(x, u, v)$ satisfy hypotheses $(3h_0)$ – $(3h_6)$, $(3g_0)$ – $(3g_3)$. Moreover, if we assume also that:*

(3h₈) $A(x, \cdot, \cdot)$ and $B(x, \cdot, \cdot)$ are even in $\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$;

(3g₅) taking θ_1, θ_2 as in hypotheses (3h₅) and (3g₃), we have that

$$\liminf_{|(u,v)| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}} > 0 \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega;$$

(3g₆) $G(x, \cdot, \cdot)$ is even in \mathbb{R}^2 for a.e. $x \in \Omega$;

then functional \mathcal{J} in (3.1.19) possesses an unbounded sequence of critical points $((u_m, v_m))_m \subset X$ such that $\mathcal{J}(u_m, v_m) \nearrow +\infty$; hence, problem (3.1.1) admits infinitely many distinct weak bounded solutions.

Finally, by reasoning as in [CS7, Corollary 5.4], we can state this further multiplicity result since the supercritical growth in (3.1.46) does not affect its proof.

Corollary 3.1. *Let $p_1, p_2 > 1$ and suppose that the functions $A(x, t, \xi)$, $B(x, t, \xi)$ and $G(x, u, v)$ satisfy assumptions $(3h_0)$ – $(3h_6)$, (3h₈), $(3g_0)$ – $(3g_3)$ and (3g₆). Furthermore, if*

(3g₇) $\inf\{G(x, w, z) : x \in \Omega, (w, z) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \text{ such that } |(w, z)| = R\} > 0$, with R as in (3g₂);

(3g₈) $\theta_1 = \theta_2$, with θ_1, θ_2 as in (3h₅) and (3g₃);

are satisfied too, the even functional \mathcal{J} in (3.1.19) possesses a sequence of critical points $((u_m, v_m))_m$ in X such that $\mathcal{J}(u_m, v_m) \nearrow +\infty$; hence, problem (3.1.1) admits infinitely many distinct weak bounded solutions.

Before turning to the proof of our main results, we observe that if assumption (3h₃), and then (3h₇), holds with $s_1 = s_2 = 0$, then Theorem 3.1 reduces to [CS6, Theorem 5.1] while Theorem 3.2 reduces to [CS6, Theorem 5.2] but with $m = 2$. Actually, the same holds true if both $p_1 \geq N$ and $p_2 \geq N$. Thus, to improve such previous results, here we assume that either $s_1 > 0$ or $s_2 > 0$ and we define

$$\ell_i(y) = \max\{\|y\|_{W_i}, \| |y|^{s_i} y \|_{W_i}\} \quad \text{if } y \in X_i, \quad \text{with } i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (3.1.67)$$

and then

$$\ell(u, v) = \max\{\|(u, v)\|_W, \|(|u|^{s_1} u, |v|^{s_2} v)\|_W\} \quad \text{if } (u, v) \in X. \quad (3.1.68)$$

From definitions (3.1.67) and (3.1.68) we have that

$$[\ell_i(y)]^{p_i} \leq \|y\|_{W_i}^{p_i} + \| |y|^{s_i} y \|_{W_i}^{p_i} \quad \text{if } y \in X_i, \quad \text{with } i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (3.1.69)$$

and

$$\max\{\ell_1(u), \ell_2(v)\} \leq \ell(u, v) \leq \ell_1(u) + \ell_2(v) \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in X. \quad (3.1.70)$$

Moreover, taking $\bar{p} = \min\{p_1, p_2\}$, direct computations imply that

$$[\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \geq \left[\frac{\ell(u, v)}{2} \right]^{\bar{p}} \quad \text{if } (u, v) \in X \text{ is such that } \ell(u, v) \geq 2. \quad (3.1.71)$$

Remark 3.9. For both $i \in \{1, 2\}$ definition (3.1.17) and identity (3.1.43) imply that the function $y \mapsto \| |y|^{s_i} y \|_{W_i}$ is continuous and well defined in $(X_i, \|\cdot\|_{X_i})$ and so $\ell_i : X_i \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous, too. Thus, from (3.1.18) we have that $(u, v) \mapsto \|(|u|^{s_1} u, |v|^{s_2} v)\|_W$ is continuous and well defined in $(X, \|\cdot\|_X)$, then also $\ell : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous with respect $\|\cdot\|_X$ and definition (3.1.68) implies that $\ell(u, v) \geq \|(u, v)\|_W$ for all $(u, v) \in X$ with $\ell(0, 0) = 0$.

Throughout the remaining part of this section, for simplicity we assume that

$$\int_{\Omega} A(x, 0, \mathbf{0}_N) dx = 0, \quad \int_{\Omega} B(x, 0, \mathbf{0}_N) dx = 0, \quad (3.1.72)$$

with $\mathbf{0}_N = (0, \dots, 0) \in \mathbb{R}^N$, and

$$\int_{\Omega} G(x, 0, 0) dx = 0. \quad (3.1.73)$$

Differently, one can always replace $\mathcal{J}(u, v)$ in (3.1.19) with the new functional

$$\mathcal{J}^*(u, v) = \mathcal{J}(u, v) - \int_{\Omega} A(x, 0, \mathbf{0}_N) dx - \int_{\Omega} B(x, 0, \mathbf{0}_N) dx + \int_{\Omega} G(x, 0, 0) dx,$$

since they share the same differential on X and so the same critical points.

Moreover, we denote by c_i every positive constant which arises during computations.

Now, we can prove our existence result.

Proof of Theorem 3.1. Firstly, hypothesis $(3g_4)$ allows us to take $\bar{\lambda} > 0$ such that

$$\limsup_{(u,v) \rightarrow (0,0)} \frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{p_1} + |v|^{p_2}} < \bar{\lambda} < \alpha_2 \min\{\lambda_{1,1}, \lambda_{2,1}\} \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \Omega. \quad (3.1.74)$$

Thus, from (3.1.74) and direct computations, estimate (3.1.13) ensures the existence of a constant $\sigma^* > 0$ such that

$$G(x, u, v) \leq \bar{\lambda}(|u|^{p_1} + |v|^{p_2}) + \sigma^*(|u|^{\bar{q}_1} + |v|^{\bar{q}_2}) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \text{ for all } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2, \quad (3.1.75)$$

with \bar{q}_1, \bar{q}_2 as in (3.1.14) so that (3.1.46) holds. Moreover, taking s_1, s_2 as in our setting of hypotheses and fixing any couple $(u, v) \in X$, from definition (3.1.19), condition (3h₇), estimate (3.1.75) together with (3.1.43) and (2.3.1) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq \left(\alpha_2 - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{1,1}} \right) \|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + \frac{\alpha_2}{(s_1+1)^{p_1}} \| |u|^{s_1} u \|_{W_1}^{p_1} - \sigma^* |u|_{\bar{q}_1}^{\bar{q}_1} \\ &\quad + \left(\alpha_2 - \frac{\bar{\lambda}}{\lambda_{2,1}} \right) \|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2} + \frac{\alpha_2}{(s_2+1)^{p_2}} \| |v|^{s_2} v \|_{W_2}^{p_2} - \sigma^* |v|_{\bar{q}_2}^{\bar{q}_2}, \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.76)$$

where from (3.1.46) and the Sobolev inequality (2.1.4) we have that

$$\int_{\Omega} |y|^{\bar{q}_i} dx = \int_{\Omega} \| |y|^{s_i} y \|_{W_i}^{\frac{\bar{q}_i}{s_i+1}} dx \leq c_1 \| |y|^{s_i} y \|_{W_i}^{\frac{\bar{q}_i}{s_i+1}} \quad \text{for all } y \in X_i, \text{ with } i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (3.1.77)$$

for a suitable $c_1 > 0$ independent of i . Then, by using (3.1.77) in (3.1.76), from (3.1.74) a positive constant $c_2 > 0$ exists such that definition (3.1.67), estimate (3.1.69) and direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq c_2 (\|u\|_{W_1}^{p_1} + \| |u|^{s_1} u \|_{W_1}^{p_1}) - c_3 \| |u|^{s_1} u \|_{W_1}^{\frac{\bar{q}_1}{s_1+1}} \\ &\quad + c_2 (\|v\|_{W_2}^{p_2} + \| |v|^{s_2} v \|_{W_2}^{p_2}) - c_3 \| |v|^{s_2} v \|_{W_2}^{\frac{\bar{q}_2}{s_2+1}} \\ &\geq [\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} \left(c_2 - c_3 [\ell_1(u)]^{\frac{\bar{q}_1}{s_1+1} - p_1} \right) + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \left(c_2 - c_3 [\ell_2(v)]^{\frac{\bar{q}_2}{s_2+1} - p_2} \right), \end{aligned}$$

for a suitable $c_3 > 0$; hence, from (3.1.46) and (3.1.70), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq [\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} \left(c_2 - c_3 [\ell(u, v)]^{\frac{\bar{q}_1}{s_1+1} - p_1} \right) \\ &\quad + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \left(c_2 - c_3 [\ell(u, v)]^{\frac{\bar{q}_2}{s_2+1} - p_2} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.78)$$

We note that, again from (3.1.46), a radius $r_0 > 0$ and a constant ϱ_1 can be found so that

$$c_2 - c_3 r_0^{\frac{\bar{q}_i}{s_i+1} - p_i} \geq \varrho_1 > 0 \quad \text{for both } i = 1 \text{ and } i = 2,$$

thus, from (3.1.70) and (3.1.78) we infer that a constant $\varrho_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$\ell(u, v) = r_0 \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \varrho_0. \quad (3.1.79)$$

On the other hand, from (3h₀)–(3h₂) and (3h₅) we have that [52, Proposition 6.5] implies the existence of some constants $b_1^*, b_2^* > 0$ such that

$$|A(x, t, \xi)| \leq b_1^* \left(1 + |t|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1} \right)} \right) + b_2^* \left(1 + |t|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1} \right) - p_1} \right) |\xi|^{p_1}$$

a.e. in Ω and for all $(t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$, with η_1, μ_2 as in (3h₂), respectively (3h₅), and, without loss of generality, we can assume $\frac{1}{\theta_1} \left(1 - \frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1} \right) - p_1 > 0$ (a priori, we can take

either μ_2 small enough or η_1 large enough). Thus, taking $\varphi_{1,1} \in X_1$ as in (2.3.2), from (3.1.19), (3.1.41), (3.1.72) and direct computations, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(\tau\varphi_{1,1}, 0) &\leq b_1^* \tau^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_{1,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} dx + b_2^* \tau^{p_1} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla\varphi_{1,1}|^{p_1} dx \\ &\quad + b_2^* \tau^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})} \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_{1,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}(1-\frac{\mu_2}{\eta_1})-p_1} |\nabla\varphi_{1,1}|^{p_1} dx \\ &\quad - \tau^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} \int_{\Omega} h_1(x) |\varphi_{1,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} dx + c_4, \end{aligned}$$

for a suitable $c_4 > 0$, which implies, from (3.1.24), that

$$\mathcal{J}(\tau\varphi_{1,1}, 0) \rightarrow -\infty \quad \text{as } \tau \rightarrow +\infty$$

as (2.3.2) and Remark 3.6 ensure that $\int_{\Omega} h_1(x) |\varphi_{1,1}|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} dx > 0$.

Hence, considering r_0, ϱ_0 so that (3.1.79) holds, a point $e_1 \in X_1$ can be found so that

$$\|(e_1, 0)\|_W > r_0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}(e_1, 0) < \varrho_0. \quad (3.1.80)$$

Finally, from (3.1.19), (3.1.72) and (3.1.73) it is $\mathcal{J}(0, 0) = 0$, which, together with Remark 3.9, (3.1.79), (3.1.80) and Propositions 3.1 and 3.2, ensures that Theorem 1.3 applies and a critical point (u, v) exists in X such that $\mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \varrho_0 > 0$. \square

To prove our multiplicity theorem, some geometric conditions are needed. In particular, if assumptions (3h₀)–(3h₆) and (3g₀)–(3g₃) hold, we are able to state the following results.

Proposition 3.3. *For any fixed $\varrho \in \mathbb{R}$, an integer $m = m(\varrho) \geq 1$ and a radius $R_m > 0$ exist such that*

$$(u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}, \quad \ell(u, v) = R_m \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \varrho.$$

Proof. Firstly, we note that (3.1.43) and (3.1.69) imply that

$$\int_{\Omega} (1 + |y|^{s_i p_i}) |\nabla y|^{p_i} dx \geq \frac{1}{(s_i + 1)^{p_i}} [\ell_i(y)]^{p_i} \quad \text{if } y \in X_i, \text{ for each } i \in \{1, 2\}. \quad (3.1.81)$$

Then, taking $(u, v) \in X$, from (3.1.19), (3.1.31), (3.1.32), (3.1.81), together with (3.1.13) where \bar{q}_1, \bar{q}_2 satisfy (3.1.46), we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq \frac{\mu_0(\mu_1\theta_1 + \mu_2)}{(s_1 + 1)^{p_1}} [\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} + \frac{\mu_0(\mu_1\theta_2 + \mu_2)}{(s_2 + 1)^{p_2}} [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \\ &\quad - \sigma_2 \int_{\Omega} |u|^{\bar{q}_1} dx - \sigma_2 \int_{\Omega} |v|^{\bar{q}_2} dx - c_1, \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.82)$$

for some $c_1 > 0$. We note that for each $i \in \{1, 2\}$ condition (3.1.46) allows us to take $r_i > 0$ so that

$$\frac{r_i}{p_i} + \frac{\bar{q}_i - r_i}{p_i^*(s_i + 1)} = 1,$$

then, reasoning as in [56, Proposition 4.5], from classical interpolation arguments, (2.1.4) and (3.1.67) we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega} |y|^{\bar{q}_i} dx \leq c_2 [\ell_i(y)]^{\frac{\bar{q}_i - r_i}{s_i + 1}} \left(\int_{\Omega} |y|^{p_i} dx \right)^{\frac{r_i}{p_i}} \quad \text{for all } y \in X_i,$$

for a suitable constant $c_2 > 0$ independent of i .

Thus, fixing any $m \in \mathbb{N}$, from (2.3.4) and, again, (3.1.67) it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} |y|^{\bar{q}_i} dx \leq c_2 \lambda_{i,m+1}^{-\frac{r_i}{p_i}} [\ell_i(y)]^{\frac{r_i s_i + \bar{q}_i}{s_i + 1}} \quad \text{for all } y \in Y_m^{X_i}, \quad (3.1.83)$$

where from (3.1.46) it is

$$\frac{r_i s_i + \bar{q}_i}{s_i + 1} > p_i. \quad (3.1.84)$$

Hence, taking any couple $(u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}$, by using estimate (3.1.83) in (3.1.82) we obtain that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq c_3 [\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} - c_4 \lambda_{1,m+1}^{-\frac{r_1}{p_1}} [\ell_1(u)]^{\frac{r_1 s_1 + \bar{q}_1}{s_1 + 1}} + c_3 [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} - c_4 \lambda_{2,m+1}^{-\frac{r_2}{p_2}} [\ell_2(v)]^{\frac{r_2 s_2 + \bar{q}_2}{s_2 + 1}} - c_1$$

or better, from (3.1.70) and (3.1.84), we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq [\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} \left(c_3 - c_4 \lambda_{1,m+1}^{-\frac{r_1}{p_1}} [\ell(u, v)]^{\frac{r_1 s_1 + \bar{q}_1}{s_1 + 1} - p_1} \right) \\ &\quad + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \left(c_3 - c_4 \lambda_{2,m+1}^{-\frac{r_2}{p_2}} [\ell(u, v)]^{\frac{r_2 s_2 + \bar{q}_2}{s_2 + 1} - p_2} \right) - c_1. \end{aligned} \quad (3.1.85)$$

Now, for each $i \in \{1, 2\}$, from (3.1.84) we can define $R_{i,m} > 0$ so that

$$c_4 \lambda_{i,m+1}^{-\frac{r_i}{p_i}} R_{i,m}^{\frac{r_i s_i + \bar{q}_i}{s_i + 1} - p_i} = \frac{c_3}{2} \iff R_{i,m} = \left(\frac{c_3}{2c_4} \lambda_{i,m+1}^{\frac{r_i}{p_i}} \right)^{\frac{s_i + 1}{r_i s_i + \bar{q}_i - p_i (s_i + 1)}} \quad (3.1.86)$$

and, since from (2.3.3) it follows that $R_{i,m} \nearrow +\infty$ as $m \rightarrow +\infty$, we have that

$$R_m := \min\{R_{1,m}, R_{2,m}\} \rightarrow +\infty \quad \text{as } m \rightarrow +\infty \quad (3.1.87)$$

which implies $R_m \geq 2$ for all $m \geq m_0$ if $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ is large enough.

So, for any $m \geq m_0$, taking $(u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2}$ such that $\ell(u, v) = R_m$, from (3.1.71) we have that

$$[\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \geq \left(\frac{R_m}{2} \right)^{\bar{p}}, \quad (3.1.88)$$

while from (3.1.85), by using (3.1.84), (3.1.86) and the definition in (3.1.87), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{J}(u, v) &\geq [\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} \left(c_3 - c_4 \lambda_{1,m+1}^{-\frac{r_1}{p_1}} R_m^{\frac{r_1 s_1 + \bar{q}_1}{s_1 + 1} - p_1} \right) \\
 &\quad + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \left(c_3 - c_4 \lambda_{2,m+1}^{-\frac{r_2}{p_2}} R_m^{\frac{r_2 s_2 + \bar{q}_2}{s_2 + 1} - p_2} \right) - c_1 \\
 &\geq [\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} \left(c_3 - c_4 \lambda_{1,m+1}^{-\frac{r_1}{p_1}} R_{1,m}^{\frac{r_1 s_1 + \bar{q}_1}{s_1 + 1} - p_1} \right) \\
 &\quad + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2} \left(c_3 - c_4 \lambda_{2,m+1}^{-\frac{r_2}{p_2}} R_{2,m}^{\frac{r_2 s_2 + \bar{q}_2}{s_2 + 1} - p_2} \right) - c_1 \\
 &= \frac{c_3}{2} ([\ell_1(u)]^{p_1} + [\ell_2(v)]^{p_2}) - c_1.
 \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for any $m \geq m_0$ estimate (3.1.88) implies that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \frac{c_3}{2} \left(\frac{R_m}{2} \right)^{\bar{p}} - c_1 \quad \text{if } (u, v) \in Y_m^{X_1} \times Y_m^{X_2} \text{ is such that } \ell(u, v) = R_m. \quad (3.1.89)$$

Finally, we note that the proof follows from (3.1.87) and (3.1.89). \square

At last, by reasoning as in the first part of the proof of [CS6, Theorem 5.2] (we note that the computations do not involve the supercritical growth of $G(x, u, v)$ but only its lower bound coming from assumption (3g₅)), the following result can be stated, too.

Proposition 3.4. *If also hypothesis (3g₅) holds, then for any finite-dimensional subspace V of X a suitable radius $R_V > 0$ exists such that*

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \leq 0 \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in V \text{ such that } \|(u, v)\|_X \geq R_V.$$

In particular, the functional \mathcal{J} is bounded from above in V .

Now, we can prove our multiplicity results.

Proof of Theorem 3.2. Firstly, we observe that (3.1.19), (3.1.72) and (3.1.73) give $\mathcal{J}(0, 0) = 0$, while assumptions (3h₈) and (3g₆) imply that the functional \mathcal{J} is even in X . Furthermore, taking any $r > 0$, we set

$$\mathcal{M}_r = \{(u, v) \in X : \ell(u, v) = r\}.$$

By definition, \mathcal{M}_r is the boundary of a symmetric neighborhood of the origin which is bounded with respect to $\|\cdot\|_W$.

Now, fixing any $\varrho > 0$, from Proposition 3.3 it follows that an integer $m_\varrho \geq 1$ and a radius $r_\varrho = r_\varrho(m_\varrho) > 0$ exist so that

$$(u, v) \in \mathcal{M}_{r_\varrho} \cap (Y_{m_\varrho}^{X_1} \times Y_{m_\varrho}^{X_2}) \implies \mathcal{J}(u, v) \geq \varrho,$$

while, by choosing $m > m_\varrho$, the m -dimensional space V_m is such that $\text{codim } Y_{m_\varrho} < \dim V_m$, and from Proposition 3.4 a radius $R_{V_m} > 0$ exists so that

$$\mathcal{J}(u, v) \leq 0 \quad \text{for all } (u, v) \in V_m \text{ such that } \|(u, v)\|_X \geq R_{V_m}.$$

Hence, assumption (\mathcal{H}_ϱ) in Theorem 1.4 is verified. Then, the arbitrariness of $\varrho > 0$ so that (\mathcal{H}_ϱ) holds, together with Propositions 3.1 and 3.2, allows us to apply Corollary 1.1 and the existence of a sequence of diverging critical levels for the functional \mathcal{J} in X is provided. \square

Finally, to better explain the required hypotheses and highlight more the supercritical nature of our problem, we consider the particular setting

$$A(x, t, \xi) = \frac{1}{p_1}(1 + |t|^{s_1 p_1})|\xi|^{p_1}, \quad B(x, t, \xi) = \frac{1}{p_2}(1 + |t|^{s_2 p_2})|\xi|^{p_2}, \quad (3.1.90)$$

and

$$G(x, u, v) = \frac{1}{q_1}|u|^{q_1} + \frac{1}{q_2}|v|^{q_2} + c_*|u|^{\gamma_1}|v|^{\gamma_2}, \quad (3.1.91)$$

with $c_* \geq 0$ and some positive exponents p_i, s_i, q_i, γ_i for each $i \in \{1, 2\}$. So, \mathcal{J} in (3.1.19) reduces to the functional $\mathcal{J}_0 : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_0(u, v) &= \frac{1}{p_1} \int_{\Omega} (1 + |u|^{s_1 p_1}) |\nabla u|^{p_1} dx + \frac{1}{p_2} \int_{\Omega} (1 + |v|^{s_2 p_2}) |\nabla v|^{p_2} dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{1}{q_1} |u|^{q_1} + \frac{1}{q_2} |v|^{q_2} + c_* |u|^{\gamma_1} |v|^{\gamma_2} \right) dx, \end{aligned}$$

and, in a suitable set of assumptions, system (3.1.1) turns into the model problem

$$\begin{cases} \begin{aligned} -\text{div}((1 + |u|^{s_1 p_1}) |\nabla u|^{p_1 - 2} \nabla u) + s_1 |u|^{s_1 p_1 - 2} u |\nabla u|^{p_1} \\ = |u|^{q_1 - 2} u + \gamma_1 c_* |u|^{\gamma_1 - 2} u |v|^{\gamma_2} \end{aligned} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ \begin{aligned} -\text{div}((1 + |v|^{s_2 p_2}) |\nabla v|^{p_2 - 2} \nabla v) + s_2 |v|^{s_2 p_2 - 2} v |\nabla v|^{p_2} \\ = \gamma_2 c_* |u|^{\gamma_1} |v|^{\gamma_2 - 2} v + |v|^{q_2 - 2} v \end{aligned} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = v = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases} \quad (3.1.92)$$

Hence, the previous results can be reworded in this way.

Theorem 3.3. *Let $A(x, t, \xi)$, $B(x, t, \xi)$ and $G(x, u, v)$ be as in (3.1.90) and (3.1.91) with $p_i > 1$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$, $c_* \geq 0$ and either $p_1 < N$ or $p_2 < N$. Assume that θ_1, θ_2 exist such that*

$$2 < 1 + p_i < p_i(s_i + 1) < \frac{1}{\theta_i} \leq q_i < p_i^*(s_i + 1) \quad \text{for } i \in \{1, 2\}, \quad (3.1.93)$$

where p_1^*, p_2^* are the critical Sobolev exponents, and also

$$1 < \gamma_1 < q_1, \quad 1 < \gamma_2 < q_2 \quad \text{are such that} \quad \gamma_1 \theta_1 + \gamma_2 \theta_2 \geq 1. \quad (3.1.94)$$

Then, if

$$\gamma_j \frac{q_i - 1}{q_i - \gamma_i} < \frac{p_i}{N} \left(1 - \frac{1}{p_i^*(s_i + 1)} \right) p_j^*(s_j + 1) \quad \text{for } i, j \in \{1, 2\}, i \neq j, \quad (3.1.95)$$

problem (3.1.92) admits infinitely many weak bounded distinct solutions.

Proof. Taking $A(x, t, \xi)$ and $B(x, t, \xi)$ as in (3.1.90), from (3.1.93) it follows that conditions (3h₀)–(3h₄) and (3h₆) hold. Moreover, if $G(x, u, v)$ is as in (3.1.91), assumptions (3.1.93)–(3.1.95) and Young inequality imply that (3g₀)–(3g₂) are satisfied with

$$t_1 = \gamma_2 \frac{q_1 - 1}{q_1 - \gamma_1}, \quad t_2 = \gamma_1 \frac{q_2 - 1}{q_2 - \gamma_2}.$$

On the other hand, again from (3.1.93), direct computations allow us to prove that hypotheses (3h₅) and (3g₃) are verified, too. At last, also condition (3g₅) holds as (3.1.93) and direct computations allow us to prove that for any $R \geq 2$ it is

$$\frac{G(x, u, v)}{|u|^{\frac{1}{\theta_1}} + |v|^{\frac{1}{\theta_2}}} \geq \frac{1}{2} \min \left\{ \frac{1}{q_1}, \frac{1}{q_2} \right\} \quad \text{if } (u, v) \in \mathbb{R}^2 \text{ is such that } |(u, v)| \geq R.$$

Then, since the symmetric assumptions (3h₈) and (3g₆) are trivially satisfied, the thesis follows from Theorem 3.2. \square

3.2 A class of N -Laplacian problems

A classical N -Laplacian problem is

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta_N u = h(u) e^{\alpha|u|^\gamma} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (3.2.1)$$

with Ω open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 2$ and $\Delta_N u = \operatorname{div}(|\nabla u|^{N-2} \nabla u)$ standard N -Laplacian operator, where $\alpha, \gamma > 0$ are given constants and $h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a continuous function which has a “subexponential” growth at infinity, i.e., which is so that

$$\lim_{|t| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{h(t)}{e^{\delta|t|^\gamma}} = 0 \quad \forall \delta > 0.$$

It is well known that this problem is governed by the Trudinger–Moser inequality

$$\sup_{\substack{u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega) \\ \|u\|_N \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} e^{\alpha_N |u|^{N'}} dx < +\infty, \quad (3.2.2)$$

where $W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ is the usual Sobolev space with norm $\|u\|_N = \left(\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^N dx \right)^{1/N}$, $\alpha_N = N \omega_{N-1}^{1/(N-1)}$, ω_{N-1} is the area of the unit sphere in \mathbb{R}^N and $N' = N/(N-1)$

is the Hölder conjugate of N (see Trudinger [180] and Moser [146]), so (3.2.1) has a subcritical growth if $\gamma < N'$ while critical if $\gamma = N'$.

Existence of solutions of problem (3.2.1) in both the subcritical and the critical case has been widely studied in the literature (see, e.g., [2, 3, 86–89, 94, 116, 154] and references therein). On the other hand, several physical phenomena, for example in the theory of superfluid film and in dissipative quantum mechanics, are described by equations where the principal part is a model of $-\operatorname{div} [(A_0(x) + A(x) |u|^{ps}) |\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u]$ (for more details, see [134] and references therein) and some existence results have been obtained for nonlinear terms with a suitable supercritical growth when such a coefficient appears (see [56]).

Thus, in the present chapter, we prove the existence of weak bounded solutions to the quasilinear problem

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div} [(A_0(x) + A(x) |u|^{Ns}) |\nabla u|^{N-2} \nabla u] + s A(x) |u|^{Ns-2} u |\nabla u|^N \\ \hspace{15em} = h(u) e^{\alpha|u|^\gamma} & \text{in } \Omega, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (3.2.3)$$

where $s > 1/N$ is a constant and the coefficients $A_0, A \in L^\infty(\Omega)$ are strictly positive and far away from zero, while the continuous function $h(u)$ has a subexponential growth at infinity and satisfies suitable estimates together with the primitive of the nonlinear term (for the complete statement, see Theorem 3.4). Anyway, even if the term $|u|^{Ns}$ in the coefficient makes the variational approach more difficult, it can allow the nonlinear term to be supercritical as it makes “stronger” the principal part. Thus, here, the novelty with respect to previous papers, is not only the presence of a coefficient but also that problem (3.2.3) has weak solutions for $0 < \gamma < (s+1)N'$ which includes also the supercritical range $N' < \gamma < (s+1)N'$.

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS2].

3.2.1 Preliminaries

Now, we are able to give the set of hypotheses we need for our problem.

In problem (3.2.3), let us suppose that the exponents s, α and γ are such that

$$s > \frac{1}{N} \quad (3.2.4)$$

and also

$$\alpha > 0, \quad 0 < \gamma < (s+1)N'. \quad (3.2.5)$$

Moreover, assume that the coefficients $A_0 : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $A : \Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are such that:

($\tilde{3}h_1$) $A_0, A \in L^\infty(\Omega)$ and a constant $\alpha_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$A_0(x) \geq \alpha_0 \quad \text{and} \quad A(x) \geq \alpha_0 \quad \text{for a.a. } x \in \Omega.$$

On the other hand, for function $h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and the related primitive

$$G(t) = \int_0^t h(v) e^{\alpha|v|^\gamma} dv, \quad (3.2.6)$$

which is well defined if $h(t)$ is continuous and $\gamma \geq 0$, we consider the following conditions:

($3\tilde{h}_2$) $h \in \mathcal{C}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$ is such that

$$\lim_{|t| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{h(t)}{e^{\delta|t|^\gamma}} = 0 \quad \forall \delta > 0, \quad (3.2.7)$$

and some constants $\bar{\delta}, \sigma_1, \sigma_2 > 0$ and a power $0 \leq q < N(s+1)$ exist such that

$$N(s+1)(1+\bar{\delta})G(t) - t h(t) e^{\alpha|t|^\gamma} \leq \sigma_1 |t|^q + \sigma_2 \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}; \quad (3.2.8)$$

($3\tilde{g}_1$) some constants $\sigma_3, \sigma_4 > 0$ and a power $\tau > N(s+1)$ exist such that

$$G(t) \geq \sigma_3 |t|^\tau - \sigma_4 \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R};$$

($3\tilde{g}_2$) some constants $\sigma, \nu > 0$ exist such that

$$G(t) \leq \left(\frac{\lambda_1 \alpha_0}{N} - \sigma \right) |t|^N \quad \text{if } |t| \leq \nu,$$

where λ_1 denotes the first eigenvalue of $-\Delta_N$ in $W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ and α_0 is as in (h_1).

Remark 3.10. If conditions (3.2.4) and ($3\tilde{h}_1$) are verified, then

$$\mathcal{A}(x, t, \xi) = \frac{1}{N} (A_0(x) + A(x)|t|^{Ns}) |\xi|^N$$

is a \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function on $\Omega \times \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$ such that for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ and all $(t, \xi) \in \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R}^N$ we have that

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{A}}{\partial t}(x, t, \xi) = sA(x)|t|^{Ns-2} |\xi|^N \quad \text{and} \quad \nabla_\xi \mathcal{A}(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi = N\mathcal{A}(x, t, \xi)$$

with also

$$\nabla_\xi \mathcal{A}(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi \geq \alpha_0(1 + |t|^{Ns}) |\xi|^N \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{\partial \mathcal{A}}{\partial t}(x, t, \xi) t = sA(x)|t|^{Ns} |\xi|^N \geq 0.$$

Hence, the hypotheses (H_0)-(H_5) and (H_7) in [56] are all satisfied.

Example 3.1. Possible examples of function $h(t)$ which satisfy all the previous assumptions are

$$h_r(t) = \begin{cases} |t|^{r-2} t & \text{if } r > N \\ \beta_0 |t|^{N-2} t & \text{if } r = N \text{ but with } 0 < \beta_0 < \lambda_1 \alpha_0. \end{cases}$$

In fact, taking $G_r(t)$ as in (3.2.6) with $h(t) = h_r(t)$, in both cases assumption $(\tilde{3}h_2)$ is satisfied as $\gamma > 0$ and direct computations imply that

$$\lim_{|t| \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{G_r(t)}{th_r(t)e^{\alpha|t|^\gamma}} = 0,$$

while $(\tilde{3}g_1)$ follows from well known properties of the exponential map and $(\tilde{3}g_2)$ is a direct consequence of

$$\lim_{|t| \rightarrow 0} \frac{G_r(t)}{|t|^N} = 0 \quad \text{if } r > N, \quad \lim_{|t| \rightarrow 0} \frac{G_N(t)}{|t|^N} = \frac{\beta_0}{N} \quad \text{with } \beta_0 < \lambda_1 \alpha_0.$$

Now, we are ready to state our main existence result.

Theorem 3.4. *Let us suppose that the exponents s , α and γ are such that (3.2.4) and (3.2.5) hold and assume that the hypotheses $(\tilde{3}h_1)$, $(\tilde{3}h_2)$, $(\tilde{3}g_1)$ and $(\tilde{3}g_2)$ are satisfied, too. Then, problem (3.2.3) possesses at least one bounded nontrivial weak solution.*

Our aim is investigating the existence of weak solutions of problem (3.2.3) by means of the abstract variational tools introduced at the beginning of this section and which involve two different Banach spaces. Thus, as first Banach space we consider

$$X = W_0^{1,N}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \tag{3.2.9}$$

endowed with the intersection norm

$$\|u\|_X = \|u\|_N + |u|_\infty, \quad u \in X,$$

while as second Banach space we consider

$$W = W_0^{1,N}(\Omega) \quad \text{with } \|u\|_W = \|u\|_N.$$

Clearly, it is $X \hookrightarrow W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ continuously with $\|u\|_N \leq \|u\|_X$ for all $u \in X$. Moreover, we have that

$$u \in X \quad \implies \quad |u|^s u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega). \tag{3.2.10}$$

Indeed, if $u \in X$ from the identity

$$|\nabla(|u|^s u)|^N = (s+1)^N |u|^{Ns} |\nabla u|^N \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \tag{3.2.11}$$

it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_\Omega |\nabla(|u|^s u)|^N dx &= (s+1)^N \int_\Omega |u|^{Ns} |\nabla u|^N dx \leq (s+1)^N |u|_\infty^{Ns} \|u\|_N^N \\ &\leq (s+1)^N \|u\|_X^{N(s+1)}, \end{aligned}$$

hence,

$$\| |u|^s u \|_N \leq (s+1) \|u\|_X^{s+1}.$$

We note that, if condition $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ is verified and $h(t)$ is a continuous map, then for any $s, \gamma \geq 0$, the functional

$$E(u) = \frac{1}{N} \int_{\Omega} (A_0(x) + A(x)|u|^{Ns}) |\nabla u|^N dx - \int_{\Omega} G(u) dx \quad (3.2.12)$$

is well defined for all $u \in X$, with $G(u)$ as in (3.2.6). Or better, taking any $u, v \in X$, if $s \geq 0$ we have that $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ and Hölder inequality imply that $(A_0(\cdot) + A(\cdot)|u|^{Ns}) |\nabla u|^{N-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \in L^1(\Omega)$, and also, again from $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ it follows that $A(\cdot)|u|^{Ns-2} u v |\nabla u|^N \in L^1(\Omega)$, while $\gamma \geq 0$ and the continuity of $h(t)$ give that $h(u)e^{\alpha|u|^\gamma} v \in L^1(\Omega)$ since both u and v are bounded. Thus, for all $u, v \in X$ the Gâteaux derivative of the functional E in u along the direction v exists and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle dE(u), v \rangle &= \int_{\Omega} (A_0(x) + A(x)|u|^{Ns}) |\nabla u|^{N-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx \\ &\quad + s \int_{\Omega} A(x)|u|^{Ns-2} u v |\nabla u|^N dx - \int_{\Omega} h(u)e^{\alpha|u|^\gamma} v dx. \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.13)$$

More precisely, the following regularity result holds.

Proposition 3.5. *Assume that (3.2.4) and $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ are verified and let $\gamma > 0$ and $h \in \mathcal{C}(\mathbb{R}, \mathbb{R})$. Then, if $(u_n)_n \subset X$, $u \in X$ are such that*

$$\|u_n - u\|_W \rightarrow 0, \quad u_n \rightarrow u \text{ a.e. in } \Omega \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow +\infty$$

and $M > 0$ exists so that $|u_n|_\infty \leq M$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$,

then

$$E(u_n) \rightarrow E(u) \quad \text{and} \quad \|dE(u_n) - dE(u)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence, $E : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a \mathcal{C}^1 functional with Fréchet derivative defined as in (3.2.13).

Proof. The proof follows from [56, Proposition 3.2] by means of Remark 3.10 and the Lebesgue's Dominated Convergence Theorem. \square

3.2.2 The weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition

The main purpose of this section is showing that the functional $E(u)$, defined as in (3.2.12), complies with Definition 1.2 on the Banach space X in (3.2.9). To this aim, we introduce some crucial lemmas.

Firstly, we note that from the classical Trudinger–Moser inequality (3.2.2) and equality (3.2.11) in X we obtain a variant of Trudinger–Moser inequality but dealing with the Banach space X :

$$K_N := \sup_{\substack{u \in X \\ \| |u|^s u \|_N \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} e^{\alpha_N |u|^{(s+1)N'}} dx < +\infty. \quad (3.2.14)$$

Such an estimate allows us to obtain the following lemma which is useful in our setting.

Lemma 3.2. *If power γ is such that (3.2.5) holds, then*

$$K_\beta := \sup_{\substack{u \in X \\ \| |u|^s u \|_N \leq 1}} \int_{\Omega} e^{\beta |u|^\gamma} dx < +\infty \quad \text{for every } \beta > 0. \quad (3.2.15)$$

Moreover, if $(u_n)_n \subset X$ is such that

$$\| |u_n|^s u_n \|_N \leq c_* \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N} \quad (3.2.16)$$

for some constant $c_* > 0$, then for every $\beta > 0$ a constant $k_\beta^* = k_\beta^*(c_*) > 0$ exists such that

$$\int_{\Omega} e^{\beta |u_n|^\gamma} dx \leq k_\beta^* \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (3.2.17)$$

Proof. Let $\beta > 0$ be fixed. Then, since (3.2.5) implies $p = \frac{(s+1)N'}{\gamma} > 1$, from the Young inequality applied to such a power, for any $\varepsilon > 0$ a constant $C_\varepsilon = C_\varepsilon(\beta) > 0$ exists such that

$$\beta |t|^\gamma \leq \varepsilon |t|^{(s+1)N'} + C_\varepsilon \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (3.2.18)$$

Thus, if $u \in X$ is such that $\| |u|^s u \|_N \leq 1$, taking $\varepsilon = \alpha_N$ in (3.2.18), from (3.2.14) we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega} e^{\beta |u|^\gamma} dx \leq \int_{\Omega} e^{\alpha_N |u|^{(s+1)N'} + C_{\alpha_N}} dx \leq e^{C_{\alpha_N}} K_N$$

which implies (3.2.15).

Now, let $(u_n)_n \subset X$ be such that (3.2.16) holds and, without loss of generality, we assume that $u_n \neq 0$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$, so that we can put

$$w_n = \frac{|u_n|^s u_n}{\| |u_n|^s u_n \|_N}$$

with $\|w_n\|_N = 1$. Thus, denoting

$$\varepsilon_N := \frac{\alpha_N}{c_*^{N'}}$$

and taking $\varepsilon = \varepsilon_N$ in (3.2.18), from (3.2.16) and direct computations it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} e^{\beta |u_n|^\gamma} dx \leq \int_{\Omega} e^{\varepsilon_N \| |u_n|^s u_n \|_N^{N'} |w_n|^{N'} + C_{\varepsilon_N}} dx \leq e^{C_{\varepsilon_N}} \int_{\Omega} e^{\alpha_N |w_n|^{N'}} dx$$

which, together with (3.2.2), implies (3.2.17). \square

Now, to consider the supercritical growth, we need the following application of the Rellich Embedding Theorem.

Lemma 3.3. Taking $p = N$ and $s > 0$, let $(u_n)_n \subset X$ be a sequence such that

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} (1 + |u_n|^{Ns}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \right)_n \text{ is bounded.}$$

Then, $u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ exists such that $|u|^s u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$, too, and, up to subsequences, if $n \rightarrow +\infty$ we have

$$u_n \rightharpoonup u \quad \text{weakly in } W_0^{1,N}(\Omega), \quad (3.2.19)$$

$$|u_n|^s u_n \rightharpoonup |u|^s u \text{ weakly in } W_0^{1,N}(\Omega), \quad (3.2.20)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega, \quad (3.2.21)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \quad \text{strongly in } L^r(\Omega) \text{ for } 1 \leq r < +\infty. \quad (3.2.22)$$

Proof. For the proof, it is enough reasoning as in [56, Lemma 3.8] but with $p^* = +\infty$. \square

Now, we are able to prove that our functional $E(u)$ satisfies the weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition.

Proposition 3.6. Under assumptions (3.2.4), (3.2.5), $(\tilde{3}h_1)$, $(\tilde{3}h_2)$ and $(\tilde{3}g_1)$, the functional $E : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ as in (3.2.12) satisfies the (wCPS) condition in \mathbb{R} .

Proof. Let $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and let $(u_n)_n \subset X$ be a (CPS) $_c$ sequence, i.e.

$$E(u_n) \rightarrow c \quad \text{and} \quad \|dE(u_n)\|_{X'}(1 + \|u_n\|_X) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (3.2.23)$$

For simplicity, our proof is divided in several steps; more precisely, we will prove that:

1. $(u_n)_n$ is bounded in $W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$, or to be more precise, that

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} (1 + |u_n|^{Ns}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \right)_n \text{ is bounded;} \quad (3.2.24)$$

hence, also $(\| |u_n|^s u_n \|_N)_n$ is bounded in $W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ and $u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ exists such that $|u|^s u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$, too, and, up to subsequences, the limits (3.2.19)–(3.2.22) hold;

2. $u \in L^\infty(\Omega)$;
3. if $k > |u|_\infty + 1$ is large enough, then $(T_k(u_n))_n$ is a Palais–Smale sequence at level c , that is

$$\|dE(T_k(u_n))\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad (3.2.25)$$

and

$$E(T_k(u_n)) \rightarrow c, \quad (3.2.26)$$

where $T_k : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is defined as

$$T_k t := \begin{cases} t & \text{if } |t| \leq k; \\ k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k; \end{cases} \quad (3.2.27)$$

4. $\|T_k u_n - u\|_N \rightarrow 0$, and then $\|u_n - u\|_N \rightarrow 0$, too;
5. $E(u) = c$ and $dE(u) = 0$.

We use the notation $(\varepsilon_n)_n$ for any infinitesimal sequence depending only on $(u_n)_n$ and $(\varepsilon_{k,n})_n$ when the infinitesimal sequence depends also on a constant k .

Step 1. Taking $\bar{\delta} > 0$ as in (3.2.8), from (3.2.12), (3.2.13), (3.2.23), $(3\tilde{h}_1)$, (3.2.8) and direct computations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned}
 N(s+1)(1+\bar{\delta})c + \varepsilon_n &= N(s+1)(1+\bar{\delta})E(u_n) - \langle dE(u_n), u_n \rangle \\
 &\geq (s+1)\bar{\delta} \alpha_0 \int_{\Omega} (1+|u_n|^{Ns}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \\
 &\quad + \int_{\Omega} \left(u_n h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} - N(s+1)(1+\bar{\delta})G(u_n) \right) dx \\
 &\geq (s+1)\bar{\delta} \alpha_0 \int_{\Omega} (1+|u_n|^{Ns}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx - \sigma_1 \int_{\Omega} |u_n|^q dx - \sigma_2 |\Omega|.
 \end{aligned} \tag{3.2.28}$$

Without loss of generality, we suppose $q \geq 1+s$. Then, from (3.2.10) and the Sobolev Embedding Theorem $W_0^{1,N}(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^{\frac{q}{s+1}}(\Omega)$ we have that

$$\int_{\Omega} |u_n|^q dx = \int_{\Omega} |u_n|^s |u_n|^{\frac{q}{s+1}} dx \leq c_1 \| |u_n|^s u_n \|_N^{\frac{q}{s+1}};$$

hence, since $q < N(s+1)$, from (3.2.28) we conclude that (3.2.24) is satisfied and then, from Lemma 3.3, a function $u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ exists which satisfies all the requirements in Step 1.

Step 2. Arguing by contradiction, assume that $u \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$; hence, either

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} u = +\infty \tag{3.2.29}$$

or

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} (-u) = +\infty. \tag{3.2.30}$$

For example, suppose that (3.2.29) holds and for any fixed $\tilde{k} \in \mathbb{N}$ we define the function

$$R_{\tilde{k}}^+ t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \leq \tilde{k} \\ t - \tilde{k} & \text{if } t > \tilde{k} \end{cases}. \tag{3.2.31}$$

Now, taking any $\delta > 0$ such that the limit in (3.2.7) is verified, a radius $R_1 > 0$ exists such that

$$|h(t)| \leq e^{\delta|t|^\gamma} \quad \text{if } |t| \geq R_1. \tag{3.2.32}$$

Thus, taking any integer $k \geq R_1$, from (3.2.29) we have that

$$|\Omega_k^+| > 0, \quad \text{with} \quad \Omega_k^+ := \{x \in \Omega : u(x) > k\}. \tag{3.2.33}$$

So, if we take $\tilde{k} = k^{s+1}$ in definition (3.2.31), from (3.2.20) it follows that

$$R_{k^{s+1}}^+(|u_n|^s u_n) \rightharpoonup R_{k^{s+1}}^+(|u|^s u) \quad \text{weakly in } W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$$

which implies, by the sequentially weakly lower semicontinuity of $\|\cdot\|_N$, that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u^{s+1}|^N dx \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n^{s+1}|^N dx, \quad (3.2.34)$$

where the set Ω_k^+ defined in (3.2.33) is such that

$$\Omega_k^+ = \{x \in \Omega : |u|^s u > k^{s+1}\} \quad (3.2.35)$$

and also

$$\Omega_{n,k}^+ := \{x \in \Omega : u_n(x) > k\} \quad \text{is such that} \quad \Omega_{n,k}^+ = \{x \in \Omega : |u_n|^s u_n > k^{s+1}\}.$$

On the other hand, from definition (3.2.31) with $\tilde{k} = k$, we have that $(R_k^+ u_n)_n \subset X$ and $\|R_k^+ u_n\|_X \leq \|u_n\|_X$, while from (3.2.22) we obtain

$$R_k^+ u_n \rightarrow R_k^+ u \quad \text{strongly in } L^2(\Omega); \quad (3.2.36)$$

hence, (3.2.23) gives

$$|\langle dE(u_n), R_k^+ u_n \rangle| \rightarrow 0. \quad (3.2.37)$$

From (3.2.37) together with (3.2.33), it follows that $n_k \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that

$$|\langle dE(u_n), R_k^+ u_n \rangle| \leq |\Omega_k^+| \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (3.2.38)$$

We note that, from (3.2.6), (3.2.13), definition (3.2.31) and hypothesis $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ we have that (3.2.11) and direct computations give

$$\begin{aligned} \langle dE(u_n), R_k^+ u_n \rangle &= \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} (A_0(x) + A(x)|u_n|^{Ns}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \\ &\quad + s \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} A(x) |u_n|^{N(s-2)} u_n (u_n - k) |\nabla u_n|^N dx - \int_{\Omega} h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} R_k^+ u_n dx \\ &\geq \alpha_0 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |u_n|^{Ns} |\nabla u|^N dx - \int_{\Omega} h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} R_k^+ u_n dx \\ &= \frac{\alpha_0}{(s+1)^N} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla(u_n^{s+1})|^N dx - \int_{\Omega} h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} R_k^+ u_n dx, \end{aligned}$$

which, together with (3.2.38), gives

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla(u_n^{s+1})|^N dx \leq \frac{(s+1)^N}{\alpha_0} \left(|\Omega_k^+| + \int_{\Omega} h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} R_k^+ u_n dx \right) \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (3.2.39)$$

From definition (3.2.31) with $\tilde{k} = k \geq R_1$ which implies $R_k^+ u_n = 0$ a.e. in $\Omega \setminus \Omega_{n,k}^+$, we have that estimate (3.2.32) and Cauchy–Schwarz inequality imply

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\Omega} h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} R_k^+ u_n dx \right| &\leq \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |h(u_n)| |R_k^+ u_n| e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} dx \\ &\leq \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} e^{(\alpha+\delta)|u_n|^\gamma} |R_k^+ u_n| dx \\ &\leq \left(\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |R_k^+ u_n|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \left(\int_{\Omega} e^{2(\alpha+\delta)|u_n|^\gamma} dx \right)^{1/2} \\ &\leq c_2 \left(\int_{\Omega} |R_k^+ u_n|^2 dx \right)^{1/2}, \end{aligned}$$

as $\left(\int_{\Omega} e^{2(\alpha+\delta)|u_n|^\gamma} dx \right)_n$ is bounded by the statement in Step 1 and Lemma 3.2 with $\beta = 2(\alpha + \delta)$. Thus, back to (3.2.39), we obtain

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla(u_n^{s+1})|^N dx \leq c_3 \left(|\Omega_k^+| + \left(\int_{\Omega} |R_k^+ u_n|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \right) \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (3.2.40)$$

Passing to the limit in (3.2.40), from (3.2.34) and (3.2.36) we have that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla(u^{s+1})|^N dx \leq c_3 \left(|\Omega_k^+| + \left(\int_{\Omega} |R_k^+ u_n|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \right), \quad (3.2.41)$$

where again from definition (3.2.31) with $\tilde{k} = k$ and direct computations it results

$$\left(\int_{\Omega} |R_k^+ u_n|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \leq \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} + k |\Omega_k^+|^{1/2}. \quad (3.2.42)$$

Therefore, as in Ω_k^+ it is $1 \leq k < u$, then $u^2 \leq u^{2N(s+1)}$ in Ω_k^+ and from (3.2.42) it follows that (3.2.41) turns into

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla(u^{s+1})|^N dx \leq c_3 \left(|\Omega_k^+| + k |\Omega_k^+|^{1/2} + \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} (u^{s+1})^{2N} dx \right)^{1/2} \right). \quad (3.2.43)$$

At last, if we set $v = |u|^s u$, with $v \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$, since (3.2.35) implies $\Omega_k^+ = \{x \in \Omega : v(x) > k^{s+1}\}$, then from (3.2.43) we obtain that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla v|^N dx \leq c_3 \left(|\Omega_k^+| + k |\Omega_k^+|^{1/2} + \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} v^{2N} dx \right)^{1/2} \right),$$

where, by direct computations, it is

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} v^{2N} dx \right)^{1/2} &\leq c_4 \left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} (v - k^{s+1})^{2N} dx + k^{2N(s+1)} |\Omega_k^+| \right)^{1/2} \\ &\leq c_4 \left(\left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} (v - k^{s+1})^{2N} dx \right)^{N/2N} + k^{(s+1)N} |\Omega_k^+|^{1/2} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, summing up, since $1 \leq k \leq k^{(s+1)N}$, we obtain

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla v|^N dx \leq c_5 \left(\left(\int_{\Omega_k^+} (v - k^{s+1})^{2N} \right)^{N/2N} + k^{(s+1)N} |\Omega_k^+| + k^{(s+1)N} |\Omega_k^+|^{1/2} \right),$$

and then Lemma 2.3 applies (with $p = N$) to function v but taking any $\tilde{k} \geq R_1^{s+1}$ and then in all the previous computations k such that $\tilde{k} = k^{s+1}$, and $r = 2N$, $m = 2$, $l_1 = l_2 = N$, $\varepsilon_1 = 1$ and $\varepsilon_2 = 1/2$.

Similar arguments allow us to exclude also (3.2.30) and then it has to be $u \in L^\infty(\Omega)$.

Step 3. The proof of this step is essentially as in Step 3 of [52, Proposition 4.6], but, for completeness and also for pointing out the different assumptions we need, here we give some details.

Firstly, consider $R_1 > 0$ so that (3.2.32) holds, and from assumption $(3\tilde{g}_1)$ a radius $R_2 > 0$ exists such that

$$G(t) \geq 0 \quad \text{if } |t| \geq R_2. \quad (3.2.44)$$

Then, fix any integer k such that $k \geq \max\{R_1, R_2, |u|_\infty\} + 1$ and define the ‘‘remainder’’ of the truncation function in (3.2.27) as

$$R_k t = t - T_k t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } |t| \leq k \\ t - k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k \end{cases}. \quad (3.2.45)$$

For the choice of k we have that it is

$$T_k u = u \quad \text{and} \quad R_k u = 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega,$$

then from (3.2.19), (3.2.21) and (3.2.22) it follows that $T_k u_n \rightharpoonup u$ weakly in $W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$,

$$R_k u_n \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{strongly in } L^2(\Omega), \quad (3.2.46)$$

$$|\Omega_{n,k}| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{with} \quad \Omega_{n,k} := \{x \in \Omega : |u_n(x)| > k\}. \quad (3.2.47)$$

Furthermore, by definition, it is $\|R_k u_n\|_X \leq \|u_n\|_X$, then (3.2.23) implies

$$\langle dE(u_n), R_k u_n \rangle \rightarrow 0$$

which gives

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_n = \langle dE(u_n), R_k u_n \rangle &= \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} (A_0(x) + A(x)|u_n|^{Ns}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \\ &+ s \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} A(x)|u_n|^{Ns} \left(1 - \frac{k}{|u_n|}\right) |\nabla u_n|^N dx - \int_{\Omega} h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} R_k u_n dx, \end{aligned}$$

where from the definition in (3.2.47) and assumption $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ it is

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}} A(x)|u_n|^{Ns} \left(1 - \frac{k}{|u_n|}\right) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \geq 0,$$

while from definition (3.2.45), estimate (3.2.32) and Cauchy–Schwarz inequality we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\Omega} h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} R_k u_n dx \right| &\leq \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |h(u_n)| e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} |R_k u_n| dx \leq \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} e^{(\delta+\alpha)|u_n|^\gamma} |R_k u_n| dx \\ &\leq \left(\int_{\Omega} e^{2(\delta+\alpha)|u_n|^\gamma} dx \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\int_{\Omega} |R_k u_n|^2 dx \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \\ &\leq c_6 \left(\int_{\Omega} |R_k u_n|^2 dx \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \end{aligned}$$

by the statement in Step 1 and Lemma 3.2 with $\beta = 2(\alpha + \delta)$. Thus, summing up, from (3.2.46) and $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ we have that

$$\varepsilon_n \geq \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} (A_0(x) + A(x)|u_n|^{N_s}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \geq \alpha_0 \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} (1 + |u_n|^{N_s}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \geq 0$$

which implies

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}} (A_0(x) + A(x)|u_n|^{N_s}) |\nabla u_n|^N dx \rightarrow 0, \quad (3.2.48)$$

and also

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |\nabla u_n|^N dx \rightarrow 0, \quad \text{i.e.,} \quad \|R_k u_n\|_N \rightarrow 0, \quad (3.2.49)$$

and

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |u_n|^{N_s} |\nabla u_n|^N dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (3.2.50)$$

Now, to prove (3.2.25), take $v \in X$ such that $\|v\|_X = 1$, whence, $|v|_\infty \leq 1$, $\|v\|_N \leq 1$. Direct computations and definition (3.2.27) allow us to prove that

$$\begin{aligned} \langle dE(T_k u_n), v \rangle &= \langle dE(u_n), v \rangle - \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} (A_0(x) + A(x)|u_n|^{N_s}) |\nabla u_n|^{N-2} \nabla u_n \cdot \nabla v dx \\ &\quad - s \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} A(x) |u_n|^{N_s-2} u_n v |\nabla u_n|^N dx + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} h(u_n) v e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} dx \\ &\quad - e^{\alpha k^\gamma} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} h(u_n) v dx, \end{aligned}$$

where from (3.2.23) we have that

$$|\langle dE(u_n), v \rangle| \leq \|dE(u_n)\|_{X'} = \varepsilon_n \quad \text{uniformly with respect to } v \in X \text{ s. t. } \|v\|_X = 1,$$

while, since $|v|_\infty \leq 1$, from (3.2.32), Cauchy–Schwarz inequality and, again, Lemma 3.2 we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} h(u_n) v e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} dx \right| &\leq \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |h(u_n)| e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} dx \leq \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} e^{(\delta+\alpha)|u_n|^\gamma} dx \\ &\leq |\Omega_{n,k}|^{1/2} \left(\int_{\Omega} e^{2(\delta+\alpha)|u_n|^\gamma} dx \right)^{1/2} \leq c_7 |\Omega_{n,k}|^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

and also from $(3\tilde{h}_2)$ it results

$$\left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} h(u_n) v \, dx \right| \leq c_8 |\Omega_{n,k}|.$$

Moreover, since for a.e. $x \in \Omega_{n,k}$ it is $1 \leq k \leq |u_n|$, being $|v|_\infty \leq 1$, from $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ it follows that

$$\left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} A(x) |u_n|^{Ns-2} u_n v |\nabla u_n|^N \, dx \right| \leq |A|_\infty \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |u_n|^{Ns} |\nabla u_n|^N \, dx,$$

while, being $\|v\|_N \leq 1$, from $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ and Hölder inequality we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} A_0(x) |\nabla u_n|^{N-2} \nabla u_n \cdot \nabla v \, dx \right| &\leq |A_0|_\infty \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |\nabla u_n|^{N-1} |\nabla v| \, dx \\ &\leq |A_0|_\infty \left(\int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |\nabla u_n|^N \, dx \right)^{\frac{N-1}{N}}; \end{aligned}$$

hence, summing up, from (3.2.47), (3.2.49) and (3.2.50) we obtain that

$$|\langle dE(T_k u_n), v \rangle| \leq \varepsilon_{k,n} + \left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} A(x) |u_n|^{Ns} |\nabla u_n|^{N-2} \nabla u_n \cdot \nabla v \, dx \right|$$

with $\varepsilon_{k,n} \rightarrow 0$ uniformly with respect to $v \in X$ such that $\|v\|_X = 1$.

At last, reasoning as in the proof of *Step 3* in [52, Proposition 4.6], by means of the test functions $\varphi_{k,n}^+ = v R_k^+ u_n$, with $R_k^+ t$ as in (3.2.31) with $\tilde{k} = k$, and $\varphi_{k,n}^- = v R_k^- u_n$, where we define

$$R_k^- t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \geq -k \\ t + k & \text{if } t < -k \end{cases},$$

and with careful estimates based on (3.2.32) and Lemma 3.2, we are able to prove also that

$$\left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} A(x) |u_n|^{Ns} |\nabla u_n|^{N-2} \nabla u_n \cdot \nabla v \, dx \right| \leq \varepsilon_{k,n},$$

with $\varepsilon_{k,n} \rightarrow 0$ uniformly with respect to $v \in X$ such that $\|v\|_X = 1$, which completes the proof of (3.2.25).

Now, to prove (3.2.26), from direct computations we have that

$$\begin{aligned} E(T_k u_n) &= E(u_n) - \frac{1}{N} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} (A_0(x) + A(x) |u_n|^{Ns}) |\nabla u_n|^N \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} G(u_n) \, dx - \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} G(T_k u_n) \, dx, \end{aligned}$$

where (3.2.48) implies

$$E(T_k u_n) = E(u_n) + \varepsilon_{k,n} + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} G(u_n) dx - \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} G(T_k u_n) dx. \quad (3.2.51)$$

We note that $|T_k u_n|_\infty \leq k$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and the continuity of $G(t)$ implies that

$$\left| \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} G(T_k u_n) dx \right| \leq c_9 |\Omega_{n,k}|,$$

while, being $k > R_2$, from (3.2.44) and assumption (3.2.8) it follows that

$$0 \leq G(u_n) \leq c_{10} (u_n h(u_n) e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} + \sigma_1 |u_n|^q + \sigma_2) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega_{n,k},$$

where, again, from (3.2.32), Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, Lemma 3.2, (3.2.22) and direct computations we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |u_n| |h(u_n)| e^{\alpha|u_n|^\gamma} dx &\leq \left(\int_{\Omega} e^{2(\delta+\alpha)|u_n|^\gamma} dx \right)^{1/2} \left(\int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |u_n|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \\ &\leq c_{11} |\Omega_{n,k}|^{1/2} \end{aligned}$$

and also

$$\int_{\Omega_{n,k}} |u_n|^q dx \leq c_{12} |\Omega_{n,k}|^{1/2}.$$

Thus, (3.2.26) follows by using all the previous estimates in (3.2.51) together with (3.2.23) and (3.2.47).

Step 4. It is enough arguing as in the proof of the corresponding step in [52, Proposition 4.6].

Step 5. The proof follows from the previous steps by applying Proposition 3.5 to the uniformly bounded sequence $(T_k u_n)_n$ as we obtain that

$$E(T_k u_n) \rightarrow E(u), \quad \|dE(T_k u_n) - dE(u)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0$$

and (3.2.25) and (3.2.26) hold. \square

3.2.3 A Mountain Pass solution

In this section we show that the functional E defined in (3.2.12) satisfies the Mountain Pass geometry which is required for applying the abstract Theorem 1.2.

Firstly, let us recall that $\lambda_1 > 0$, the first eigenvalue of $-\Delta_N$ in $W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$, is achieved by a unique (up to constants) function $\varphi_1 \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega)$ such that

$$\varphi_1 > 0, \quad \int_{\Omega} |\varphi_1|^N dx = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_{\Omega} |\nabla \varphi_1|^N dx = \lambda_1 \quad (3.2.52)$$

(see, e.g., [127]); furthermore, it is also $\varphi_1 \in L^\infty(\Omega)$, hence $\varphi_1 \in X$, and

$$\int_{\Omega} |u|^N dx \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_1} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^N dx \quad \text{for all } u \in W_0^{1,N}(\Omega). \quad (3.2.53)$$

Now, we define

$$\ell_s(u) := \left(\int_{\Omega} (1 + |u|^{Ns}) |\nabla u|^N dx \right)^{\frac{1}{N}} \quad \text{for all } u \in X. \quad (3.2.54)$$

Clearly, the map $\ell_s : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is continuous with $\ell_s(0) = 0$ and from (3.2.11) it is such that

$$\ell_s(u) \geq \|u\|_N, \quad \ell_s(u) \geq \frac{1}{s+1} \| |u|^s u \|_N \quad \text{for all } u \in X. \quad (3.2.55)$$

Proposition 3.7. *If the hypotheses of Theorem 3.4 hold, then a constant $r_0 > 0$ exists such that*

$$\inf_{\ell_s(u)=r_0} E(u) > 0.$$

Proof. From assumption (3.2.7) a radius $R_1 > 0$ exists such that (3.2.32) holds. Without loss of generality, we can suppose $R_1 \geq \max\{\nu, 1\}$ with ν so that condition $(3\tilde{g}_2)$ holds. Then, by applying the estimates (3.2.8) and (3.2.32) and choosing a power $\beta_1 \geq 0$ so that $q + \beta_1 \geq N + 1$, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} G(t) &\leq c_1 |t| |h(t)| e^{\alpha|t|^\gamma} + c_2 |t|^q + c_3 \\ &\leq c_1 |t|^{N+1} e^{(\delta+\alpha)|t|^\gamma} + c_2 |t|^{q+\beta_1} + c_3 |t|^{N+1} \quad \text{if } |t| \geq R_1, \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.56)$$

while the continuity of $G(t)$ and direct computations imply that

$$G(t) \leq \max_{|t| \leq R_1} |G(t)| \leq c_4 |t|^{N+1} \quad \text{if } \nu \leq |t| \leq R_1. \quad (3.2.57)$$

Hence, without loss of generality assuming $\frac{\lambda_1 \alpha_0}{N} - \sigma > 0$ in $(3\tilde{g}_2)$, summing up estimates (3.2.56), (3.2.57) and hypothesis $(3\tilde{g}_2)$ it follows that

$$G(t) \leq \left(\frac{\lambda_1 \alpha_0}{N} - \sigma \right) |t|^N + c_1 |t|^{N+1} e^{(\delta+\alpha)|t|^\gamma} + c_2 |t|^{q+\beta_1} + c_5 |t|^{N+1} \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}$$

which implies

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} G(u) dx &\leq \left(\frac{\lambda_1 \alpha_0}{N} - \sigma \right) \int_{\Omega} |u|^N dx + c_1 \int_{\Omega} |u|^{N+1} e^{(\delta+\alpha)|u|^\gamma} dx \\ &\quad + c_2 \int_{\Omega} |u|^{q+\beta_1} dx + c_5 \int_{\Omega} |u|^{N+1} dx \end{aligned} \quad (3.2.58)$$

for all $u \in X$.

We note that, for all $u \in X$ such that $\ell_s(u) \leq \frac{1}{s+1}$, from Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, (3.2.15) with $\beta = 2(\delta + \alpha)$, Sobolev Embedding Theorem and (3.2.55), we obtain

$$\int_{\Omega} |u|^{N+1} e^{(\delta+\alpha)|u|^\gamma} dx \leq \left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{2(N+1)} dx \right)^{1/2} \left(\int_{\Omega} e^{2(\delta+\alpha)|u|^\gamma} dx \right)^{1/2} \leq c_6 \|u\|_N^{N+1},$$

so, by using (3.2.53) and (3.2.55) in (3.2.58), from direct computations it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} G(u) dx \leq \left(\frac{\alpha_0}{N} - \frac{\sigma}{\lambda_1} \right) [\ell_s(u)]^N + c_7 [\ell_s(u)]^{N+1} + c_8 [\ell_s(u)]^{q+\beta_1}. \quad (3.2.59)$$

Thus, combining (3.2.59) with definitions (3.2.12) and (3.2.54) and hypothesis $(3\tilde{h}_1)$, and taking $\ell_s(u) = r_0$ with $r_0 \leq \frac{1}{s+1}$, we have that

$$E(u) \geq \frac{\sigma}{\lambda_1} r_0^N - c_7 r_0^{N+1} - c_8 r_0^{q+\beta_1}$$

and, as $q + \beta_1 > N$, the desired result follows from taking $r_0 > 0$ sufficiently small. \square

Proposition 3.8. *If $\varphi_1 \in X$ is as in (3.2.52), then we have that*

$$E(t\varphi_1) \rightarrow -\infty \quad \text{as } t \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Proof. From (3.2.12), hypotheses $(3\tilde{h}_1)$ and $(3\tilde{g}_1)$, the properties of φ_1 in (3.2.52) and also (3.2.11), for all $t > 0$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} E(t\varphi_1) &= \frac{1}{N} \int_{\Omega} (A_0(x) + A(x)|t\varphi_1|^{Ns}) |\nabla t\varphi_1|^N dx - \int_{\Omega} G(t\varphi_1) dx \\ &\leq c_1 t^N \lambda_1 + c_2 t^{N(s+1)} \| |\varphi_1|^s \varphi_1 \|_N^N - \sigma_3 t^\tau \int_{\Omega} \varphi_1^\tau dx + c_3. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, since by assumption $\tau > N(s+1)$, as $t \rightarrow +\infty$ we obtain the desired result. \square

Proof of the Theorem 3.4. By considering the function $\ell_s(u)$ as in (3.2.54), from Propositions 3.6, 3.7 and 3.8 we have that Theorem 1.2 applies to functional E in (3.2.12) and a mountain pass nontrivial critical point of E on X exists. \square

Quasilinear modified Schrödinger equations in \mathbb{R}^N

In this chapter we investigate the existence of weak bounded solutions for the quasilinear elliptic problem

$$-\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}A_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p + V(x)|u|^{p-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.0.1)$$

with $N \geq 2$, $p > 1$, where $A : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function with partial derivative $A_t(x, t) = \frac{\partial A}{\partial t}(x, t)$, potential $V : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a suitable measurable function and $g : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a given Carathéodory function.

Our study is motivated by the fact that many examples of problem (4.0.1) are related to the existence of solitary waves for the quasilinear Schrödinger equation

$$iz_t = -\Delta z + V(x)z - h(|z|^2)z - \Delta(l(|z|^2))l'(|z|^2)z \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.0.2)$$

where $V : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a given potential, $l, h : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are real functions and the solution $z = z(x, t)$ is a complex function in $\mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R}$. In fact, by using the ansatz $z(x, t) = e^{-iEt}u(x)$ in (4.0.2) with $E \in \mathbb{R}$, the unknown strictly positive real function $u(x)$ is a solution of the corresponding elliptic problem

$$-\Delta u - \Delta(l(u^2))l'(u^2)u + V(x)u = Eu + h(u^2)u \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N,$$

often referred as modified Schrödinger equation, which matches with (4.0.1), but taking $p = 2$, for suitable choices of function $l(s)$. And, again, the structure of the real term $l(s)$ allows one to use quasilinear equation (4.0.2) for describing several physical phenomena such as the self-channeling of a high-power ultrashort laser, or also some problems which arise in plasma physics, fluid mechanics, mechanics and in the condensed matter theory (see [185] and references therein or also [CS4] for some model problems).

On the other hand, if $A(x, t)$ is a constant, equation (4.0.1) turns into the p -Laplacian equation

$$-\Delta_p u + V(x)|u|^{p-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \quad (4.0.3)$$

which has been widely investigated starting from the pioneer papers [32, 159]. Indeed, it is well known that (4.0.3) has a variational structure but there is a lack of compactness as such a problem is settled in the whole space \mathbb{R}^N and classical variational tools cannot work easily; thus, suitable assumptions on potential $V(x)$ are required (see, e.g., [130] and references therein).

Here two main difficulties arise: the presence of a coefficient which depends on the solution itself and the lack of compactness.

In the first section of this chapter we address the study of equation (4.0.1) showing the existence of a weak bounded solution under suitable assumptions on the coefficient $A(x, u)$ and the potential $V(x)$.

Moreover, in the second one we discuss the strict relation between equation (4.0.2) and the intensively investigated stationary Schrödinger equation

$$-\Delta u - \Delta(l(u^2))l'(u^2)u + V(x)u = f(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3$$

where $f : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $l : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are real maps. In particular, we will emphasize how the variational approach we employ to study problem (4.0.1) leads to such a good result so that the outcomes obtained in correspondence of particular forms of $l(u)$ can be easily deduced from our general result. For example, if $l(s) = \sqrt{1+s}$, the previous equation describes the self-channeling of a high-power ultrashort laser in matter (see e.g. [122]) and, if $l(s) = s$, it reduces to the superfluid film equation in Plasma Physics (see e.g. [120]).

Finally, the last section deals with the existence of multiple solutions for (p, q) -Laplacian equation

$$\begin{aligned} & -\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}A_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p - \operatorname{div}(B(x, u)|\nabla u|^{q-2}\nabla u) \\ & + \frac{1}{q}B_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^q + V(x)|u|^{p-2}u + W(x)|u|^{q-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \end{aligned}$$

where $1 < q \leq p \leq N$, $A, B : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory functions with $A_t(x, u) = \frac{\partial A}{\partial t}(x, u)$, $B_t(x, u) = \frac{\partial B}{\partial t}(x, u)$, $V, W : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are suitable potentials in a sense discussed later and $g : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Carathéodory function. As if $p = q$ it turns into the simplest one

$$-\operatorname{div}(C(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}C_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p + Z(x)|u|^{p-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N,$$

where we set $C(x, u) = A(x, u) + B(x, u)$ and $Z(x) = V(x) + W(x)$, we can deduce a multiplicity result for equation (4.0.1), too.

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS3, CS4, CS10].

4.1 Schrödinger-type equations in \mathbb{R}^N

In this Section we deal with the Schrödinger-type equation (4.0.1) involving a coefficient which depends on the solution itself. Following the ideas introduced in Chapters 1, 2, 3 under some quite natural conditions, we are able to prove that such a problem has a “good” variational structure and its solutions are critical points of a functional $\mathcal{J} \in C^1$ in a suitable Banach space $X \subset L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$ equipped with an intersection norm $\|\cdot\|_X$ (see Proposition 4.1).

Also, as mentioned before, another main issue related to problem (4.0.1) is a lack of compactness as such a problem is settled in the whole space \mathbb{R}^N ; Thus, suitable assumptions on potential $V(x)$ are required (see, e.g., [130] and references therein).

Here, we assume that the potential $V : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Lebesgue measurable function such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} V(x) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{|x| \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_1(x)} \frac{1}{V(y)} dy = 0, \quad (4.1.1)$$

where $B_1(x)$ denotes the unitary sphere of \mathbb{R}^N centered in x .

Such assumptions (4.1.1) have already been used in [28, 29] for investigating the quasilinear equation (4.0.3) as they ensure a compactness embedding in suitable weighted Lebesgue spaces on \mathbb{R}^N (see [34, Theorem 3.1]). A similar compact embedding has been stated in [31, 32] under suitable conditions on the level sets of V (for a comparison with assumption (4.1.1), see [165]).

Anyway, in the more general setting of problem (4.0.1) this is not enough and also an approximation argument is considered. More precisely, for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we introduce the approximating quasilinear problem

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}A_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p = g(x, u) - V(x)|u|^{p-2}u & \text{in } B_k, \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial B_k, \end{cases} \quad (4.1.2)$$

with $B_k = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : |x| < k\}$, and the related functional \mathcal{J}_{B_k} on the “right” Banach space X_{B_k} (see definition (4.1.40), respectively (4.1.37)). Then, if “good” assumptions are satisfied (see Section 4.1.1) for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ a weak bounded solution u_k of problem (4.1.2) exists and a nontrivial solution for equation (4.0.1) is constructed as a suitable limit of sequence $(u_k)_k$.

Thus, the first step is solving the given equation in bounded domains by following the ideas developed in [51, 52], then we pass to the limit in a “weak sense” so to find a weak bounded solution of (4.0.1) which has to be nontrivial.

We note that, since our variational principle requires that X is contained in $L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$ (see definition (4.1.11)), in some sense the “transition” through bounded domain is mandatory as every “limit point” has to be a bounded function and the technical lemma, which allows it, holds only on bounded domains (see Lemma 4.5).

4.1.1 Variational principle and first properties

From now on, let $V : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable function such that

$$(V_1) \quad \operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} V(x) > 0,$$

which satisfies also

$$(V_2) \quad \lim_{|x| \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_1(x)} \frac{1}{V(y)} dy = 0.$$

Remark 4.1. If potential $V(x)$ satisfies assumption (V_1) , then the following continuous embeddings hold:

$$L_V^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq r < +\infty, \quad (4.1.3)$$

$$W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow W^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq p < +\infty. \quad (4.1.4)$$

From Remark 4.1 and Sobolev Embedding Theorems, we deduce the following result (for the compact embeddings, see [34, Theorem 3.1]).

Theorem 4.1. *Let $V : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a Lebesgue measurable function satisfying assumption (V_1) . Then, the following continuous embeddings hold:*

- if $p < N$ then

$$W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } p \leq r \leq \frac{Np}{N-p}; \quad (4.1.5)$$

- if $p = N$ then

$$W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } p \leq r < +\infty; \quad (4.1.6)$$

- if $p > N$ then

$$W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } p \leq r \leq +\infty. \quad (4.1.7)$$

Furthermore, if assumption (V_2) also occurs, the compact embedding

$$W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } p \leq r < p^* \quad (4.1.8)$$

holds, with

$$p^* = \begin{cases} \frac{Np}{N-p} & \text{if } p < N, \\ +\infty & \text{if } p \geq N. \end{cases}$$

From Theorem 4.1 it follows that, for any $r \geq p$ so that (4.1.5), respectively (4.1.6) or (4.1.7), holds then a constant $\tau_r > 0$ exists such that

$$|u|_r \leq \tau_r \|u\|_V \quad \text{for all } u \in W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N). \quad (4.1.9)$$

On the other hand, taking Ω open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N and $p < N$, a classical embedding theorem implies that a constant $\sigma_* > 0$, independent of Ω and depending only on p and N , exists such that

$$|u|_{\Omega, p^*} \leq \sigma_* \|u\|_{\Omega} \quad \text{for all } u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega). \quad (4.1.10)$$

From now on, we assume that potential $V(x)$ is a measurable function which satisfies condition (V_1) and we set

$$X := W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{and} \quad \|u\|_X = \|u\|_V + |u|_\infty \quad \text{for any } u \in X. \quad (4.1.11)$$

In the following, we assume $p \leq N$ (otherwise, embedding (4.1.7) implies that $X = W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ and all the arguments and proofs can be simplified).

Lemma 4.1. *Taking $p \leq r < +\infty$, we have that*

$$X \hookrightarrow L_V^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{with} \quad |u|_{V,r} \leq \|u\|_X \quad \text{for all } u \in X. \quad (4.1.12)$$

Proof. Taking any $u \in X$, definitions (0.0.5) and (4.1.11) imply that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u|^r dx \leq |u|_\infty^{r-p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u|^p dx \leq |u|_\infty^{r-p} \|u\|_V^p \leq \|u\|_X^r$$

which gives the proof. \square

Remark 4.2. From (4.1.3), definition (4.1.11) and Lemma 4.1 it follows that

$$X \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } p \leq r \leq +\infty.$$

Lemma 4.2. *If $(u_n)_n \subset X$, $u \in X$ and $M > 0$ are such that*

$$\|u_n - u\|_V \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty \quad (4.1.13)$$

and

$$|u_n|_\infty \leq M \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (4.1.14)$$

then $u_n \rightarrow u$ strongly in $L_V^r(\mathbb{R}^N)$ for any $p \leq r < +\infty$.

Proof. From (4.1.14) we have that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_n - u|^r dx \leq |u_n - u|_\infty^{r-p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_n - u|^p dx \leq (M + |u|_\infty)^{r-p} \|u_n - u\|_V^p,$$

which, together with (V_1) , (0.0.4) and (4.1.13), implies the desired result. \square

Let $A : (x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto A(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}$ be a given function such that the following conditions hold:

(4h₀) $A(x, t)$ is a \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function with $A_t(x, t) = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} A(x, t)$;

(4h₁) for any $\rho > 0$ we have that

$$\sup_{|t| \leq \rho} |A(\cdot, t)| \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N), \quad \sup_{|t| \leq \rho} |A_t(\cdot, t)| \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N).$$

Furthermore, we assume that $g : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exists such that:

(4g₀) $g(x, t)$ is a \mathcal{C}^0 -Carathéodory function;

(4g₁) $a_1, a_2 > 0$ and $q \geq p$ exist such that

$$|g(x, t)| \leq a_1 |t|^{p-1} + a_2 |t|^{q-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Remark 4.3. Assumptions (4g₀) and (4g₁) imply that

$$G : (x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto \int_0^t g(x, s) ds \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4.1.15)$$

is a well defined \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function and

$$|G(x, t)| \leq \frac{a_1}{p} |t|^p + \frac{a_2}{q} |t|^q \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.1.16)$$

In particular, (g₁) and (4.1.15) imply that

$$G(x, 0) = g(x, 0) = 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.17)$$

Taking any $u \in X$, from assumption (4h₁) and definition (4.1.11) it follows that $A(\cdot, u)|\nabla u(\cdot)|^p \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$, while hypotheses (4g₀), (4g₁) and Remark 4.2 provide that $G(\cdot, u) \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$. Then, assumption (V₁) implies that functional

$$\mathcal{J}(u) = \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u)|\nabla u|^p dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u|^p dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, u) dx \quad (4.1.18)$$

is well defined for all $u \in X$. Moreover, taking any $u, v \in X$, the same assumptions imply that $A_t(\cdot, u)v|\nabla u(\cdot)|^p \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$ and $g(\cdot, u)v \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$, then the Gâteaux differential of functional \mathcal{J} in u along the direction v is well defined and is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d\mathcal{J}(u), v \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A_t(x, u)v|\nabla u|^p dx \\ &+ \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u|^{p-2} uv dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u)v dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.19)$$

By reasoning as in [58, Lemma 3.4], from Lemma 2.1 we deduce the following result.

Lemma 4.3. *Taking $p > 1$, a constant $C_1 = C_1(p) > 0$ exists such that for any open domain $\Omega \subset \mathbb{R}^N$ it results*

$$\int_{\Omega} \left| |\nabla w|^p - |\nabla z|^p \right| dx \leq C_1 \|w - z\|_{\Omega} \left(\|w\|_{\Omega}^{p-1} + \|z\|_{\Omega}^{p-1} \right) \quad \forall w, z \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Now, we are ready to state a suitable variational principle.

Proposition 4.1. *Let $p > 1$ and suppose that hypotheses (V_1) , $(4h_0)$ – $(4h_1)$ and $(4g_0)$ – $(4g_1)$ hold. If $(u_n)_n \subset X$ and $u \in X$ are such that*

$$u_n \rightarrow u \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \tag{4.1.20}$$

and (4.1.13), (4.1.14) hold for a constant $M > 0$, then

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(u) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n) - d\mathcal{J}(u)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence, \mathcal{J} is a \mathcal{C}^1 functional in X with Fréchet differential defined as in (4.1.19).

Proof. For the sake of convenience, we set $\mathcal{J} = \mathcal{J}_1 + \mathcal{J}_2 - \mathcal{J}_3$, where

$$\mathcal{J}_1 : u \in X \mapsto \mathcal{J}_1(u) = \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u) |\nabla u|^p dx \in \mathbb{R},$$

$$\mathcal{J}_2 : u \in X \mapsto \mathcal{J}_2(u) = \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u|^p dx \in \mathbb{R},$$

$$\mathcal{J}_3 : u \in X \mapsto \mathcal{J}_3(u) = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, u) dx \in \mathbb{R},$$

with related Gâteaux differentials

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}_1(u), v \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A_t(x, u) v |\nabla u|^p dx,$$

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}_2(u), v \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u|^{p-2} uv dx,$$

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}_3(u), v \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u) v dx,$$

for any $u, v \in X$.

Now, let $(u_n)_n \subset X$, $u \in X$ and $M > 0$ be such that (4.1.13), (4.1.14) and (4.1.20) hold. Firstly, we note that (4.1.4) and (4.1.13) imply $\|u_n - u\| \rightarrow 0$, then from the proof of [58, Proposition 3.6] it follows that

$$\mathcal{J}_1(u_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}_1(u) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}_1(u_n) - d\mathcal{J}_1(u)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0,$$

$$\mathcal{J}_3(u_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}_3(u) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}_3(u_n) - d\mathcal{J}_3(u)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0.$$

Moreover, from definitions (0.0.4) and (0.0.5), limit (4.1.13) implies also that

$$|\mathcal{J}_2(u_n) - \mathcal{J}_2(u)| = \frac{1}{p} \left| \|u_n\|_{V,p}^p - \|u\|_{V,p}^p \right| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

At last, taking $v \in X$ such that $\|v\|_X = 1$, so

$$|v|_\infty \leq 1, \quad |v|_{V,p} \leq 1, \quad (4.1.21)$$

from (V_1) and by definition we have that

$$|\langle d\mathcal{J}_2(u_n) - d\mathcal{J}_2(u), v \rangle| \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) | |u_n|^{p-2}u_n - |u|^{p-2}u | |v| dx. \quad (4.1.22)$$

Thus, if $1 < p \leq 2$, from (2.1.39), Hölder inequality with $V(x) = V^{\frac{1}{p}}(x)V^{\frac{p-1}{p}}(x)$ and (4.1.21) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) | |u_n|^{p-2}u_n - |u|^{p-2}u | |v| dx &\leq C_0 \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_n - u|^{p-1} |v| dx \\ &\leq C_0 |u_n - u|_{V,p}^{p-1} |v|_{V,p} \leq C_0 |u_n - u|_{V,p}^{p-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.23)$$

On the other hand, if $p > 2$, again from Hölder inequality with $V(x) = V^{\frac{1}{p}}(x)V^{\frac{p-1}{p}}(x)$, and (2.1.38), (4.1.21) and direct computations we have that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) | |u_n|^{p-2}u_n - |u|^{p-2}u | |v| dx \\ &\leq \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) | |u_n|^{p-2}u_n - |u|^{p-2}u |^{\frac{p}{p-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} |v|_{V,p} \\ &\leq C_0 \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_n - u|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} (|u_n| + |u|)^{\frac{p(p-2)}{p-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.24)$$

where once again from Hölder inequality but with $V(x) = V^{\frac{1}{p-1}}(x)V^{\frac{p-2}{p-1}}(x)$ it results

$$\begin{aligned} &\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_n - u|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} (|u_n| + |u|)^{\frac{p(p-2)}{p-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \\ &\leq |u_n - u|_{V,p} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) (|u_n| + |u|)^p dx \right)^{\frac{p-2}{p}}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, from (4.1.24), direct computations imply that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) | |u_n|^{p-2}u_n - |u|^{p-2}u | |v| dx \leq C_0^* |u_n - u|_{V,p} (|u_n|_{V,p}^{p-2} + |u|_{V,p}^{p-2}) \quad (4.1.25)$$

for a suitable constant $C_0^* > 0$.

Thus, summing up, from (4.1.22) and (4.1.23), respectively (4.1.25), it follows that

$$|\langle d\mathcal{J}_2(u_n) - d\mathcal{J}_2(u), v \rangle| \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{uniformly with respect to } v \in X, \|v\|_X = 1,$$

and the desired result holds. \square

From now on, besides hypotheses (V_1) , $(4h_0)$ – $(4h_1)$, $(4g_0)$ – $(4g_1)$, which imply that \mathcal{J} as in (4.1.18) is a C^1 functional on X as in (4.1.11) (see Proposition 4.1), we consider also assumption (V_2) and the following conditions on functions $A(x, t)$, $g(x, t)$ and $V(x)$:

(4h₂) a constant $\alpha_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$A(x, t) \geq \alpha_0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R};$$

(4h₃) some constants $\mu > p$ and $\alpha_1 > 0$ exist so that

$$(\mu - p)A(x, t) - A_t(x, t)t \geq \alpha_1 A(x, t) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R};$$

(4h₄) a constant $\alpha_2 > 0$ exists such that

$$pA(x, t) + A_t(x, t)t \geq \alpha_2 A(x, t) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R};$$

(4g₂) we have that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{g(x, t)}{|t|^{p-2}t} = \bar{\alpha} < \frac{\alpha_0}{\tau_p^p} \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N,$$

where α_0 is as in assumption (4h₂) and τ_p is as in (4.1.9) with $r = p$;

(4g₃) having μ as in hypothesis (4h₃), then

$$0 < \mu G(x, t) \leq g(x, t)t \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\};$$

(V₃) for any $\varrho > 0$, a constant $C_\varrho > 0$ exists such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{|x| \leq \varrho} V(x) \leq C_\varrho.$$

Remark 4.4. If (4h₂) holds, then, without loss of generality, we can assume $\alpha_0 \leq 1$. Moreover, taking $t = 0$ in (4h₃), we have also $\mu - p \geq \alpha_1$.

Remark 4.5. By means of (4.1.15), assumptions (4g₀) and (4g₂) imply that the existence of

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{G(x, t)}{|t|^p} = \frac{\bar{\alpha}}{p} \quad \text{uniformly a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N$$

is provided, too. In particular, from hypotheses (4g₁)-(4g₂) and direct computations it follows that for any $\varepsilon > 0$ a constant $c_\varepsilon > 0$ exists so that not only

$$|g(x, t)| \leq (\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon)|t|^{p-1} + c_\varepsilon|t|^{q-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R},$$

but also

$$|G(x, t)| \leq \frac{\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon}{p}|t|^p + \frac{c_\varepsilon}{q}|t|^q \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (4.1.26)$$

if assumption (4g₀) holds, too.

Remark 4.6. We note that (4.1.15), assumptions $(4g_0)$ – $(4g_1)$, $(4g_3)$ and straightforward computations imply that for any $\varepsilon > 0$ a function $\eta_\varepsilon \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$ exists so that $\eta_\varepsilon > 0$ for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and

$$G(x, t) \geq \eta_\varepsilon(x)|t|^\mu \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N \text{ if } |t| \geq \varepsilon. \quad (4.1.27)$$

Hence, from (4.1.16) and (4.1.27) it follows that

$$p < \mu \leq q. \quad (4.1.28)$$

Now, we are ready to state our main result.

Theorem 4.2. *Under assumptions (V_1) – (V_3) , $(4h_0)$ – $(4h_4)$ and $(4g_0)$ – $(4g_3)$, with the growth exponent q in $(4g_1)$ such that*

$$q < p^*, \quad (4.1.29)$$

then problem (4.0.1) admits at least one weak nontrivial bounded solution.

Remark 4.7. In our set of hypotheses, summing up (4.1.28) and (4.1.29) we have that

$$1 < p < \mu \leq q < p^*,$$

with μ as in $(4h_3)$ and $(4g_3)$.

As useful in the following, firstly we give a convergence result.

Proposition 4.2. *Suppose that hypotheses (V_1) – (V_2) , $(4h_0)$ – $(4h_3)$, $(4g_0)$ – $(4g_1)$ and $(4g_3)$ hold. Thus, taking any $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$, we have that any $(CPS)_\beta$ -sequence $(u_n)_n \subset X$ is bounded in $W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$. Furthermore, $u \in W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ exists such that, up to subsequences, as $n \rightarrow +\infty$ the following limits hold:*

$$u_n \rightharpoonup u \text{ weakly in } W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N), \quad (4.1.30)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ strongly in } L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \text{ for each } r \in [p, p^*[, \quad (4.1.31)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.32)$$

Proof. Taking $\beta \in \mathbb{R}$, let $(u_n)_n \subset X$ be a $(CPS)_\beta$ -sequence of \mathcal{J} , i.e.,

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n) \rightarrow \beta \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n)\|_{X'}(1 + \|u_n\|_X) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (4.1.33)$$

Thus, from (4.1.18), (4.1.19), (4.1.33), assumptions $(4h_2)$ – $(4h_3)$, $(4g_3)$ and also (0.0.5), direct computations give

$$\begin{aligned} \mu\beta + \varepsilon_n &= \mu\mathcal{J}(u_n) - \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_n), u_n \rangle \\ &\geq \frac{\alpha_0\alpha_1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_n|^p dx + \frac{\mu-p}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u_n|^p dx \geq c_1 \|u_n\|_V^p, \end{aligned}$$

for a suitable constant $c_1 > 0$. So, $(u_n)_n$ is bounded in $W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ and (4.1.30)–(4.1.32) follows from (4.1.8). \square

Now, we prove that the geometrical assumptions needed to apply Theorem 1.2 hold. To this aim, we start giving the following lemma.

Lemma 4.4. *Under assumptions $(4h_0)$ and $(4h_2)$ – $(4h_3)$, we have that*

$$A(x, st) \leq s^{\mu-p-\alpha_1} A(x, t) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R} \text{ and } s \geq 1. \quad (4.1.34)$$

Proof. Taking $t \in \mathbb{R}$, for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and for all $s > 0$, assumptions $(4h_0)$ and $(4h_3)$ imply that

$$\frac{d}{ds} A(x, st) = A_t(x, st)t \leq \frac{\mu - p - \alpha_1}{s} A(x, st).$$

Hence, from hypothesis $(4h_2)$ we obtain that

$$\frac{\frac{d}{ds} A(x, st)}{A(x, st)} \leq \frac{\mu - p - \alpha_1}{s},$$

where Remark 4.4 ensures that $\mu - p - \alpha_1 \geq 0$. Thus, if $s \geq 1$ by integrating we obtain the desired result. \square

Proposition 4.3. *Under assumptions (V_1) , $(4h_0)$ – $(4h_2)$, $(4g_0)$ – $(4g_2)$, if $p < q < p^*$ then two positive constants $\varrho, \alpha^* > 0$ exist so that*

$$u \in X, \|u\|_V = \varrho \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(u) \geq \alpha^*. \quad (4.1.35)$$

Proof. Let $u \in X$ and, from $(4g_2)$, take $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon < \frac{\alpha_0}{\tau_p}$, i.e.,

$$\alpha_0 - (\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon)\tau_p^p > 0. \quad (4.1.36)$$

Then, from $(4h_2)$ with $\alpha_0 \leq 1$ (see Remark 4.4), (4.1.26) and (4.1.9), definitions (0.0.5) and (4.1.18) imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u) &\geq \frac{\alpha_0}{p} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u|^p dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u|^p dx \right) - \frac{\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u|^p dx - \frac{c_\varepsilon}{\mu} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u|^q dx \\ &\geq \frac{1}{p} \left(\alpha_0 - (\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon)\tau_p^p \right) \|u\|_V^p - \frac{c_\varepsilon}{\mu} \tau_q^q \|u\|_V^q. \end{aligned}$$

Then, (4.1.36) and $p < q$ allow us to find two positive constants ϱ and α^* so that (4.1.35) holds. \square

Proposition 4.4. *Assume that (V_1) , $(4h_0)$, $(4h_2)$ – $(4h_3)$, $(4g_0)$ – $(4g_1)$ and $(4g_3)$ hold. Then, fixing $\bar{u} \in X \setminus \{0\}$, it follows that*

$$\mathcal{J}(s\bar{u}) \rightarrow -\infty \quad \text{as } s \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Proof. Since $\bar{u} \neq 0$, there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that

$$|\Omega_\varepsilon^{\bar{u}}| > 0 \quad \text{with} \quad \Omega_\varepsilon^{\bar{u}} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : |\bar{u}(x)| > \varepsilon\}.$$

From (4.1.18), (4.1.34), inequality (4.1.27) and direct computations, for any $s \geq 1$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(s\bar{u}) &= \frac{s^p}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, s\bar{u}) |\nabla \bar{u}|^p dx + \frac{s^p}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |\bar{u}|^p dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, s\bar{u}) dx \\ &\leq \frac{s^{\mu-\alpha_1}}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, \bar{u}) |\nabla \bar{u}|^p dx + \frac{s^p}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |\bar{u}|^p dx - s^\mu \int_{\Omega_{\frac{\bar{u}}{s}}} \eta_1(x) |\bar{u}|^\mu dx. \end{aligned}$$

Thus, being $\int_{\Omega_{\frac{\bar{u}}{s}}} \eta_1(x) |\bar{u}|^\mu dx > 0$, inequality (4.1.28), together with assumption $\alpha_1 > 0$, gives the desired result. \square

4.1.2 An existence result on bounded domains

From now on, let Ω denote an open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N . Thus, we define

$$X_\Omega = W_{0,V}^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \quad (4.1.37)$$

endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_{X_\Omega} = \|u\|_{\Omega,V} + |u|_{\Omega,\infty} \quad \text{for any } u \in X_\Omega \quad (4.1.38)$$

and with dual space X'_Ω .

Actually, since any function $u \in X_\Omega$ can be trivially extended to a function $\tilde{u} \in X$ just assuming $\tilde{u}(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega$, then

$$\|\tilde{u}\| = \|u\|_\Omega, \quad \|\tilde{u}\|_V = \|u\|_{\Omega,V}, \quad |\tilde{u}|_\infty = |u|_{\Omega,\infty}, \quad \|\tilde{u}\|_X = \|u\|_{X_\Omega}. \quad (4.1.39)$$

Remark 4.8. As Ω is a bounded domain, not only $\|u\|_\Omega$ and $|\nabla u|_{\Omega,p}$ are equivalent norms but also, if assumption (V_3) holds, a constant $c_\Omega \geq 1$ exists such that

$$\|u\|_{\Omega,V}^p = \int_\Omega |\nabla u|^p dx + \int_\Omega V(x) |u|^p dx \leq \int_\Omega |\nabla u|^p dx + c_\Omega \int_\Omega |u|^p dx \leq c_\Omega \|u\|_\Omega^p,$$

which, together with (4.1.4) and (4.1.39), implies that the norms $\|\cdot\|_{\Omega,V}$ and $\|\cdot\|_\Omega$ are equivalent, too.

From (4.1.17) and (4.1.18) it follows that the restriction of the functional \mathcal{J} to X_Ω , namely

$$\mathcal{J}_\Omega = \mathcal{J}|_{X_\Omega},$$

is such that

$$\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u) = \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^p dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega V(x) |u|^p dx - \int_\Omega G(x, u) dx, \quad u \in X_\Omega. \quad (4.1.40)$$

We note that, setting

$$\tilde{g}(x, t) = g(x, t) - V(x) |t|^{p-2} t \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \text{all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (4.1.41)$$

from (4g₀) we have that \tilde{g} is a C^0 -Caratheodory function such that

$$\tilde{G}(x, t) = \int_0^t \tilde{g}(x, s) ds = G(x, t) - \frac{1}{p} V(x) |t|^p \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \text{all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.1.42)$$

Then, by means of assumptions (4g₁), (V₁) and (V₃), we have that

$$|\tilde{g}(x, t)| \leq (a_1 + |V|_{\Omega, \infty}) |t|^{p-1} + a_2 |t|^{q-1} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \text{all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (4.1.43)$$

and from (4.1.40) and (4.1.42) we have that

$$\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u) = \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^p dx - \int_\Omega \tilde{G}(x, u) dx, \quad u \in X_\Omega. \quad (4.1.44)$$

Hence, arguing as in [52, Proposition 3.1], it follows that $\mathcal{J}_\Omega : X_\Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a C^1 functional such that, for any $u, v \in X_\Omega$, its Fréchet differential in u along the direction v is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u), v \rangle &= \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega A_t(x, u) v |\nabla u|^p dx \\ &\quad + \int_\Omega V(x) |u|^{p-2} u v dx - \int_\Omega g(x, u) v dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.45)$$

To apply Theorem 1.2 to functional \mathcal{J}_Ω as in (4.1.40), we start proving that it satisfies the (*wCPS*) condition in \mathbb{R} (see Definition 1.2).

Proposition 4.5. *Suppose that hypotheses (V₁), (V₃), (4h₀)–(4h₄), (4g₀)–(4g₁) and (4g₃) hold. Then, if also (4.1.29) is verified, functional \mathcal{J}_Ω satisfies the (*wCPS*) condition in \mathbb{R} .*

Proof. Firstly, we note that from Remark 4.8 the norm in (4.1.38) can be replaced with the equivalent one, still denoted by $\|\cdot\|_{X_\Omega}$, given by

$$\|u\|_{X_\Omega} = |\nabla u|_{\Omega, p} + |u|_{\Omega, \infty} \quad \text{for any } u \in X_\Omega.$$

Then, being $\mu > p$, from (4g₃), (4.1.41)–(4.1.42) and direct computations we obtain that

$$\mu \tilde{G}(x, t) \leq \tilde{g}(x, t) t \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \text{all } t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Thus, from conditions (4h₀)–(4h₄) and (4.1.43), together with (4.1.29), we have that [52, Proposition 4.6] applies to functional \mathcal{J}_Ω written as in (4.1.44). \square

Remark 4.9. To apply [52, Proposition 4.6] to functional \mathcal{J}_Ω in X_Ω condition $\tilde{G}(x, t) > 0$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ if $|t| \geq R$, for a suitable $R > 0$, is not necessary (such an assumption is required in [52] for proving one of the geometric conditions of the Mountain Pass Theorem).

For simplicity, let us assume that $0 \in \Omega$ so $\varepsilon^* > 0$ exists such that $B_{\varepsilon^*} \subset \Omega$.

Remark 4.10. Assume that the hypotheses of Propositions 4.3 and 4.4 are satisfied and fix $\bar{u} \in X \setminus \{0\}$ with $\text{supp } \bar{u} \subset B_{\varepsilon^*}$. Then, $\bar{u} \in X_\Omega$ and, from Proposition 4.4, $\bar{s} > 0$ exists so that

$$\|u^*\|_{\Omega, V} > \varrho \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u^*) < \alpha^* \quad (4.1.46)$$

with $u^* = \bar{s}\bar{u}$ and ϱ, α^* as in Proposition 4.3.

Clearly, we have that $\text{supp } u^* \subset B_{\varepsilon^*}$, so $u^* \in X_\Omega$, and if we consider the segment joining 0 to u^* , namely

$$\gamma^* : s \in [0, 1] \mapsto su^* \in X, \quad (4.1.47)$$

we obtain that not only $\gamma^*([0, 1]) \subset X_\Omega$ but also $\text{supp } \gamma^*(s) \subset B_{\varepsilon^*}$ for all $s \in [0, 1]$.

Proposition 4.6. *Under the assumptions in Theorem 4.2, functional \mathcal{J}_Ω has at least a critical point $u_\Omega \in X_\Omega$ such that*

$$\alpha^* \leq \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_\Omega) \leq \sup_{s \in [0, 1]} \mathcal{J}(su^*), \quad (4.1.48)$$

with α^* as in Proposition 4.3 and u^* as in Remark 4.10.

Proof. From (4.1.17) we have that $\mathcal{J}_\Omega(0) = 0$. Moreover, from (4.1.39), (4.1.40) and Proposition 4.3 we have that

$$u \in X_\Omega, \quad \|u\|_{\Omega, V} = \varrho \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u) \geq \alpha^*.$$

Then, taking $u^* \in X_\Omega$ as in Remark 4.10, from (4.1.46) and Proposition 4.5 we have that Theorem 1.2 applies to \mathcal{J}_Ω in the Banach space X_Ω and a critical point $u_\Omega \in X_\Omega$ exists such that

$$\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_\Omega) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma_\Omega} \sup_{s \in [0, 1]} \mathcal{J}_\Omega(\gamma(s)) \geq \alpha^*$$

with $\Gamma_\Omega = \{\gamma \in C([0, 1], X_\Omega) : \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = u^*\}$.

On the other hand, also the second inequality in (4.1.48) is true as, from Remark 4.10, segment γ^* in (4.1.47) is such that $\gamma^* \in \Gamma_\Omega$. \square

At last, let us point out that, in the following, we need to prove a uniform boundedness for a sequence which is bounded in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Clearly, since Ω is a bounded subset of \mathbb{R}^N , if $p > N$ from the Sobolev Embedding Theorem such a boundedness is trivially satisfied but, on the contrary, if $p \leq N$ the following sufficient conditions are required.

Lemma 4.5. *Let Ω be an open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N and consider p, q so that $1 < p \leq N$ and $p \leq q < p^*$ (if $N = p$ we just require that p^* is any number larger than q) and take $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. If $a^* > 0$ and $m_0 \in \mathbb{N}$ exist such that*

$$\int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \leq a^* \left(m^q |\Omega_m^+| + \int_{\Omega_m^+} |u|^q dx \right) \quad \text{for all } m \geq m_0, \quad (4.1.49)$$

with $\Omega_m^+ = \{x \in \Omega : u(x) > m\}$, then $\operatorname{ess\,sup}_\Omega u$ is bounded from above by a positive constant which can be chosen so that it depends only on $|\Omega_{m_0}^+|$, N , p , q , a^* , m_0 , $\|u\|_\Omega$, or better by a positive constant which can be chosen so that it depends only on N , p , q , a^* , m_0 and a_0^* for any $a_0^* > 0$ such that

$$\max\{|\Omega_{m_0}^+|, \|u\|_\Omega\} \leq a_0^*.$$

Vice versa, if inequality

$$\int_{\Omega_m^-} |\nabla u|^p dx \leq a^* \left(m^q |\Omega_m^-| + \int_{\Omega_m^-} |u|^q dx \right) \quad \text{for all } m \geq m_0,$$

holds, with $\Omega_m^- = \{x \in \Omega : u(x) < -m\}$, then $\operatorname{ess\,sup}_\Omega(-u)$ is bounded from above by a positive constant which can be chosen so that it depends only on N , p , q , a^* , m_0 and any constant which is greater than both $|\Omega_{m_0}^-|$ and $\|u\|_\Omega$.

Proof. The proof is essentially as in [121, Theorem II.5.1] but, to point out some uniform estimates on the L^∞ -norms of a sequence which is bounded in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$, here we prefer to give some more details.

Firstly, taking any $m \in \mathbb{N}$ we note that direct computations, the Hölder inequality and (4.1.10) imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_m^+} (u - m)^q dx &\leq |\Omega_m^+|^{1 - \frac{q}{p^*}} \left(\int_{\Omega_m^+} (u - m)^{p^*} dx \right)^{\frac{q}{p^*}} \\ &\leq \sigma_*^q |\Omega_m^+|^{1 - \frac{q}{p^*}} \left(\int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \right)^{\frac{q}{p}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.50)$$

with $\sigma_* > 0$ as in (4.1.10), since $\max\{u - m, 0\} \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$. Thus, from (4.1.50) and direct computations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega_m^+} |u|^q dx &\leq 2^{q-1} \left(m^q |\Omega_m^+| + \int_{\Omega_m^+} (u - m)^q dx \right) \\ &\leq 2^{q-1} \left(m^q |\Omega_m^+| + \sigma_*^q |\Omega_m^+|^{1 - \frac{q}{p^*}} \left(\int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \right)^{\frac{q}{p}} \right) \\ &\leq 2^{q-1} \left(m^q |\Omega_m^+| + \sigma_*^q |\Omega_m^+|^{1 - \frac{q}{p^*}} \|u\|_\Omega^{q-p} \int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \right). \end{aligned}$$

Now, if $m \geq m_0$, from one hand (4.1.10) gives

$$m^{p^*} |\Omega_m^+| \leq \int_{\Omega_m^+} |u|^{p^*} dx \leq \int_\Omega |u|^{p^*} dx \leq L, \quad (4.1.51)$$

with

$$L^{\frac{1}{p^*}} = \sigma_* \|u\|_\Omega, \quad (4.1.52)$$

while, from the other hand, (4.1.49) and (4.1.51), (4.1.52) imply that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx &\leq a^*(1 + 2^{q-1})m^q |\Omega_m^+| \\
 &\quad + 2^{q-1}a^*\sigma_*^q |\Omega_m^+|^{1-\frac{q}{p^*}} \|u\|_{\Omega}^{q-p} \int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \\
 &\leq a^*(1 + 2^{q-1})m^q |\Omega_m^+| + 2^{q-1}a^*\sigma_*^q \frac{L^{1-\frac{q}{p^*}}}{m^{p^*-q}} \|u\|_{\Omega}^{q-p} \int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \\
 &\leq a^*(1 + 2^{q-1})m^q |\Omega_m^+| + 2^{q-1}a^*\sigma_*^{p^*} \frac{\|u\|_{\Omega}^{p^*-p}}{m^{p^*-q}} \int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1.53}$$

Hence, taking $m_1 \in \mathbb{N}$ such that

$$m_1 \geq \max \left\{ m_0, \left(2^q a^* \sigma_*^{p^*} \|u\|_{\Omega}^{p^*-p} \right)^{\frac{1}{p^*-q}} \right\}, \tag{4.1.54}$$

from (4.1.51), (4.1.53) and direct computations it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \leq a_1^* m^q |\Omega_m^+| \leq a_1^* m^p |\Omega_m^+| \left(\frac{L}{|\Omega_m^+|} \right)^{\frac{q-p}{p^*}} \quad \text{for all } m \geq m_1,$$

with $a_1^* = 2a^*(1 + 2^{q-1})$, that is,

$$\int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \leq a_1^* L^{\frac{q-p}{p^*}} m^p |\Omega_m^+|^{1-\frac{p}{N}+\varepsilon} \quad \text{for all } m \geq m_1,$$

where $\varepsilon = \frac{p}{N} - \frac{q-p}{p^*} > 0$ as $q < p^*$. Then, by using the same arguments required by estimate (4.1.50) but with q replaced by 1, for all $m \geq m_1$ this last inequality implies that

$$\int_{\Omega_m^+} (u - m) dx \leq \sigma_* |\Omega_m^+|^{1-\frac{1}{p^*}} \left(\int_{\Omega_m^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq a_2^* L^{\frac{q-p}{pp^*}} m |\Omega_m^+|^{1+\frac{\varepsilon}{p}}$$

with $a_2^* = \sigma_*(a_1^*)^{\frac{1}{p}}$. Thus, reasoning as in the proof of [121, Lemma II.5.1] but with our setting, from direct computations we have that

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} u \leq 2^{\frac{p}{\varepsilon}} \left(m_1 + a_3^* L^{\frac{q-p}{\varepsilon p^*}} \int_{\Omega_{m_1}^+} |u| dx \right) \tag{4.1.55}$$

with $a_3^* = (a_2^*)^{1+\frac{p}{\varepsilon}}$. So, since from (4.1.54) and Hölder inequality we have that

$$\int_{\Omega_{m_1}^+} |u| dx \leq \int_{\Omega_{m_0}^+} |u| dx \leq |\Omega_{m_0}^+|^{1-\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\Omega_{m_0}^+} |u|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \leq |\Omega_{m_0}^+|^{1-\frac{1}{p}} \|u\|_{\Omega},$$

from (4.1.52) estimate (4.1.55) becomes

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega} u \leq 2^{\frac{p}{\varepsilon}} \left(m_1 + a_3^* \sigma_*^{\frac{q-p}{\varepsilon}} |\Omega_{m_0}^+|^{1-\frac{1}{p}} \|u\|_{\Omega}^{1+\frac{q-p}{\varepsilon}} \right). \tag{4.1.56}$$

At last, if we take $a_0^* \geq \max\{\|u\|_\Omega, |\Omega_{m_0}^+|\}$, estimate (4.1.56) implies

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_\Omega u \leq 2^{\frac{p}{\varepsilon}} \left(m_1^* + a_3^* \sigma_*^{\frac{q-p}{\varepsilon}} (a_0^*)^{2+\frac{q-p}{\varepsilon}-\frac{1}{p}} \right)$$

with m_1^* defined as in (4.1.54) but replacing $\|u\|_\Omega$ with a_0^* .

Finally, the proof of the second statement of this lemma follows from the first part but applied to function $-u$. \square

4.1.3 Proof of Theorem 4.2

Throughout this section, we suppose that the assumptions in Theorem 4.2 are satisfied and for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we consider as bounded set the open ball B_k , its related Banach space X_{B_k} as in (4.1.37) and the functional

$$\mathcal{J}_k : u \in X_{B_k} \mapsto \mathcal{J}_k(u) = \mathcal{J}_{B_k}(u) \in \mathbb{R}$$

with $\mathcal{J}_{B_k}(u)$ defined as in (4.1.40).

Remark 4.11. For the sake of convenience, if $u \in X_{B_k}$ we always consider its trivial extension as 0 in $\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_k$. Then, if we still denote such an extension by u , we have that $u \in X$, too. Moreover, from (4.1.17), definitions (4.1.18) and (4.1.40), respectively (4.1.19) and (4.1.45), imply that $\mathcal{J}_k(u) = \mathcal{J}(u)$, respectively

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}_k(u), v \rangle = \langle d\mathcal{J}(u), v \rangle \quad \text{for all } v \in X_{B_k}.$$

Remark 4.12. If in Remark 4.10 we take $\varepsilon^* \leq 1$, then $u^* \in X_{B_1}$ and segment γ^* in (4.1.47) is such that $\operatorname{supp} \gamma^*(s) \subset B_1$ for all $s \in [0, 1]$. Hence, for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we have that $\gamma^* \in \Gamma_{B_k}$, with

$$\Gamma_{B_k} = \{\gamma \in C([0, 1], X_{B_k}) : \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = u^*\}.$$

Moreover, for the continuity of $\mathcal{J} \circ \gamma^* : s \in [0, 1] \mapsto \mathcal{J}(s u^*) \in \mathbb{R}$, $\alpha^{**} \in \mathbb{R}$ exists, independent of k , such that

$$\alpha^{**} = \max_{s \in [0, 1]} \mathcal{J}(s u^*).$$

Since for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ Proposition 4.6 applies to \mathcal{J}_k in X_{B_k} , from Remarks 4.11 and 4.12, a sequence $(u_k)_k \subset X$ exists such that for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ it results:

- (i) $u_k \in X_{B_k}$ with $u_k = 0$ in $\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_k$,
- (ii) $\alpha^* \leq \mathcal{J}(u_k) \leq \alpha^{**}$,
- (iii) $\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), v \rangle = 0$ for all $v \in X_{B_k}$,

with α^* as in Proposition 4.3 and α^{**} as in Remark 4.12.

The proof of Theorem 4.2 requires different steps.

Firstly, we prove that sequence $(u_k)_k$ is bounded in X . If $p > N$, from the Sobolev Embedding Theorem it is enough to verify that $(\|u_k\|)_k$ is bounded while, if $p \leq N$, such a boundedness is not enough and Lemma 4.5 needs.

From now on, we denote any strictly positive constant independent of k by d_i .

Proposition 4.7. *A constant $M_0 > 0$ exists such that*

$$\|u_k\|_X \leq M_0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (4.1.57)$$

Moreover, for every $r \geq p$ we have also that

$$|u_k|_{V,r} \leq M_0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (4.1.58)$$

Proof. From conditions (i) and (iii) we infer that

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), u_k \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (4.1.59)$$

then, taking μ as in assumption (4h₃), from (4.1.59), definitions (4.1.18), (4.1.19), assumptions (4h₂)–(4h₃), (V₁), (4g₃), (0.0.5) and direct computations we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu\mathcal{J}(u_k) &= \mu\mathcal{J}(u_k) - \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), u_k \rangle \\ &\geq \frac{\alpha_0\alpha_1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_k|^p dx + \left(\frac{\mu}{p} - 1\right) \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u_k|^p dx \geq d_1 \|u_k\|_V^p \end{aligned}$$

for a suitable constant $d_1 > 0$. Whence, condition (ii) implies that

$$\|u_k\|_V \leq d_2 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N} \quad (4.1.60)$$

with $d_2 = \left(\frac{\mu\alpha^{**}}{d_1}\right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$.

Now, to obtain estimate (4.1.57) if $p \leq N$, from definition (4.1.11) we need to prove that $(u_k)_k$ is a bounded sequence in $L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$, too. To this aim, we note that for a fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$ either $|u_k|_\infty \leq 1$ or $|u_k|_\infty > 1$.

If $|u_k|_\infty > 1$, then

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N} u_k > 1 \quad \text{and/or} \quad \operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N} (-u_k) > 1.$$

Assume that $\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N} u_k > 1$ and consider the set

$$B_{k,1}^+ = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : u_k(x) > 1\}.$$

From condition (i) we have that

$$B_{k,1}^+ \subset B_k,$$

moreover, $B_{k,1}^+$ is an open bounded domain such that not only $|B_{k,1}^+| > 0$ but also, by means of (4.1.4), it is

$$|B_{k,1}^+| \leq \int_{B_{k,1}^+} |u_k|^p dx \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u_k|^p dx \leq \|u_k\|^p \leq d_3 \|u_k\|_V^p$$

for a suitable $d_3 > 0$. Hence, estimate (4.1.60) gives

$$|B_{k,1}^+| \leq d_4 \quad (4.1.61)$$

with $d_4 = d_2^p d_3$.

To prove that Lemma 4.5 applies, for any $m \in \mathbb{N}$ we consider the new function $R_m^+ : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined as

$$t \mapsto R_m^+ t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \leq m \\ t - m & \text{if } t > m \end{cases}.$$

Since taking $t = 0$ in (h_4) we obtain $\alpha_2 \leq p$, for any $m \geq 1$, we have that $R_m^+ u_k \in X_k$ and from condition (iii), definition (4.1.45) and hypotheses (V_1) , $(4h_2)$, $(4h_4)$ and direct computations it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), R_m^+ u_k \rangle = \int_{B_{k,m}^+} \left(1 - \frac{m}{u_k}\right) \left(A(x, u_k) + \frac{1}{p} A_t(x, u_k) u_k\right) |\nabla u_k|^p dx \\ &\quad + \int_{B_{k,m}^+} \frac{m}{u_k} A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^p dx + \int_{B_{k,m}^+} \left(1 - \frac{m}{u_k}\right) V(x) |u_k|^p dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) R_m^+ u_k dx \\ &\geq \frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{p} \int_{B_{k,m}^+} |\nabla u_k|^p dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) R_m^+ u_k dx, \end{aligned}$$

i.e.,

$$\frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{p} \int_{B_{k,m}^+} |\nabla u_k|^p dx \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) R_m^+ u_k dx, \quad (4.1.62)$$

with $B_{k,m}^+ = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : u_k(x) > m\}$. Clearly, it is $B_{k,m}^+ \subseteq B_{k,1}^+$ so from (4.1.61) we have that

$$|B_{k,m}^+| \leq d_4. \quad (4.1.63)$$

Since (g_3) implies $g(x, t) > 0$ if $t > 0$ for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$, then $g(x, u_k(x)) > 0$ for a.e. $x \in B_{k,m}^+$; so, from $(4g_1)$, (4.1.28) and the Young inequality with conjugate exponents $\frac{q}{p} > 1$ and $\frac{q}{q-p}$, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) R_m^+ u_k dx &\leq \int_{B_{k,m}^+} g(x, u_k) u_k dx \leq \int_{B_{k,m}^+} (a_1 u_k^p + a_2 u_k^q) dx \\ &\leq \int_{B_{k,m}^+} \left(\frac{q-p}{q} a_1^{\frac{q}{q-p}} + \frac{p}{q} u_k^q \right) dx + a_2 \int_{B_{k,m}^+} u_k^q dx \\ &= \frac{q-p}{q} a_1^{\frac{q}{q-p}} |B_{k,m}^+| + \left(\frac{p}{q} + a_2 \right) \int_{B_{k,m}^+} u_k^q dx. \end{aligned}$$

Hence, from (4.1.62) we obtain that

$$\int_{B_{k,m}^+} |\nabla u_k|^p dx \leq a^* \left(|B_{k,m}^+| + \int_{B_{k,m}^+} u_k^q dx \right) \quad \text{for all } m \geq 1,$$

with $a^* > 0$ independent of m and k . Then, Lemma 4.5 with $\Omega = B_k$ applies and $d_5 > 1$ exists such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{B_k} u_k \leq d_5$$

where, from Lemma 4.5, (4.1.4), (4.1.60) and (4.1.63) imply that constant d_5 can be chosen independent of $k \in \mathbb{N}$.

Similar arguments apply if $\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N}(-u_k) > 1$, then, summing up, $d_6 \geq 1$ exists such that

$$|u_k|_\infty \leq d_6 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}.$$

So, (4.1.57) holds and from estimate (4.1.12) also (4.1.58) is satisfied. \square

From estimate (4.1.57) and (4.1.8) it follows that $u_\infty \in W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ exists such that, up to a subsequence still denoted by $(u_k)_k$, it is

$$u_k \rightharpoonup u_\infty \quad \text{weakly in } W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N), \quad (4.1.64)$$

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{strongly in } L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \text{ for any } p \leq r < p^*, \quad (4.1.65)$$

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.66)$$

Proposition 4.8. $u_\infty \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$; hence, $u_\infty \in X$.

Proof. Taking

$$A = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : \lim_{k \rightarrow +\infty} u_k(x) = u_\infty(x)\},$$

for all $x \in A$ an integer $\nu_{x,1} \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that

$$|u_k(x) - u_\infty(x)| < 1 \quad \text{for all } k \geq \nu_{x,1},$$

then from (4.1.57) we have that

$$|u_\infty(x)| \leq |u_\infty(x) - u_{\nu_{x,1}}(x)| + |u_{\nu_{x,1}}(x)| \leq 1 + M_0.$$

On the other hand, from (4.1.66) it follows that $|\mathbb{R}^N \setminus A| = 0$, which completes the proof. \square

Remark 4.13. Let $R \geq 1$ be fixed. Actually, since B_R is a bounded domain, from Remark 4.8 and (4.1.65) it follows that

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{strongly in } L_V^p(B_R). \quad (4.1.67)$$

Corollary 4.1. For all $1 \leq r < +\infty$ we have that

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{strongly in } L_V^r(B_R) \quad \text{for all } R \geq 1. \quad (4.1.68)$$

Proof. Taking $1 \leq r \leq p$, the boundedness of B_R gives $L^p(B_R) \hookrightarrow L^r(B_R)$ which, together with (0.0.4), assumption (V_3) and (4.1.65), ensures that (4.1.68) holds.

On the other hand, if we take $r > p$, then Propositions 4.7 and 4.8, together with (4.1.67), allow us to apply Lemma 4.2, so (4.1.68) holds, too. \square

Proposition 4.9. *We have that*

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{strongly in } W_V^{1,p}(B_R) \quad \text{for all } R \geq 1. \quad (4.1.69)$$

Proof. For simplicity, throughout this proof we denote any infinitesimal sequence by $(\varepsilon_k)_k$.

Fixing any $R \geq 1$, from (4.1.67) it is enough to prove that

$$|\nabla u_k - \nabla u_\infty|_{B_{R,p}} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (4.1.70)$$

To this aim, following an idea introduced in [44], let us consider the real map $\psi(t) = te^{\eta t^2}$, where $\eta > (\frac{\beta_2}{2\beta_1})^2$ will be fixed once $\beta_1, \beta_2 > 0$ are chosen in a suitable way later on. By definition, we have that

$$\beta_1 \psi'(t) - \beta_2 |\psi(t)| > \frac{\beta_1}{2} \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.1.71)$$

Defining $v_k = u_k - u_\infty$, limit (4.1.64) implies that

$$v_k \rightharpoonup 0 \quad \text{weakly in } W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N), \quad (4.1.72)$$

while from (4.1.65), respectively (4.1.66), it follows that

$$v_k \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{strongly in } L^p(\mathbb{R}^N), \quad (4.1.73)$$

respectively

$$v_k \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.74)$$

Moreover, from Proposition 4.8 and (4.1.57) we obtain that

$$v_k \in X \quad \text{and} \quad |v_k|_\infty \leq \bar{M}_0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (4.1.75)$$

with $\bar{M}_0 = M_0 + |u_\infty|_\infty$. Now, let $\chi_R \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$ be a cut-off function such that

$$\chi_R(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } |x| \leq R \\ 0 & \text{if } |x| \geq R+1 \end{cases}, \quad \text{with } 0 \leq \chi_R(x) \leq 1 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.1.76)$$

and

$$|\nabla \chi_R(x)| \leq 2 \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.77)$$

Thus, for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ we consider the new function

$$w_{R,k} : x \in \mathbb{R}^N \mapsto w_{R,k}(x) = \chi_R(x) \psi(v_k(x)) \in \mathbb{R}.$$

We note that (4.1.75) gives

$$|\psi(v_k)| \leq \psi(\bar{M}_0), \quad 0 < \psi'(v_k) \leq \psi'(\bar{M}_0) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.1.78)$$

while (4.1.74) implies

$$\psi(v_k) \rightarrow 0, \quad \psi'(v_k) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.79)$$

Then, from (4.1.76) and (4.1.78) we have that $\text{supp } w_{R,k} \subset \text{supp } \chi_R \subset B_{R+1}$ and also

$$|w_{R,k}| \leq \psi(\bar{M}_0) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.80)$$

Moreover (4.1.79) implies that

$$w_{R,k} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.1.81)$$

while from

$$\nabla w_{R,k} = \psi(v_k) \nabla \chi_R + \chi_R \psi'(v_k) \nabla v_k \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \quad (4.1.82)$$

and (4.1.75)–(4.1.78) it follows that $w_{R,k} \in X_{B_{R+1}}$. Hence, for all $k \geq R+1$ we have that

$$w_{R,k} \in X_{B_k}$$

so (iii), (4.1.19) and (4.1.82) imply that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), w_{R,k} \rangle = \int_{B_{R+1}} \psi(v_k) A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla \chi_R dx \\ &+ \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R \psi'(v_k) A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_{B_{R+1}} A_t(x, u_k) w_{R,k} |\nabla u_k|^p dx \\ &+ \int_{B_{R+1}} V(x) |u_k|^{p-2} u_k w_{R,k} dx - \int_{B_{R+1}} g(x, u_k) w_{R,k} dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.83)$$

We note that (4g₀)–(4g₁) together with (4.1.57), (4.1.66), (4.1.80), (4.1.81) and Dominated Convergence Theorem on the bounded set B_{R+1} imply that

$$\int_{B_{R+1}} g(x, u_k) w_{R,k} dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (4.1.84)$$

Moreover, from assumption (4h₁), (4.1.57), (4.1.77) and Hölder inequality we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k) A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla \chi_R| dx &\leq d_1 \int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-1} dx \\ &\leq d_1 \|u_k\|_{B_{R+1}}^{p-1} \left(\int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k)|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}; \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.85)$$

now, from (4.1.78), (4.1.79) and the boundedness of the set B_{R+1} , by means of Dominated Convergence Theorem, we obtain

$$\int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k)|^p dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (4.1.86)$$

Hence, estimate (4.1.57), together with (4.1.85) and (4.1.86), guarantees that

$$\int_{B_{R+1}} \psi(v_k) A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla \chi_R dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (4.1.87)$$

Furthermore, from (V_3) , (4.1.76), Hölder inequality, (4.1.57) and (4.1.86) it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{B_{R+1}} V(x) |u_k|^{p-2} u_k w_{R,k} dx \right| &\leq C_{R+1} \int_{B_{R+1}} |u_k|^{p-1} |\psi(v_k)| dx \\ &\leq C_{R+1} |u_k|_{B_{R+1}, p}^{p-1} \left(\int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k)|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.88)$$

On the other hand, (4.1.57), (4.1.76), assumptions $(4h_1)$ – $(4h_2)$ and direct computations ensure the existence of a constant $d_2 > 0$, independent of k , such that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A_t(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) |\nabla u_k|^p dx \right| &\leq \frac{d_2}{\alpha_0} \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_k) |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^p dx \\ &= \frac{d_2}{\alpha_0} \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_k) |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx \\ &\quad + \frac{d_2}{\alpha_0} \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_k) |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla u_\infty dx. \end{aligned}$$

We note that hypothesis $(4h_1)$, (4.1.57), (4.1.76) and Hölder inequality give

$$\begin{aligned} &\left| \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_n) |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla u_\infty dx \right| \\ &\leq d_3 \left(\int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k)|^p |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{B_{R+1}} |\nabla u_k|^p dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \\ &\leq d_4 \left(\int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k)|^p |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \rightarrow 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.89)$$

as (4.1.78), (4.1.79) and, again, Dominated Convergence Theorem imply that

$$\int_{B_{R+1}} |\psi(v_k)|^p |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Then, from estimate (4.1.83) and (4.1.84), (4.1.87)–(4.1.89), we obtain that

$$\varepsilon_k \geq \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_k) h_k |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx \quad (4.1.90)$$

if we set

$$h_k(x) = \psi'(v_k(x)) - \frac{d_2}{p\alpha_0} |\psi(v_k(x))| \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N.$$

Now, back to (4.1.71) and taking $\beta_1 = 1, \beta_2 = \frac{d_2}{p\alpha_0}$, from (4.1.78), (4.1.79) and direct computations not only we have that

$$h_k(x) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \quad \text{and} \quad |h_k(x)| \leq \psi'(\bar{M}_0) + d_5 |\psi(\bar{M}_0)| \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.1.91)$$

but also

$$h_k(x) > \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.1.92)$$

At last, back to (4.1.90), direct computations give

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_k &\geq \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_k) h_k |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx \\ &= \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_\infty) |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k dx \\ &\quad + \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R (h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)) |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k dx \\ &\quad + \int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_k) h_k (|\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla v_k dx, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.93)$$

where from (4.1.72) it follows that

$$\int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R A(x, u_\infty) |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Now, from Hölder inequality, we have that

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{B_{R+1}} \chi_R |(h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)) |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k| dx \\ &\leq \left(\int_{B_{R+1}} |h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \|v_k\|_{B_{R+1}} \rightarrow 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.94)$$

since assumption (4h₀), (4.1.66), (4.1.76) and (4.1.91) imply that

$$h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N,$$

while (4.1.57), (4.1.91), Proposition 4.8 and (4h₁) give

$$|h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} |\nabla u_\infty|^p \leq d_6 |\nabla u_\infty|^p \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N.$$

Hence, Dominated Convergence Theorem applies which, together with (4.1.73), guarantees that the limit in (4.1.94) holds.

Moreover, using the previous estimates in (4.1.93), from (4.1.76), (4.1.92), hypothesis

(4h₂) and the strong convexity of the power function with exponent $p > 1$, we have that

$$\varepsilon_k \geq \frac{\alpha_0}{2} \int_{B_{R+1}} (|\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla v_k dx \geq 0,$$

which implies that

$$\int_{B_{R+1}} (|\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla v_k dx \rightarrow 0;$$

hence, (4.1.70) follows from (4.1.64). \square

Proposition 4.10. *We have that*

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty), \varphi \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for all } \varphi \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad (4.1.95)$$

with $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{\varphi \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) : \text{supp } \varphi \subset\subset \mathbb{R}^N\}$. Hence, $d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty) = 0$ in X .

Proof. Taking $\varphi \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$, a radius $R \geq 1$ exists such that $\text{supp } \varphi \subset B_R$. Thus, for all $k \geq R$ we have that $\varphi \in X_k$ so (iii) applies and $\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), \varphi \rangle = 0$. Furthermore, direct computations give

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &\leq |\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty), \varphi \rangle| = |\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), \varphi \rangle - \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty), \varphi \rangle| \\ &\leq \int_{B_R} |A(x, u_k)| \left| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \right| |\nabla \varphi| dx \\ &\quad + \int_{B_R} |A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)| |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-1} |\nabla \varphi| dx \\ &\quad + \frac{|\varphi|_\infty}{p} \int_{B_R} |A_t(x, u_k)| \left| |\nabla u_k|^p - |\nabla u_\infty|^p \right| dx \\ &\quad + \frac{|\varphi|_\infty}{p} \int_{B_R} |A_t(x, u_k) - A_t(x, u_\infty)| |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \\ &\quad + |\varphi|_\infty \int_{B_R} V(x) \left| |u_k|^{p-2} u_k - |u_\infty|^{p-2} u_\infty \right| dx \\ &\quad + |\varphi|_\infty \int_{B_R} |g(x, u_k) - g(x, u_\infty)| dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.96)$$

We note that the boundedness of B_R together with (4g₀)-(4g₁), (4.1.57), (4.1.66) and Proposition 4.8 allow us to apply the Dominated Convergence Theorem and

$$\int_{B_R} |g(x, u_k) - g(x, u_\infty)| dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Moreover, by using some arguments similar to those ones in the proof of Proposition 4.1 we have that assumption (V₃) and (4.1.65) imply that

$$\int_{B_R} V(x) \left| |u_k|^{p-2} u_k - |u_\infty|^{p-2} u_\infty \right| dx \rightarrow 0.$$

On the other hand, by means of $(4h_1)$, Hölder inequality and direct computations, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{B_R} |A(x, u_k)| \left| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \right| |\nabla \varphi| dx \\ \leq d_1 \left(\int_{B_R} \left| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \right|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}}, \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.97)$$

for a suitable constant $d_1 = d_1(|\varphi|_\infty) > 0$. Now, if $p > 2$, then Lemma 2.1, again Hölder inequality with conjugate exponents $p - 1$ and $\frac{p-1}{p-2}$, (4.1.57) and direct computations imply that

$$\left(\int_{B_R} \left| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \right|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \leq d_2 \|u_k - u_\infty\|_{B_R}. \quad (4.1.98)$$

Conversely, if $1 < p \leq 2$ again Lemma 2.1 applies so that

$$\left(\int_{B_R} \left| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \right|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \leq \|u_k - u_\infty\|_{B_R}^{p-1}. \quad (4.1.99)$$

Thus, from (4.1.97)–(4.1.99) and (4.1.69) it follows that

$$\int_{B_R} |A(x, u_k)| \left| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \right| |\nabla \varphi| dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (4.1.100)$$

Furthermore, from assumption $(4h_1)$, (4.1.57), (4.1.69) and Lemma 4.3 we have that

$$\int_{B_R} |A_t(x, u_k)| \left| |\nabla u_k|^p - |\nabla u_\infty|^p \right| dx \rightarrow 0,$$

while, from Dominated Convergence Theorem it results

$$\int_{B_R} |A_t(x, u_k) - A_t(x, u_\infty)| |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \rightarrow 0$$

as $(4h_0)$ and (4.1.69) imply that

$$|A_t(x, u_k) - A_t(x, u_\infty)| |\nabla u_\infty|^p \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N$$

and $(4h_1)$, (4.1.57) give

$$|A_t(x, u_k) - A_t(x, u_\infty)| |\nabla u_\infty|^p \leq d_3 |\nabla u_\infty|^p \in L^1(B_R).$$

So, summing up, (4.1.96) guarantees that (4.1.95) holds and the proof follows from the density of $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$ in X . \square

Proof of Theorem 4.2. From Proposition 4.10 we have that the statement of Theorem 4.2 is true if we prove $u_\infty \not\equiv 0$.

Arguing by contradiction, assume that $u_\infty = 0$. Hence, from assumption $(4g_1)$ with $q < p^*$ and (4.1.65) we have that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) u_k dx \rightarrow 0, \quad (4.1.101)$$

which, together with assumption $(4g_3)$, ensures that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, u_k) dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (4.1.102)$$

Furthermore, from (4.1.19), (iii) , $(4h_4)$ and also $(4h_2)$ it results

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), u_k \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^p dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A_t(x, u_k) u_k |\nabla u_k|^p dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_k|^p dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) u_k dx \\ &\geq \frac{\alpha_2 \alpha_0}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_k|^p dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_k|^p dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) u_k dx, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$\|u_k\|_V \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty \quad (4.1.103)$$

by means of (0.0.5) and (4.1.101). Hence, from (4.1.18), $(4h_1)$, (4.1.57), (4.1.102) and (4.1.103) we infer

$$\mathcal{J}(u_k) \leq d_1 \|u_k\|_V^p - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, u_k) dx \rightarrow 0$$

in contradiction with estimate (ii) . \square

Remark 4.14. Unlike the results in [28, 29, 165] and other similar works, here managing our problem directly on \mathbb{R}^N seems quite hard. In fact, the choice of the working space in (4.1.11) requires that the $(wCPS)$ condition holds if $u \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$ too, but we have no knowledge of a result similar to Lemma 4.5 but settled in the whole Euclidean space \mathbb{R}^N .

4.2 Quasilinear modified Schrödinger equations in Applied Sciences

In this section, we deal with the existence of positive solutions, often named soliton solutions, for the quasilinear modified Schrödinger equation

$$-\operatorname{div}(g^2(u) \nabla u) + g(u) g'(u) |\nabla u|^2 + V(x) u = f(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (4.2.1)$$

where potential $V : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a suitable measurable function and $g : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $f : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are given maps.

The noteworthiness of problem (4.2.1) is based on its connection to the study of solitary wave solutions for the quasilinear Schrödinger equation

$$i\partial_t z = -\Delta z - \Delta(l(|z|^2))l'(|z|^2)z + W(x)z - k(x, |z|)z, \quad \text{with } x \in \mathbb{R}^3, t \geq 0, \quad (4.2.2)$$

where the solution we look for $z(x, t)$ is complex in $\mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}_+$ while $W : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $k : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $l : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are real functions.

In fact, by using the ansatz $z(x, t) = e^{-iEt}u(x)$ in (4.2.2) with $E \in \mathbb{R}$, we have that $u : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is an unknown real function which solves the stationary Schrödinger problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u - \Delta(l(u^2))l'(u^2)u + V(x)u = f(x, u) & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3 \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3 \end{cases} \quad (4.2.3)$$

with the new potential $V(x) = W(x) - E$ and $f(x, u) = k(x, u)u$.

The relation between the equation asserted in (4.2.1) and that one in (4.2.3) is exhibited through the particular choice of function $g(u)$. In fact, if $l(s)$ is a C^2 map on \mathbb{R}_+ , having

$$g^2(u) = 1 + \frac{[(l(u^2))']^2}{2} = 1 + 2u^2[l'(u^2)]^2, \quad (4.2.4)$$

we obtain

$$g(u)g'(u) = 2u l'(u^2)[l'(u^2) + 2u^2 l''(u^2)] \quad (4.2.5)$$

and

$$\operatorname{div}(g^2(u)\nabla u) = 2g(u)g'(u)|\nabla u|^2 + g^2(u)\Delta u,$$

then, via direct computations, we infer that

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta u + \Delta(l(u^2))l'(u^2)u &= \Delta u + g(u)g'(u)|\nabla u|^2 + 2u^2[l'(u^2)]^2\Delta u \\ &= \operatorname{div}(g^2(u)\nabla u) - g(u)g'(u)|\nabla u|^2 \end{aligned}$$

so that the equation in (4.2.3) boils down exactly to equation (4.2.1).

Thus, the importance of problem (4.2.1) rests upon the wide interest in Schrödinger equation (4.2.2) which turns up in several fields such as, for example, Plasma Physics and Fluid Mechanics (see [120]), Mechanics (see [115]), Condensed Matter Theory (see [136]). More precisely, it has been derived as model equation of various physical phenomena according to the special form given to the nonlinear term $l(s)$.

Throughout this chapter, we will focus on the equations which are originated by choosing $l(s) = s$ and $l(s) = \sqrt{1 + s}$.

In particular, taking $l(s) = s$ in (4.2.3), definition (4.2.4) gives

$$g^2(u) = 1 + 2u^2 \quad (4.2.6)$$

and (4.2.1) reduces to the superfluid film equation in Plasma Physics so that we are interested in solving the model problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u - u \Delta(u^2) + V(x)u = f(x, u) & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3 \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3 \end{cases} \quad (4.2.7)$$

with a nonlinear function $f(x, u)$ at the place of $k(x, u)u$ (see [120]).

On the other hand, if $l(s) = \sqrt{1+s}$ from (4.2.4) we have that

$$g^2(u) = 1 + \frac{u^2}{2(1+u^2)} \quad (4.2.8)$$

so problem (4.2.1) turns into

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u - \frac{u}{2\sqrt{1+u^2}} \Delta(\sqrt{1+u^2}) + V(x)u = f(x, u) & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3 \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3 \end{cases} \quad (4.2.9)$$

which describes the self-channeling of a high-power ultrashort laser in matter (see [122]).

As far as we know, the first existence results for equation (4.2.7), via a variational approach, are gained through a constrained minimization argument (see [132, 158]). Later on, a further general existence result was derived in [133] by using a suitable change of variable which reduces the quasilinear equation (4.2.7) to a semilinear one so that a Orlicz space framework can be used and the existence of positive solutions follows from the Mountain Pass Theorem. The same approach was employed in [74, 95], but a most common setting involving the usual Sobolev space $H^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$ was exploited. More precisely, since the action functional associated to (4.2.7) is not well defined in $H^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$, taking $h(t)$ odd extension of the solution of the ordinary differential equation

$$h'(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1+2h^2(t)}} \quad \text{if } t \geq 0,$$

the existence of a spherically symmetric solution is established by means of the change of variable $v = h^{-1}(u)$ and of classical results provided by Berestycki and Lions in [38]. We refer the reader interested in other results about existence of standing wave for nonlinear Schrödinger equations with potentials to the pioneering works [10, 91, 159], to the more recent results contained in [8, 11, 71, 72] and references therein.

On the other hand, very few results are known about equation (4.2.9) (see, e.g., [82]) but, more recently, Y. Schen and Y. Wang in [174] choose to introduce a unified method for studying both (4.2.7) and (4.2.9) looking for standing wave solutions for (4.2.1) so that they have the existence of positive solutions for the model problems, too. As they point out, variational methods cannot apply directly so, by taking advance of the special form of (4.2.1), in the natural associated functional they make the change of variable

$$v = G(u) = \int_0^u g(t) dt$$

and then investigate the existence of weak solutions of the corresponding problem by means of the Mountain Pass Theorem. Clearly, with such an approach the hypotheses on the nonlinear term $f(x, u)$ are affected by $g(u)$ (for more details, see Remark 4.15).

Here we deal with (4.2.1), too, but we use a completely different strategy. In fact, we consider (4.2.1) as a model problem of the quasilinear modified Schrödinger equation

$$-\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}A_u(x, u)|\nabla u|^p + V(x)|u|^{p-2}u = f(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \quad (4.2.10)$$

with $p > 1$ and $A : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that $A_u(x, u) = \frac{\partial A}{\partial u}(x, u)$, which has been studied in [CS3, 57].

Here, it has to be $N = 3$, $p = 2$, $A(x, u) = g^2(u)$ as in (4.2.4) and, as in [CS3, 34], potential $V : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies the following conditions (V_1) – (V_3) in Section 4.1 but with $N = 3$.

Moreover, we suppose that the nonlinear term $f : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is such that:

(f_0^+) $f(x, u)$ is a Carathéodory function with $f(x, 0) = 0$ for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$;

(f_1^+) $a_1, a_2 > 0$ and $q \geq 2$ exist such that

$$|f(x, u)| \leq a_1u + a_2u^{q-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3, \text{ for all } u \geq 0;$$

(f_2^+) $\lim_{u \rightarrow 0^+} \frac{f(x, u)}{u} = \bar{\alpha} < \frac{1}{\tau_2^2}$ uniformly a.e. with respect to $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$;

(f_3^+) $\mu > 2$ exists such that

$$0 < \mu F(x, u) \leq f(x, u)u \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3, \text{ for all } u > 0;$$

where $\tau_2 > 0$ is a constant coming from a suitable embedding theorem (i.e., so that (4.2.15) holds), and

$$F : (x, u) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto \int_0^u f(x, t)dt \in \mathbb{R}.$$

In the following subsections we will state existence results for problem (4.2.1) (see Theorems 4.7 and 4.8), which allow us to state the following theorems for the model problems (4.2.7) and (4.2.9).

Theorem 4.3. *Assume that potential $V(x)$ satisfies assumptions (V_1) – (V_3) , while the nonlinear term $f(x, u)$ is such that conditions (f_0^+) – (f_3^+) are verified.*

Then, if

$$q < 6 \quad \text{and} \quad \mu > 4 \quad (4.2.11)$$

with q as in (f_1^+) and μ as in (f_3^+) , problem (4.2.7) admits at least one weak bounded solution.

Theorem 4.4. *Assume that potential $V(x)$ satisfies assumptions (V_1) – (V_3) , while the nonlinear term $f(x, u)$ is such that conditions (f_0^+) – (f_3^+) are verified. Then, if (4.2.11) holds, problem (4.2.9) admits at least one weak bounded solution.*

Remark 4.15. In [174] potential $V(x)$ is required to be continuous on \mathbb{R}^3 , with $V(x) \geq V_0 > 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and so that

$$\lim_{|x| \rightarrow +\infty} V(x) = V(\infty) \quad \text{and} \quad V(x) \leq V(\infty) \quad \text{for all } x \in \mathbb{R}^3.$$

Hence, (V_1) and (V_3) are essentially verified, but hypothesis (V_2) cannot hold. On the other hand, here the hypotheses on $f(x, u)$, namely (f_0^+) – (f_3^+) , are not affected by $g(u)$ or, more precisely, any particular form given to $l(u)$ in (4.2.4), hence also condition (4.2.11) does not change. Such independence is a great improvement when dealing with general settings but it is too rigid when working with both the special problems (4.2.7) and (4.2.9). In fact, as pointed out in [174], differently from Theorem 4.3, respectively Theorem 4.4, if (4.2.6) holds then it can be $q < 12$ (see [174, Remark 1.4]) while (4.2.8) has a solution even when the weaker estimate $\mu > \sqrt{6}$ holds (see [174, Corollary 1.5]).

4.2.1 Variational setting and first properties

Some of the needed features have been already pointed out in Section 4.1. Anyway, for the reader convenience, we prefer to write them here but specialized for the case $N = 3$. To start, we observe that weight $V(x)$ satisfies assumption (V_1) , then we have the following continuous embeddings:

$$L_V^r(\mathbb{R}^3) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^3) \quad \text{for any } 1 \leq r < +\infty, \quad (4.2.12)$$

and then

$$H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3) \hookrightarrow H^1(\mathbb{R}^3).$$

Hence, byclassical Sobolev Embedding Theorems, we deduce the following result (for the compact embeddings, see [34, Theorem 3.1]).

Theorem 4.5. *If weight $V : \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies assumption (V_1) , then the following continuous embedding hold:*

$$H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^3) \quad \text{for any } 2 \leq r \leq 6. \quad (4.2.13)$$

Furthermore, if assumption (V_2) also occurs, we have the compact embedding

$$H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3) \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^3) \quad \text{for any } 2 \leq r < 6. \quad (4.2.14)$$

For any $r \geq 2$ so that (4.2.13) holds, Theorem 4.5 implies that a constant $\tau_r > 0$ exists such that

$$|u|_r \leq \tau_r \|u\|_V \quad \text{for all } u \in H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3). \quad (4.2.15)$$

On the other hand, taking Ω open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^3 , the classical embedding theorem implies that a constant $\sigma_* > 0$ exists, independent of Ω , such that

$$|v|_{\Omega, 2^*} \leq \sigma_* \|v\|_{\Omega} \quad \text{for all } v \in H_0^1(\Omega).$$

From now on, we assume that potential $V(x)$ satisfies condition (V_1) and we set

$$X := H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3) \cap L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3) \quad \text{and} \quad \|u\|_X = \|u\|_V + |u|_\infty \quad \text{for any } u \in X. \quad (4.2.16)$$

Remark 4.16. From (4.2.12) and [CS3, Lemma 3.3] it follows that the continuous embedding $X \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^3)$ holds for every $r \geq 2$.

Now, we briefly recall the existence result for solutions of problem (4.2.10) as stated in [CS3]. To this aim, for the coefficient $A : (x, u) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto A(x, u) \in \mathbb{R}$ we consider the following conditions:

(4 \tilde{h}_0) $A(x, u)$ is a \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function with $A_u(x, u) = \frac{\partial}{\partial u} A(x, u)$, i.e., a function measurable in x for all $u \in \mathbb{R}$ and \mathcal{C}^1 in u for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$;

(4 \tilde{h}_1) for any $\rho > 0$ we have that

$$\sup_{|u| \leq \rho} |A(\cdot, u)| \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3), \quad \sup_{|u| \leq \rho} |A_u(\cdot, u)| \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3);$$

(4 \tilde{h}_2) a constant $\alpha_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$A(x, u) \geq \alpha_0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3, \quad \text{for all } u \in \mathbb{R};$$

(4 \tilde{h}_3) some constants $\mu > 2$ and $\alpha_1 > 0$ exist so that

$$(\mu - 2)A(x, u) - A_u(x, u)u \geq \alpha_1 A(x, u) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3, \quad \text{for all } u \in \mathbb{R};$$

(4 \tilde{h}_4) a constant $\alpha_2 > 0$ exists such that

$$2A(x, u) + A_u(x, u)u \geq \alpha_2 A(x, u) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3, \quad \text{for all } u \in \mathbb{R}.$$

On the other hand, we suppose that the nonlinear term $f : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ may satisfy the following hypotheses:

(f_0) $f(x, u)$ is a Carathéodory function;

(f_1) $a_1, a_2 > 0$ and $q \geq 2$ exist such that

$$|f(x, u)| \leq a_1|u| + a_2|u|^{q-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3, \quad \text{for all } u \in \mathbb{R};$$

(f_2) $\limsup_{u \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(x, u)}{u} = \bar{\alpha} < \frac{1}{\tau_2^2}$ uniformly a.e. with respect to $x \in \mathbb{R}^3$;

(f_3) a constant $\mu > 2$ exists such that

$$0 < \mu F(x, u) \leq f(x, u)u \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3, \text{ for all } u \neq 0;$$

where $\tau_2 > 0$ is so that (4.2.15) holds with $r = 2$.

Remark 4.17. From hypotheses (f_0), (f_1), we infer that

$$F : (x, u) \in \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto \int_0^u f(x, t) dt \in \mathbb{R}$$

is a well defined \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function. Moreover, assumption (f_1) establishes also that

$$F(x, 0) = f(x, 0) = 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3. \quad (4.2.17)$$

Thus, from [CS3, Theorem 4.4] with $p = 2$ and $N = 3$, hence $p^* = 6$, the following result can be stated.

Theorem 4.6. *Under assumptions (V_1)–(V_3), ($4\tilde{h}_0$)–($4\tilde{h}_4$) and (f_0)–(f_3), so that the same μ satisfies both ($4\tilde{h}_3$) and (f_3), and the growth exponent q in (f_1) is such that*

$$q < 6,$$

then problem (4.2.10) admits at least one weak nontrivial bounded solution.

Remark 4.18. If q is as in (f_1) and μ is as in (f_3), then in the hypotheses of Theorem 4.6 it has to be $\mu \leq q$, hence we have that

$$2 < \mu \leq q < 6.$$

We recall that the existence of solutions of equation (4.2.10) is obtained by means of a variational approach. More precisely, the hypotheses (V_1), ($4\tilde{h}_0$)–($4\tilde{h}_1$) and (f_0)–(f_1) allow us to state a good variational principle so that we have to look for critical points of the functional

$$\mathcal{J}_*(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} A(x, u) |\nabla u|^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} V(x) u^2 dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} F(x, u) dx \quad (4.2.18)$$

which is well defined and of class \mathcal{C}^1 in the Banach space X defined in (4.2.16) (see [CS3, Proposition 3.10]).

Unluckily, due to the intersection norm in (4.2.16) which involves both the $H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3)$ -norm and the $L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3)$ one, functional \mathcal{J}_* cannot satisfy the classical Palais–Smale condition (or its variants) in X even if we replace the whole Euclidean space with one bounded subset (see [54, Example 4.3]), so we have to consider the weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition and consider X equipped with two different norms, namely $\|\cdot\|_X$ and $\|\cdot\|_V$.

The idea of the proof of Theorem 4.6 relies also on an approximation argument as a sequence $(u_k)_k$ is found so that for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ function u_k is a weak bounded solution of equation (4.2.10) but in the open ball B_k with Dirichlet boundary condition $u_k = 0$ on ∂B_k . Then, a nontrivial critical point for \mathcal{J}_* in X is constructed as a suitable limit of sequence $(u_k)_k$.

4.2.2 An existence result

Now, we are ready to state the main existence result for problem (4.2.1) which is considered a particular case of equation (4.2.10).

Theorem 4.7. *Assume that potential $V(x)$ satisfies conditions (V_1) – (V_3) and that the nonlinear term $f(x, u)$ is so that hypotheses (f_0) – (f_3) hold. Moreover, let us consider a function $l : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that:*

(\mathcal{H}_0) $l(s)$ is of class \mathcal{C}^2 on \mathbb{R}_+ ;

(\mathcal{H}_1) $l'(s)l''(s) \leq 0$ for all $s \geq 0$;

(\mathcal{H}_2) a constant $\alpha_* > 0$ exists such that

$$[l'(s)]^2 + sl'(s)l''(s) \geq \alpha_*[l'(s)]^2 \quad \text{for all } s \geq 0.$$

If q in (f_1) and μ in (f_3) are such that (4.2.11) is verified then, taking $g(u)$ as in (4.2.4), problem (4.2.1) admits at least one weak nontrivial bounded solution.

Proof. Taking $A(x, u) = g^2(u)$, from (4.2.4) we have that

$$A(x, u) = 1 + 2u^2[l'(u^2)]^2, \quad A_u(x, u) = 4u([l'(u^2)]^2 + 2u^2l'(u^2)l''(u^2)), \quad (4.2.19)$$

then $A(x, u) \equiv A(u) \geq 1$ for all $u \in \mathbb{R}$ and assumption (\mathcal{H}_0) implies that $A(x, u)$ satisfies conditions $(4\tilde{h}_0)$ – $(4\tilde{h}_2)$.

On the other hand, in our setting $(4\tilde{h}_3)$ reduces to

$$\mu - 2 + 2(\mu - 4)u^2[l'(u^2)]^2 - 4u^4l'(u^2)l''(u^2) \geq \alpha_1 + 2\alpha_1u^2[l'(u^2)]^2 \quad \text{for all } u \in \mathbb{R},$$

and a suitable $\alpha_1 > 0$ exists if (\mathcal{H}_1) holds just taking any $\mu > 4$, in particular taking μ as in (f_3) so that (4.2.11) is satisfied.

At last, direct computations and (4.2.19) allow us to prove that $(4\tilde{h}_4)$ follows from (\mathcal{H}_2) . Hence, the existence result for problem (4.2.1) is a corollary of Theorem 4.6. \square

Remark 4.19. As already pointed out, the weak solutions of (4.2.10) we look for are critical points of \mathcal{J}_* defined in X as in (4.2.18). Thus, in the setting of equation (4.2.1), if hypotheses (V_1) , (\mathcal{H}_0) and (f_0) – (f_1) hold, such a functional reduces to

$$\mathcal{J}(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} g^2(u) |\nabla u|^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} V(x)u^2 dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} F(x, u) dx \quad (4.2.20)$$

which is of class \mathcal{C}^1 in X with Fréchet differential in u along the direction v given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d\mathcal{J}(u), v \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} g^2(u) \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} g(u)g'(u)v |\nabla u|^2 dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} V(x)uv dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f(x, u)v dx \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.21)$$

for any $u, v \in X$ (see [CS3, Proposition 3.10]).

At the beginning of this Section we have justified the importance of equation (4.2.1) by means of its connections to the quasilinear Schrödinger equation (4.2.2), in particular pointing out the stationary Schrödinger problem (4.2.3). Then, to consider its possible applications, we have to look for positive solutions of (4.2.1), i.e., we have to solve problem

$$\begin{cases} -\operatorname{div}(g^2(u)\nabla u) + g(u)g'(u)|\nabla u|^2 + V(x)u = f(x, u) & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3, \\ u > 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^3. \end{cases} \quad (4.2.22)$$

To this aim, we need the following Harnack type inequality for weak solutions of p -Laplacian type equations that we adapt to our setting (see [181, Theorem 1.1]).

Lemma 4.6. *Taking $p > 1$ and Ω domain in \mathbb{R}^N , let $\bar{u} \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ be a weak solution of the equation*

$$-\operatorname{div}(a(x, u, \nabla u)) = h(x, u, \nabla u) \quad \text{in a cube } K(3r) \subset \Omega.$$

Assume that $M > 0$ exists such that $0 \leq \bar{u}(x) < M$ for a.e. $x \in K(3r)$. If some constants $b_i \geq 0$, eventually depending on M , exist such that

$$\begin{aligned} |a(x, t, \xi)| &\leq b_0 |\xi|^{p-1} + b_1 |t|^{p-1}, \\ a(x, t, \xi) \cdot \xi &\geq |\xi|^p - b_2 |t|^p, \\ |h(x, t, \xi)| &\leq b_3 |\xi|^p + b_4 |\xi|^{p-1} + b_5 |t|^{p-1} \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.23)$$

for a.e. $x \in \Omega$ and all $(t, \xi) \in]-M, M[\times \mathbb{R}^3$, then

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{x \in K(r)} \bar{u}(x) \leq C \operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in K(r)} \bar{u}(x),$$

where C depends only on N, p, M, r and the constants which appear in the hypotheses.

So, we can state and prove the existence result for positive solutions of (4.2.1).

Theorem 4.8. *Assume that potential $V(x)$ satisfies conditions (V_1) – (V_3) and a given function $l : \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is such that (\mathcal{H}_0) – (\mathcal{H}_2) hold. Then, if the nonlinear term $f(x, u)$ is so that hypotheses (f_0^+) – (f_3^+) are verified with q and μ satisfying estimate (4.2.11), taking $g(u)$ as in (4.2.4), equation (4.2.1) admits at least one weak bounded strictly positive solution, i.e., problem (4.2.22) has a solution.*

Proof. In the hypotheses (f_0^+) – (f_3^+) , we can consider the function $f_+ : \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined as

$$f_+(x, u) = \begin{cases} f(x, u) & \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3, \text{ all } u \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3, \text{ all } u < 0, \end{cases}$$

and its related primitive

$$F_+(x, u) = \int_0^u f_+(x, t) dt = \begin{cases} F(x, u) & \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3, \text{ all } u \geq 0, \\ 0 & \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3, \text{ all } u < 0. \end{cases}$$

Hence, direct computations allow one to check that $f_+(x, u)$ and $F_+(x, u)$ satisfy assumptions (f_0) – (f_2) while the “partial condition” in (f_3^+) is enough for replacing (f_3) still obtaining the existence of a critical point of the C^1 functional

$$\mathcal{J}_+(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} g^2(u) |\nabla u|^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} V(x) u^2 dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} F_+(x, u) dx$$

in the Banach space X defined in (4.2.16) (see Remark 4.19). We note that, for any $u, v \in X$, its Fréchet differential is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d\mathcal{J}_+(u), v \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} g^2(u) \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} g(u) g'(u) v |\nabla u|^2 dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} V(x) u v dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f_+(x, u) v dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.2.24)$$

Now, let $\bar{u} \in X$ be a critical point of \mathcal{J}_+ in X . We claim that it is $\bar{u} \geq 0$ a.e. in \mathbb{R}^3 ; hence, $\mathcal{J}(\bar{u}) = \mathcal{J}_+(\bar{u})$ and \bar{u} is a critical point for the functional (4.2.20), too. The proof is similar to that one of [59, Proposition 4.5], but, for completeness, we give here the details.

Firstly, we note that, from (\mathcal{H}_0) and (4.2.5) some constants $M > 0$ and $k_M > 0$ exist such that

$$|\bar{u}|_\infty \leq M, \quad \max_{|t| \leq M} |g(t)g'(t)| \leq k_M, \quad (4.2.25)$$

which imply that

$$|g(\bar{u}(x))g'(\bar{u}(x))| \leq k_M \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3. \quad (4.2.26)$$

Then, let us consider the real map

$$\psi(t) = te^{\eta t^2}, \quad \text{with } \eta > \left(\frac{k_M}{2}\right)^2 > 0,$$

so, by definition, we have that $\psi(t)$ is a smooth odd function such that

$$t\psi(t) \geq t^2 \geq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \psi'(t) - k_M|\psi(t)| > \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.2.27)$$

Now, if $\bar{u}_- = \max\{-\bar{u}, 0\}$, we have that

$$\bar{u} = -\bar{u}_- \text{ in } \Omega_- = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \bar{u}(x) \leq 0\} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{u}_- = 0 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \Omega_-. \quad (4.2.28)$$

Moreover, it is $\psi(-\bar{u}_-) \in X$. Hence, from $d\mathcal{J}_+(\bar{u}) = 0$, taking $v = \psi(-\bar{u}_-)$ in (4.2.24) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} \psi'(-\bar{u}_-) g^2(\bar{u}) \nabla \bar{u} \cdot \nabla (-\bar{u}_-) dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} g(\bar{u}) g'(\bar{u}) \psi(-\bar{u}_-) |\nabla \bar{u}|^2 dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} V(x) \bar{u} \psi(-\bar{u}_-) dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f_+(x, \bar{u}) \psi(-\bar{u}_-) dx, \end{aligned}$$

where from (4.2.28) it follows that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^3} f_+(x, \bar{u})\psi(-\bar{u}_-)dx = 0.$$

Thus, (4.2.4), (4.2.26)–(4.2.28), (V_1) and direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \int_{\Omega_-} \psi'(-\bar{u}_-)g^2(-\bar{u}_-)|\nabla(-\bar{u}_-)|^2 dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\Omega_-} g(-\bar{u}_-)g'(-\bar{u}_-)\psi(-\bar{u}_-)|\nabla(-\bar{u}_-)|^2 dx + \int_{\Omega_-} V(x)(-\bar{u}_-)\psi(-\bar{u}_-)dx \\ &\geq \int_{\Omega_-} (\psi'(\bar{u}) - k_M|\psi(\bar{u})|)|\nabla(\bar{u})|^2 dx + \int_{\Omega_-} V(x)(-\bar{u}_-)\psi(-\bar{u}_-)dx \\ &\geq \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega_-} |\nabla(\bar{u})|^2 dx + \int_{\Omega_-} V(x)|\bar{u}|^2 dx \geq \frac{1}{2} \|\bar{u}_-\|_V^2 \end{aligned}$$

which provides that $\bar{u}_- = 0$ a.e. in \mathbb{R}^3 .

Thus, we have proved that $\bar{u} \in X$ is a nontrivial weak solution of (4.2.1) with $\bar{u} \geq 0$ a.e. in \mathbb{R}^3 and, to prove $\bar{u} > 0$ a.e. in \mathbb{R}^3 , we have to apply Lemma 4.6 with $N = 3$, $p = 2$, $\Omega = \mathbb{R}^3$ and

$$a(x, t, \xi) = g^2(t)\xi, \quad h(x, t, \xi) = -g(t)g'(t)|\xi|^2 - V(x)t + f_+(x, t)$$

as $f_+(x, \bar{u}) = f(x, \bar{u})$ a.e. in \mathbb{R}^3 .

To this aim, taking any cube $K(3r)$ in \mathbb{R}^3 with center in the origin, from (\mathcal{H}_0) , (V_1) , (V_3) , (f_1^+) , (4.2.4), (4.2.25) and direct computations we have that conditions (4.2.23) hold with

$$b_0 = \max_{|t| \leq M} g^2(t), \quad b_3 = k_M, \quad b_5 = \operatorname{ess\,sup}_{x \in K(3r)} V(x) + a_1 + a_2 M^{q-2}, \quad b_1 = b_2 = b_4 = 0.$$

Then, arguing by contradiction, assume that $\bar{u} = 0$ in a set with positive 3-dimensional Lebesgue measure. Thus, $\bar{r} > 0$ exists so that for all $r \geq \bar{r}$ it results

$$\operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in K(r)} \bar{u}(x) = 0$$

which implies $\bar{u} = 0$ a.e. in $K(r)$ from Lemma 4.6. Hence, $\bar{u} = 0$ a.e. in \mathbb{R}^3 for the arbitrariness of the cube $K(r)$ and by a standard covering argument, in contradiction with \bar{u} nontrivial.

So, \bar{u} is a weak bounded strictly positive solution of (4.2.1). \square

Proof of Theorems 4.3 and 4.4. From (4.2.4) we have that problem (4.2.22) reduces to (4.2.7) if $l(s) = s$, respectively to (4.2.9) if $l(s) = \sqrt{1+s}$. Hence, since direct computations allow us to prove that both the functions $l(s) = s$ and $l(s) = \sqrt{1+s}$ satisfy conditions (\mathcal{H}_0) – (\mathcal{H}_2) , then Theorem 4.3, respectively Theorem 4.4, follows from Theorem 4.8. \square

As we have just proved Theorem 4.7 as a corollary of Theorem 4.6, in the final part of this section our we briefly outline the main arguments of a direct proof of Theorem 4.7 to point out both the variational approach and the approximating arguments we use.

Thus, from now on we assume that the hypotheses of Theorem 4.7 are satisfied and, as noted in Remark 4.19, from assumptions (V_1) , (\mathcal{H}_0) and (f_0) – (f_1) it follows that the weak (bounded) solutions of equation (4.2.1) are the critical points of the \mathcal{C}^1 functional $\mathcal{J} : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined in (4.2.20), on the Banach space X as in (4.2.16), with Fréchet differential given by (4.2.21).

On the other hand, for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ let us consider the open ball B_k with center 0 and radius k and define

$$X_k = X_{B_k} = H_{0,V}^1(B_k) \cap L^\infty(B_k)$$

endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_{X_k} = \|u\|_{B_k,V} + |u|_{B_k,\infty} \quad \text{for any } u \in X_k$$

and with dual space X'_k . Actually, since any function $u \in X_k$ can be trivially extended to a function $\tilde{u} \in X$ just assuming $\tilde{u}(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^3 \setminus B_k$, then

$$\|\tilde{u}\| = \|u\|_{B_k}, \quad \|\tilde{u}\|_V = \|u\|_{B_k,V}, \quad |\tilde{u}|_\infty = |u|_{B_k,\infty}, \quad \|\tilde{u}\|_X = \|u\|_{X_k},$$

where the norms $|\nabla u|_{B_k,2}$, $\|u\|_{B_k}$ and $\|u\|_{B_k,V}$ are equivalent since B_k is bounded and (V_3) holds.

So, if we consider the restriction

$$\mathcal{J}_k : u \in X_k \mapsto \mathcal{J}_k(u) = \mathcal{J}|_{X_k}(u) \in \mathbb{R},$$

we obtain that

$$\mathcal{J}_k(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{B_k} g^2(u) |\nabla u|^2 dx - \int_{B_k} \tilde{F}(x, u) dx, \quad u \in X_k,$$

where we take

$$\tilde{F}(x, u) = F(x, u) - \frac{1}{2} V(x) |u|^2 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3. \quad (4.2.29)$$

We note that, in hypotheses (V_1) , (V_3) and (f_0) – (f_3) the map

$$\tilde{f}(x, u) = f(x, u) - V(x)u \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad \text{all } u \in \mathbb{R},$$

is a Carathéodory function such that

$$|\tilde{f}(x, u)| \leq (a_1 + |V|_{B_k,\infty})|u| + a_2|u|^{q-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } B_k, \quad \text{for all } u \in \mathbb{R},$$

$$\limsup_{u \rightarrow 0} \frac{\tilde{f}(x, u)}{u} \leq \bar{\alpha} < \frac{1}{\tau_2^2} \quad \text{uniformly a.e. with respect to } x \in B_k,$$

and

$$0 < \mu \tilde{F}(x, u) \leq \tilde{f}(x, u)u \quad \text{a.e. in } B_k, \text{ for all } u \neq 0.$$

Thus, functional \mathcal{J}_k is \mathcal{C}^1 in X_k with Fréchet differential given by

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}_k(u), v \rangle = \int_{B_k} g^2(u) \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \int_{B_k} g(u) g'(u) v |\nabla u|^2 dx - \int_{B_k} \tilde{f}(x, u) v dx$$

for any $u, v \in X_k$. Moreover, from (4.2.4), (4.2.19) and properties (\mathcal{H}_0) – (\mathcal{H}_1) it satisfies the (*wCPS*) condition in \mathbb{R} (see [51, Proposition 3.4]).

Now, as in [CS3, Section 4], we claim that in our setting the geometrical assumptions required by Theorem 1.2 are satisfied but so to obtain some constants independent of the particular radius k of the bounded domain B_k .

In fact, $\varrho, \alpha^* > 0$ exist so that

$$u \in X, \|u\|_V = \varrho \quad \implies \quad \mathcal{J}(u) \geq \alpha^* \quad (4.2.30)$$

(see [CS3, Proposition 4.8]) Furthermore, fixing $\bar{u} \in X$ such that

$$\text{supp } \bar{u} \subset B_1 \quad \text{and} \quad |\Omega_1^{\bar{u}}| > 0, \quad \text{with} \quad \Omega_1^{\bar{u}} = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^3 : |\bar{u}(x)| > 1\},$$

it follows that

$$\mathcal{J}(s\bar{u}) \rightarrow -\infty \quad \text{as } s \rightarrow +\infty$$

(see [CS3, Proposition 4.9]). Thus, $\bar{s} > 0$ exists so that

$$\|u^*\|_V > \varrho \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}(u^*) < \alpha^*$$

with $u^* = \bar{s}\bar{u}$, $\text{supp } u^* \subset B_1$ and ϱ, α^* as in (4.2.30).

Clearly, for all $k \geq 1$ we have that $\text{supp } u^* \subset B_k$, so $u^* \in X_k$, and if we consider the segment joining 0 to u^* , namely

$$\gamma^* : s \in [0, 1] \mapsto su^* \in X,$$

we obtain that $\text{supp } \gamma^*(s) \subset B_k$ for all $s \in [0, 1]$. Hence, $\gamma^*([0, 1]) \subset X_k$ and then $\gamma^* \in \Gamma_k$, with

$$\Gamma_k = \{\gamma \in C([0, 1], X_{B_k}) : \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = u^*\},$$

and, for the continuity of $\mathcal{J} \circ \gamma^* : s \in [0, 1] \mapsto \mathcal{J}(su^*) \in \mathbb{R}$, $\alpha^{**} \in \mathbb{R}$ exists, independent of k , such that

$$\alpha^{**} = \max_{s \in [0, 1]} \mathcal{J}(su^*). \quad (4.2.31)$$

Moreover, from (4.2.17) and (4.2.29) we obtain $\mathcal{J}_k(0) = 0$. Thus, Theorem 1.2 applies to \mathcal{J}_k in X_k , and, for the arbitrariness of $k \in \mathbb{N}$, a sequence $(u_k)_k \subset X$ exists such that for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$ it results:

- (i) $u_k \in X_k$ with $u_k = 0$ in $\mathbb{R}^3 \setminus B_k$,
- (ii) $\alpha^* \leq \mathcal{J}(u_k) \leq \alpha^{**}$,
- (iii) $\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), v \rangle = 0$ for all $v \in X_k$,

with α^* as in (4.2.30) and α^{**} as in (4.2.31), both independent of k .

Then, as in [CS3, Propositions 6.3 and 6.4], a positive constant M_0 exists such that

$$\|u_k\|_X \leq M_0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Hence, a function $u_\infty \in H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3)$ exists such that, up to subsequences, also from (4.2.14) we have that

$$\begin{aligned} u_k &\rightharpoonup u_\infty && \text{in } H_V^1(\mathbb{R}^3), \\ u_k &\rightarrow u_\infty && \text{strongly in } L^2(\mathbb{R}^3), \\ u_k &\rightarrow u_\infty && \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^3. \end{aligned}$$

Actually, $u_\infty \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$, too (see [CS3, Proposition 6.5]); hence, by definition (4.2.16), we infer that $u_\infty \in X$.

Finally, as in [CS3, Propositions 6.8 and 6.9], we are able to prove that

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{strongly in } H_V^1(B_R) \text{ for all } R \geq 1$$

and also

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty), \varphi \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for all } \varphi \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3)$$

with $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3) = \{\varphi \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^3) : \text{supp } \varphi \subset\subset \mathbb{R}^3\}$.

Hence, $d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty) = 0$ in X and, by using again the compact embedding (4.2.14) and arguing by contradiction as in the proof of [CS3, Theorem 4.4], we are able to prove that u_∞ is a nontrivial weak solution of equation (4.2.1).

4.3 Generalized (p, q) -Laplacian equations on unbounded domains

In this section we study the existence of solutions for the generalized (p, q) -Laplacian equation

$$\begin{aligned} & -\operatorname{div}(A(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}A_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p - \operatorname{div}(B(x, u)|\nabla u|^{q-2}\nabla u) \\ & + \frac{1}{q}B_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^q + V(x)|u|^{p-2}u + W(x)|u|^{q-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \end{aligned} \tag{4.3.1}$$

where $1 < q \leq p \leq N$, $A, B : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory functions with $A_t(x, u) = \frac{\partial A}{\partial t}(x, u)$, $B_t(x, u) = \frac{\partial B}{\partial t}(x, u)$, $V, W : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are suitable potentials in a sense discussed later and $g : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a Carathéodory function. To motivate

the choice of this problem and highlight the relevance of our results, we present some examples which illustrate the equation covered in this chapter.

Firstly, we note that if $p = q$ equation (4.3.1) turns into the simplest one (4.0.1), i.e.

$$-\operatorname{div}(C(x, u)|\nabla u|^{p-2}\nabla u) + \frac{1}{p}C_t(x, u)|\nabla u|^p + Z(x)|u|^{p-2}u = g(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.3.2)$$

where we set $C(x, u) = A(x, u) + B(x, u)$ and $Z(x) = V(x) + W(x)$.

Moreover, if $p \neq q$, the interest in the study of the equation (4.3.1) is twofold. On the one hand, it is quite challenging from a mathematical viewpoint. On the other hand, equation (4.3.1) has several employments in the Applied Sciences. Observe that if $A(x, u) = B(x, u) \equiv 1$, (4.3.1) reduces to a classical (p, q) -Laplacian equation. In this case, a model of elementary particle physics was studied in [33]. However, some classical results about (p, q) -Laplacian problems in bounded or unbounded domains can be found, for example, in [5, 14, 30, 119, 147, 148, 157] and references therein.

Moreover, we figure it is worth to highlight the correlation with the well known Born-Infeld equation

$$-\operatorname{div}\left(\frac{\nabla u}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{1}{a^2}|\nabla u|^2}}\right) = f(u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.3.3)$$

with $a \in \mathbb{R}$. Equation (4.3.3) appears quite naturally in several fields such as electromagnetism and in relativity where it represents the mean curvature operator in Lorentz-Minkowski space. The relation between (4.3.1) and (4.3.3) is shown via the first order approximation of the Taylor expansion

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{1-x}} = 1 + \frac{x}{2} + \frac{3}{8}x^2 + \sum_{k=3}^{\infty} \binom{k - \frac{1}{2}}{k} x^k \quad \text{for } |x| < 1,$$

which makes equation (4.3.3) turn into

$$-\Delta u - \frac{1}{2a^2}\Delta_4 u = f(u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N$$

and exhibit a particular case of (4.3.1) with $p = 4$, $q = 2$, $A(x, u) = B(x, u) \equiv 1$ and $V(x) = W(x) \equiv 0$.

More in general, equation (4.3.1) has been used to model steady-state solutions of reaction-diffusion problems arising in biophysics, in plasma physics and in the study of chemical reaction design. The prototype for these models can be written in the form

$$-\Delta_p u - \Delta_q u + |u|^{p-2}u + |u|^{q-2}u = f(x, u) \quad \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N,$$

which originates from a general reaction-diffusion system

$$u_t = -\operatorname{div}(D(u)\nabla u) + g(x, u), \quad \text{with } D(u) = |\nabla u|^{p-2} + |\nabla u|^{q-2}.$$

In the above mentioned settings, the function u generally stands for a concentration, the term $\operatorname{div}(D(u)\nabla u)$ corresponds to the diffusion with coefficient $D(u)$, and $g(x, u)$

is the reaction term related to source and loss processes. Typically, in chemical and biological applications, the reaction term $g(x, u)$ is a polynomial of u with variable coefficients (see e.g. [70] and references therein).

Outlined the range of conceivable applications, from now on we assume $q < p$ and we consider equation (4.3.1) in its most general formulation. As (4.3.1) is settled in \mathbb{R}^N , the lack of compactness which occurs makes the classical variational tools difficult to handle. Here, we do not gain neither from symmetry assumptions (see [58]) nor from concentration compactness arguments (see [119]) but, drawing on the leading work [34], we enforce suitable assumption on the potentials $V(x), W(x)$, namely

$$\operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} V(x) > 0, \quad \operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} W(x) > 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{|x| \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{B_1(x)} \frac{1}{V(y)} dy = 0, \quad (4.3.4)$$

where $B_1(x)$ stands for the unitary sphere of \mathbb{R}^N centered in the point x .

As stated in [34, Theorem 3.1], hypothesis (4.3.4) assures a compact embedding in suitable weighted Lebesgue spaces on \mathbb{R}^N . On the other hand, even if problem (4.3.1) is characterized by the presence of two coefficient which depends on the solution itself, we give some sufficient conditions for recognizing the variational structure of problem (4.3.1), so that enquire its solutions shrinks to detect the critical points of a suitable nonlinear variational functional. We proceed introducing the necessary variational setting.

4.3.1 Variational setting

Although we have already introduced the embedding results in Section 4.1, for the sake of convenience we prefer to recall theme here.

Remark 4.20. Let $U : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a measurable function such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,inf}_{x \in \mathbb{R}^N} U(x) > 0. \quad (4.3.5)$$

Hence, the following continuous embeddings hold:

$$L_U^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq r < +\infty,$$

$$W_U^{1,r}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow W^{1,r}(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for all } 1 \leq r < +\infty. \quad (4.3.6)$$

Clearly, (4.3.6) holds also replacing \mathbb{R}^N with Ω open subset of \mathbb{R}^N with smooth boundary.

Theorem 4.9. *Let $U : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be a Lebesgue measurable function such that (4.3.5) holds. Then, the following continuous embeddings hold:*

- if $l < N$ then

$$W_U^{1,l}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } l \leq r \leq \frac{Nl}{N-l}; \quad (4.3.7)$$

- if $l = N$ then

$$W_U^{1,l}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } l \leq r < +\infty; \quad (4.3.8)$$

- if $l > N$ then

$$W_U^{1,l}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } l \leq r \leq +\infty. \quad (4.3.9)$$

Furthermore, if also

$$\int_{B_1(x)} \frac{1}{U(y)} dy \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } |x| \rightarrow +\infty,$$

the compact embedding

$$W_U^{1,l}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } l \leq r < l^* \quad (4.3.10)$$

holds true, with

$$l^* = \begin{cases} \frac{Nl}{N-l} & \text{if } l < N, \\ +\infty & \text{if } l \geq N. \end{cases}$$

In particular, from Theorem 4.9, it follows that for any $r \geq p$ so that (4.3.7), respectively (4.3.8) or (4.3.9), holds with $r = p$, then a constant $\tau_{r,V} > 0$ exists such that

$$|u|_r \leq \tau_{r,V} \|u\|_{V,p} \quad \text{for all } u \in W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N). \quad (4.3.11)$$

From now on, we suppose that:

(P₁) the potentials $V, W : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ are Lebesgue measurable functions such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,inf}_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) > 0, \quad \operatorname{ess\,inf}_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) > 0;$$

(P₂) it is

$$\int_{B_1(x)} \frac{1}{V(y)} dy \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{as } |x| \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Thereby, taking $p, q \in]1, +\infty[$, we can consider the weighted spaces $(W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N), \|\cdot\|_V)$ and $(W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N), \|\cdot\|_W)$.

From now on, we set

$$X := W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad (4.3.12)$$

endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_X := \|u\|_V + \|u\|_W + |u|_\infty \quad (4.3.13)$$

where, in order not to weigh down the notations, we denote

$$\|\cdot\|_V = \|\cdot\|_{V,p} \quad \text{and} \quad \|\cdot\|_W = \|\cdot\|_{W,q}. \quad (4.3.14)$$

Furthermore, Theorem 4.9 and definition (4.3.12) allow us to provide the following result.

Corollary 4.2. *If assumptions (P_1) – (P_2) hold, thus*

- i) $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \hookrightarrow (L^r(\mathbb{R}^N), |\cdot|_r)$ continuously for any $q \leq r \leq +\infty$;
- ii) $(X, \|\cdot\|_X) \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow (L^r(\mathbb{R}^N), |\cdot|_r)$ compactly for any $p \leq r < +\infty$.

Proof. The embedding i is trivially satisfied availing only of hypothesis (P_1) . On the other hand, if also (P_2) holds, from (4.3.12) and (4.3.10) it follows that

$$X \hookrightarrow\hookrightarrow L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad \text{for any } r \in [p, p^*[. \quad (4.3.15)$$

Now, let $r \geq p^*$ and $(u_n)_n \subset X$, $u \in X$ such that $u_n \rightharpoonup u$ in X . Thus, fixing any $\varepsilon > 0$ with $p < p^* - \varepsilon < p^*$, from (4.3.15) we have

$$|u_n - u|_r^r \leq |u_n - u|_\infty^{r-p^*+\varepsilon} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u_n - u|^{p^*-\varepsilon} dx \rightarrow 0$$

and then ii) is fully verified. □

We proceed providing a suitable decomposition for the spaces $W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ and X . We define the subset

$$\mathcal{S} = \{v \in W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) : |v|_p = 1\},$$

the functional $\Phi : W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ by

$$\Phi(u) = \|u\|_V^p$$

and

$$\eta_1 = \inf_{v \in \mathcal{S}} \Phi(v) \geq 0.$$

From (4.3.10), there exists $\psi_1 \in \mathcal{S}$ such that $\eta_1 = \Phi(\psi_1)$. Thus, starting from η_1 , the existence of a sequence of positive numbers $(\eta_j)_j$, such that

$$\eta_j \nearrow +\infty \quad \text{as } j \rightarrow +\infty \quad (4.3.16)$$

and whose corresponding functions are $(\psi_j)_j$, $\psi_j \neq \psi_k$, if $j \neq k$, is established (see, [52, Section 5]). Moreover, they generate the whole space $W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N)$. To be more precise, setting $Y_V^j = \text{span}\{\psi_1, \dots, \psi_j\}$ and denoting by Z_V^j its complement, for all $j \in \mathbb{N}$ the decomposition

$$W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) = Y_V^j \oplus Z_V^j$$

holds true. Moreover, availing of [52, Lemma 5.4], we recall the inequality

$$\eta_{j+1}|u|_p^p \leq \|u\|_V^p \quad \text{for all } u \in Z_V^j. \quad (4.3.17)$$

Now, setting

$$Z^j := Z_V^j \cap X, \quad (4.3.18)$$

we have that Z^j is a closed subspace of X of finite codimension. Then a finite dimensional subspace Y^j of X exists which is its topological complement, i.e. the decomposition

$$X = Y^j \oplus Z^j$$

holds true.

To bring out the variational nature of our problem, we introduce some preliminary assumptions. We assume that:

(4 \mathcal{h}_0) A and B are \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory functions;

(4 \mathcal{h}_1) for any $\rho > 0$ we have that

$$\begin{aligned} \sup_{|t| \leq \rho} |A(\cdot, t)| &\in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N), & \sup_{|t| \leq \rho} |A_t(\cdot, t)| &\in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N); \\ \sup_{|t| \leq \rho} |B(\cdot, t)| &\in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N), & \sup_{|t| \leq \rho} |B_t(\cdot, t)| &\in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N). \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, we assume that $g : \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ exists such that:

(4 g_0) $g(x, t)$ is a \mathcal{C}^0 -Carathéodory function;

(4 g_1) $a > 0$ and $p < s$ exist such that

$$|g(x, t)| \leq a(|t|^{p-1} + |t|^{s-1}) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Remark 4.21. Assumptions (4 g_0) and (4 g_1) imply that

$$G : (x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^N \times \mathbb{R} \mapsto \int_0^t g(x, s) ds \in \mathbb{R} \quad (4.3.19)$$

is a well defined \mathcal{C}^1 -Carathéodory function and

$$|G(x, t)| \leq \frac{a}{p}|t|^p + \frac{a}{s}|t|^s \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.3.20)$$

In particular, from (4.3.19) and (4.3.20) it follows that

$$G(x, 0) = g(x, 0) = 0 \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.3.21)$$

Let $u \in X$. Assumption (4 \mathcal{h}_1) and (4.3.12) ensure that both $A(\cdot, u)|\nabla u(\cdot)|^p \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$ and $B(\cdot, u)|\nabla u(\cdot)|^q \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$. On the other hand, embedding i) in Corollary 4.2 and hypotheses (4 g_0), (4 g_1) provide that $G(\cdot, u) \in L^1(\mathbb{R}^N)$, too. Thus, the functional

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u) &= \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u)|\nabla u|^p dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B(x, u)|\nabla u|^q dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u|^p dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x)|u|^q dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, u) dx \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.22)$$

is well defined for all $u \in X$. Furthermore, taking any $u, v \in X$, the Gâteaux differential of \mathcal{J} in u along the direction v is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d\mathcal{J}(u), v \rangle &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B(x, u) |\nabla u|^{q-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx \\ &+ \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A_t(x, u) v |\nabla u|^p dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B_t(x, u) v |\nabla u|^q dx \\ &+ \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u|^{p-2} u v dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) |u|^{q-2} u v dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u) v dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.23)$$

In particular, the following regularity result can be stated.

Proposition 4.11. *Suppose that hypotheses (P_1) , $(4\mathfrak{h}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{h}_1)$ and $(4\mathfrak{g}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{g}_1)$ hold. If $(u_n)_n \subset X$, $u \in X$ and $M > 0$ are such that*

$$\begin{aligned} u_n &\rightarrow u \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \\ \|u_n - u\|_V &\rightarrow 0, \quad \|u_n - u\|_W \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty, \\ |u_n|_\infty &\leq M \quad \text{for all } n \in \mathbb{N}, \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(u) \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n) - d\mathcal{J}(u)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty.$$

Hence, \mathcal{J} is a C^1 functional in X with Fréchet differential defined as in (4.3.23).

Proof. From definition (4.3.22), the desired result occurs by using same arguments as in [CS3, Proposition 3.10]. \square

4.3.2 Statement of the main existence and multiplicity results

From now on, besides hypotheses (P_1) – (P_2) , $(4\mathfrak{h}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{h}_1)$, $(4\mathfrak{g}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{g}_1)$ we consider the following additional conditions:

$(4\mathfrak{h}_2)$ a constant $\alpha_0 > 0$ exists such that

$$\begin{aligned} A(x, t) &\geq \alpha_0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \\ B(x, t) &\geq \alpha_0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}; \end{aligned}$$

$(4\mathfrak{h}_3)$ some constants $\mu > p$ (in particular it is $\mu > q$, too) and $\alpha_1 > 0$ exist so that

$$\begin{aligned} (\mu - p)A(x, t) - A_t(x, t)t &\geq \alpha_1 A(x, t) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \\ (\mu - q)B(x, t) - B_t(x, t)t &\geq \alpha_1 B(x, t) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}; \end{aligned}$$

$(4\mathfrak{h}_4)$ a constant $\alpha_2 > 0$ exists such that

$$\begin{aligned} pA(x, t) + A_t(x, t)t &\geq \alpha_2 A(x, t) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \\ qB(x, t) + B_t(x, t)t &\geq \alpha_2 B(x, t) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}; \end{aligned}$$

(4g₂) having μ as in hypothesis (4h₃), then

$$0 < \mu G(x, t) \leq g(x, t)t \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\};$$

(4g₃) taking α_0 as in assumption (4h₂) and $\tau_{p,V}$ as in (4.3.11), it is

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{g(x, t)}{|t|^{p-2}t} = \bar{\alpha} < \frac{\alpha_0}{\tau_{p,V}^p};$$

(P₃) for any $\varrho > 0$, a constant $C_\varrho > 0$ exists such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{|x| \leq \varrho} V(x) \leq C_\varrho \quad \text{and} \quad \operatorname{ess\,sup}_{|x| \leq \varrho} W(x) \leq C_\varrho.$$

Remark 4.22. If (4h₂) holds, then, without loss of generality, we can assume $\alpha_0 \leq 1$. Moreover, taking $t = 0$ in (4h₃), we have also $\mu - p \geq \alpha_1$.

Remark 4.23. From assumptions (4h₁), (4h₃) and direct computations we infer that

$$\begin{aligned} A(x, t) &\leq a_1 + a_2|t|^{\mu-p-\alpha_1} && \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \\ B(x, t) &\leq a_1 + a_2|t|^{\mu-q-\alpha_1} && \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \end{aligned}$$

where a_1, a_2 denotes two positive constants.

Remark 4.24. We note that (4.3.19), assumptions (4g₀)-(4g₂) and straightforward computations imply that for any $\varepsilon > 0$ a function $\eta_\varepsilon \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$ exists so that $\eta_\varepsilon > 0$ for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$ and

$$G(x, t) \geq \eta_\varepsilon(x)|t|^\mu \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N \text{ if } |t| \geq \varepsilon. \quad (4.3.24)$$

Furthermore, hypotheses (4g₀)-(4g₁) and (4g₃) imply that for any $\varepsilon > 0$ a constant $c_\varepsilon > 0$ exists such that

$$|g(x, t)| \leq (\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon)|t|^{p-1} + c_\varepsilon|t|^{s-1} \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}$$

and

$$|G(x, t)| \leq \frac{\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon}{p}|t|^p + \frac{c_\varepsilon}{s}|t|^s \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \text{ for all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.3.25)$$

Hence, from (4.3.20) and (4.3.24) it follows that

$$1 < q \leq p < \mu \leq s. \quad (4.3.26)$$

Thus, we are ready to state our existence and multiplicity results.

Theorem 4.10. *Suppose that assumptions (P₁)-(P₃), (4h₀)-(4h₄) and (4g₀)-(4g₃) hold with*

$$s < p^*. \quad (4.3.27)$$

Then problem (4.3.1) admits at least one weak nontrivial bounded solution.

Theorem 4.11. *Under the same hypotheses of Theorem 4.10, but replacing assumption $(4g_3)$ with the requirement that $g(x, \cdot)$ is odd, problem (4.3.1) has infinitely many weak bounded solutions whose critical levels positively diverge.*

Remark 4.25. If $q = p$, Theorem 4.10 has been already issued (see [CS3, Theorem 4.4]). On the other hand, the multiplicity result stated in Theorem 4.11 is completely new both in the case $q = p$ and $q \neq p$.

Remark 4.26. Taking μ as in $(4h_3)$, $(4g_2)$ and s as in $(4g_1)$, it follows by (4.3.26) and (4.3.27) that Theorems 4.10 and 4.11 hold with

$$1 < q \leq p < \mu \leq s < p^*.$$

Under the assumptions of Theorems 4.10 and 4.11, the following geometrical conditions can be provided.

Proposition 4.12. *Assume that hypotheses $(4h_0)$ - $(4h_1)$, $(4h_3)$, $(4g_0)$ - $(4g_2)$ and (P_1) hold. Thus, for any finite dimensional subspace $F \subset X$, we have*

$$\lim_{\substack{v \in F \\ \|v\|_X \rightarrow +\infty}} \mathcal{J}(v) = -\infty. \quad (4.3.28)$$

Proof. Suppose by contradiction that a finite dimensional subspace $F \subset X$ exists which does not serve condition (4.3.28), namely $(u_n)_n \subset F$ can be exhibited so that

$$\|u_n\|_X \rightarrow +\infty \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty \quad (4.3.29)$$

and for some $M > 0$ it is $\mathcal{J}(u_n) \geq -M$, for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Now, setting $v_n := \frac{u_n}{\|u_n\|_X}$ we have that $\|v_n\|_X = 1$ and a renamed subsequence exists such that $v_n \rightharpoonup v$ weakly in X . Actually, since F is a finite dimensional subspace, it follows that $v_n \rightarrow v$ strongly in X and almost everywhere in \mathbb{R}^N . Thus, in particular, it is $\|v\|_X = 1$ and, setting $A := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : v(x) \neq 0\}$, we have $|A| > 0$. Now, for a.e. $x \in A$, it is $\lim_n |v_n(x)| = |v(x)| > 0$ which, together with (4.3.29), ensures that $|u_n(x)| \rightarrow +\infty$. Hence, from (4.3.24) we obtain that

$$\lim_n \frac{G(x, u_n(x))}{|u_n(x)|^{\mu-\alpha_1}} |v_n(x)|^{\mu-\alpha_1} = +\infty \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in A, \quad (4.3.30)$$

where $\mu - \alpha_1 \geq p$ (see Remark 4.22). Now, since (4.3.29) holds, it is not binding to suppose $\|u_n\|_X \geq 1$ for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$. Thus, Remark 4.23, (4.3.13) and straightforward

computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^p + V(x) |u_n|^p) dx \\
 & + \frac{1}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (B(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^q dx + W(x) |u_n|^q dx) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{p} \left(a_1 \|u_n\|_V^p + a_2 |u_n|_\infty^{\mu-p-\alpha_1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_n|^p dx \right) \\
 & + \frac{1}{q} \left(a_1 \|u_n\|_W^q + a_2 |u_n|_\infty^{\mu-q-\alpha_1} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_n|^q dx \right) \\
 & \leq \frac{1}{p} (a_1 \|u_n\|_X^p + a_2 \|u_n\|_X^{\mu-\alpha_1}) + \frac{1}{q} (a_1 \|u_n\|_X^q + a_2 \|u_n\|_X^{\mu-\alpha_1}) \\
 & \leq \frac{2}{q} (a_1 + a_2) \|u_n\|_X^{\mu-\alpha_1}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.3.31}$$

Summing up, from (4.3.22), (4.3.31), hypothesis $(4g_2)$ and Fatou's Lemma we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 0 & = \lim_n \frac{-M}{\|u_n\|_X^{\mu-\alpha_1}} \leq \limsup_n \frac{\mathcal{J}(u_n)}{\|u_n\|_X^{\mu-\alpha_1}} \\
 & \leq \limsup_n \left(\frac{2}{q} (a_1 + a_2) - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \frac{G(x, u_n(x))}{\|u_n\|_X^{\mu-\alpha_1}} dx \right) \\
 & \leq \frac{2}{q} (a_1 + a_2) - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \liminf_n \frac{G(x, u_n(x))}{|u_n(x)|^{\mu-\alpha_1}} |v_n(x)|^{\mu-\alpha_1} dx.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then it is

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \liminf_n \frac{G(x, u_n(x))}{|u_n(x)|^{\mu-\alpha_1}} |v_n(x)|^{\mu-\alpha_1} dx \leq \frac{2}{q} (a_1 + a_2),$$

which denies (4.3.30) as $|A| > 0$. \square

Proposition 4.13. *Assume that $(4h_0)$ - $(4h_2)$, $(4g_0)$ - $(4g_1)$, $(4g_3)$ and (P_1) hold. Then two positive constants $\rho, \beta > 0$ exist so that*

$$\mathcal{J}(u) \geq \beta \quad \text{for all } u \in X \text{ with } \|u\|_V = \rho. \tag{4.3.32}$$

Proof. Let $u \in X$ and, from $(4g_3)$, take $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon < \frac{\alpha_0}{\tau_{p,V}^p}$, i.e.,

$$\alpha_0 - (\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon) \tau_{p,V}^p > 0. \tag{4.3.33}$$

Then, from $(4h_2)$ with $\alpha_0 \leq 1$ (see Remark 4.22), (4.3.22), (4.3.25) and (4.3.11) we have that

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathcal{J}(u) & \geq \frac{\alpha_0}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (|\nabla u|^p dx + V(x) |u|^p) dx + \frac{\alpha_0}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (|\nabla u|^q dx + W(x) |u|^q) dx \\
 & - \frac{\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u|^p dx - \frac{c_\varepsilon}{s} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u|^s dx \\
 & \geq \frac{1}{p} (\alpha_0 - (\bar{\alpha} + \varepsilon) \tau_{p,V}^p) \|u\|_V^p - \frac{c_\varepsilon}{s} \tau_{s,V}^s \|u\|_V^s.
 \end{aligned}$$

Then, (4.3.33) and $p < s$ allow us to find two positive constants ρ and β so that (4.3.32) holds. \square

Moreover, to prove Theorem 4.11, the following result is needed, too.

Proposition 4.14. *Suppose that assumptions $(4\mathfrak{h}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{h}_2)$, $(4\mathfrak{g}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{g}_1)$ and (P_1) – (P_2) hold. Fixing any $\beta > 0$, thus $j \in \mathbb{N}$ and ϱ sufficiently large exist such that*

$$\mathcal{J}(u) \geq \beta \quad \text{for all } u \in Z^j \text{ with } \|u\|_V = \varrho,$$

with Z^j as in (4.3.18).

Proof. Let $\beta > 0$ be fixed. Taking $u \in Z^j$, $j \in \mathbb{N}$, from (4.3.22), hypothesis $(4\mathfrak{h}_2)$, (4.3.20), (4.3.11), (4.3.17) and Hölder inequality we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}(u) &\geq \frac{1}{p} \left(\alpha_0 - \frac{a}{\eta_{j+1}} \right) \|u\|_V^p + \frac{\alpha_0}{q} \|u\|_W^q - \frac{a}{s} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u|^s dx \\ &\geq \frac{1}{p} \left(\alpha_0 - \frac{a}{\eta_{j+1}} - \frac{a\tau_{p^*,V}^{s-r}}{s\eta_{j+1}^{\frac{r}{p}}} \|u\|_V^{s-p} \right) \|u\|_V^p \end{aligned}$$

where r is taken in such a way that $\frac{r}{p} + \frac{s-r}{p^*} = 1$. Relying of (4.3.16), we can always choose ϱ large enough such that

$$\frac{\alpha_0}{2p} \varrho^p > \beta$$

and j large so that

$$\alpha_0 - \frac{a}{\eta_{j+1}} - \frac{a\tau_{p^*,V}^{s-r}}{s\eta_{j+1}^{\frac{r}{p}}} \varrho^{s-p} > \frac{\alpha_0}{2},$$

whence we obtain the desired result. \square

Lastly, we provide a convergence result in the whole \mathbb{R}^N .

Proposition 4.15. *Suppose that hypotheses (P_1) – (P_2) , $(4\mathfrak{h}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{h}_3)$, $(4\mathfrak{g}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{g}_2)$ hold. Thus, taking any $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$, we have that any $(CPS)_\gamma$ -sequence $(u_n)_n \subset X$ is bounded in $W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N)$. Furthermore, $u \in W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ exists such that, up to subsequences, the following limits hold:*

$$u_n \rightharpoonup u \text{ weakly in } W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N), \quad (4.3.34)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ strongly in } L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \text{ for each } r \in [p, p^*], \quad (4.3.35)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.3.36)$$

Proof. Taking $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$, let $(u_n)_n \subset X$ be a $(CPS)_\gamma$ -sequence of \mathcal{J} , i.e.,

$$\mathcal{J}(u_n) \rightarrow \gamma \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}(u_n)\|_{X'}(1 + \|u_n\|_X) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (4.3.37)$$

Thus, from (4.3.22), (4.3.23), (4.3.37), assumptions $(4\mathfrak{h}_2)$ – $(4\mathfrak{h}_3)$, $(4\mathfrak{g}_2)$ and also (0.0.5), direct computations imply that

$$\begin{aligned} \mu\gamma + \varepsilon_n &= \mu\mathcal{J}(u_n) - \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_n), u_n \rangle \geq \frac{\alpha_0\alpha_1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_n|^p dx + \frac{\mu-p}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u_n|^p dx \\ &\quad + \frac{\alpha_0\alpha_1}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_n|^q dx + \frac{\mu-q}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x)|u_n|^q dx. \end{aligned}$$

It follows, in particular, that $(u_n)_n$ is bounded in the reflexive Banach space $W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ and then we have (4.3.34). At last, since

$$W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N) \hookrightarrow W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N),$$

we gain the claimed result by using (4.3.10) with $l = p$. \square

4.3.3 Changeover through bounded domains

From now on, let Ω denote an open bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N . Thus, we define

$$X_\Omega = W_{0,V}^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap W_{0,W}^{1,q}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega) \quad (4.3.38)$$

endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_{X_\Omega} = \|u\|_{\Omega,V} + \|u\|_{\Omega,W} + |u|_{\Omega,\infty} \quad \text{for any } u \in X_\Omega$$

where, matching with the notations used in (4.3.14), we set

$$\|\cdot\|_{\Omega,V} = \|\cdot\|_{\Omega,V,p} \quad \text{and} \quad \|\cdot\|_{\Omega,W} = \|\cdot\|_{\Omega,W,q}.$$

We denote by X'_Ω the dual space of X .

Remark 4.27. As Ω is a bounded domain, not only $\|u\|_{\Omega,p}$ and $|\nabla u|_{\Omega,p}$ are equivalent norms but also, if assumption (P_3) holds, a constant $c_\Omega \geq 1$ exists such that

$$\|u\|_{\Omega,V,p}^p = \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^p dx + \int_{\Omega} V(x)|u|^p dx \leq \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^p dx + c_\Omega \int_{\Omega} |u|^p dx \leq c_\Omega \|u\|_{\Omega,p}^p.$$

Hence, Remark 4.20 implies that the norms $\|\cdot\|_{\Omega,V,p}$ and $\|\cdot\|_{\Omega,p}$ are equivalent, too. Same arguments applies for the norms $\|\cdot\|_{\Omega,W,q}$ and $\|\cdot\|_{\Omega,q}$.

Moreover, since definition (4.3.38) holds with $1 < q \leq p$ and Ω is a bounded domain, from now on we refer to X_Ω as

$$X_\Omega = W_{0,V}^{1,p}(\Omega) \cap L^\infty(\Omega)$$

which can be equipped with the norm

$$\|u\|_{X_\Omega} = \|u\|_{\Omega,p} + |u|_{\Omega,\infty} \quad \text{for any } u \in X_\Omega.$$

Actually, since any function $u \in X_\Omega$ can be trivially extended to a function $\tilde{u} \in X$ just assuming $\tilde{u}(x) = 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega$, then

$$\|\tilde{u}\|_V = \|u\|_{\Omega, V}, \quad \|\tilde{u}\|_W = \|u\|_{\Omega, W}, \quad |\tilde{u}|_\infty = |u|_{\Omega, \infty}, \quad \|\tilde{u}\|_X = \|u\|_{X_\Omega}. \quad (4.3.39)$$

In this setting, (4.3.21) and (4.3.22) imply that the restriction of the functional \mathcal{J} to X_Ω , namely

$$\mathcal{J}_\Omega = \mathcal{J}|_{X_\Omega},$$

is such that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u) &= \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^p dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega B(x, u) |\nabla u|^q dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega V(x) |u|^p dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega W(x) |u|^q dx - \int_\Omega G(x, u) dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.40)$$

Remark 4.28. We note that, setting

$$\tilde{g}(x, t) = g(x, t) - V(x) |t|^{p-2} t - W(x) |t|^{q-2} t \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N, \quad \text{all } t \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (4.3.41)$$

from $(4g_0)$ and (P_1) we have that \tilde{g} is a C^0 -Caratheodory function such that

$$\tilde{G}(x, t) = \int_0^t \tilde{g}(x, s) ds = G(x, t) - \frac{1}{p} V(x) |t|^p - \frac{1}{q} W(x) |t|^q \quad (4.3.42)$$

for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$, all $t \in \mathbb{R}$. Then, by means of assumptions $(4g_1)$ and (P_3) , some positive constants \tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2 depending on Ω exist such that

$$|\tilde{g}(x, t)| \leq \tilde{a}_1 |t|^{s-1} + \tilde{a}_2 |t|^{q-1} \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega, \quad \text{all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.3.43)$$

In particular, from (4.3.40) and (4.3.42) the functional \mathcal{J}_Ω can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u) &= \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^p dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega B(x, u) |\nabla u|^q dx \\ &\quad - \int_\Omega \tilde{G}(x, u) dx, \quad u \in X_\Omega. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.44)$$

Hence, arguing as in [52, Proposition 3.1], it follows that $\mathcal{J}_\Omega : X_\Omega \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a C^1 functional and for any $u, v \in X_\Omega$, its Fréchet differential in u along the direction v is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \langle d\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u), v \rangle &= \int_\Omega A(x, u) |\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_\Omega A_t(x, u) v |\nabla u|^p dx \\ &\quad + \int_\Omega B(x, u) |\nabla u|^{q-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_\Omega B_t(x, u) v |\nabla u|^q dx \\ &\quad - \int_\Omega \tilde{g}(x, u) v dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.45)$$

We prove that the functional \mathcal{J}_Ω complies with Definition 1.2. For simplicity, here and in the following we use the notation $(\varepsilon_n)_n$ for any infinitesimal sequence.

Proposition 4.16. *Under assumptions (P_1) – (P_3) , $(4\mathfrak{h}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{h}_4)$ and $(4\mathfrak{g}_0)$ – $(4\mathfrak{g}_2)$, the functional defined in (4.3.40) satisfies the $(wCPS)$ condition in \mathbb{R} .*

Proof. Taking $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$, let $(u_n)_n \subset X_\Omega$ be a $(CPS)_\gamma$ -sequence, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_n) \rightarrow \gamma \quad \text{and} \quad \|d\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_n)\|_{X'_\Omega}(1 + \|u_n\|_{X_\Omega}) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{if } n \rightarrow +\infty. \quad (4.3.46)$$

We want to prove that $u \in X_\Omega$ exists such that

$$(i) \quad \|u_n - u\|_{\Omega, p} \rightarrow 0 \text{ (up to subsequences),}$$

$$(ii) \quad \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u) = \gamma, \quad d\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u) = 0.$$

The proof will be divided in the following steps:

1. $(u_n)_n$ is bounded in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$; hence, up to subsequences, $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ exists such that if $n \rightarrow +\infty$, then

$$u_n \rightharpoonup u \text{ weakly in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega), \quad (4.3.47)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ strongly in } L^r(\Omega) \text{ for each } r \in [1, p^*[, \quad (4.3.48)$$

$$u_n \rightarrow u \text{ a.e. in } \Omega. \quad (4.3.49)$$

2. $u \in L^\infty(\Omega)$;
3. having defined $T_k : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$T_k t = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } |t| \leq k \\ k \frac{t}{|t|} & \text{if } |t| > k \end{cases},$$

if $k \geq \|u\|_{\infty, \Omega} + 1$ then

$$\|d\mathcal{J}_\Omega(T_k u_n)\|_{X'_\Omega} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}_\Omega(T_k u_n) \rightarrow \gamma \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow +\infty;$$

4. $\|T_k u_n - u\|_{\Omega, p} \rightarrow 0$ if $n \rightarrow +\infty$; hence, (i) holds;
5. (ii) is satisfied.

Step 1. Let $\gamma \in \mathbb{R}$ be fixed and consider a sequence $(u_n)_n \subset X$ satisfying (4.3.46). Thus, from Remark 4.27 and same arguments as in Proposition 4.15, we infer that

$$\mu\gamma + \varepsilon_n \geq d_1 \|u_n\|_{\Omega, p}^p + d_2 \|u_n\|_{\Omega, q}^q.$$

It follows that $(u_n)_n$ is bounded in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ and then $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ exists so that, up to subsequences, (4.3.47)–(4.3.49) hold.

Step 2. If $u \notin L^\infty(\Omega)$, either

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_\Omega u = +\infty \quad (4.3.50)$$

or

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\Omega}(-u) = +\infty. \quad (4.3.51)$$

For example, suppose that (4.3.50) holds. Then, for any fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we have

$$|\Omega_k^+| > 0, \quad (4.3.52)$$

with $\Omega_k^+ := \{x \in \Omega \mid u(x) > k\}$. Now, we consider the new function $R_k^+ : t \in \mathbb{R} \mapsto R_k^+ t \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$R_k^+ t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \leq k \\ t - k & \text{if } t > k \end{cases}.$$

From (4.3.47), we have

$$R_k^+ u_n \rightharpoonup R_k^+ u \quad \text{in } W_0^{1,p}(\Omega).$$

Thus, by the sequentially weakly lower semicontinuity of $\|\cdot\|_{\Omega,p}$, it follows that

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla R_k^+ u|^p dx \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla R_k^+ u_n|^p dx,$$

i.e.,

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^p dx, \quad (4.3.53)$$

with $\Omega_{n,k}^+ := \{x \in \Omega \mid u_n(x) > k\}$. On the other hand, by definition, we have

$$\|R_k^+ u_n\|_{X_{\Omega}} \leq \|u_n\|_{X_{\Omega}}.$$

Hence, (4.3.46) implies that

$$|\langle d\mathcal{J}_{\Omega}(u_n), R_k^+ u_n \rangle| \rightarrow 0;$$

thus, from (4.3.52) an integer $n_k \in \mathbb{N}$ exists such that

$$|\langle d\mathcal{J}_{\Omega}(u_n), R_k^+ u_n \rangle| < |\Omega_k^+| \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (4.3.54)$$

We observe that, taking any $k \geq 1$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}$, from (4.3.41), (4.3.45), hypotheses (P_1) , $(4\mathfrak{h}_2)$ and $(4\mathfrak{h}_4)$ with $\alpha_2 < q < p$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
 \langle d\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_n), R_k^+ u_n \rangle &= \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \left(1 - \frac{k}{u_n}\right) \left(A(x, u_n) + \frac{1}{p} A_t(x, u_n) u_n\right) |\nabla u_n|^p dx \\
 &+ \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \frac{k}{u_n} A(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^p dx + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \left(1 - \frac{k}{u_n}\right) V(x) |u_n|^p dx \\
 &+ \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \left(1 - \frac{k}{u_n}\right) \left(B(x, u_n) + \frac{1}{q} B_t(x, u_n) u_n\right) |\nabla u_n|^q dx \\
 &+ \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \frac{k}{u_n} B(x, u_n) |\nabla u_n|^q dx + \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} \left(1 - \frac{k}{u_n}\right) W(x) |u_n|^q dx \\
 &- \int_{\Omega} g(x, u_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \\
 &\geq \frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{p} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^p dx + \frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{q} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^q dx - \int_{\Omega} g(x, u_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \\
 &\geq \frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{p} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^p dx - \int_{\Omega} g(x, u_n) R_k^+ u_n dx
 \end{aligned}$$

which, together with (4.3.54), implies

$$\frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{p} \int_{\Omega_{n,k}^+} |\nabla u_n|^p dx \leq |\Omega_k^+| + \int_{\Omega} g(x, u_n) R_k^+ u_n dx \quad \text{for all } n \geq n_k. \quad (4.3.55)$$

Now, from (4.3.49) and hypothesis $(4\mathfrak{g}_0)$, we have

$$g(x, u_n) R_k^+ u_n \rightarrow g(x, u) R_k^+ u \quad \text{a.e. in } \Omega.$$

Furthermore, since $|R_k^+ u_n| \leq |u_n|$ for a.e. $x \in \Omega$, by using assumption $(4\mathfrak{g}_1)$ and (4.3.48), we infer that $h \in L^1(\Omega)$ exists so that

$$|g(x, u_n) R_k^+ u_n| \leq d_3(|u_n|^s + |u_n|^p) \leq h(x) \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \Omega$$

see [46, Theorem 4.9]. Thus, Dominated Convergence Theorem applies and we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \int_{\Omega} g(x, u_n) R_k^+ u_n dx = \int_{\Omega} g(x, u) R_k^+ u dx. \quad (4.3.56)$$

Now, again hypothesis $(4\mathfrak{g}_1)$ and (4.3.27), (4.3.53), (4.3.55), (4.3.56) ensure that

$$\int_{\Omega_k^+} |\nabla u|^p dx \leq d_4 \left(|\Omega_k^+| + \int_{\Omega_k^+} |u|^s dx \right).$$

As this inequality holds for any $k \geq 1$, thus [52, Lemma 4.5] applies and then $\text{ess sup}_{\Omega} u$ is bounded, yielding a contradiction to (4.3.50).

Now, suppose that (4.3.51) holds; it implies that, fixing any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, it is

$$|\Omega_k^-| > 0 \quad \text{with } \Omega_k^- = \{x \in \Omega : u(x) < -k\}.$$

In this case, by replacing function R_k^+ with $R_k^- : t \in \mathbb{R} \mapsto R_k^- t \in \mathbb{R}$ such that

$$R_k^- t := \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \geq -k \\ t + k & \text{if } t < -k \end{cases},$$

we can reason as above so to apply again [52, Lemma 4.5] which yields a contradiction to (4.3.51). Then, it has to be $u \in L^\infty(\Omega)$.

The remaining Steps 3, 4, 5 can be addressed arguing as in [52, Proposition 4.6], just taking \tilde{g} as in (4.3.41) and considering the functional as in (4.3.44). \square

From now on, assume that $0 \in \Omega$. Then $\varepsilon^* > 0$ can be found so that $B_{\varepsilon^*}(0) \subset \Omega$.

Remark 4.29. Suppose that hypotheses of Proposition 4.12 hold. Thus, fixing $\bar{u} \in X \setminus \{0\}$ such that $\text{supp } \bar{u} \subset B_{\varepsilon^*}(0)$, a sufficiently large constant $\bar{\sigma}$ can be found such that

$$\|u^*\|_{\Omega, V} \geq \rho \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u^*) < \beta, \quad (4.3.57)$$

where $u^* = \bar{\sigma}\bar{u}$ and ρ, β comply with Proposition 4.13.

Proposition 4.17. *Under the assumptions of Theorem 4.10, there exists $\beta > 0$ such that the functional \mathcal{J}_Ω admits at least a critical point $u_\Omega \in X_\Omega$ satisfying*

$$\beta \leq \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_\Omega) \leq \sup_{\sigma \in [0, 1]} \mathcal{J}_\Omega(\sigma u^*).$$

Proof. Firstly, we observe that \mathcal{J}_Ω is a C^1 functional satisfying the weak Cerami–Palais–Smale condition (see Propositions 4.11 and 4.16) and by (4.3.21) we have $\mathcal{J}_\Omega(0) = 0$. Furthermore, from (4.3.39), (4.3.40) and Proposition 4.13 we infer the existence of $\rho, \beta > 0$ which does not depend on Ω and satisfy

$$\mathcal{J}(u) \geq \beta \quad \text{for all } u \in X_\Omega, \|u\|_{\Omega, V} = \rho.$$

Now, taking u^* as in Remark 4.29, from (4.3.57) we have that Theorem 1.2 applies to the functional \mathcal{J}_Ω in the Banach space $X_\Omega \hookrightarrow W_{0, V}^{1, p}(\Omega)$. Thus, a critical point $u_\Omega \in X_\Omega$ exists such that

$$\mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_\Omega) = \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma_\Omega} \sup_{\sigma \in [0, 1]} \mathcal{J}_\Omega(\gamma(\sigma)) \geq \beta,$$

with $\Gamma_\Omega = \{\gamma \in C([0, 1], X_\Omega) : \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = u^*\}$. Since we assumed $B_{\varepsilon^*}(0) \subset \Omega$, the claimed result follows by noting that the function

$$\gamma^* : \sigma \in [0, 1] \mapsto \sigma u^* \in X_\Omega$$

belongs to Γ_Ω . \square

Proposition 4.18. *Let the assumptions of Theorem 4.11 hold. Thus, for any $\beta > 0$, the functional \mathcal{J}_Ω admits at least a pair of symmetric critical points in X_Ω , whose corresponding critical level belongs to $[\beta, \beta^*]$, with β^* independent of Ω .*

Proof. As already mentioned in Proposition 4.17, the functional \mathcal{J}_Ω is of class \mathcal{C}^1 and satisfies the weak–Cerami–Palais–Smale condition. Moreover, as $g(x, \cdot)$ is odd, it follows from (4.3.40) that \mathcal{J}_Ω is even. Now, fixing $\beta > 0$, Propositions 4.12 and 4.14 guarantee that Theorem 1.4 applies. Hence, a pair $u_\Omega, -u_\Omega$ of critical points of \mathcal{J}_Ω exists such that

$$\beta \leq \mathcal{J}_\Omega(u_\Omega) \leq \sup_{Y^j} \mathcal{J}(u),$$

where Y^j is the topological supplement of Z^j in X , with j and Z^j as in Proposition 4.14. We note that $\sup_{Y^j} \mathcal{J}(u)$ is a real constant independent of Ω . \square

4.3.4 Existence and multiplicity over unbounded domains

Throughout this section, for each $k \in \mathbb{N}$, we consider as bounded set the open ball B_k , its related Banach space X_{B_k} as in (4.3.38) and the functional

$$\mathcal{J}_k : u \in X_{B_k} \mapsto \mathcal{J}_k(u) = \mathcal{J}_{B_k}(u) \in \mathbb{R}$$

with $\mathcal{J}_{B_k} = \mathcal{J}|_{B_k}$.

Remark 4.30. For the sake of convenience, if $u \in X_{B_k}$ we always consider its trivial extension to 0 in $\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_k$. Then, if we still denote such an extension by u , we have that $u \in X$, too. Moreover, from (4.3.21), definitions (4.3.22) and (4.3.40), respectively (4.3.23) and (4.3.45), imply that $\mathcal{J}_k(u) = \mathcal{J}(u)$, respectively

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}_k(u), v \rangle = \langle d\mathcal{J}(u), v \rangle \quad \text{for all } v \in X_{B_k}.$$

Now, suppose that the assumptions in Theorem 4.10 are satisfied. Since for all $k \in \mathbb{N}$ Proposition 4.17 applies to \mathcal{J}_k in X_{B_k} , from Remark 4.30 a sequence $(u_k)_k \subset X$ exists such that for every $k \in \mathbb{N}$ it results:

- (i) $u_k \in X_{B_k}$ with $u_k = 0$ in $\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_k$,
- (ii) $\beta \leq \mathcal{J}(u_k) \leq \sup_{\sigma \in [0,1]} \mathcal{J}(\sigma u^*) =: \beta^*$,
- (iii) $\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), v \rangle = 0$ for all $v \in X_{B_k}$,

where β and β^* are real constants which does not depend on k . The proof of Theorem 4.10 requires different steps. Firstly, we prove that sequence $(u_k)_k$ is bounded in X . To this aim, we will need Lemma 4.5.

Proposition 4.19. *A constant $M_0 > 0$ exists such that*

$$\|u_k\|_X \leq M_0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}. \tag{4.3.58}$$

Proof. From conditions (i) and (iii) we infer that

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), u_k \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (4.3.59)$$

Thus from (4.3.59), taking μ as in assumption (h_3) and arguing as in Proposition 4.15 we get

$$\mu\mathcal{J}(u_k) = \mu\mathcal{J}(u_k) - \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), u_k \rangle \geq d_1\|u_k\|_V^p + d_2\|u_k\|_W^q,$$

which, combined with condition (ii), ensures that

$$\|u_k\|_V + \|u_k\|_W \leq d_3 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (4.3.60)$$

In particular, from Remark 4.20, (4.3.14) and (4.3.60) we get

$$\|u_k\|_{B_{k,p}} \leq d_4 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (4.3.61)$$

Now, to obtain estimate (4.3.58), from definition (4.3.12) we need to prove that $(u_k)_k$ is a bounded sequence in $L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N)$, too. To this aim, we note that for a fixed $k \in \mathbb{N}$ either $|u_k|_\infty \leq 1$ or $|u_k|_\infty > 1$. If $|u_k|_\infty > 1$, then

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N} u_k > 1 \quad \text{and/or} \quad \operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N} (-u_k) > 1.$$

Assume that $\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N} u_k > 1$ and consider the set

$$B_{k,1}^+ = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : u_k(x) > 1\}.$$

From condition (i) we have that

$$B_{k,1}^+ \subset B_k,$$

moreover, $B_{k,1}^+$ is an open bounded domain such that not only $|B_{k,1}^+| > 0$ but also, by means of (4.3.6), it is

$$\begin{aligned} |B_{k,1}^+| &\leq \int_{B_{k,1}^+} (|u_k|^p + |u_k|^q) dx \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (|u_k|^p + |u_k|^q) dx \leq \|u_k\|^p + \|u_k\|^q \\ &\leq d_5(\|u_k\|_V^p + \|u_k\|_W^q). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, estimate (4.3.60) gives

$$|B_{k,1}^+| \leq d_6. \quad (4.3.62)$$

Now, for any $m \in \mathbb{N}$ we consider the new function $R_m^+ : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ defined as

$$t \mapsto R_m^+ t = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } t \leq m \\ t - m & \text{if } t > m \end{cases}.$$

Clearly, for any $m \geq 1$, we have that $R_m^+ u_k \in X_k$ and from condition (iii), (4.3.45) and hypotheses (V_1) , $(4\mathfrak{h}_2)$, $(4\mathfrak{h}_4)$ and same arguments as in Step 2 of Proposition 4.16, it follows that

$$0 = \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), R_m^+ u_k \rangle \geq \frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{p} \int_{B_{k,m}^+} |\nabla u_k|^p - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) R_m^+ u_k dx$$

i.e.,

$$\frac{\alpha_0 \alpha_2}{p} \int_{B_{k,m}^+} |\nabla u_k|^p dx \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) R_m^+ u_k dx, \quad (4.3.63)$$

with $B_{k,m}^+ = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^N : u_k(x) > m\}$. Clearly, it is $B_{k,m}^+ \subseteq B_{k,1}^+$ so from (4.3.62) we have that

$$|B_{k,m}^+| \leq d_7. \quad (4.3.64)$$

Since (4g₂) implies $g(x, t) > 0$ if $t > 0$ for a.e. $x \in \mathbb{R}^N$, then $g(x, u_k(x)) > 0$ for a.e. $x \in B_{k,m}^+$; so, hypothesis (4g₁) implies that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) R_m^+ u_k dx \leq \int_{B_{k,m}^+} g(x, u_k) u_k dx \leq 2a \int_{B_{k,m}^+} u_k^s dx,$$

which, together with (4.3.63), suggest

$$\int_{B_{k,m}^+} |\nabla u_k|^p dx \leq d_8 \int_{B_{k,m}^+} u_k^s dx \quad \text{for all } m \geq 1,$$

with $d_8 > 0$ independent of m and k . Then, since (4.3.27) holds, Lemma 4.5 applies with $\Omega = B_k$ and $d_9 > 1$ exists such that

$$\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{B_k} u_k \leq d_{10},$$

where the constant d_9 can be chosen independent of k as it only rely upon N, p, s, d_8 and a_0^* , with $a_0^* \geq \max\{d_7, d_4\}$ (see (4.3.61) and (4.3.64)).

Similar arguments apply if $\operatorname{ess\,sup}_{\mathbb{R}^N}(-u_k) > 1$. Then, summing up, $d_{10} \geq 1$ exists such that

$$|u_k|_\infty \leq d_9 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}$$

and (4.3.58) is complied. \square

From estimate (4.3.58) and (4.3.12) it follows that $u_\infty \in W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N)$ exists such that, up to subsequences,

$$u_k \rightharpoonup u_\infty \quad \text{weakly in } W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N). \quad (4.3.65)$$

Furthermore, from *ii*) in Corollary 4.2 it follows that, up to subsequences,

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{strongly in } L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \text{ for each } r \geq p; \quad (4.3.66)$$

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.3.67)$$

On the other hand, from (4.3.58) and (4.3.67), we have

$$u_\infty \in L^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) \quad (4.3.68)$$

(see [CS3, Proposition 6.5] for the details). Hence, by definition (4.3.12), $u_\infty \in X$.

Proposition 4.20. *We have that*

$$u_k \rightarrow u_\infty \quad \text{strongly in } W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N). \quad (4.3.69)$$

Proof. Following an idea introduced in [44], let us consider the real map $\psi(t) = te^{\eta t^2}$, where $\eta > (\frac{\beta_2}{2\beta_1})^2$ will be fixed once $\beta_1, \beta_2 > 0$ are chosen in a suitable way later on. By definition, we have that

$$\beta_1 \psi'(t) - \beta_2 |\psi(t)| > \frac{\beta_1}{2} \quad \text{for all } t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4.3.70)$$

Defining $v_k = u_k - u_\infty$, limit (4.3.65) implies that

$$v_k \rightharpoonup 0 \quad \text{weakly in } W_V^{1,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap W_W^{1,q}(\mathbb{R}^N), \quad (4.3.71)$$

while from (4.3.66), respectively (4.3.67), it follows that

$$v_k \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{strongly in } L^r(\mathbb{R}^N) \text{ for each } r \geq p; \quad (4.3.72)$$

respectively

$$v_k \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.3.73)$$

Moreover, from (4.3.68) and (4.3.58) we obtain that

$$v_k \in X \quad \text{and} \quad |v_k|_\infty \leq \bar{M}_0 \quad \text{for all } k \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (4.3.74)$$

with $\bar{M}_0 = M_0 + |u_\infty|_\infty$. Hence, from (4.3.74) we give

$$|\psi(v_k)| \leq \psi(\bar{M}_0), \quad 0 < \psi'(v_k) \leq \psi'(\bar{M}_0) \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.3.75)$$

while (4.3.73) implies

$$\psi(v_k) \rightarrow 0, \quad \psi'(v_k) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.3.76)$$

Thus, since $\psi(v_k) \in X_{B_k}$, from (iii) and (4.3.23) we infer that

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), \psi(v_k) \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi'(v_k) A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} \psi'(v_k) B(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^{q-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A_t(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) |\nabla u_k|^p dx \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B_t(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) |\nabla u_k|^q dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_k|^{p-2} u_k \psi(v_k) dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) |u_k|^{q-2} u_k \psi(v_k) dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.77)$$

We note that $(4g_0)$ - $(4g_1)$ together with (4.3.75), Hölder inequality, (4.3.7) (4.3.58), imply that

$$\left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) dx \right| \leq d_1 (|u_k|_p^{p-1} |v_k|_p^p + |u_k|_s^{s-1} |v_k|_s^s) \leq d_2 (|v_k|_p^p + |v_k|_s^s)$$

which, together with (4.3.72) ensures that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (4.3.78)$$

Moreover (4.3.58), assumptions $(4\mathfrak{h}_1)$ – $(4\mathfrak{h}_2)$ and direct computations give

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A_t(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) |\nabla u_k|^p dx \right| &\leq d_3 \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^p dx \\ &= d_3 \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla u_\infty dx \right) \\ &= d_3 \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx + \varepsilon_k. \end{aligned}$$

In fact, by means of Hölder inequality and (4.3.58) we have

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla u_\infty dx \\ &\leq d_4 \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)|^p |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_k|^p dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \\ &\leq d_5 \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)|^p |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \rightarrow 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.79)$$

as (4.3.75), (4.3.76) set off Dominated Convergence Theorem which ensures that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)|^p |\nabla u_\infty|^p dx \rightarrow 0.$$

Same arguments can be rearranged to prove that

$$\left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B_t(x, u_k) \psi(v_k) |\nabla u_k|^q dx \right| \leq d_6 \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\psi(v_k)| |\nabla u_k|^{q-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx + \varepsilon_k. \quad (4.3.80)$$

Then, back to (4.3.77), using estimates (4.3.78)–(4.3.80) and setting

$$h_k(x) = \psi'(v_k(x)) - d_7 |\psi(v_k(x))| \quad \text{for a.e. } x \in \mathbb{R}^N,$$

with $d_7 = \max \left\{ \frac{d_3}{p}, \frac{d_6}{q} \right\}$, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_k &\geq \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u_k) h_k(x) |\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B(x, u_k) h_k(x) |\nabla u_k|^{q-2} \nabla u_k \cdot \nabla v_k dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_k|^{p-2} u_k \psi(v_k) dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) |u_k|^{q-2} u_k \psi(v_k) dx. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.81)$$

On the other hand, taking $\beta_1 = 1$ and $\beta_2 = d_7$, from (4.3.75), (4.3.76) and direct computations we have that

$$h_k(x) \rightarrow 1 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \quad \text{and} \quad |h_k(x)| \leq \psi'(\bar{M}_0) + d_7 |\psi(\bar{M}_0)| \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N, \quad (4.3.82)$$

while from (4.3.70), it is

$$h_k(x) > \frac{1}{2} \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (4.3.83)$$

At last, back to (4.3.81), direct computations give

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_k \geq & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)) |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k \, dx \\ & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} h_k A(x, u_k) (|\nabla u_k|^{p-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla v_k \, dx \\ & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (h_k B(x, u_k) - B(x, u_\infty)) |\nabla u_\infty|^{q-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k \, dx \\ & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} h_k B(x, u_k) (|\nabla u_k|^{q-2} \nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{q-2} \nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla v_k \, dx \\ & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) (|u_k|^{p-2} u_k - |u_\infty|^{p-2} u_\infty) \psi(v_k) \, dx \\ & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_\infty|^{p-2} u_\infty \psi(v_k) \, dx \\ & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) (|u_k|^{q-2} u_k - |u_\infty|^{q-2} u_\infty) \psi(v_k) \, dx \\ & + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) |u_\infty|^{q-2} u_\infty \psi(v_k) \, dx \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.84)$$

where we have used (4.3.71) to infer that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u_\infty) |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k \, dx & \rightarrow 0, \\ \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B(x, u_\infty) |\nabla u_\infty|^{q-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k \, dx & \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, from Hölder inequality, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |(h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)) |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2} \nabla u_\infty \cdot \nabla v_k| \, dx \\ & \leq \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} |\nabla u_\infty|^p \, dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \|v_k\|_p \rightarrow 0, \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.85)$$

since assumption $(4\mathfrak{h}_0)$, (4.3.67) and (4.3.82) imply that

$$h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty) \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N,$$

while (4.3.58), (4.3.82), (4.3.68) and $(4\mathfrak{h}_1)$ give

$$|h_k A(x, u_k) - A(x, u_\infty)|^{\frac{p}{p-1}} |\nabla u_\infty|^p \leq d_8 |\nabla u_\infty|^p \quad \text{a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N.$$

Thus (4.3.85) follows by (4.3.72) and Dominated Convergence Theorem.

Moreover, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_\infty|^{p-2} u_\infty \psi(v_k) \, dx & \rightarrow 0, \\ \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) |u_\infty|^{q-2} u_\infty \psi(v_k) \, dx & \rightarrow 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.3.86)$$

In fact, via the identification

$$\varphi \in L_V^p(\mathbb{R}^N) \mapsto \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u_\infty|^{p-2}u_\infty \varphi \, dx \in \mathbb{R}$$

and Hölder inequality, we obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u_\infty|^{p-2}u_\infty \varphi \, dx \right| &\leq \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|\varphi|^p \, dx \right)^{\frac{1}{p}} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)|u_\infty|^p \, dx \right)^{\frac{p-1}{p}} \\ &\leq d_9 \|\varphi\|_V^{p-1}, \end{aligned}$$

i.e. $V(x)|u_\infty|^{p-2}u_\infty \in (L_V^p(\mathbb{R}^N))'$. Since the above argument can be redrafted to prove that $W(x)|u_\infty|^{q-2}u_\infty \in (L_W^q(\mathbb{R}^N))'$, we deduce from (4.3.71) that (4.3.86) holds true. Finally, summing up, from (4.3.83)–(4.3.86), assumption (P_1) , the definition of $\psi(v_k)$ and strong convexity of the power function with exponent $p, q > 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon_k &\geq \frac{\alpha_0}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (|\nabla u_k|^{p-2}\nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2}\nabla u_\infty) \, dx \\ &\quad + \frac{\alpha_0}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (|\nabla u_k|^{q-2}\nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{q-2}\nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla v_k \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)(|u_k|^{p-2}u_k - |u_\infty|^{p-2}u_\infty)v_k \, dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x)(|u_k|^{q-2}u_k - |u_\infty|^{q-2}u_\infty)v_k \, dx \geq 0. \end{aligned}$$

Hence we infer that both

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (|\nabla u_k|^{p-2}\nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{p-2}\nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla(u_k - u_\infty) \, dx &\rightarrow 0, \\ \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} (|\nabla u_k|^{q-2}\nabla u_k - |\nabla u_\infty|^{q-2}\nabla u_\infty) \cdot \nabla(u_k - u_\infty) \, dx &\rightarrow 0 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x)(|u_k|^{p-2}u_k - |u_\infty|^{p-2}u_\infty)(u_k - u_\infty) \, dx &\rightarrow 0, \\ \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x)(|u_k|^{q-2}u_k - |u_\infty|^{q-2}u_\infty)(u_k - u_\infty) \, dx &\rightarrow 0. \end{aligned}$$

Thus (4.3.69) holds. □

Proposition 4.21. *There is*

$$\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty), \varphi \rangle = 0 \quad \text{for all } \varphi \in C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) \tag{4.3.87}$$

with $C_c^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{\varphi \in C^\infty(\mathbb{R}^N) : \text{supp } \varphi \subset\subset \mathbb{R}^N\}$. Hence, $d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty) = 0$ in X .

Proof. Let $\varphi \in C_c^\infty(\Omega)$. Thus, a radius $R \geq 1$ exists such that $\text{supp } \varphi \subset B_R$. Now, for all $k \geq R$ we have that $\varphi \in X_k$ so (iii) holds and $\langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), \varphi \rangle = 0$. Moreover, (4.3.58), (4.3.67), Propositions 4.20 and 4.11, ensure that

$$\|d\mathcal{J}(u_k) - d\mathcal{J}(u_\infty)\|_{X'} \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty,$$

hence (4.3.87) holds. \square

Proof of Theorem 4.10. Thanks to Proposition 4.21, the statement of Theorem 4.10 is true if we prove $u_\infty \neq 0$.

Suppose by contradiction that $u_\infty = 0$. Thus, from assumption (4g₁) and (4.3.66) we have that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) u_k dx \rightarrow 0, \quad (4.3.88)$$

which, together with assumption (4g₂), ensures that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, u_k) dx \rightarrow 0. \quad (4.3.89)$$

Furthermore, from (4.3.23), (iii), (4h₄) and also (4h₂) it results

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \langle d\mathcal{J}(u_k), u_k \rangle = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^p dx + \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} A_t(x, u_k) u_k |\nabla u_k|^p dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_k|^p dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B(x, u_k) |\nabla u_k|^q dx + \frac{1}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} B_t(x, u_k) u_k |\nabla u_k|^q dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) |u_k|^q dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) u_k dx \\ &\geq \frac{\alpha_2 \alpha_0}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_k|^p dx + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} V(x) |u_k|^p dx + \frac{\alpha_2 \alpha_0}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |\nabla u_k|^q dx \\ &\quad + \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} W(x) |u_k|^q dx - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} g(x, u_k) u_k dx, \end{aligned}$$

which implies that

$$\|u_k\|_V^p + \|u_k\|_W^q \rightarrow 0 \quad \text{as } k \rightarrow +\infty \quad (4.3.90)$$

by means of (4.3.88). Hence, from (4.3.22), (4.3.89), (4.3.58), assumption (4h₁), and (4.3.90) we infer

$$\mathcal{J}(u_k) \leq d_1 (\|u_k\|_V^p + \|u_k\|_W^q) - \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} G(x, u_k) dx \rightarrow 0$$

in contradiction with the estimate in (ii). \square

Proof of Theorem 4.11. Fix $\beta > 0$. For any $k \in \mathbb{N}$, let u_k be the critical point established via Proposition 4.18. Thus, the sequence $(u_k)_k \subset X$ meets conditions (i)–(iii) and, in particular

$$\beta \leq \mathcal{J}(u_k) \leq \beta^*,$$

where β^* is independent of k . Arguing as done above, it follows that $u_\infty \in X$ exists which is a critical point for the functional \mathcal{J} . Clearly, Proposition 4.11 implies

$$\mathcal{J}(u_k) \rightarrow \mathcal{J}(u_\infty),$$

hence $\mathcal{J}(u_\infty) \geq \beta$. Summing up, for any $\beta > 0$, a critical point $u_\infty \in X$ exists with critical level greater or equal to β . By the arbitrariness of β , we obtain the claimed result. \square

PART II

**New existence results for local and
nonlocal critical elliptic problems**

New linking theorems and elliptic problems with jumping nonlinearities

In this chapter we present some new linking theorems needed to address semilinear critical growth elliptic problems with jumping nonlinearities.

Our aim is to study the existence of nontrivial solutions to critical growth elliptic problems with jumping nonlinearities such as

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = bu^+ - au^- + |u|^{2^*-2}u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (5.0.1)$$

where Ω is a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N , $N \geq 4$, $2^* = 2N/(N-2)$ is the critical Sobolev exponent, $a, b > 0$, and $u^\pm = \max\{\pm u, 0\}$ are the positive and negative parts of u , respectively. When $a = b = \lambda$, this problem reduces to the well-known Brézis-Nirenberg problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = \lambda u + |u|^{2^*-2}u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases} \quad (5.0.2)$$

(see [48]). It was shown in [48] that problem (5.0.2) has a positive solution when $0 < \lambda < \lambda_1$, where $\lambda_1 > 0$ is the first Dirichlet eigenvalue of $-\Delta$ in Ω . Capozzi et al. [64] have extended this result by proving the existence of a nontrivial solution when $N = 4$ and $\lambda > \lambda_1$ is not an eigenvalue, or $N \geq 5$ and $\lambda \geq \lambda_1$. The proofs of their results are based on a decomposition of $H_0^1(\Omega)$ into eigenspaces of $-\Delta$. In contrast, the asymptotic problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = bu^+ - au^- & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases} \quad (5.0.3)$$

associated with problem (5.0.1) is nonlinear and therefore its solution set is not a linear subspace of $H_0^1(\Omega)$ when it has nontrivial solutions. Therefore the arguments in [64] cannot be used to obtain nontrivial solutions of problem (5.0.1). We will show that the variational functional

$$E(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^2 dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx - \frac{1}{2^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx, \quad u \in H_0^1(\Omega)$$

associated with problem (5.0.1) admits, depending on the location of the point (a, b) in the plane, certain linking structures based on a splitting of $H_0^1(\Omega)$ into nonlinear submanifolds. We will show that problem (5.0.1) admits nontrivial solutions when (a, b) are located in certain regions of the plane by availing on some new linking theorems we prove in Section 5.2.

To state our results for problem (5.0.1), recall that the set $\Sigma(-\Delta)$ consisting of points $(a, b) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ for which problem (5.0.3) has a nontrivial solution is called the Dancer-Fučík spectrum of $-\Delta$ in Ω . Dancer [80, 81] and Fučík [104] recognized its significance for the solvability of the problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = bu^+ - au^- + f(u) & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases}$$

for a continuous function f satisfying $f(t)/t \rightarrow 0$ as $|t| \rightarrow \infty$. Denoting by (λ_l) the sequence of Dirichlet eigenvalues of $-\Delta$ in Ω , $\Sigma(-\Delta)$ contains the points (λ_l, λ_l) since problem (5.0.3) reduces to the Dirichlet eigenvalue problem for $-\Delta$ when $a = b$. When $N = 1$, Fučík showed in [104] that $\Sigma(-d^2/dx^2)$ consists of a sequence of hyperbolic-like curves passing through the points (λ_l, λ_l) , with one or two curves going through each point. When $N \geq 2$, $\Sigma(-\Delta)$ consists locally of curves emanating from the points (λ_l, λ_l) (see [49, 78, 84, 105, 124, 125, 135, 137, 164, 166]). In particular, Schechter showed in [166] that in the square

$$Q_l = (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}) \times (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}),$$

$\Sigma(-\Delta)$ contains two strictly decreasing curves

$$C_l : b = \nu_{l-1}(a), \quad C^l : b = \mu_l(a),$$

with

$$\nu_{l-1}(a) \leq \mu_l(a), \quad \nu_{l-1}(\lambda_l) = \lambda_l = \mu_l(\lambda_l),$$

such that the points in Q_l that are either below the lower curve C_l or above the upper curve C^l are not in $\Sigma(-\Delta)$, while the points between them may or may not belong to $\Sigma(-\Delta)$ when they do not coincide.

Using the previous notations, we provide our main existence theorems.

Theorem 5.1. *Let $N \geq 4$. If $(a, b) \in Q_l$ and*

$$b < \nu_{l-1}(a)$$

for some $l \geq 2$, then problem (5.0.1) has a nontrivial solution.

Theorem 5.2. *Let $N \geq 5$. If $(a, b) \in Q_l$ and*

$$b \geq \mu_l(a)$$

for some $l \geq 2$, then problem (5.0.1) has a nontrivial solution.

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS1].

5.1 Preliminaries on the Dancer-Fučík spectrum

In this preliminary chapter we briefly recall the construction of the minimal and maximal curves of the Dancer-Fučík spectrum in an abstract setting introduced in Perera and Schechter [153, Chapter 4]. Let H be a Hilbert space with the inner product (\cdot, \cdot) and the associated norm $\|\cdot\|$. Recall that an operator $\varphi : H \rightarrow H$ is monotone if $(\varphi(u) - \varphi(v), u - v) \geq 0$ for all $u, v \in H$ and that $\varphi \in C(H, H)$ is a potential operator if $\varphi = \Phi'$ for some functional $\Phi \in C^1(H, \mathbb{R})$, called a potential for φ . Assume that there are positive homogeneous monotone potential operators $p, n \in C(H, H)$ such that

$$p(u) + n(u) = u, \quad (p(u), n(u)) = 0 \quad \forall u \in H.$$

We use the suggestive notation $u^+ = p(u)$, $u^- = -n(u)$, so that

$$u = u^+ - u^-, \quad (u^+, u^-) = 0.$$

This implies

$$\|u\|^2 = \|u^+\|^2 + \|u^-\|^2, \tag{5.1.1}$$

in particular, $\|u^\pm\| \leq \|u\|$.

Let A be a self-adjoint operator on H with the spectrum $\sigma(A) \subset (0, \infty)$ and A^{-1} compact. Then $\sigma(A)$ consists of isolated eigenvalues λ_l , $l \geq 1$ of finite multiplicities satisfying $0 < \lambda_1 < \dots < \lambda_l < \dots$. Moreover, $D = D(A^{1/2})$ is a Hilbert space with the inner product

$$(u, v)_D = (A^{1/2}u, A^{1/2}v) = (Au, v)$$

and the associated norm

$$\|u\|_D = \|A^{1/2}u\| = (Au, u)^{1/2}.$$

We have

$$\|u\|_D^2 = (Au, u) \geq \lambda_1 (u, u) = \lambda_1 \|u\|^2 \quad \forall u \in H,$$

so $D \hookrightarrow H$, and the embedding is compact since A^{-1} is a compact operator. Let E_l be the eigenspace of λ_l ,

$$N_l = \bigoplus_{j=1}^l E_j, \quad M_l = N_l^\perp \cap D.$$

Then $D = N_l \oplus M_l$, $u = v + w$ is an orthogonal decomposition with respect to both (\cdot, \cdot) and $(\cdot, \cdot)_D$. Moreover,

$$\|v\|_D^2 = (Av, v) \leq \lambda_l(v, v) = \lambda_l \|v\|^2 \quad \forall v \in N_l \quad (5.1.2)$$

and

$$\|w\|_D^2 = (Aw, w) \geq \lambda_{l+1}(w, w) = \lambda_{l+1} \|w\|^2 \quad \forall w \in M_l. \quad (5.1.3)$$

We assume that $w^\pm \neq 0$ for all $w \in M_l \setminus \{0\}$. The set $\Sigma(A)$ consisting of points $(a, b) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ for which the equation

$$Au = bu^+ - au^-, \quad u \in D \quad (5.1.4)$$

has a nontrivial solution is called the Dancer-Fučík spectrum of A . It is a closed subset of \mathbb{R}^2 (see [153, Proposition 4.4.3]). Since equation (5.1.4) reduces to $Au = \lambda u$ when $a = b = \lambda$, $\Sigma(A)$ contains the points (λ_l, λ_l) .

It is easily seen that A is a potential operator with the potential

$$\frac{1}{2} (Au, u) = \frac{1}{2} \|u\|_D^2.$$

The potentials of p and n are

$$\frac{1}{2} (p(u), u) = \frac{1}{2} \|u^+\|^2, \quad \frac{1}{2} (n(u), u) = \frac{1}{2} \|u^-\|^2,$$

respectively (see [153, Proposition 4.3.2]). So solutions of equation (5.1.4) coincide with critical points of the C^1 -functional

$$I(u, a, b) = \|u\|_D^2 - a \|u^-\|^2 - b \|u^+\|^2, \quad u \in D,$$

and $(a, b) \in \Sigma(A)$ if and only if $I(\cdot, a, b)$ has a nontrivial critical point. Let

$$Q_l = (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}) \times (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}), \quad l \geq 2.$$

If $(a, b) \in Q_l$, then $I(v + y + w, a, b)$, $v + y + w \in N_{l-1} \oplus E_l \oplus M_l$ is strictly concave in v and strictly convex in w , i.e., for $v_1 \neq v_2 \in N_{l-1}$, $w \in M_{l-1}$,

$$I((1-t)v_1 + tv_2 + w, a, b) > (1-t)I(v_1 + w, a, b) + tI(v_2 + w, a, b) \quad \forall t \in (0, 1),$$

and for $v \in N_l$, $w_1 \neq w_2 \in M_l$,

$$I(v + (1-t)w_1 + tw_2, a, b) < (1-t)I(v + w_1, a, b) + tI(v + w_2, a, b) \quad \forall t \in (0, 1)$$

(see [153, Proposition 4.6.1]).

Proposition 5.1 ([153, Proposition 4.7.1, Corollary 4.7.3, & Proposition 4.7.4]). *Let $(a, b) \in Q_l$.*

- (i) There is a positive homogeneous map $\theta(\cdot, a, b) \in C(M_{l-1}, N_{l-1})$ such that $v = \theta(w, a, b)$ is the unique solution of

$$I(v + w, a, b) = \sup_{v' \in N_{l-1}} I(v' + w, a, b), \quad w \in M_{l-1}.$$

Moreover, θ is continuous on $M_{l-1} \times Q_l$, $\theta(w, \lambda_l, \lambda_l) = 0$ for all $w \in M_{l-1}$, and $I'(v + w, a, b) \perp N_{l-1}$ if and only if $v = \theta(w, a, b)$.

- (ii) There is a positive homogeneous map $\tau(\cdot, a, b) \in C(N_l, M_l)$ such that $w = \tau(v, a, b)$ is the unique solution of

$$I(v + w, a, b) = \inf_{w' \in M_l} I(v + w', a, b), \quad v \in N_l.$$

Moreover, τ is continuous on $N_l \times Q_l$, $\tau(v, \lambda_l, \lambda_l) = 0$ for all $v \in N_l$, and $I'(v + w, a, b) \perp M_l$ if and only if $w = \tau(v, a, b)$.

Let $S = \{u \in D : \|u\|_D = 1\}$ be the unit sphere in D . Set

$$n_{l-1}(a, b) = \inf_{w \in M_{l-1} \cap S} I(\theta(w, a, b) + w, a, b) \quad (5.1.5)$$

and

$$m_l(a, b) = \sup_{v \in N_l \cap S} I(v + \tau(v, a, b), a, b). \quad (5.1.6)$$

Since $I(u, a, b)$ is nonincreasing in a for fixed u and b , and in b for fixed u and a , $n_{l-1}(a, b)$ and $m_l(a, b)$ are nonincreasing in a for fixed b , and in b for fixed a . Moreover, n_{l-1} and m_l are continuous on Q_l and $n_{l-1}(\lambda_l, \lambda_l) = 0 = m_l(\lambda_l, \lambda_l)$ (see [153, Lemma 4.7.6 & Proposition 4.7.7]). For $a \in (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1})$, set

$$\nu_{l-1}(a) = \sup \{b \in (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}) : n_{l-1}(a, b) \geq 0\} \quad (5.1.7)$$

and

$$\mu_l(a) = \inf \{b \in (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}) : m_l(a, b) \leq 0\}. \quad (5.1.8)$$

Proposition 5.2 ([153, Theorem 4.7.9]). *Let $(a, b) \in Q_l$.*

- (i) ν_{l-1} is a continuous and strictly decreasing function, $\nu_{l-1}(\lambda_l) = \lambda_l$, $(a, b) \in \Sigma(A)$ if $b = \nu_{l-1}(a)$, and $(a, b) \notin \Sigma(A)$ if $b < \nu_{l-1}(a)$.
- (ii) μ_l is a continuous and strictly decreasing function, $\mu_l(\lambda_l) = \lambda_l$, $(a, b) \in \Sigma(A)$ if $b = \mu_l(a)$, and $(a, b) \notin \Sigma(A)$ if $b > \mu_l(a)$.
- (iii) $\nu_{l-1}(a) \leq \mu_l(a)$.

Thus,

$$C_l : b = \nu_{l-1}(a), \quad C^l : b = \mu_l(a)$$

are strictly decreasing curves in Q_l that belong to $\Sigma(A)$. They both pass through the point (λ_l, λ_l) and may coincide. The region $\{(a, b) \in Q_l : b < \nu_{l-1}(a)\}$ below the lower curve C_l and the region $\{(a, b) \in Q_l : b > \mu_l(a)\}$ above the upper curve C^l are free of $\Sigma(A)$. They are the minimal and maximal curves of $\Sigma(A)$ in Q_l in this sense. Points in the region $\{(a, b) \in Q_l : \nu_{l-1}(a) < b < \mu_l(a)\}$ between C_l and C^l , when it is nonempty, may or may not belong to $\Sigma(A)$.

5.2 New linking theorems

To state our linking theorems, let E be a C^1 -functional on a Banach space X . Denote by H the class of homeomorphisms h of X onto itself such that h and h^{-1} map bounded sets into bounded sets. Recall that a mapping $\varphi : Y \rightarrow Z$ between linear spaces is positive homogeneous if $\varphi(tu) = t\varphi(u)$ for all $u \in Y$ and $t \geq 0$. Let $X = N \oplus M$, $u = v + w$ be a direct sum decomposition with N finite dimensional and M closed and nontrivial. For $\rho > 0$, let $S_\rho = \{u \in X : \|u\| = \rho\}$. We have the following theorems.

Theorem 5.3. *Let $\theta \in C(M, N)$ be a positive homogeneous map. Assume that there exist $\rho > 0$ and $e \in X \setminus N$ such that*

$$\sup_{v \in N} E(v) < \inf_{u \in A} E(u), \quad \sup_{u \in Q} E(u) < \infty, \quad (5.2.1)$$

where $A = \{\theta(w) + w : w \in M \cap S_\rho\}$ and $Q = \{v + se : v \in N, s \geq 0\}$. Then

$$\inf_{u \in A} E(u) \leq c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) \leq \sup_{u \in Q} E(u), \quad (5.2.2)$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_N = id\}$. Moreover, if E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then c is a critical value of E .

Theorem 5.4. *Let $\tau \in C(N, M)$ be a positive homogeneous map and let $B = \{v + \tau(v) : v \in N\}$. Assume that there exist $\rho > 0$ and $e \in X \setminus B$ with $-e \notin B$ such that*

$$\sup_{u \in B} E(u) < \inf_{w \in A} E(w), \quad \sup_{u \in Q} E(u) < \infty, \quad (5.2.3)$$

where $A = M \cap S_\rho$ and $Q = \{u + se : u \in B, s \geq 0\}$. Then

$$\inf_{w \in A} E(w) \leq c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) \leq \sup_{u \in Q} E(u), \quad (5.2.4)$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_B = id\}$. Moreover, if E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then c is a critical value of E .

We proceed proving Theorems 5.3 and 5.4 and a generalization of Theorem 5.3 (see Theorem 5.6). The following variant definition of linking was given in Schechter [167] and is a refined version of a definition given in Schechter and Tintarev [168]. Let X be a Banach space. Denote by Φ the set of all mappings $\Gamma \in C(X \times [0, 1], X)$ such that, writing $\Gamma(u, t) = \Gamma(t)u$, we have

- (i) $\Gamma(0) = id$,
- (ii) $\Gamma(t)$ is a homeomorphism of X for all $t \in [0, 1)$, and the mapping $\Gamma^{-1} : X \times [0, 1) \rightarrow X$, $(u, t) \mapsto \Gamma(t)^{-1}u$ is continuous,
- (iii) $\Gamma(1)X$ is a single point in X , and $\Gamma(t)u \rightarrow \Gamma(1)X$ as $t \rightarrow 1$, uniformly on bounded subsets of X ,

(iv) for each bounded subset A of X and $t_0 \in [0, 1)$,

$$\sup_{(u,t) \in A \times [0,t_0]} \left(\|\Gamma(t)u\| + \|\Gamma^{-1}(t)u\| \right) < \infty.$$

Definition 5.1 ([167]). Let A and B be disjoint nonempty subsets of X . We say that A links B if

$$\Gamma(A \times (0, 1]) \cap B \neq \emptyset \quad \forall \Gamma \in \Phi.$$

Denote by H the class of homeomorphisms h of X onto itself such that h and h^{-1} map bounded sets into bounded sets. The following proposition was proved in Schechter [167].

Proposition 5.3 ([167, Proposition 2.5]). *If A links B and $h \in H$, then $h(A)$ links $h(B)$.*

Let E be a C^1 -functional on X . Recall that a subset B of X is a cone if $tu \in B$ whenever $u \in B$ and $t \geq 0$. We will obtain Theorems 5.3, 5.4, and 5.6 as corollaries of the following more general result.

Theorem 5.5. *Let A and B be disjoint nonempty subsets of X such that A links B . Assume that B is a cone and there exists $e \in X \setminus B$ with $-e \notin B$ such that*

$$\sup_{u \in B} E(u) < \inf_{u \in A} E(u), \quad \sup_{u \in Q} E(u) < \infty, \quad (5.2.5)$$

where $Q = \{u + se : u \in B, s \geq 0\}$. Then

$$\inf_{u \in A} E(u) \leq c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) \leq \sup_{u \in Q} E(u), \quad (5.2.6)$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_B = id\}$. Moreover, if E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then c is a critical value of E .

First we prove the following lemma.

Lemma 5.1. *Let B be a nonempty cone, let $e \in X \setminus B$ with $-e \notin B$, and let $Q = \{u + se : u \in B, s \geq 0\}$. Then no subset of $X \setminus Q$ can link B .*

Proof. We will show that

$$\Gamma((X \setminus Q) \times (0, 1]) \cap B = \emptyset \quad (5.2.7)$$

for the mapping $\Gamma \in \Phi$ given by

$$\Gamma(u, t) = (1 - t)u - te, \quad (u, t) \in X \times [0, 1].$$

Suppose (5.2.7) does not hold. Then there exist $(u, t) \in (X \setminus Q) \times (0, 1]$ and $v \in B$ such that

$$(1 - t)u - te = v.$$

Since $-e \notin B$, $t \neq 1$ and

$$u = \frac{v}{1-t} + \frac{te}{1-t}. \quad (5.2.8)$$

Since $v \in B$ and B is a cone, $v/(1-t) \in B$, so the right-hand side of (5.2.8) is in Q . This is a contradiction since $u \in X \setminus Q$. \square

Next we prove the following intersection lemma.

Lemma 5.2. *Let A and B be disjoint nonempty subsets of X such that A links B . Assume that B is a cone, $e \in X \setminus B$ with $-e \notin B$, and let $Q = \{u + se : u \in B, s \geq 0\}$. Then*

$$h(Q) \cap A \neq \emptyset \quad \forall h \in \tilde{H},$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_B = id\}$.

Proof. Suppose $h(Q) \cap A = \emptyset$ for some $h \in \tilde{H}$. Then $h^{-1}(A) \subset X \setminus Q$. Since A links B and $h^{-1} \in H$, $h^{-1}(A)$ links $h^{-1}(B)$ by Schechter [167, Proposition 2.5]. Since $h \in \tilde{H}$, $h^{-1} \in \tilde{H}$ and hence $h^{-1}(B) = B$, so $h^{-1}(A)$ links B . This contradicts Lemma 5.1 since $h^{-1}(A) \subset X \setminus Q$. \square

We are now ready to prove Theorem 5.5.

Proof of Theorem 5.5. Since $h(Q) \cap A \neq \emptyset$ for all $h \in \tilde{H}$ by Lemma 5.2 and the identity map is in \tilde{H} , (5.2.6) holds. It follows from (5.2.5) and (5.2.6) that

$$\sup_{u \in B} E(u) < c < \infty. \quad (5.2.9)$$

Suppose E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, but c is a regular value of E . By the first deformation lemma, then there exist $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ and, for each $\varepsilon \in (0, \varepsilon_0)$, an $\eta \in H$ such that

$$E(u) < c - 2\varepsilon \implies \eta(u) = u \quad (5.2.10)$$

and

$$E(u) \leq c + \varepsilon \implies E(\eta(u)) \leq c - \varepsilon \quad (5.2.11)$$

(see, e.g., Perera and Schechter [153, Lemma 1.3.5]). By (5.2.9) and (5.2.10), taking ε sufficiently small, we may assume that $\eta|_B$ is the identity and hence $\eta \in \tilde{H}$. By the definition of c , there exists $h \in \tilde{H}$ such that

$$\sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) \leq c + \varepsilon.$$

Then $\tilde{h} := \eta \circ h \in \tilde{H}$ and

$$\sup_{u \in \tilde{h}(Q)} E(u) \leq c - \varepsilon$$

by (5.2.11), contradicting the definition of c . \square

Let $X = N \oplus M$, $u = v + w$ be a direct sum decomposition with N finite dimensional and M closed and nontrivial. For $\rho > 0$, let $S_\rho = \{u \in X : \|u\| = \rho\}$. The following proposition was proved in Schechter [167].

Proposition 5.4 ([167, Corollary 2.7]). *For any $\rho > 0$, $M \cap S_\rho$ links N .*

We are now ready to prove Theorems 5.3 and 5.4.

Proof of Theorem 5.3. It suffices to show that A links N by Theorem 5.5. By Proposition 5.4, $M \cap S_\rho$ links N . Since $\theta \in C(M, N)$, the mapping

$$h : X \rightarrow X, \quad v + w \mapsto v + \theta(w) + w,$$

with the inverse

$$h^{-1} : X \rightarrow X, \quad v + w \mapsto v - \theta(w) + w,$$

is in H . So $h(M \cap S_\rho) = A$ links $h(N) = N$ by Proposition 5.3. \square

Proof of Theorem 5.4. Since τ is positive homogeneous, B is a cone, so it suffices to show that A links B by Theorem 5.5. By Proposition 5.4, A links N . Since $\tau \in C(N, M)$, the mapping

$$h : X \rightarrow X, \quad v + w \mapsto v + \tau(v) + w,$$

with the inverse

$$h^{-1} : X \rightarrow X, \quad v + w \mapsto v - \tau(v) + w,$$

is in H . So $h(A) = A$ links $h(N) = B$ by Proposition 5.3. \square

Finally we prove the following generalization of Theorem 5.3.

Theorem 5.6. *Let $\theta \in C(M, N)$ be a positive homogeneous map and let $T : N \rightarrow X$ be a bounded linear map. If $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small, where I is the identity map on N , and there exist $\rho > 0$ and $e \in X \setminus T(N)$ such that*

$$\sup_{u \in T(N)} E(u) < \inf_{u \in A} E(u), \quad \sup_{u \in Q} E(u) < \infty, \quad (5.2.12)$$

where $A = \{\theta(w) + w : w \in M \cap S_\rho\}$ and $Q = \{u + se : u \in T(N), s \geq 0\}$, then

$$\inf_{u \in A} E(u) \leq c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) \leq \sup_{u \in Q} E(u), \quad (5.2.13)$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_{T(N)} = id\}$. Moreover, if E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then c is a critical value of E .

First we prove the following linking result.

Lemma 5.3. *Let $T : N \rightarrow X$ be a bounded linear map. If $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small, where I is the identity map on N , then $M \cap S_\rho$ links $T(N)$ for any $\rho > 0$.*

Proof. By Proposition 5.4, it suffices to show that $X = T(N) \oplus M$. Let $P_N : X \rightarrow N$, $u \mapsto v$ and $P_M : X \rightarrow M$, $u \mapsto w$ be the projections onto N and M , respectively. Since $(I - P_N T)v = P_N(I - T)v$ for all $v \in N$,

$$\|I - P_N T\| = \|P_N(I - T)\| \leq \|P_N\| \|I - T\| \leq \|I - T\|.$$

So if $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small, then the mapping $P_N T : N \rightarrow N$ is invertible and hence

$$P_N(T(N)) = N.$$

So given $u = v + w \in N \oplus M$, there exists $z \in T(N)$ such that $v = P_N z$. Since $z = P_N z + P_M z$, then

$$u = P_N z + w = z + (w - P_M z) \in T(N) \oplus M. \quad (5.2.14)$$

Denoting by S the unit sphere in X , $N \cap S$ is compact since N is finite dimensional, and $M \cap S$ is closed since M is closed, so

$$\text{dist}(N \cap S, M \cap S) > 0.$$

So if $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small, then $T(N) \cap M = \{0\}$ and hence the decomposition in (5.2.14) is unique. Hence $X = T(N) \oplus M$. \square

We are now ready to prove Theorem 5.6.

Proof of Theorem 5.6. We will show that A links $T(N)$ if $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small. The desired conclusions will then follow from Theorem 5.5. Let $\Gamma \in \Phi$. Define $\tilde{\Gamma} \in \Phi$ by

$$\tilde{\Gamma}(u, t) = \begin{cases} v + 2t\theta(w) + w & \text{if } t \in [0, 1/2] \\ \Gamma(2t - 1)(v + \theta(w) + w) & \text{if } t \in (1/2, 1] \end{cases}$$

for $u = v + w \in N \oplus M$. If $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small, then $M \cap S_\rho$ links $T(N)$ by Lemma 5.3, so

$$\tilde{\Gamma}((M \cap S_\rho) \times [0, 1]) \cap T(N) \neq \emptyset. \quad (5.2.15)$$

We have

$$\tilde{\Gamma}((M \cap S_\rho) \times [0, 1]) = C_\rho \cup \Gamma(A \times (0, 1]), \quad (5.2.16)$$

where

$$C_\rho = \{t\theta(w) + w : w \in M \cap S_\rho, t \in [0, 1]\}.$$

We will show that if $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small, then

$$C_\rho \cap T(N) = \emptyset. \quad (5.2.17)$$

This together with (5.2.15) and (11.2) will show that

$$\Gamma(A \times (0, 1]) \cap T(N) \neq \emptyset$$

and complete the proof.

Let S be the unit sphere in X and let $\pi : X \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow S$, $u \mapsto u/\|u\|$ be the radial projection onto S . Since θ is positive homogeneous and T is linear, to show that (5.2.17) holds, it suffices to show that

$$\pi(C_\rho) \cap T(N) = \emptyset. \quad (5.2.18)$$

We will show that $\pi(C_\rho)$ is closed. Since N is finite dimensional, $N \cap S$ is compact, so this will imply that

$$\text{dist}(\pi(C_\rho), N \cap S) > 0$$

and hence (5.2.18) holds if $\|I - T\|$ is sufficiently small.

It remains to show that $\pi(C_\rho)$ is closed. Let

$$D = \{t\theta(w) + w : w \in M, t \in [0, 1]\}.$$

Since

$$\pi(C_\rho) = D \cap S,$$

it suffices to show that D is closed. Let $(w_j) \subset M$, $(t_j) \subset [0, 1]$ be sequences such that

$$t_j\theta(w_j) + w_j \rightarrow u = v + w \in N \oplus M.$$

Since M and N are closed subspaces, the projection $P_M : X \rightarrow M$, $u \mapsto w$ is continuous, so

$$w_j = P_M(t_j\theta(w_j) + w_j) \rightarrow P_M(u) = w.$$

Since θ is continuous, then $\theta(w_j) \rightarrow \theta(w)$. For a renamed subsequence, t_j converges to some $t \in [0, 1]$. Then

$$t_j\theta(w_j) + w_j \rightarrow t\theta(w) + w,$$

so $u = t\theta(w) + w \in D$ and hence D is closed. \square

Local critical elliptic problems with jumping nonlinearities

We will prove Theorems 5.1 and 5.2 in Sections 6.2. Our proofs are based on two new abstract existence results that we will prove in Section 6.1 by using Theorems 5.3 and 5.4 (see Theorems 6.1 and 6.2). These abstract results are of independent interest and can be used to obtain nontrivial solutions of other problems with jumping nonlinearities as well.

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS1].

6.1 Existence results for the local case

In this section we prove two abstract existence results based on Theorems 5.3 and 5.4 in the setting of Chapter 5. We consider the operator equation

$$Au = bu^+ - au^- + f(u), \quad u \in D, \quad (6.1.1)$$

where $a, b > 0$ and $f \in C(D, H)$ is a potential operator. Let $F \in C^1(D, \mathbb{R})$ be the potential of f that satisfies $F(0) = 0$, i.e.,

$$F(u) = \int_0^1 (f(su), u) ds, \quad u \in D$$

(see [153, Proposition 4.3.2]). Solutions of equation (6.1.1) coincide with critical points of the C^1 -functional

$$E(u) = \frac{1}{2} \|u\|_D^2 - \frac{a}{2} \|u^-\|^2 - \frac{b}{2} \|u^+\|^2 - F(u) = \frac{1}{2} I(u, a, b) - F(u), \quad u \in D.$$

We assume that

(F₁) $F(u) = o(\|u\|_D^2)$ as $\|u\|_D \rightarrow 0$,

(F₂) $F(u) \geq 0$ for all $u \in D$,

(F₃) there exists $c^* > 0$ such that for each $c \in (0, c^*)$, every (PS)_c sequence of E has a subsequence that converges weakly to a nontrivial critical point of E .

Theorem 6.1. *Assume (F₁)–(F₃). If $(a, b) \in Q_l$,*

$$b < \nu_{l-1}(a),$$

and there exists $e \in X \setminus N_{l-1}$ such that

$$\sup_{u \in Q} E(u) < c^*, \tag{6.1.2}$$

where $Q = \{v + se : v \in N_{l-1}, s \geq 0\}$, then equation (6.1.1) has a nontrivial solution.

Proof. Since $b < \nu_{l-1}(a)$ and ν_{l-1} is continuous,

$$b/(1 - \delta) \leq \nu_{l-1}(a/(1 - \delta))$$

if $\delta \in (0, 1 - \max\{a, b\} / \lambda_{l+1})$ is sufficiently small. Then

$$n_{l-1}(a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta)) \geq 0$$

(see (5.1.7)) and hence

$$I(\theta(w, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta)) + w, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta)) \geq 0 \quad \forall w \in M_{l-1} \tag{6.1.3}$$

(see (5.1.5)). For $\rho > 0$ and $w \in M_{l-1} \cap S_\rho$, set $u = \theta(w, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta)) + w$. Then

$$E(u) = \frac{\delta}{2} \|u\|_D^2 + \frac{1 - \delta}{2} \left(\|u\|_D^2 - \frac{a}{1 - \delta} \|u^-\|^2 - \frac{b}{1 - \delta} \|u^+\|^2 \right) - F(u),$$

and the quantity inside the parentheses is equal to $I(u, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta))$ and hence nonnegative by (6.1.3), so

$$E(u) \geq \frac{\delta}{2} \|u\|_D^2 + o(\|u\|_D^2) \text{ as } \|u\|_D \rightarrow 0$$

in view of (F₁). Since

$$\|u\|_D^2 = \|\theta(w, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta))\|_D^2 + \|w\|_D^2$$

and $\|\theta(w, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta))\|_D = O(\|w\|_D)$ by positive homogeneity (see [153, Proposition 4.3.1]), it follows that

$$E(u) \geq \frac{\delta}{2} \rho^2 + o(\rho^2) \text{ as } \rho \rightarrow 0.$$

So if $\rho > 0$ is sufficiently small,

$$\inf_{u \in A} E(u) > 0, \quad (6.1.4)$$

where $A = \{\theta(w, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta)) + w : w \in M_{l-1} \cap S_\rho\}$.

Now we apply Theorem 5.3 with $M = M_{l-1}$, $N = N_{l-1}$, and $\theta = \theta(\cdot, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta))$. Since $(a, b) \in Q_l$, $a, b > \lambda_{l-1}$ and hence

$$\begin{aligned} I(v, a, b) &\leq \|v\|_D^2 - \lambda_{l-1} (\|v^+\|^2 + \|v^-\|^2) \\ &= \|v\|_D^2 - \lambda_{l-1} \|v\|^2 \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad \forall v \in N_{l-1} \quad (6.1.5)$$

by (5.1.1) and (5.1.2). This together with (F_2) and the fact that $E(0) = 0$ implies

$$\sup_{v \in N_{l-1}} E(v) = 0.$$

Together with (6.1.4), this gives the first inequality in (5.2.1). The second inequality also holds by (6.1.2), so (5.2.2) together with (6.1.4) and (6.1.2) gives

$$0 < c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) < c^*,$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_{N_{l-1}} = id\}$. If E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then Theorem 5.3 gives a critical point of E at the level c , which is nontrivial since $c > 0$. If, on the other hand, E does not satisfy the $(PS)_c$ condition, then E has a $(PS)_c$ sequence without a convergent subsequence, which then has a subsequence that converges weakly to a nontrivial critical point of E by (F_3) . \square

Theorem 6.2. *Assume (F_1) – (F_3) and let $B = \{v + \tau(v, a, b) : v \in N_l\}$. If $(a, b) \in Q_l$,*

$$b \geq \mu_l(a),$$

and there exists $e \in X \setminus B$ with $-e \notin B$ such that

$$\sup_{u \in Q} E(u) < c^*, \quad (6.1.6)$$

where $Q = \{u + se : u \in B, s \geq 0\}$, then equation (6.1.1) has a nontrivial solution.

Proof. We apply Theorem 5.4 with $N = N_l$, $M = M_l$, and $\tau = \tau(\cdot, a, b)$. Since $b \geq \mu_l(a)$,

$$m_l(a, b) \leq 0$$

(see (5.1.8)) and hence

$$I(v + \tau(v, a, b), a, b) \leq 0 \quad \forall v \in N_l \quad (6.1.7)$$

(see (5.1.6)). This together with (F_2) and the fact that $E(0) = 0$ implies

$$\sup_{u \in B} E(u) = 0. \quad (6.1.8)$$

Since $(a, b) \in Q_l$, $a, b \leq \lambda_{l+1} - \delta$ if $\delta > 0$ is sufficiently small. Then

$$I(w, a, b) \geq \|w\|_D^2 - (\lambda_{l+1} - \delta) \|w\|^2 \geq \frac{\delta}{\lambda_{l+1}} \|w\|_D^2 \quad \forall w \in M_l$$

by (5.1.1) and (5.1.3), so

$$E(w) \geq \frac{\delta}{2\lambda_{l+1}} \|w\|_D^2 + o(\|w\|_D^2) \text{ as } \|w\|_D \rightarrow 0$$

in view of (F_1) . So if $\rho > 0$ is sufficiently small,

$$\inf_{w \in A} E(w) > 0, \tag{6.1.9}$$

where $A = M_l \cap S_\rho$. Together with (6.1.8), this gives the first inequality in (5.2.3). The second inequality also holds by (6.1.6), so (5.2.4) together with (6.1.9) and (6.1.6) gives

$$0 < c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) < c^*,$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_B = id\}$. If E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then Theorem 5.4 gives a critical point of E at the level c , which is nontrivial since $c > 0$. If, on the other hand, E does not satisfy the $(PS)_c$ condition, then E has a $(PS)_c$ sequence without a convergent subsequence, which then has a subsequence that converges weakly to a nontrivial critical point of E by (F_3) . \square

6.2 Proofs of Theorems 5.1 and 5.2

In this section we prove Theorems 5.1 and 5.2. First we prove Theorem 5.1 for $N \geq 5$ and Theorem 5.2 using Theorems 6.1 and 6.2, respectively. Then we prove Theorem 5.1 for $N = 4$ using Theorem 5.6.

Since $u^\pm = (-u)^\mp$, u solves (5.0.3) (resp. (5.0.1)) if and only if $-u$ solves (5.0.3) (resp. (5.0.1)) with a and b interchanged. So $\Sigma(-\Delta)$ is symmetric about the line $a = b$ and we may assume without loss of generality that $a \leq b$.

Problem (5.0.1) fits into the abstract setting of Sections 5.1 and 6.1 with $H = L^2(\Omega)$, $p(u) = u^+$, $n(u) = -u^-$, $D = H_0^1(\Omega)$, and A equal to the inverse of the solution operator $L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow H_0^1(\Omega)$, $g \mapsto u = (-\Delta)^{-1}g$ of the problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = g(x) & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases}$$

Since the embedding $H_0^1(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^2(\Omega)$ is compact, A^{-1} is compact on $L^2(\Omega)$. The potential

$$F(u) = \frac{1}{2^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx, \quad u \in H_0^1(\Omega)$$

clearly satisfies (F_1) and (F_2) . It is also well-known that the associated variational functional

$$E(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^2 dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx - \frac{1}{2^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx, \quad u \in H_0^1(\Omega)$$

satisfies (F_3) with

$$c^* = \frac{1}{N} S_N^{N/2},$$

where

$$S_N = \inf_{u \in H_0^1(\Omega) \setminus \{0\}} \frac{\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^2 dx}{\left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx \right)^{2/2^*}} \quad (6.2.1)$$

is the best Sobolev constant (see Gazzola and Ruf [108, Lemma 1]).

Recall that the infimum in (6.2.1) is attained on the functions

$$u_{\varepsilon}(x) = c_N \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon^2 + |x|^2} \right)^{(N-2)/2}, \quad \varepsilon > 0,$$

where $c_N = [N(N-2)]^{(N-2)/4}$ (see Talenti [179]). Fix $x_0 \in \Omega$ and $\mu_0 > 1/\text{dist}(x_0, \partial\Omega)$. Let $\xi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a smooth function such that $\xi(s) = 1$ for $s \leq 1/4$ and $\xi(s) = 0$ for $s \geq 1/2$. Set

$$u_{\varepsilon, \mu}(x) = \xi(\mu|x - x_0|) u_{\varepsilon}(x - x_0), \quad \varepsilon > 0, \mu \geq \mu_0.$$

We will apply Theorems 6.1, 6.2, and 5.6 taking $e = u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$ with $\varepsilon > 0$ sufficiently small and $\mu \geq \mu_0$ sufficiently large. We have the estimates

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_{\varepsilon, \mu}|^2 dx \leq S_N^{N/2} + c_1 (\mu\varepsilon)^{N-2}, \quad (6.2.2)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^{2^*} dx \geq S_N^{N/2} - c_2 (\mu\varepsilon)^N, \quad (6.2.3)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^2 dx \geq \begin{cases} c_3 \varepsilon^2 - c_4 \mu^{N-4} \varepsilon^{N-2} & \text{if } N \geq 5 \\ c_3 \varepsilon^2 |\log(\mu\varepsilon)| - c_4 \varepsilon^2 & \text{if } N = 4, \end{cases} \quad (6.2.4)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu} dx \leq c_5 \mu^{-2} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2}, \quad (6.2.5)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^{2^*-1} dx \leq c_6 \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} \quad (6.2.6)$$

for some constants $c_1, \dots, c_6 > 0$ (estimates (6.2.2)–(6.2.4) can be found in Degiovanni and Lancelotti [90], and (6.2.5) and (6.2.6) are easily verified).

6.2.1 Proofs of Theorem 5.1 for $N \geq 5$ and Theorem 5.2

For $N \geq 5$, $(N+2)/N < (N-2)/2$. Fix

$$\frac{N+2}{N} < \beta < \frac{N-2}{2}. \quad (6.2.7)$$

Let $S = \{u \in H_0^1(\Omega) : \|u\| = 1\}$.

Lemma 6.1. *Let K be a subset of $S \cap C^2(\Omega)$ such that*

$$\sup_{u \in K} \|u\|_{C^2(\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)})} < \infty. \quad (6.2.8)$$

Then there exist constants $c_7, \dots, c_{15} > 0$ such that for all $\varepsilon > 0$, $\mu \geq \mu_0$, $u \in K$, and $s, t \geq 0$,

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})|^2 dx \leq (1 + c_7 \mu^{-(N+2)}) t^2 + (S_N^{N/2} + c_8 (\mu\varepsilon)^{N-2}) s^2, \quad (6.2.9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} |tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu}|^{2^*} dx &\geq \left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx - c_9 \mu^{-N} - c_{10} \varepsilon^{N[1-2\beta/(N-2)]} \right) t^{2^*} \\ &\quad + \left(S_N^{N/2} - c_{11} (\mu\varepsilon)^N - c_{12} \varepsilon^{2N\beta/(N+2)} \right) s^{2^*}, \end{aligned} \quad (6.2.10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \left[a((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^-)^2 + b((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^+)^2 \right] dx &\geq \left(\int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx \right. \\ &\quad \left. - c_{13} \mu^{-4} \right) t^2 + \left(c_{14} \varepsilon^2 - c_{15} \mu^{N-4} \varepsilon^{N-2} \right) s^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.2.11)$$

In particular,

$$\begin{aligned} E(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu}) &\leq \frac{1}{2} \left(I(u, a, b) + c_{16} \mu^{-4} \right) t^2 - \frac{1}{2^*} \left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx - c_9 \mu^{-N} \right. \\ &\quad \left. - c_{10} \varepsilon^{N[1-2\beta/(N-2)]} \right) t^{2^*} + \frac{1}{2} \left(S_N^{N/2} - c_{14} \varepsilon^2 + c_{17} (\mu\varepsilon)^{N-2} \right) s^2 \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2^*} \left(S_N^{N/2} - c_{11} (\mu\varepsilon)^N - c_{12} \varepsilon^{2N\beta/(N+2)} \right) s^{2^*} \end{aligned}$$

for some constants $c_{16}, c_{17} > 0$.

Proof. We have

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})|^2 dx = t^2 + 2ts \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla u_{\varepsilon, \mu} dx + s^2 \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_{\varepsilon, \mu}|^2 dx \quad (6.2.12)$$

since $u \in S$. Since $u_{\varepsilon, \mu} = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$,

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla u_{\varepsilon, \mu} dx = - \int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu} \Delta u dx \leq c_7 \mu^{-2} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} \quad (6.2.13)$$

for some constant $c_7 > 0$ by (6.2.8) and (6.2.5). Combining (6.2.12) with (6.2.13) and (6.2.2), and noting that

$$2ts\mu^{-2} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} = 2\mu^{-(N+2)/2} t (\mu\varepsilon)^{(N-2)/2} s \leq \mu^{-(N+2)} t^2 + (\mu\varepsilon)^{N-2} s^2,$$

gives (6.2.9) for some constant $c_8 > 0$.

The elementary inequality

$$|y + z|^p \geq |y|^p + |z|^p - p(p-1) 2^{p-2} (|y|^{p-1} |z| + |y| |z|^{p-1}) \quad \forall y, z \in \mathbb{R}, p > 2$$

together with (6.2.3), (6.2.8), (6.2.5), and (6.2.6) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} |tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu}|^{2^*} dx &\geq t^{2^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx + s^{2^*} \int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^{2^*} dx \\ &- 2^*(2^* - 1) 2^{2^*-2} \left(t^{2^*-1} s \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*-1} u_{\varepsilon, \mu} dx + ts^{2^*-1} \int_{\Omega} |u| u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^{2^*-1} dx \right) \\ &\geq t^{2^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx + s^{2^*} \left(S_N^{N/2} - c_2 (\mu\varepsilon)^N \right) - c_9 \left(t^{2^*-1} s \mu^{-2} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} + ts^{2^*-1} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} \right) \end{aligned}$$

for some constant $c_9 > 0$. Since

$$t^{2^*-1} s \mu^{-2} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} = \mu^{-(N+2)/2} t^{2^*-1} (\mu\varepsilon)^{(N-2)/2} s \leq \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^*}\right) \mu^{-N} t^{2^*} + \frac{1}{2^*} (\mu\varepsilon)^N s^{2^*}$$

and

$$ts^{2^*-1} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} = \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2-\beta} t \varepsilon^{\beta} s^{2^*-1} \leq \frac{1}{2^*} \varepsilon^{N[1-2\beta/(N-2)]} t^{2^*} + \left(1 - \frac{1}{2^*}\right) \varepsilon^{2N\beta/(N+2)} s^{2^*}$$

by Young's inequality, (6.2.10) follows.

Since $u_{\varepsilon, \mu} = 0$ outside $B_{1/\mu}(x_0)$,

$$\begin{aligned} &\int_{\Omega} \left[a \left((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^- \right)^2 + b \left((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^+ \right)^2 \right] dx \\ &= t^2 \int_{\Omega \setminus B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} \left[a (u^-)^2 + b (u^+)^2 \right] dx \\ &\quad + \int_{B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} \left[a \left((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^- \right)^2 + b \left((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^+ \right)^2 \right] dx \\ &= t^2 \int_{\Omega} \left[a (u^-)^2 + b (u^+)^2 \right] dx \\ &\quad + \int_{B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} \left[a \left((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^- \right)^2 + b \left((tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^+ \right)^2 - a (tu^-)^2 - b (tu^+)^2 \right] dx. \end{aligned}$$

Since $a \leq b$, the last integral is greater than or equal to

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} [a(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \mu})^2 - b(tu)^2] dx = -(b-a)t^2 \int_{B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} u^2 dx \\ & \quad + 2ats \int_{B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} uu_{\varepsilon, \mu} dx + as^2 \int_{B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^2 dx \\ & \geq -c_{13}t^2 \mu^{-N} - 2c_{14}ts\mu^{-2} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} + as^2 (c_3 \varepsilon^2 - c_4 \mu^{N-4} \varepsilon^{N-2}) \end{aligned}$$

for some constants $c_{13}, c_{14} > 0$ by (6.2.8), (6.2.5), and (6.2.4). Since

$$2ts\mu^{-2} \varepsilon^{(N-2)/2} \leq \mu^{-4} t^2 + \varepsilon^{N-2} s^2$$

and $N \geq 5$, (6.2.11) follows. \square

Noting that $1/N < 1 - 2/(N-2)$ for $N \geq 5$, now we fix

$$\frac{1}{N} < \gamma < 1 - \frac{2}{N-2} \quad (6.2.14)$$

and take $\mu = \varepsilon^{-\gamma}$. Then $(\mu\varepsilon)^{N-2} = \varepsilon^{(N-2)(1-\gamma)}$ and $(N-2)(1-\gamma) > 2$ by (6.2.14), so it follows from Lemma 6.1 that for all small $\varepsilon > 0$, $u \in K$, and $s, t \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} E(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}) & \leq \frac{1}{2} (I(u, a, b) + c_{16} \varepsilon^{4\gamma}) t^2 - \frac{1}{2^*} \left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx - c_9 \varepsilon^{N\gamma} \right. \\ & \quad \left. - c_{10} \varepsilon^{N[1-2\beta/(N-2)]} \right) t^{2^*} + \frac{1}{2} (S_N^{N/2} - c_{18} \varepsilon^2) s^2 - \frac{1}{2^*} (S_N^{N/2} - c_{11} \varepsilon^{N(1-\gamma)} \\ & \quad \left. - c_{12} \varepsilon^{2N\beta/(N+2)} \right) s^{2^*} \quad (6.2.15) \end{aligned}$$

for some constant $c_{18} > 0$. The next lemma is crucial.

Lemma 6.2. *Let K be a subset of $S \cap C^2(\Omega)$ such that (6.2.8) holds and*

$$I(u, a, b) \leq 0 \quad \forall u \in K. \quad (6.2.16)$$

Then

$$\sup_{u \in K, s, t \geq 0} E(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}) < \frac{1}{N} S_N^{N/2}$$

for all sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$.

Proof. For $u \in K$, (6.2.16) together with the assumption $a \leq b$ and the Hölder inequality gives

$$1 \leq \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx \leq b \int_{\Omega} u^2 dx \leq b |\Omega|^{2/N} \left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx \right)^{2/2^*},$$

so

$$\inf_{u \in K} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2^*} dx > 0. \quad (6.2.17)$$

It follows from (6.2.15)–(6.2.17) that for all sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$, $u \in K$, and $s, t \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} E(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}) \leq & \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 - c_{19} \varepsilon^2) s^2 - \frac{1}{2^*} (1 - c_{20} \varepsilon^{N(1-\gamma)} - c_{21} \varepsilon^{2N\beta/(N+2)}) s^{2^*} \right] S_N^{N/2} \\ & + c_{22} \varepsilon^{4\gamma} t^2 - c_{23} t^{2^*} \end{aligned}$$

for some constants $c_{19}, \dots, c_{23} > 0$. Maximizing the right-hand side over all $s, t \geq 0$ then gives

$$E(tu + su_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}) \leq \frac{1}{N} \frac{(1 - c_{19} \varepsilon^2)^{N/2}}{(1 - c_{20} \varepsilon^{N(1-\gamma)} - c_{21} \varepsilon^{2N\beta/(N+2)})^{(N-2)/2}} S_N^{N/2} + c_{24} \varepsilon^{2N\gamma}$$

for some constant $c_{24} > 0$. Since $2N\beta/(N+2) > 2$ by (6.2.7), and $N(1-\gamma) > 2$ and $2N\gamma > 2$ by (6.2.14), the desired conclusion follows. \square

We are now ready to prove Theorem 5.1 for $N \geq 5$ and Theorem 5.2.

Proof of Theorem 5.1 for $N \geq 5$. We apply Theorem 6.1 taking $e = u_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}$ with $\varepsilon > 0$ sufficiently small. Functions $u_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}$ with different centers x_0 and sufficiently small ε have disjoint supports and are therefore linearly independent. Since N_{l-1} is finite dimensional, it follows that $x_0 \in \Omega$ can be chosen so that $u_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}} \notin N_{l-1}$.

To verify (6.1.2), we use Lemma 6.2 with $K = S \cap N_{l-1}$. As in the proof of Theorem 6.1, (6.2.16) holds (see (6.1.5)). By the interior regularity of eigenfunctions, $N_{l-1} \subset C^2(\Omega)$. So the restrictions of functions in N_{l-1} to $\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)}$ form a finite dimensional subspace of $C^2(\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)})$. Since the restrictions of functions in K to $\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)}$ is a subset of this subspace and is bounded in the H^1 -norm, (6.2.8) follows. \square

Proof of Theorem 5.2. We apply Theorem 6.2 taking $e = u_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}$ with $\varepsilon > 0$ sufficiently small. Gradients $I'(u_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}}, a, b)$ with different centers x_0 and sufficiently small ε have disjoint supports and are therefore linearly independent. By Proposition 5.1, $I'(v + \tau(v, a, b), a, b) \perp M_l$ for all $v \in N_l$ and hence $\{I'(v + \tau(v, a, b), a, b) : v \in N_l\}$ is a subset of N_l . Since N_l is finite dimensional, it follows that $x_0 \in \Omega$ can be chosen so that $\pm u_{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-\gamma}} \notin B := \{v + \tau(v, a, b) : v \in N_l\}$.

To verify (6.1.6), we use Lemma 6.2 with $K = S \cap B$. As in the proof of Theorem 6.2, (6.2.16) holds (see (6.1.7)). It only remains to show that (6.2.8) holds. Let $u \in K$. By Proposition 5.1, $I'(u, a, b) = z_u$ for some $z_u \in N_l$. Then

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla \zeta dx - \int_{\Omega} (bu^+ - au^-) \zeta dx = \int_{\Omega} \nabla z_u \cdot \nabla \zeta dx \quad \forall \zeta \in H_0^1(\Omega), \quad (6.2.18)$$

so u is a weak solution of

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = bu^+ - au^- - \Delta z_u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases}$$

Testing (6.2.18) with z_u gives

$$\|z_u\|^2 \leq \|u\| \|z_u\| + (a|u^-|_2 + b|u^+|_2) |z_u|_2,$$

and since $K \subset S$, this implies that $\{z_u : u \in K\}$ is bounded in $H_0^1(\Omega)$. By the interior regularity of eigenfunctions, $N_l \subset C^{2,\alpha}(\Omega)$. So the restrictions of functions in N_l to $\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)}$ form a finite dimensional subspace of $C^{2,\alpha}(\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)})$. Since the restrictions of functions in the set $\{z_u : u \in K\}$ to $\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)}$ is a subset of this subspace and is bounded in the H^1 -norm, it follows that this set is also bounded in $C^{2,\alpha}(\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)})$. Now it follows from standard arguments in elliptic regularity theory that K is bounded in $C^{2,\alpha}(\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)})$. \square

6.2.2 Proof of Theorem 5.1 for $\mathbb{N} = 4$

Let $\eta : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a smooth function such that $\eta(s) = 0$ for $s \leq 3/4$, $\eta(s) = 1$ for $s \geq 1$, and $|\eta'(s)| \leq 5$ for all s . Set

$$v_\mu(x) = \eta(\mu|x - x_0|) v(x), \quad v \in N_{l-1}, \mu \geq \mu_0.$$

We will apply Theorem 5.6 taking T to be the bounded linear map from N_{l-1} to $H_0^1(\Omega)$ given by $Tv = v_\mu$ with $\mu \geq \mu_0$ sufficiently large. The critical exponent $2^* = 4$ now and the estimates (6.2.2)–(6.2.4) reduce to

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u_{\varepsilon, \mu}|^2 dx \leq S_4^2 + c_1 (\mu\varepsilon)^2, \quad (6.2.19)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^4 dx \geq S_4^2 - c_2 (\mu\varepsilon)^4, \quad (6.2.20)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^2 dx \geq c_3 \varepsilon^2 |\log(\mu\varepsilon)| - c_4 \varepsilon^2. \quad (6.2.21)$$

Lemma 6.3. *There exist constants $c_{25}, \dots, c_{28} > 0$ such that for all $\mu \geq \mu_0$ and $v \in N_{l-1} \cap S$,*

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla(v_{\mu} - v)|^2 dx \leq c_{25} \mu^{-2}, \quad (6.2.22)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla v_{\mu}|^2 dx \leq \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^2 dx + c_{26} \mu^{-2}, \quad (6.2.23)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} v_{\mu}^4 dx \geq \int_{\Omega} v^4 dx - c_{27} \mu^{-4}, \quad (6.2.24)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} [a(v_{\mu}^{-})^2 + b(v_{\mu}^{+})^2] dx \geq \int_{\Omega} [a(v^{-})^2 + b(v^{+})^2] dx - c_{28} \mu^{-4}. \quad (6.2.25)$$

In particular, for all $t \geq 0$,

$$E(tv_{\mu}) \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(I(v, a, b) + c_{29} \mu^{-2} \right) t^2 - \frac{1}{4} \left(\int_{\Omega} v^4 dx - c_{27} \mu^{-4} \right) t^4$$

for some constant $c_{29} > 0$.

Proof. We have

$$\nabla v_{\mu}(x) = \eta(\mu|x - x_0|) \nabla v(x) + \mu \eta'(\mu|x - x_0|) \frac{x - x_0}{|x - x_0|} v(x)$$

and hence $|\nabla(v_{\mu} - v)| \leq |\nabla v| + 5\mu|v|$. Since $v_{\mu} = v$ outside $B_{1/\mu}(x_0)$, this gives

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla(v_{\mu} - v)|^2 dx \leq \int_{B_{1/\mu}(x_0)} (|\nabla v| + 5\mu|v|)^2 dx,$$

and (6.2.22) follows from this since the restrictions of functions in N_{l-1} to $\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)}$ form a finite dimensional subspace of $C^1(\overline{B_{1/\mu_0}(x_0)})$ by the interior regularity of eigenfunctions. Proofs of (6.2.23)–(6.2.25) are similar. \square

Lemma 6.4. *We have*

$$\sup_{v \in N_{l-1} \cap S, s, t \geq 0} E(tv_{\mu} + su_{\varepsilon, \mu}) < \frac{1}{2} S_4^2 \quad (6.2.26)$$

for all sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$ and sufficiently large $\mu \geq \mu_0$.

Proof. For $v \in N_{l-1} \cap S$ and $s, t \geq 0$,

$$E(tv_{\mu} + su_{\varepsilon, \mu}) = E(tv_{\mu}) + E(su_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \quad (6.2.27)$$

since v_{μ} and $u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$ have disjoint supports. Since $a \leq b$ and $(a, b) \in Q_l$,

$$I(v, a, b) = 1 - \int_{\Omega} [a(v^{-})^2 + b(v^{+})^2] dx \leq 1 - a \int_{\Omega} v^2 dx \leq 1 - \frac{a}{\lambda_{l-1}} < 0.$$

Moreover,

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{l-1}} \leq \int_{\Omega} v^2 dx \leq |\Omega|^{1/2} \left(\int_{\Omega} v^4 dx \right)^{1/2}$$

and hence

$$\inf_{v \in N_{l-1} \cap S} \int_{\Omega} v^4 dx > 0.$$

So it follows from Lemma 6.3 that $E(tv_{\mu}) \leq 0$ for all sufficiently large $\mu \geq \mu_0$. Then (6.2.27) together with (6.2.19)–(6.2.21) gives for all sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$E(tv_{\mu} + su_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \leq E(su_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \leq \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 - c_{30} \varepsilon^2 |\log \varepsilon|) s^2 - \frac{1}{4} (1 - c_{31} \varepsilon^4) s^4 \right] S_4^2$$

for some constants $c_{30}, c_{31} > 0$ depending on μ . Maximizing the right-hand side over all $s \geq 0$ then gives

$$E(tv_{\mu} + su_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \leq \frac{1}{4} \frac{(1 - c_{30} \varepsilon^2 |\log \varepsilon|)^2}{1 - c_{31} \varepsilon^4} S_4^2,$$

from which the desired conclusion follows. \square

We are now ready to prove Theorem 5.1 for $N = 4$.

Proof of Theorem 5.1 for $N = 4$. As in the proof of Theorem 6.1, if

$$\delta \in (0, 1 - \max\{a, b\}/\lambda_{l+1})$$

and $\rho > 0$ are sufficiently small,

$$\inf_{u \in A} E(u) > 0, \tag{6.2.28}$$

where $A = \{\theta(w, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta)) + w : w \in M_{l-1} \cap S_{\rho}\}$. We apply Theorem 5.6 taking $M = M_{l-1}$, $N = N_{l-1}$, $\theta = \theta(\cdot, a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta))$, $T : N_{l-1} \rightarrow H_0^1(\Omega)$ to be the bounded linear map given by

$$Tv = v_{\mu}, \quad v \in N_{l-1},$$

and $e = u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$, with $\varepsilon > 0$ sufficiently small and $\mu \geq \mu_0$ sufficiently large. Since $u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$ and functions in $T(N_{l-1})$ have disjoint supports, $u_{\varepsilon, \mu} \in H_0^1(\Omega) \setminus T(N_{l-1})$. We have

$$\|I - T\| = \sup_{v \in N_{l-1} \cap S} \left(\int_{\Omega} |\nabla(v_{\mu} - v)|^2 dx \right)^{1/2} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \mu \rightarrow \infty$$

by (6.2.22), where I is the identity map on N_{l-1} . If $\mu \geq \mu_0$ is sufficiently large, $E(tv_{\mu}) \leq 0$ for all $v \in N_{l-1} \cap S$ and $t \geq 0$ as in the proof of Lemma 6.4, so

$$\sup_{u \in T(N_{l-1})} E(u) = 0.$$

Together with (6.2.28), this gives the first inequality in (5.2.12). The second inequality also holds by Lemma 6.4, so (5.2.13) together with (6.2.28) and (6.2.26) gives

$$0 < c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) < \frac{1}{2} S_4^2,$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_{T(N_{i-1})} = id\}$. If E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then Theorem 5.6 gives a critical point of E at the level c , which is nontrivial since $c > 0$. If, on the other hand, E does not satisfy the $(PS)_c$ condition, then E has a $(PS)_c$ sequence without a convergent subsequence, which then has a subsequence that converges weakly to a nontrivial critical point of E (see Gazzola and Ruf [108, Lemma 1]). \square

6.3 Existence result for the case $\mathbb{N} = 2$

As previously mentioned, the abstract results stated in Section 5.2 are of independent interest and can be used to obtain nontrivial solutions of other problems with jumping nonlinearities as well. For that reason, we choose to deal with the critical growth problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = bu^+ - au^- + (e^{u^2} - 1)u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (6.3.1)$$

where Ω is a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^2 . We prove the following results for problem (6.3.1).

Theorem 6.3. *Let $N = 2$. If $(a, b) \in Q_l$ and*

$$b < \nu_{l-1}(a)$$

for some $l \geq 2$, then problem (6.3.1) has a nontrivial solution.

Theorem 6.4. *Let $N = 2$. If $(a, b) \in Q_l$ and*

$$b > \mu_l(a)$$

for some $l \geq 2$, then problem (6.3.1) has a nontrivial solution.

Here we prove Theorems 6.3 and 6.4 using Theorems 6.1 and 6.2, respectively. As in the last section, we assume without loss of generality that $a \leq b$. Problem (6.3.1) fits into the abstract setting of Sections 5.1 and 6.1 as before. The potential

$$F(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (e^{u^2} - 1 - u^2) dx, \quad u \in H_0^1(\Omega)$$

clearly satisfies (F_1) and (F_2) . Moreover, the associated variational functional

$$E(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^2 dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (e^{u^2} - 1 - u^2) dx, \quad u \in H_0^1(\Omega)$$

satisfies (F_3) with

$$c^* = 2\pi$$

(see de Figueiredo et al. [88, Proposition 2.1]).

Fix $x_0 \in \Omega$ and $0 < d_0 < \text{dist}(x_0, \partial\Omega)$. Let

$$\omega_{j,d}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \begin{cases} \sqrt{\log j} & \text{if } |x - x_0| \leq d/j \\ \frac{\log(d/|x - x_0|)}{\sqrt{\log j}} & \text{if } d/j < |x - x_0| < d, \\ 0 & \text{if } |x - x_0| \geq d \end{cases} \quad j \geq 2, 0 < d \leq d_0$$

be the Moser sequence concentrating at x_0 . Note that $\omega_{j,d} \in H_0^1(\Omega)$ with $\|\omega_{j,d}\| = 1$. We will apply Theorems 6.1 and 6.2 taking $e = \omega_{j,d}$ with $j \geq 2$ sufficiently large and $0 < d \leq d_0$ sufficiently small. We have the estimates

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla \omega_{j,d}| dx \leq c_{32} \frac{d}{\sqrt{\log j}}, \quad (6.3.2)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \omega_{j,d} dx \leq c_{33} \frac{d^2}{\sqrt{\log j}}, \quad (6.3.3)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} \omega_{j,d}^2 dx \geq c_{34} \frac{d^2}{\log j} \quad (6.3.4)$$

for some constants $c_{32}, \dots, c_{34} > 0$. Let $S = \{u \in H_0^1(\Omega) : \|u\| = 1\}$.

Lemma 6.5. *Let K be a subset of $S \cap C^2(\Omega)$ such that*

$$\sup_{u \in K} \|u\|_{C^2(\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)})} < \infty. \quad (6.3.5)$$

Then there exist constants $c_{35}, \dots, c_{37} > 0$ such that for all $j \geq 2, 0 < d \leq d_0, u \in K$, and $s, t \geq 0$,

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla(tu + s\omega_{j,d})|^2 dx \leq \left(1 + c_{35} \frac{d^2}{\sqrt{\log j}}\right) (t^2 + s^2), \quad (6.3.6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \left[a((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^-)^2 + b((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^+)^2 \right] dx \\ & \geq \left(\int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx - c_{36} d^2 \right) t^2 + c_{37} \frac{d^2}{\log j} s^2. \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.7)$$

In particular,

$$I(tu + s\omega_{j,d}, a, b) \leq \left(I(u, a, b) + c_{38} d^2 \right) t^2 + \left(1 + c_{35} \frac{d^2}{\sqrt{\log j}} \right) s^2$$

for some constant $c_{38} > 0$.

Proof. We have

$$\int_{\Omega} |\nabla(tu + s\omega_{j,d})|^2 dx = t^2 + 2ts \int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla \omega_{j,d} dx + s^2$$

since $u, \omega_{j,d} \in S$. Since $\omega_{j,d} = 0$ on $\partial\Omega$,

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla \omega_{j,d} dx = - \int_{\Omega} \omega_{j,d} \Delta u dx \leq c_{35} \frac{d^2}{\sqrt{\log j}}$$

for some constant $c_{35} > 0$ by (6.3.5) and (6.3.3), so (6.3.6) follows. Since $\omega_{j,d} = 0$ outside $B_d(x_0)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\Omega} \left[a((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^-)^2 + b((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^+)^2 \right] dx \\ &= t^2 \int_{\Omega \setminus B_d(x_0)} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx \\ & \quad + \int_{B_d(x_0)} \left[a((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^-)^2 + b((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^+)^2 \right] dx \\ &= t^2 \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx \\ & \quad + \int_{B_d(x_0)} \left[a((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^-)^2 + b((tu + s\omega_{j,d})^+)^2 - a(tu^-)^2 - b(tu^+)^2 \right] dx. \end{aligned}$$

Since $a \leq b$, the last integral is greater than or equal to

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{B_d(x_0)} [a(tu + s\omega_{j,d})^2 - b(tu)^2] dx = -(b-a)t^2 \int_{B_d(x_0)} u^2 dx \\ & \quad + 2ats \int_{B_d(x_0)} u\omega_{j,d} dx + as^2 \int_{B_d(x_0)} \omega_{j,d}^2 dx \geq -c_{36} d^2 t^2 + c_{37} \frac{d^2}{\log j} s^2 \end{aligned}$$

for some constants $c_{36}, c_{37} > 0$ by (6.3.5), (6.3.3), and (6.3.4), so (6.3.7) also follows. \square

Now we take $d = (\log j)^{-1/4}$. Then it follows from Lemma 6.5 that for all large $j \geq 2$, $u \in K$, and $s, t \geq 0$,

$$I(tu + s\omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}}, a, b) \leq \left(I(u, a, b) + \frac{c_{38}}{\sqrt{\log j}} \right) t^2 + \left(1 + \frac{c_{35}}{\log j} \right) s^2. \quad (6.3.8)$$

We have the following lemmas.

Lemma 6.6. *Let K be a subset of $S \cap C^2(\Omega)$ such that (6.3.5) holds and*

$$I(u, a, b) \leq 0 \quad \forall u \in K. \quad (6.3.9)$$

Then

$$E(tu) \leq 0 \quad \forall u \in K, t \geq 0,$$

and for all sufficiently large $j \geq 2$,

$$\sup_{u \in K, s, t \geq 0} E(tu + s \omega_{j, (\log j)^{-1/4}}) < \infty \quad (6.3.10)$$

and

$$E(tu + s \omega_{j, (\log j)^{-1/4}}) \rightarrow -\infty \text{ as } s^2 + t^2 \rightarrow \infty, \text{ uniformly in } u \in K. \quad (6.3.11)$$

Proof. For $u \in K$ and $t \geq 0$,

$$E(tu) = \frac{t^2}{2} I(u, a, b) - F(tu) \leq 0$$

by (6.3.9) and (F_2) .

Set $v = tu + s \omega_{j, (\log j)^{-1/4}}$. Since $a, b > 0$ and $e^{v^2} \geq 1 + v^2 + v^4/2$,

$$E(v) \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^2 dx - \frac{1}{4} \int_{\Omega} v^4 dx \leq \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v|^2 dx - \frac{1}{4|\Omega|} \left(\int_{\Omega} v^2 dx \right)^2 \quad (6.3.12)$$

by the Hölder inequality. Taking $a = b$ in (6.3.7) gives

$$\int_{\Omega} v^2 dx \geq \left(\int_{\Omega} u^2 dx - \frac{c_{39}}{\sqrt{\log j}} \right) t^2 + \frac{c_{40}}{(\log j)^{3/2}} s^2 \quad (6.3.13)$$

for some constants $c_{39}, c_{40} > 0$. For $u \in K$, (6.3.9) together with the assumption that $a \leq b$ gives

$$1 \leq \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx \leq b \int_{\Omega} u^2 dx$$

and hence

$$\int_{\Omega} u^2 dx \geq \frac{1}{b}. \quad (6.3.14)$$

Combining (6.3.12), (6.3.6), (6.3.13), and (6.3.14) gives

$$E(v) \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(1 + \frac{c_{35}}{\log j} \right) (t^2 + s^2) - \frac{1}{4|\Omega|} \left[\left(\frac{1}{b} - \frac{c_{39}}{\sqrt{\log j}} \right) t^2 + \frac{c_{40}}{(\log j)^{3/2}} s^2 \right]^2,$$

from which (6.3.10) and (6.3.11) follow for all sufficiently large $j \geq 2$. \square

Lemma 6.7. *Let K be a subset of $S \cap C^2(\Omega)$ such that (6.3.5) holds and*

$$\sup_{u \in K} I(u, a, b) < 0. \quad (6.3.15)$$

Then there exists $j_0 \geq 2$ such that

$$\sup_{u \in K, s, t \geq 0} E(tu + s \omega_{j_0, (\log j_0)^{-1/4}}) < 2\pi.$$

Proof. If the conclusion is false, then it follows from Lemma 6.6 that for all $j \geq 2$, there exist $u_j \in K$, $s_j > 0$, and $t_j \geq 0$ such that

$$E(t_j u_j + s_j \omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}}) = \sup_{u \in K, s, t \geq 0} E(tu + s \omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}}) \geq 2\pi.$$

Set $v_j = t_j u_j + s_j \omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}}$. Then

$$E(v_j) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v_j|^2 dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} [a(v_j^-)^2 + b(v_j^+)^2] dx - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (e^{v_j^2} - 1 - v_j^2) dx \geq 2\pi. \quad (6.3.16)$$

Moreover, $\tau v_j \in \{tu + s \omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}} : u \in K, s, t \geq 0\}$ for all $\tau \geq 0$ and $E(\tau v_j)$ attains its maximum at $\tau = 1$, so

$$\begin{aligned} \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} E(\tau v_j) \right|_{\tau=1} &= E'(v_j) v_j = \int_{\Omega} |\nabla v_j|^2 dx \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} [a(v_j^-)^2 + b(v_j^+)^2] dx - \int_{\Omega} (e^{v_j^2} - 1) v_j^2 dx = 0. \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.17)$$

Since $e^{v_j^2} \geq 1 + v_j^2$, it follows from (6.3.16) and (6.3.8) that

$$4\pi \leq I(v_j, a, b) \leq \left(I(u_j, a, b) + \frac{c_{38}}{\sqrt{\log j}} \right) t_j^2 + \left(1 + \frac{c_{35}}{\log j} \right) s_j^2.$$

In view of (6.3.15), this implies that for all sufficiently large $j \geq 2$,

$$4\pi + c_{41} t_j^2 \leq \left(1 + \frac{c_{35}}{\log j} \right) s_j^2 \quad (6.3.18)$$

for some constant $c_{41} > 0$. So

$$s_j^2 - 4\pi \geq -\frac{c_{42}}{\log j} \quad (6.3.19)$$

and

$$t_j \leq c_{43} s_j \quad (6.3.20)$$

for some constants $c_{42}, c_{43} > 0$.

Since $a, b > 0$, (6.3.17) gives

$$\int_{\Omega} v_j^2 e^{v_j^2} dx \leq \int_{\Omega} (|\nabla v_j|^2 + v_j^2) dx. \quad (6.3.21)$$

For $|x - x_0| \leq d/j$ and sufficiently large j ,

$$|v_j| \geq s_j \omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}} - t_j |u_j| \geq \sqrt{\frac{\log j}{2\pi}} \left(s_j - \frac{c_{44} t_j}{\sqrt{\log j}} \right) \geq c_{45} s_j \sqrt{\log j}$$

for some constants $c_{44}, c_{45} > 0$ by (6.3.5) and (6.3.20). So

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} v_j^2 e^{v_j^2} dx &\geq c_{45}^2 s_j^2 \log j e^{(s_j - c_{44} t_j / \sqrt{\log j})^2 \log j / 2\pi} \pi \left(\frac{d}{j}\right)^2 \\ &= c_{46} s_j^2 \sqrt{\log j} j^{[(s_j - c_{44} t_j / \sqrt{\log j})^2 - 4\pi] / 2\pi} \end{aligned} \quad (6.3.22)$$

for some constant $c_{46} > 0$. On the other hand, by the Poincaré inequality, (6.3.6), and (6.3.20),

$$\int_{\Omega} (|\nabla v_j|^2 + v_j^2) dx \leq c_{47} s_j^2 \quad (6.3.23)$$

for some constant $c_{47} > 0$. Combining (6.3.21)–(6.3.23) gives

$$j^{[(s_j - c_{44} t_j / \sqrt{\log j})^2 - 4\pi] / 2\pi} \leq \frac{c_{48}}{\sqrt{\log j}} \quad (6.3.24)$$

for some constant $c_{48} > 0$.

For sufficiently large j , (6.3.24) implies that

$$s_j \leq 2\sqrt{\pi} + \frac{c_{44} t_j}{\sqrt{\log j}},$$

and combining this with (6.3.18) gives

$$t_j \leq \frac{c_{49}}{\sqrt{\log j}}$$

for some constant $c_{49} > 0$. So

$$s_j t_j \leq \frac{c_{50}}{\sqrt{\log j}}$$

for some constant $c_{50} > 0$. This together with (6.3.19) gives

$$j^{[(s_j - c_{44} t_j / \sqrt{\log j})^2 - 4\pi] / 2\pi} \geq j^{[s_j^2 - 4\pi - 2c_{44} s_j t_j / \sqrt{\log j}] / 2\pi} \geq j^{-c_{51} / \log j} = e^{-c_{51}}$$

for some constant $c_{51} > 0$, contradicting (6.3.24). \square

We are now ready to prove Theorems 6.3 and 6.4.

Proof of Theorem 6.3. We apply Theorem 6.1 taking $e = \omega_{j, (\log j)^{-1/4}}$ with $j \geq 2$ sufficiently large. Functions $\omega_{j, (\log j)^{-1/4}}$ with different centers x_0 and sufficiently large j have disjoint supports and are therefore linearly independent. Since N_{l-1} is finite dimensional, it follows that $x_0 \in \Omega$ can be chosen so that $\omega_{j, (\log j)^{-1/4}} \notin N_{l-1}$.

To verify (6.1.2), we use Lemma 6.7 with $K = S \cap N_{l-1}$. For $u \in K$,

$$I(u, a, b) = 1 - \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx \leq 1 - a \int_{\Omega} u^2 dx \leq 1 - \frac{a}{\lambda_{l-1}} < 0$$

since $b \geq a > \lambda_{l-1}$, so (6.3.15) holds. By the interior regularity of eigenfunctions, $N_{l-1} \subset C^2(\Omega)$. So the restrictions of functions in N_{l-1} to $\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)}$ form a finite dimensional subspace of $C^2(\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)})$. Since the restrictions of functions in K to $\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)}$ is a subset of this subspace and is bounded in the H^1 -norm, (6.3.5) follows. \square

Proof of Theorem 6.4. We apply Theorem 6.2 taking $e = \omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}}$ with $j \geq 2$ sufficiently large. Gradients $I'(\omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}}, a, b)$ with different centers x_0 and sufficiently large j have disjoint supports and are therefore linearly independent. By Proposition 5.1, $I'(v + \tau(v, a, b), a, b) \perp M_l$ for all $v \in N_l$ and hence $\{I'(v + \tau(v, a, b), a, b) : v \in N_l\}$ is a subset of N_l . Since N_l is finite dimensional, it follows that $x_0 \in \Omega$ can be chosen so that $\pm \omega_{j,(\log j)^{-1/4}} \notin B := \{v + \tau(v, a, b) : v \in N_l\}$.

To verify (6.1.6), we use Lemma 6.7 with $K = S \cap B$. To see that (6.3.5) holds, let $u \in K$. By Proposition 5.1, $I'(u, a, b) = z_u$ for some $z_u \in N_l$. Then

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla u \cdot \nabla \zeta \, dx - \int_{\Omega} (bu^+ - au^-) \zeta \, dx = \int_{\Omega} \nabla z_u \cdot \nabla \zeta \, dx \quad \forall \zeta \in H_0^1(\Omega), \quad (6.3.25)$$

so u is a weak solution of

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta u = bu^+ - au^- - \Delta z_u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega. \end{cases}$$

Testing (6.3.25) with z_u gives

$$\|z_u\|^2 \leq \|u\| \|z_u\| + (a|u^-|_2 + b|u^+|_2) |z_u|_2,$$

and since $K \subset S$, this implies that $\{z_u : u \in K\}$ is bounded in $H_0^1(\Omega)$. By the interior regularity of eigenfunctions, $N_l \subset C^{2,\alpha}(\Omega)$. So the restrictions of functions in N_l to $\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)}$ form a finite dimensional subspace of $C^{2,\alpha}(\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)})$. Since the restrictions of functions in the set $\{z_u : u \in K\}$ to $\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)}$ is a subset of this subspace and is bounded in the H^1 -norm, it follows that this set is also bounded in $C^{2,\alpha}(\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)})$. Now it follows from standard arguments in elliptic regularity theory that K is bounded in $C^{2,\alpha}(\overline{B_{d_0}(x_0)})$.

It remains to show that (6.3.15) holds. Let $u = v + \tau(v, a, b) \in K$, where $v \in N_l$. Then

$$1 = \|u\|^2 = \|v\|^2 + \|\tau(v, a, b)\|^2 \leq c_{52} \|v\|^2$$

for some constant $c_{52} > 0$ since τ is positive homogeneous (see [153, Proposition 4.3.1]), so

$$\|v\|^2 \geq \frac{1}{c_{52}}. \quad (6.3.26)$$

Since $b > \mu_l(a)$ and μ_l is continuous,

$$b/(1 + \delta) \geq \mu_l(a/(1 + \delta))$$

if $\delta \in (0, \min\{a, b\}/\lambda_{l-1} - 1)$ is sufficiently small. Then

$$m_l(a/(1 + \delta), b/(1 + \delta)) \leq 0$$

(see (5.1.8)) and hence

$$I(z, a/(1 + \delta), b/(1 + \delta)) \leq 0,$$

where $z = v + \tau(v, a/(1 + \delta), b/(1 + \delta))$ (see (5.1.6)). By Proposition 5.1, then

$$I(u, a, b) \leq I(z, a, b) = (1 + \delta) I(z, a/(1 + \delta), b/(1 + \delta)) - \delta \|z\|^2 \leq -\delta \|z\|^2. \quad (6.3.27)$$

Since

$$\|z\|^2 = \|v\|^2 + \|\tau(v, a/(1 + \delta), b/(1 + \delta))\|^2 \geq \|v\|^2,$$

it follows from (6.3.27) and (6.3.26) that

$$I(u, a, b) \leq -\frac{\delta}{c_{52}},$$

so (6.3.15) holds. □

Nonlocal critical elliptic problems with jumping nonlinearities

In this chapter we study the existence of nontrivial solutions to the nonlocal critical growth elliptic problem with a jumping nonlinearity

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = bu^+ - au^- + |u|^{2_s^*-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (7.0.1)$$

where Ω is a bounded Lipschitz domain in \mathbb{R}^N satisfying the exterior ball condition, $(-\Delta)^s$ is the fractional Laplacian operator defined on smooth functions by

$$(-\Delta)^s u(x) = 2 \lim_{\varepsilon \searrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_\varepsilon(x)} \frac{u(x) - u(y)}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dy, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N,$$

$s \in (0, 1)$, $N > 2s$, $2_s^* = 2N/(N - 2s)$ is the fractional critical Sobolev exponent, $a, b > 0$, and $u^\pm = \max\{\pm u, 0\}$ are the positive and negative parts of u , respectively.

When $a = b = \lambda$, problem (7.0.1) reduces to the Brézis-Nirenberg problem for the fractional Laplacian

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = \lambda u + |u|^{2_s^*-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega. \end{cases} \quad (7.0.2)$$

It was shown in Servadei [169, 170] and Servadei and Valdinoci [171, 172] that this problem has a nontrivial solution in each of the following cases:

- (i) $N > 4s$ and $\lambda > 0$,
- (ii) $N = 4s$ and $\lambda > 0$ is not a Dirichlet eigenvalue of $(-\Delta)^s$ in Ω ,

(iii) $2s < N < 4s$ and $\lambda > 0$ is sufficiently large.

This extends to the fractional setting the well-known results of Brézis and Nirenberg [48] and Capozzi et al. [64] for critical Laplacian problems (see also Ambrosetti and Struwe [13] and Costa and Silva [77]).

The set $\Sigma((-\Delta)^s)$ consisting of points $(a, b) \in \mathbb{R}^2$ for which the problem

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = bu^+ - au^- & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases} \quad (7.0.3)$$

has a nontrivial solution is called the Dancer-Fučík spectrum of $(-\Delta)^s$ in Ω . Denoting by (λ_l) the sequence of Dirichlet eigenvalues of $(-\Delta)^s$, $\Sigma((-\Delta)^s)$ contains the points (λ_l, λ_l) since problem (7.0.3) reduces to the Dirichlet eigenvalue problem for $(-\Delta)^s$ when $a = b$. Moreover, it follows from the abstract results in Perera and Schechter [153, Chapter 4] that in the square

$$Q_l = (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}) \times (\lambda_{l-1}, \lambda_{l+1}),$$

$\Sigma((-\Delta)^s)$ contains two strictly decreasing curves

$$C_l : b = \nu_{l-1}(a), \quad C^l : b = \mu_l(a),$$

with

$$\nu_{l-1}(a) \leq \mu_l(a), \quad \nu_{l-1}(\lambda_l) = \lambda_l = \mu_l(\lambda_l),$$

such that the points in Q_l that are either below the lower curve C_l or above the upper curve C^l are not in $\Sigma((-\Delta)^s)$, while the points between them may or may not belong to $\Sigma((-\Delta)^s)$ when they do not coincide (see Proposition 5.2). Our main results here is the following.

Theorem 7.1. *Let $N \geq 4s$. If $(a, b) \in Q_l$ and*

$$b < \nu_{l-1}(a)$$

for some $l \geq 2$, then problem (7.0.1) has a nontrivial solution.

The issues highlighted in Chapter 5 persist in the nonlocal case. In fact, the classical linking arguments used to obtain nontrivial solutions of problem (7.0.2) in [169–171] rely on the decomposition of $H_0^s(\Omega)$ into eigenspaces of $(-\Delta)^s$. These arguments are not suitable for proving Theorem 7.1 since problem (7.0.3) is nonlinear and therefore its solution set is not a linear subspace of $H_0^s(\Omega)$ when $(a, b) \in \Sigma((-\Delta)^s)$. We will prove our existence results using an abstract existence result for problems with jumping nonlinearities and a new linking theorem based on a nonlinear splitting of the underlying space that were recently proved in Perera and Sportelli [CS1] (see Theorems 6.1, 6.2 and 5.6).

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS12]

7.1 Preliminaries

Since $u^\pm = (-u)^\mp$, u solves (7.0.3) (resp. (7.0.1)) if and only if $-u$ solves (7.0.3) (resp. (7.0.1)) with a and b interchanged. So $\Sigma(-\Delta)$ is symmetric about the line $a = b$ and we may assume without loss of generality that $a \leq b$.

Let

$$[u]_s = \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \right)^{1/2}$$

be the Gagliardo seminorm of a measurable function $u : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and let

$$H^s(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{u \in L^2(\mathbb{R}^N) : [u]_s < \infty\}$$

be the fractional Sobolev space endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_s = (|u|_2^2 + [u]_s^2)^{1/2},$$

where $|\cdot|_2$ denotes the norm in $L^2(\mathbb{R}^N)$. We work in the closed linear subspace

$$H_0^s(\Omega) = \{u \in H^s(\mathbb{R}^N) : u = 0 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega\},$$

equivalently renormed by setting $\|\cdot\| = [\cdot]_s$. Problem (7.0.1) fits into the abstract setting of the last section with $H = L^2(\Omega)$, $p(u) = u^+$, $n(u) = -u^-$, $D = H_0^s(\Omega)$, and A equal to the inverse of the solution operator $L^2(\Omega) \rightarrow H_0^s(\Omega)$, $g \mapsto u = ((-\Delta)^s)^{-1}g$ of the problem

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = g(x) & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega. \end{cases}$$

Since the embedding $H_0^s(\Omega) \hookrightarrow L^2(\Omega)$ is compact, A^{-1} is compact on $L^2(\Omega)$.

Let $0 < \lambda_1 < \dots < \lambda_l < \dots$ be the sequence of distinct eigenvalues of the problem

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)^s u = \lambda u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (7.1.1)$$

let E_l be the eigenspace of λ_l , and let

$$N_l = \bigoplus_{j=1}^l E_j.$$

We will need the following regularity result.

Lemma 7.1. *We have $N_l \subset C^s(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap C^2(\Omega)$.*

Proof. We have $N_l \subset L^\infty(\Omega)$ by Servadei and Valdinoci [171, Proposition 4]. Then $N_l \subset C^s(\mathbb{R}^N)$ by Ros-Oton and Serra [163, Proposition 1.1] and (7.1.1). Now iterating Ros-Oton and Serra [163, Proposition 1.4] shows that $N_l \subset C^2(\Omega)$. \square

The potential

$$F(u) = \frac{1}{2_s^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2_s^*} dx, \quad u \in H_0^s(\Omega)$$

clearly satisfies (F_1) and (F_2) stated in the abstract Section 6.1. It also follows from standard arguments that the associated variational functional

$$\begin{aligned} E(u) &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy - \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} [a(u^-)^2 + b(u^+)^2] dx - \frac{1}{2_s^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2_s^*} dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} I(u, a, b) - F(u) \end{aligned}$$

defined on $H_0^s(\Omega)$ satisfies (F_3) in Section 6.1 with

$$c^* = \frac{S}{N} S_{N,s}^{N/2s},$$

where

$$S_{N,s} = \inf_{u \in \dot{H}^s(\mathbb{R}^N) \setminus \{0\}} \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy}{\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u|^{2_s^*} dx \right)^{2/2_s^*}} \quad (7.1.2)$$

is the best fractional Sobolev constant and

$$\dot{H}^s(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{u \in L^{2_s^*}(\mathbb{R}^N) : [u]_s < \infty\}$$

endowed with the norm $\|\cdot\|$.

The infimum in (7.1.2) is attained on the functions

$$u_\varepsilon(x) = c_{N,s} \left(\frac{\varepsilon}{\varepsilon^2 + |x|^2} \right)^{(N-2s)/2}, \quad \varepsilon > 0,$$

where the constant $c_{N,s} > 0$ is chosen so that

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_\varepsilon(x) - u_\varepsilon(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} u_\varepsilon^{2_s^*} dx = S_{N,s}^{N/2s}$$

(see Servadei and Valdinoci [172]). Fix $x_0 \in \Omega$ and $\mu_0 > 2/\text{dist}(x_0, \partial\Omega)$. Let $\xi : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a smooth function such that $\xi(s) = 1$ for $s \leq 1/4$ and $\xi(s) = 0$ for $s \geq 1/2$. Set

$$u_{\varepsilon,\mu}(x) = \xi(\mu|x - x_0|) u_\varepsilon(x - x_0), \quad \varepsilon > 0, \mu \geq \mu_0.$$

We will apply Theorems 6.1, 6.2 and 5.6 taking $e = u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$ with $\varepsilon > 0$ sufficiently small and $\mu \geq \mu_0$ sufficiently large. We have the following estimates for u_{ε, μ_0} (see Servadei and Valdinoci [172, Propositions 21 & 22]):

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_{\varepsilon, \mu_0}(x) - u_{\varepsilon, \mu_0}(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \leq S_{N, s}^{N/2s} + c_1 \varepsilon^{N-2s}, \quad (7.1.3)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu_0}^{2_s^*} dx \geq S_{N, s}^{N/2s} - c_2 \varepsilon^N, \quad (7.1.4)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu_0}^2 dx \geq \begin{cases} c_3 \varepsilon^{2s} - c_4 \varepsilon^{N-2s} & \text{if } N > 4s \\ c_3 \varepsilon^{2s} |\log \varepsilon| - c_4 \varepsilon^{2s} & \text{if } N = 4s \\ c_3 \varepsilon^{N-2s} - c_4 \varepsilon^{2s} & \text{if } 2s < N < 4s \end{cases} \quad (7.1.5)$$

for some constants $c_1, \dots, c_4 > 0$. Noting that

$$u_{\varepsilon, \mu}(x) = \tilde{\mu}^{(N-2s)/2} u_{\tilde{\mu}\varepsilon, \mu_0}(\tilde{\mu}x),$$

where $\tilde{\mu} = \mu/\mu_0$, we get the following estimates for $u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$ from (7.1.3)–(7.1.5):

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_{\varepsilon, \mu}(x) - u_{\varepsilon, \mu}(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \leq S_{N, s}^{N/2s} + c_5 (\mu\varepsilon)^{N-2s}, \quad (7.1.6)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^{2_s^*} dx \geq S_{N, s}^{N/2s} - c_6 (\mu\varepsilon)^N, \quad (7.1.7)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^2 dx \geq \begin{cases} c_7 \varepsilon^{2s} - c_8 \mu^{N-4s} \varepsilon^{N-2s} & \text{if } N > 4s \\ c_7 \varepsilon^{2s} |\log(\mu\varepsilon)| - c_8 \varepsilon^{2s} & \text{if } N = 4s \\ c_7 \mu^{N-4s} \varepsilon^{N-2s} - c_8 \varepsilon^{2s} & \text{if } 2s < N < 4s \end{cases} \quad (7.1.8)$$

for some constants $c_5, \dots, c_8 > 0$. We will also need the following easily verified estimates:

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu} dx \leq c_9 \mu^{-2s} \varepsilon^{(N-2s)/2}, \quad (7.1.9)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} u_{\varepsilon, \mu}^{2_s^*-1} dx \leq c_{10} \varepsilon^{(N-2s)/2} \quad (7.1.10)$$

for some constants $c_9, c_{10} > 0$.

7.2 Proof of Theorem 7.1

In this section we prove Theorem 7.1 using Theorem 5.6. Let $\eta : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a smooth function such that $\eta(s) = 0$ for $s \leq 3/4$, $\eta(s) = 1$ for $s \geq 1$, and $|\eta'(s)| \leq 5$

for all s . Set

$$v_\mu(x) = \eta(\mu |x - x_0|) v(x), \quad v \in N_{l-1}, \mu \geq \mu_0.$$

We will apply Theorem 5.6 taking T to be the bounded linear map from N_{l-1} to $H_0^s(\Omega)$ given by $Tv = v_\mu$ with $\mu \geq \mu_0$ sufficiently large.

Lemma 7.2. *There exist constants $c_{29}, \dots, c_{32} > 0$ such that for all $\mu \geq \mu_0$ and $v \in N_{l-1} \cap S$,*

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|(v_\mu - v)(x) - (v_\mu - v)(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \leq c_{29} \mu^{-(N-2s)}, \quad (7.2.1)$$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|v_\mu(x) - v_\mu(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \leq \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy + c_{30} \mu^{-(N-2s)}, \quad (7.2.2)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} |v_\mu|^{2_s^*} dx \geq \int_{\Omega} |v|^{2_s^*} dx - c_{31} \mu^{-N}, \quad (7.2.3)$$

$$\int_{\Omega} [a(v_\mu^-)^2 + b(v_\mu^+)^2] dx \geq \int_{\Omega} [a(v^-)^2 + b(v^+)^2] dx - c_{32} \mu^{-N}. \quad (7.2.4)$$

In particular, for all $\tau \geq 0$,

$$E(\tau v_\mu) \leq \frac{1}{2} \left(I(v, a, b) + c_{33} \mu^{-(N-2s)} \right) \tau^2 - \frac{1}{2_s^*} \left(\int_{\Omega} |v|^{2_s^*} dx - c_{31} \mu^{-N} \right) \tau^{2_s^*}$$

for some constant $c_{33} > 0$.

Proof. First we note that since $N_{l-1} \cap S$ is bounded in $H_0^s(\Omega)$ and contained in the finite dimensional subspace N_{l-1} , which in turn is contained in $C^s(\mathbb{R}^N) \cap C^2(\Omega)$ by Lemma 7.1, $N_{l-1} \cap S$ is bounded in $C^1(\overline{B_{2/\mu_0}(x_0)}) \cap C(\overline{\Omega})$.

Since $v_\mu = v$ outside $B_{1/\mu}(x_0)$,

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|(v_\mu - v)(x) - (v_\mu - v)(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \\ & \leq \int_{B_{2/\mu} \times B_{2/\mu}} \frac{|(v_\mu - v)(x) - (v_\mu - v)(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \\ & \quad + 2 \int_{B_{1/\mu} \times B_{2/\mu}^c} \frac{|(v_\mu - v)(x)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy =: I_1 + 2I_2. \end{aligned}$$

For $(x, y) \in B_{2/\mu}(x_0) \times B_{2/\mu}(x_0)$,

$$|(v_\mu - v)(x) - (v_\mu - v)(y)| \leq \left(\sup_{B_{2/\mu}(x_0)} |\nabla(v_\mu - v)| \right) |x - y|.$$

We have

$$\nabla(v_\mu - v)(x) = (\eta(\mu|x - x_0|) - 1) \nabla v(x) + \mu \eta'(\mu|x - x_0|) \frac{x - x_0}{|x - x_0|} v(x)$$

and hence

$$|\nabla(v_\mu - v)(x)| \leq |\nabla v(x)| + 5\mu |v(x)| \leq \left(\frac{|\nabla v(x)|}{\mu_0} + 5|v(x)| \right) \mu \leq c_{34} \mu \quad \forall x \in B_{2/\mu}(x_0)$$

for some constant $c_{34} > 0$. Then

$$I_1 \leq c_{34}^2 \mu^2 \int_{B_{2/\mu} \times B_{2/\mu}} \frac{dx dy}{|x - y|^{N-2(1-s)}} \leq c_{34}^2 \mu^2 \int_{B_{2/\mu} \times B_{4/\mu}} \frac{dx dz}{|z|^{N-2(1-s)}} = c_{35} \mu^{-(N-2s)}$$

for some constant $c_{35} > 0$. On the other hand, for $(x, y) \in B_{1/\mu}(x_0) \times B_{2/\mu}(x_0)^c$,

$$|(v_\mu - v)(x)| \leq |v(x)| \leq c_{36}$$

for some constant $c_{36} > 0$ and $|x - y| \geq |y| - |x| > 1/\mu$, so

$$I_2 \leq c_{36}^2 \int_{B_{1/\mu} \times B_{1/\mu}^c} \frac{dx dz}{|z|^{N+2s}} = c_{37} \mu^{-(N-2s)}$$

for some constant $c_{37} > 0$. So (7.2.1) follows.

Proof of (7.2.2) is similar and the proofs of (7.2.3) and (7.2.4) are straightforward. \square

Lemma 7.3. *We have*

$$\sup_{v \in N_{l-1} \cap S, \sigma, \tau \geq 0} E(\tau v_\mu + \sigma u_{\varepsilon, \mu}) < \frac{S}{N} S_{N, s}^{N/2s} \quad (7.2.5)$$

for all sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$ and sufficiently large $\mu \geq \mu_0$.

Proof. For $v \in N_{l-1} \cap S$ and $\sigma, \tau \geq 0$,

$$E(\tau v_\mu + \sigma u_{\varepsilon, \mu}) = E(\tau v_\mu) + E(\sigma u_{\varepsilon, \mu}) - 2\tau\sigma \int_{B_{1/2\mu} \times B_{3/4\mu}^c} \frac{u_{\varepsilon, \mu}(x) v_\mu(y)}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \quad (7.2.6)$$

since $u_{\varepsilon, \mu} = 0$ outside $B_{1/2\mu}(x_0)$ and $v_\mu = 0$ in $B_{3/4\mu}(x_0)$. For $(x, y) \in B_{1/2\mu}(x_0) \times B_{3/4\mu}(x_0)^c$,

$$|v_\mu(y)| \leq |v(y)| \leq c_{38}$$

for some constant $c_{38} > 0$ since $N_{l-1} \cap S$ is bounded in $C(\bar{\Omega})$ as in the proof of Lemma 7.2, and $|x - y| \geq |y| - |x| > 1/4\mu$, so

$$\left| \int_{B_{1/2\mu} \times B_{3/4\mu}^c} \frac{u_{\varepsilon, \mu}(x) v_\mu(y)}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \right| \leq c_{38} \int_{B_{1/2\mu} \times B_{1/4\mu}^c} \frac{u_{\varepsilon, \mu}(x)}{|z|^{N+2s}} dx dz \leq c_{39} \varepsilon^{(N-2s)/2}$$

for some constant $c_{39} > 0$ by (7.1.9). So (7.2.6) gives

$$E(\tau v_\mu + \sigma u_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \leq E(\tau v_\mu) + c_{39} \mu^{-(N-2s)} \tau^2 + E(\sigma u_{\varepsilon, \mu}) + c_{39} (\mu \varepsilon)^{N-2s} \sigma^2. \quad (7.2.7)$$

Since $a \leq b$ and $(a, b) \in Q_l$,

$$I(v, a, b) = 1 - \int_{\Omega} [a(v^-)^2 + b(v^+)^2] dx \leq 1 - a \int_{\Omega} v^2 dx \leq 1 - \frac{a}{\lambda_{l-1}} < 0.$$

Moreover,

$$\frac{1}{\lambda_{l-1}} \leq \int_{\Omega} v^2 dx \leq |\Omega|^{2s/N} \left(\int_{\Omega} |v|^{2^*_s} dx \right)^{2/2^*_s}$$

and hence

$$\inf_{v \in N_{l-1} \cap S} \int_{\Omega} |v|^{2^*_s} dx > 0.$$

So it follows from Lemma 7.2 that

$$E(\tau v_\mu) + c_{39} \mu^{-(N-2s)} \tau^2 \leq 0$$

for all sufficiently large $\mu \geq \mu_0$. Then (7.2.7) together with (7.1.6)–(7.1.8) gives for all sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$,

$$E(\tau v_\mu + \sigma u_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \leq \begin{cases} \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 - c_{40} \varepsilon^{2s}) \sigma^2 - \frac{1}{2^*_s} (1 - c_{41} \varepsilon^N) \sigma^{2^*_s} \right] S_{N,s}^{N/2s} & \text{if } N > 4s \\ \left[\frac{1}{2} (1 - c_{40} \varepsilon^{2s} |\log \varepsilon|) \sigma^2 - \frac{1}{4} (1 - c_{41} \varepsilon^{4s}) \sigma^4 \right] S_{4s,s}^2 & \text{if } N = 4s \end{cases}$$

for some constants $c_{40}, c_{41} > 0$ depending on μ . Maximizing the right-hand side over all $\sigma \geq 0$ then gives

$$E(\tau v_\mu + \sigma u_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \leq \begin{cases} \frac{s}{N} \frac{(1 - c_{40} \varepsilon^{2s})^{N/2s}}{(1 - c_{41} \varepsilon^N)^{(N-2s)/2s}} S_{N,s}^{N/2s} & \text{if } N > 4s \\ \frac{1}{4} \frac{(1 - c_{40} \varepsilon^{2s} |\log \varepsilon|)^2}{1 - c_{41} \varepsilon^{4s}} S_{4s,s}^2 & \text{if } N = 4s, \end{cases}$$

from which the desired conclusion follows. \square

Proof of Theorem 7.1. Since $b < \nu_{l-1}(a)$ and ν_{l-1} is continuous,

$$b/(1 - \delta) \leq \nu_{l-1}(a/(1 - \delta))$$

if $\delta \in (0, 1 - \max\{a, b\}/\lambda_{l+1})$ is sufficiently small. Then

$$n_{l-1}(a/(1 - \delta), b/(1 - \delta)) \geq 0$$

(see (5.1.7)) and hence

$$I(\theta(w, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta)) + w, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta)) \geq 0 \quad \forall w \in M_{l-1} \quad (7.2.8)$$

(see (5.1.5)). For $\rho > 0$ and $w \in M_{l-1} \cap S_\rho$, set $u = \theta(w, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta)) + w$. Then

$$E(u) = \frac{\delta}{2} \|u\|^2 + \frac{1-\delta}{2} \left(\|u\|^2 - \int_{\Omega} \left[\frac{a}{1-\delta} (u^-)^2 + \frac{b}{1-\delta} (u^+)^2 \right] dx \right) - \frac{1}{2_s^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{2_s^*} dx,$$

and the quantity inside the parentheses is equal to $I(u, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta))$ and hence nonnegative by (7.2.8), so

$$E(u) \geq \frac{\delta}{2} \|u\|^2 + o(\|u\|^2) \text{ as } \|u\| \rightarrow 0.$$

Since

$$\|u\|^2 = \|\theta(w, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta))\|^2 + \|w\|^2$$

and $\|\theta(w, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta))\| = O(\|w\|)$ by positive homogeneity (see [153, Proposition 4.3.1]), it follows that

$$E(u) \geq \frac{\delta}{2} \rho^2 + o(\rho^2) \text{ as } \rho \rightarrow 0.$$

So if $\rho > 0$ is sufficiently small,

$$\inf_{u \in A} E(u) > 0, \quad (7.2.9)$$

where $A = \{\theta(w, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta)) + w : w \in M_{l-1} \cap S_\rho\}$.

We apply Theorem 5.6 taking $M = M_{l-1}$, $N = N_{l-1}$, $\theta = \theta(\cdot, a/(1-\delta), b/(1-\delta))$, $T : N_{l-1} \rightarrow H_0^s(\Omega)$ to be the bounded linear map given by

$$Tv = v_\mu, \quad v \in N_{l-1},$$

and $e = u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$, with $\varepsilon > 0$ sufficiently small and $\mu \geq \mu_0$ sufficiently large. Since $u_{\varepsilon, \mu}$ and functions in $T(N_{l-1})$ have disjoint supports, $u_{\varepsilon, \mu} \in H_0^s(\Omega) \setminus T(N_{l-1})$. We have

$$\|I - T\| = \sup_{v \in N_{l-1} \cap S} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|(v_\mu - v)(x) - (v_\mu - v)(y)|^2}{|x - y|^{N+2s}} dx dy \right)^{1/2} \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } \mu \rightarrow \infty$$

by (7.2.1), where I is the identity map on N_{l-1} . If $\mu \geq \mu_0$ is sufficiently large, $E(\tau v_\mu) \leq 0$ for all $v \in N_{l-1} \cap S$ and $\tau \geq 0$ as in the proof of Lemma 7.3, so

$$\sup_{u \in T(N_{l-1})} E(u) = 0.$$

Together with (7.2.9), this gives the first inequality in (5.2.12). The second inequality also holds by Lemma 7.3, so (5.2.13) together with (7.2.9) and (7.2.5) gives

$$0 < c := \inf_{h \in \tilde{H}} \sup_{u \in h(Q)} E(u) < \frac{S}{N} S_{N,s}^{N/2s},$$

where $\tilde{H} = \{h \in H : h|_{T(N_{l-1})} = id\}$ and H denotes the class of homeomorphisms h of $H_0^s(\Omega)$ onto itself such that h and h^{-1} map bounded sets into bounded sets. If E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition, then Theorem 5.6 gives a critical point of E at the level c , which is nontrivial since $c > 0$. If, on the other hand, E does not satisfy the $(PS)_c$ condition, then E has a $(PS)_c$ sequence without a convergent subsequence, which then has a subsequence that converges weakly to a nontrivial critical point of E (see Gazzola and Ruf [108, Lemma 1]). \square

As pointed out in the introduction, we cannot provide a result similar to Theorem 5.2 at this time. Anyway, it is subject of our ongoing investigations.

Critical elliptic problems involving local and nonlocal operators

Elliptic problems involving sums of nonlocal operators have been recently studied in the literature (see, e.g., [4, 15, 16, 39–42, 69, 111] and their references). The purpose of the present chapter is to consider critical elliptic problems involving differences of such operators. Here a new phenomenon appears: there exist two nontrivial weak solutions, one with negative energy and the other with positive energy, for all sufficiently small values of a parameter.

We consider the nonlocal problem

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)_p^s u - \mu (-\Delta)_q^t u = \lambda |u|^{p-2} u + |u|^{p_s^*-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (8.0.1)$$

where Ω is a bounded domain in \mathbb{R}^N with Lipschitz boundary, $0 < t < s < 1$, $1 < q < p < N/s$, $(-\Delta)_p^s$ is the fractional p -Laplacian operator defined on smooth functions by

$$(-\Delta)_p^s u(x) = 2 \lim_{\varepsilon \searrow 0} \int_{\mathbb{R}^N \setminus B_\varepsilon(x)} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^{p-2} (u(x) - u(y))}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dy, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}^N,$$

$p_s^* = Np/(N - sp)$ is the fractional critical Sobolev exponent, and $\lambda, \mu > 0$ are parameters. Let $|\cdot|_p$ denote the norm in $L^p(\mathbb{R}^N)$, let

$$[u]_{s,p} = \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \right)^{1/p}$$

be the Gagliardo seminorm of a measurable function $u : \mathbb{R}^N \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, and let

$$W^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{u \in L^p(\mathbb{R}^N) : [u]_{s,p} < \infty\}$$

be the fractional Sobolev space endowed with the norm

$$\|u\|_{s,p} = \left(|u|_p^p + [u]_{s,p}^p \right)^{1/p}.$$

We work in the closed linear subspace

$$W_0^{s,p}(\Omega) = \{u \in W^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) : u = 0 \text{ a.e. in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega\},$$

equivalently renormed by setting $\|\cdot\| = [\cdot]_{s,p}$. A weak solution of problem (8.0.1) is a function $u \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega)$ satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^{p-2} (u(x) - u(y)) (v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \\ & - \mu \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^{q-2} (u(x) - u(y)) (v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} dx dy - \lambda \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p-2} uv dx \\ & - \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p_s^*-2} uv dx = 0 \quad \forall v \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega). \end{aligned}$$

Weak solutions coincide with critical points of the C^1 -functional

$$\begin{aligned} E(u) = & \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy - \frac{\mu}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^q}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} dx dy - \frac{\lambda}{p} \int_{\Omega} |u|^p dx \\ & - \frac{1}{p_s^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p_s^*} dx, \quad u \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega). \end{aligned}$$

Let $\sigma((-\Delta)_p^s)$ denote the Dirichlet spectrum of $(-\Delta)_p^s$ on Ω , consisting of those $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ for which the eigenvalue problem

$$\begin{cases} (-\Delta)_p^s u = \lambda |u|^{p-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega \end{cases}$$

has a nontrivial weak solution. Let

$$\dot{W}^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) = \{u \in L^{p_s^*}(\mathbb{R}^N) : [u]_{s,p} < \infty\}$$

endowed with the norm $\|\cdot\|$, and let

$$S = \inf_{u \in \dot{W}^{s,p}(\mathbb{R}^N) \setminus \{0\}} \frac{\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy}{\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} |u|^{p_s^*} dx \right)^{p/p_s^*}} \quad (8.0.2)$$

be the best fractional Sobolev constant. We will prove the following multiplicity result.

Theorem 8.1. *Assume that $0 < t < s < 1$, $1 < q < p < N/s$, $N \geq sp^2$, and $\lambda \in (0, \infty) \setminus \sigma((-\Delta)_p^s)$. Then $\exists \mu_0, \kappa > 0$ such that problem (8.0.1) has two nontrivial weak solutions u_1 and u_2 with*

$$E(u_1) < 0 < E(u_2) < \frac{s}{N} S^{N/sp} - \kappa\mu$$

for all $\mu \in (0, \mu_0)$.

When $0 < \lambda < \lambda_1$, where $\lambda_1 > 0$ is the first Dirichlet eigenvalue of $(-\Delta)_p^s$ on Ω , this theorem can be proved using a local minimization argument and the mountain pass theorem. However, when $\lambda > \lambda_1$, the functional E no longer has the mountain pass geometry. In this case, our proof will be based on an abstract multiplicity result recently proved in Perera [151], and our solutions are neither local minimizers nor of mountain pass type. They are higher critical points in the sense that they have nontrivial higher critical groups.

Remark 8.1. When $\mu = 0$, one nontrivial weak solution u with

$$0 < E(u) < \frac{s}{N} S^{N/sp}$$

was obtained in Mosconi et al. [145].

Remark 8.2. When $s > 0$ is not an integer and $1 \leq q < p \leq \infty$, $W_0^{s,p}(\Omega) \not\subset W_0^{s,q}(\Omega)$ (see Mironescu and Sickel [143]). So when $t = s$, the functional E is not defined on $W_0^{s,p}(\Omega)$ and existence of solutions to problem (8.0.1) is an open problem.

Theorem 8.1 also holds in the limiting case $s = 1$, where we have the mixed local-nonlocal problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta_p u - \mu (-\Delta)_q^t u = \lambda |u|^{p-2} u + |u|^{p^*-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{in } \mathbb{R}^N \setminus \Omega, \end{cases} \quad (8.0.3)$$

where $0 < t < 1$, $1 < q < p < N$, $\Delta_p u = \operatorname{div}(|\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u)$ is the p -Laplacian of u , $p^* = Np/(N-p)$ is the critical Sobolev exponent, and $\lambda, \mu > 0$ are parameters. A weak solution of this problem is a function $u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ satisfying

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^{p-2} \nabla u \cdot \nabla v \, dx - \mu \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^{q-2} (u(x) - u(y)) (v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} \, dx dy \\ - \lambda \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p-2} uv \, dx - \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p^*-2} uv \, dx = 0 \quad \forall v \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega), \end{aligned}$$

where functions in $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega)$ are extended to be zero outside Ω . Weak solutions coincide with critical points of the C^1 -functional

$$\begin{aligned} E(u) = \frac{1}{p} \int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^p \, dx - \frac{\mu}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^q}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} \, dx dy - \frac{\lambda}{p} \int_{\Omega} |u|^p \, dx - \frac{1}{p^*} \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p^*} \, dx, \\ u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega). \end{aligned}$$

Let $\sigma(-\Delta_p)$ denote the Dirichlet spectrum of $-\Delta_p$ on Ω , consisting of those $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}$ for which the eigenvalue problem

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta_p u = \lambda |u|^{p-2} u & \text{in } \Omega \\ u = 0 & \text{on } \partial\Omega \end{cases}$$

has a nontrivial weak solution, and let

$$S = \inf_{u \in W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \setminus \{0\}} \frac{\int_{\Omega} |\nabla u|^p dx}{\left(\int_{\Omega} |u|^{p^*} dx \right)^{p/p^*}}$$

be the best Sobolev constant. We have the following multiplicity result.

Theorem 8.2. *Assume that $0 < t < 1$, $1 < q < p < N$, $N \geq p^2$, and $\lambda \in (0, \infty) \setminus \sigma(-\Delta_p)$. Then $\exists \mu_0, \kappa > 0$ such that problem (8.0.3) has two nontrivial weak solutions u_1 and u_2 with*

$$E(u_1) < 0 < E(u_2) < \frac{1}{N} S^{N/p} - \kappa\mu$$

for all $\mu \in (0, \mu_0)$.

Remark 8.3. When $\mu = 0$, one nontrivial weak solution u with

$$0 < E(u) < \frac{1}{N} S^{N/p}$$

was obtained in García Azorero and Peral Alonso [106], Egnell [98], Guedda and Véron [113], Arioli and Gazzola [24], and Degiovanni and Lancelotti [90].

Remark 8.4. When $t = 1$, the noncompactness of the embedding $W_0^{1,p}(\Omega) \subset W_0^{1,q}(\Omega)$ makes it difficult to verify that the functional E satisfies the (PS) condition and existence of solutions to problem (8.0.3) is an open problem.

Remark 8.5. A mixed problem arising in the description of an ecological niche subject to local and nonlocal dispersals was recently considered in Dipierro and Valdinoci [93].

In the next section we will recall the abstract result from Perera [151] that we will need to prove Theorem 8.1. In the last section we will give the proof of Theorem 8.1. Proof of Theorem 8.2 is similar and therefore omitted.

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS8].

8.1 Abstract multiplicity result

Let $(W, \|\cdot\|)$ be a uniformly convex Banach space with dual $(W^*, \|\cdot\|^*)$ and duality pairing (\cdot, \cdot) . Recall that $h \in C(W, W^*)$ is a potential operator if there is a functional

$H \in C^1(W, \mathbb{R})$, called a potential for h , such that $H' = h$. We consider the nonlinear operator equation

$$A_p u - \mu f(u) = \lambda B_p u + g(u) \quad (8.1.1)$$

in W^* , where $A_p, B_p, f, g \in C(W, W^*)$ are potential operators satisfying the following assumptions and $\lambda, \mu > 0$ are parameters:

(\mathcal{A}_1) A_p is $(p - 1)$ -homogeneous and odd for some $p \in (1, \infty)$, i.e., $A_p(tu) = |t|^{p-2} t A_p u$ for all $u \in W$ and $t \in \mathbb{R}$,

(\mathcal{A}_2) $(A_p u, v) \leq \|u\|^{p-1} \|v\|$ for all $u, v \in W$, and equality holds if and only if $\alpha u = \beta v$ for some $\alpha, \beta \geq 0$, not both zero (in particular, $(A_p u, u) = \|u\|^p$ for all $u \in W$),

(\mathcal{B}_1) B_p is $(p - 1)$ -homogeneous and odd, i.e., $B_p(tu) = |t|^{p-2} t B_p u$ for all $u \in W$ and $t \in \mathbb{R}$,

(\mathcal{B}_2) $(B_p u, u) > 0$ for all $u \in W \setminus \{0\}$, and $(B_p u, v) \leq (B_p u, u)^{(p-1)/p} (B_p v, v)^{1/p}$ for all $u, v \in W$,

(\mathcal{B}_3) B_p is a compact operator,

(\mathcal{F}_1) the potential F of f with $F(0) = 0$ satisfies $\lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{F(tu)}{|t|^p} = +\infty$ uniformly on compact subsets of $W \setminus \{0\}$,

(\mathcal{F}_2) $F(u) > 0$ for all $u \in W \setminus \{0\}$,

(\mathcal{F}_3) F is bounded on bounded subsets of W ,

(\mathcal{G}_1) the potential G of g with $G(0) = 0$ satisfies $G(u) = o(\|u\|^p)$ as $u \rightarrow 0$,

(\mathcal{G}_2) $G(u) > 0$ for all $u \in W \setminus \{0\}$,

(\mathcal{G}_3) G is bounded on bounded subsets of W ,

(\mathcal{G}_4) $\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \frac{G(tu)}{t^p} = +\infty$ uniformly on compact subsets of $W \setminus \{0\}$.

Solutions of equation (8.1.1) coincide with critical points of the C^1 -functional

$$E(u) = I_p(u) - \lambda J_p(u) - \mu F(u) - G(u), \quad u \in W,$$

where

$$I_p(u) = \frac{1}{p} (A_p u, u) = \frac{1}{p} \|u\|^p, \quad J_p(u) = \frac{1}{p} (B_p u, u)$$

are the potentials of A_p and B_p satisfying $I_p(0) = J_p(0) = 0$, respectively (see [151, Proposition 3.1]).

Let $\mathcal{M} = \{u \in W : I_p(u) = 1\}$. Then $\mathcal{M} \subset W \setminus \{0\}$ is a bounded complete symmetric C^1 -Finsler manifold radially homeomorphic to the unit sphere in W , and eigenvalues of the nonlinear eigenvalue problem

$$A_p u = \lambda B_p u \quad (8.1.2)$$

coincide with critical values of the C^1 -functional

$$\Psi(u) = \frac{1}{J_p(u)}, \quad u \in \mathcal{M}.$$

Denote by \mathcal{F} the class of symmetric subsets of \mathcal{M} and by $i(M)$ the \mathbb{Z}_2 -cohomological index of $M \in \mathcal{F}$ (see Fadell and Rabinowitz [100]). For $k \in \mathbb{N}$, let $\mathcal{F}_k = \{M \in \mathcal{F} : i(M) \geq k\}$ and set

$$\lambda_k := \inf_{M \in \mathcal{F}_k} \sup_{u \in M} \Psi(u).$$

Then $\lambda_1 = \inf \Psi(\mathcal{M}) > 0$ is the first eigenvalue of problem (8.1.2) and $\lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots$ is an unbounded sequence of eigenvalues (see Perera [150]). Moreover, denoting by $\Psi^a = \{u \in \mathcal{M} : \Psi(u) \leq a\}$ (resp. $\Psi_a = \{u \in \mathcal{M} : \Psi(u) \geq a\}$) the sublevel (resp. superlevel) sets of Ψ , we have

$$\lambda_k < \lambda_{k+1} \implies i(\Psi^{\lambda_k}) = i(\mathcal{M} \setminus \Psi_{\lambda_{k+1}}) = k$$

(see Perera et al. [152, Theorem 4.6]). The following multiplicity result was proved in Perera [151].

Theorem 8.3 ([151, Theorem 1.7]). *Assume that (\mathcal{A}_1) – (\mathcal{G}_4) hold, $\exists c_\mu > 0$ such that E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition for all $c < c_\mu$, $\lambda_k \leq \lambda < \lambda_{k+1}$, and there exist a compact symmetric subset C of Ψ^λ with $i(C) = k$ and $w_0 \in \mathcal{M} \setminus C$ such that*

$$\sup_{v \in C, \sigma, \tau \geq 0} E(\sigma v + \tau w_0) < c_\mu \quad (8.1.3)$$

for all sufficiently small $\mu > 0$. Then $\exists \mu_0 > 0$ such that equation (8.1.1) has two nontrivial solutions u_1 and u_2 with

$$E(u_1) < 0 < E(u_2) < c_\mu$$

for all $\mu \in (0, \mu_0)$.

In the next section we will apply Theorem 8.3 to prove Theorem 8.1.

8.2 Proof of Theorem 8.1

We apply Theorem 8.3 with $W = W_0^{s,p}(\Omega)$ and the operators $A_p, B_p, f, g \in C(W_0^{s,p}(\Omega), W^{-s,p'}(\Omega))$ given by

$$\begin{aligned} (A_p u, v) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^{p-2} (u(x) - u(y)) (v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy, \\ (B_p u, v) &= \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p-2} uv dx, \\ (f(u), v) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^{q-2} (u(x) - u(y)) (v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} dx dy, \\ (g(u), v) &= \int_{\Omega} |u|^{p_s^*-2} uv dx, \quad u, v \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega). \end{aligned}$$

It is easily seen that (\mathcal{A}_1) – (\mathcal{G}_4) hold.

First we determine a threshold level below which the functional E satisfies the (PS) condition.

Lemma 8.1. *Let $\mu \in (0, 1)$. Then $\exists \kappa > 0$ such that E satisfies the $(PS)_c$ condition for all*

$$c < \frac{S}{N} S^{N/sp} - \kappa \mu. \quad (8.2.1)$$

Proof. Let $c \in \mathbb{R}$ and let (u_j) be a sequence in $W_0^{s,p}(\Omega)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} E(u_j) &= \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_j(x) - u_j(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy - \frac{\mu}{q} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_j(x) - u_j(y)|^q}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} dx dy \\ &\quad - \frac{\lambda}{p} \int_{\Omega} |u_j|^p dx - \frac{1}{p_s^*} \int_{\Omega} |u_j|^{p_s^*} dx = c + o(1) \end{aligned} \quad (8.2.2)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} (E'(u_j), v) &= \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_j(x) - u_j(y)|^{p-2} (u_j(x) - u_j(y)) (v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \\ &\quad - \mu \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_j(x) - u_j(y)|^{q-2} (u_j(x) - u_j(y)) (v(x) - v(y))}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} dx dy \\ &\quad - \lambda \int_{\Omega} |u_j|^{p-2} uv dx - \int_{\Omega} |u_j|^{p_s^*-2} uv dx = o(\|v\|) \quad \forall v \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega). \end{aligned} \quad (8.2.3)$$

Taking $v = u_j$ in (8.2.3) gives

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_j(x) - u_j(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy - \mu \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_j(x) - u_j(y)|^q}{|x - y|^{N+ tq}} dx dy - \lambda \int_{\Omega} |u_j|^p dx \\ - \int_{\Omega} |u_j|^{p_s^*} dx = o(\|u_j\|). \end{aligned} \quad (8.2.4)$$

Fix $r \in (p, p_s^*)$. Dividing (8.2.4) by r and subtracting from (8.2.2) gives

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{r}\right) \|u_j\|^p - \mu \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{r}\right) [u_j]_{t,q}^q - \lambda \left(\frac{1}{p} - \frac{1}{r}\right) |u_j|_p^p + \left(\frac{1}{r} - \frac{1}{p_s^*}\right) |u_j|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} \\ & = c + \mathfrak{o}(1) + \mathfrak{o}(\|u_j\|). \end{aligned}$$

Since $t < s$ and $q < p < r < p_s^*$, this implies that $\exists a_0 > 0$, independent of $\mu \in (0, 1)$, such that $\|u_j\| \leq a_0$. So a renamed subsequence of (u_j) converges to some u weakly in $W_0^{s,p}(\Omega)$, strongly in $W^{t,q}(\Omega)$ and in $L^p(\Omega)$, and a.e. in Ω . Moreover,

$$\|u\| \leq \liminf_{j \rightarrow \infty} \|u_j\| \leq a_0.$$

Setting $\tilde{u}_j = u_j - u$, we will show that $\tilde{u}_j \rightarrow 0$ in $W_0^{s,p}(\Omega)$.

Equation (8.2.4) implies

$$\|u_j\|^p = |u_j|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} + \mu [u]_{t,q}^q + \lambda |u|_p^p + \mathfrak{o}(1), \quad (8.2.5)$$

where $|\cdot|_{p_s^*}$ denotes the $L^{p_s^*}(\Omega)$ -norm. Taking $v = u$ in (8.2.3) and passing to the limit gives

$$\|u\|^p = |u|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} + \mu [u]_{t,q}^q + \lambda |u|_p^p. \quad (8.2.6)$$

Since

$$\|\tilde{u}_j\|^p = \|u_j\|^p - \|u\|^p + \mathfrak{o}(1) \quad (8.2.7)$$

and

$$|\tilde{u}_j|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} = |u_j|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} - |u|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} + \mathfrak{o}(1)$$

by the Brézis-Lieb lemma [47, Theorem 1], (8.2.5) and (8.2.6) imply

$$\|\tilde{u}_j\|^p = |\tilde{u}_j|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} + \mathfrak{o}(1) \leq \frac{\|\tilde{u}_j\|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*}}{S^{p_s^*/p}} + \mathfrak{o}(1),$$

so

$$\|\tilde{u}_j\|^p \left(S^{N/(N-sp)} - \|\tilde{u}_j\|^{sp^2/(N-sp)} \right) \leq \mathfrak{o}(1). \quad (8.2.8)$$

On the other hand, (8.2.2) implies

$$c = \frac{1}{p} \|u_j\|^p - \frac{1}{p_s^*} |u_j|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} - \frac{\mu}{q} [u]_{t,q}^q - \frac{\lambda}{p} |u|_p^p + \mathfrak{o}(1),$$

and a straightforward calculation combining this with (8.2.5)–(8.2.7) gives

$$c = \frac{s}{N} \|\tilde{u}_j\|^p + \frac{s}{N} |u|_{p_s^*}^{p_s^*} - \mu \left(\frac{1}{q} - \frac{1}{p}\right) [u]_{t,q}^q + \mathfrak{o}(1).$$

Since $\|u\| \leq a_0$, this gives

$$\|\tilde{u}_j\|^p \leq \frac{N}{s} (c + \kappa\mu) + \mathfrak{o}(1)$$

for some constant $\kappa > 0$. Combining this with (8.2.8) shows that $\tilde{u}_j \rightarrow 0$ when (8.2.1) holds. \square

As we have noted in the introduction, the result follows from a local minimization argument and the mountain pass theorem when $0 < \lambda < \lambda_1$, so suppose $\lambda > \lambda_1$. Since $\lambda \notin \sigma((-\Delta)_p^s)$, then $\lambda_k < \lambda < \lambda_{k+1}$ for some $k \geq 1$. We apply Theorem 8.3 with

$$c_\mu = \frac{S}{N} S^{N/sp} - \kappa\mu,$$

where $\kappa > 0$ is as in Lemma 8.1. We have $\mathcal{M} = \{u \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega) : \|u\|^p = p\}$ and $\Psi(u) = p / \int_\Omega |u|^p dx$ for $u \in \mathcal{M}$. Let

$$E_0(u) = \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u(x) - u(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy - \frac{\lambda}{p} \int_\Omega |u|^p dx - \frac{1}{p_s^*} \int_\Omega |u|^{p_s^*} dx, \quad u \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega).$$

We will show that there exist a compact symmetric subset C of Ψ^λ with $i(C) = k$ and $w_0 \in \mathcal{M} \setminus C$ such that

$$\sup_{v \in C, \sigma, \tau \geq 0} E_0(\sigma v + \tau w_0) < \frac{S}{N} S^{N/sp}. \quad (8.2.9)$$

Since $E(u) \leq E_0(u)$ for all $u \in W_0^{s,p}(\Omega)$, then (8.1.3) will hold if $\mu > 0$ is sufficiently small, so the desired conclusion will follow.

We may assume without loss of generality that $0 \in \Omega$. Let $\delta_0 = \text{dist}(0, \partial\Omega)$. Since $\lambda_k < \lambda_{k+1}$, Ψ^{λ_k} has a compact symmetric subset C_0 of index k that is bounded in $L^\infty(\Omega)$ (see Mosconi et al. [145, Proposition 3.1]). Let $\eta : [0, \infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ be a smooth function such that $\eta(t) = 0$ for $t \leq 3/4$ and $\eta(t) = 1$ for $t \geq 1$, let

$$u_\delta(x) = \eta\left(\frac{|x|}{\delta}\right) u(x), \quad u \in C_0, \quad 0 < \delta \leq \delta_0/2,$$

and set

$$C = \{\pi_{\mathcal{M}}(u_\delta) : u \in C_0\},$$

where $\pi_{\mathcal{M}} : W_0^{s,p}(\Omega) \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$, $u \mapsto p^{1/p} u / \|u\|$ is the radial projection onto \mathcal{M} . The following lemma was proved in Mosconi et al. [145].

Lemma 8.2 (Mosconi et al. [145, Proposition 3.2]). *The set C is a compact symmetric subset of $\Psi^{\lambda_k + c_1 \delta^{N-sp}}$ for some constant $c_1 > 0$ and is bounded in $L^\infty(\Omega)$. If $\lambda_k + c_1 \delta^{N-sp} < \lambda_{k+1}$, then $i(C) = k$.*

Let $\delta \in (0, \delta_0/2]$ be so small that $\lambda_k + c_1 \delta^{N-sp} < \lambda$. Then C is a compact symmetric subset of Ψ^λ with $i(C) = k$ that is bounded in $L^\infty(\Omega)$ by Lemma 8.2. We will show that $\exists w_0 \in \mathcal{M} \setminus C$ with support in $B_{\delta/2}(0)$ such that (8.2.9) holds.

Recall that there exists a nonnegative, radially symmetric, and decreasing minimizer $U(x) = U(r)$, $r = |x|$ for S satisfying

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|U(x) - U(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} U(x)^{p_s^*} dx = S^{N/sp}$$

and

$$c_2 r^{-(N-sp)/(p-1)} \leq U(r) \leq c_3 r^{-(N-sp)/(p-1)} \quad \forall r \geq 1 \quad (8.2.10)$$

for some constants $c_2, c_3 > 0$ (see Brasco et al. [45]). Then the functions

$$u_\varepsilon(x) = \varepsilon^{-(N-sp)/p} U\left(\frac{|x|}{\varepsilon}\right), \quad \varepsilon > 0$$

are also minimizers for S satisfying

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|u_\varepsilon(x) - u_\varepsilon(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy = \int_{\mathbb{R}^N} u_\varepsilon(x)^{p_s^*} dx = S^{N/sp}$$

and

$$\frac{U(\theta r)}{U(r)} \leq \frac{c_3}{c_2} \theta^{-(N-sp)/(p-1)} \leq \frac{1}{2} \quad \forall r \geq 1$$

if $\theta > 1$ is a sufficiently large constant. Let

$$u_{\varepsilon,\delta}(x) = \begin{cases} u_\varepsilon(x) & \text{if } |x| \leq \delta \\ \frac{u_\varepsilon(\delta)(u_\varepsilon(x) - u_\varepsilon(\theta\delta))}{u_\varepsilon(\delta) - u_\varepsilon(\theta\delta)} & \text{if } \delta < |x| < \theta\delta \\ 0 & \text{if } |x| \geq \theta\delta \end{cases}$$

and

$$w_{\varepsilon,\delta}(x) = \frac{u_{\varepsilon,\delta}(x)}{\left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} u_{\varepsilon,\delta}(x)^{p_s^*} dx\right)^{1/p_s^*}}$$

for $0 < \delta \leq \delta_0/2$. Then

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} w_{\varepsilon,\delta}(x)^{p_s^*} dx = 1 \quad (8.2.11)$$

and for $\varepsilon \leq \delta/2$ we have the estimates

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|w_{\varepsilon,\delta}(x) - w_{\varepsilon,\delta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \leq S + c_4 (\varepsilon/\delta)^{(N-sp)/(p-1)}, \quad (8.2.12)$$

$$\int_{\mathbb{R}^N} w_{\varepsilon,\delta}^p(x) dx \geq \begin{cases} c_5 \varepsilon^{sp} & \text{if } N > sp^2 \\ c_5 \varepsilon^{sp} |\log(\varepsilon/\delta)| & \text{if } N = sp^2 \end{cases} \quad (8.2.13)$$

for some constants $c_4, c_5 > 0$ (see Mosconi et al. [145, Lemma 2.7]). Let

$$w_0 = \pi_{\mathcal{M}}(w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}).$$

Since functions in C have their supports in $\Omega \setminus B_{3\delta/4}(0)$, while the support of w_0 is in $\overline{B_{\delta/2}(0)}$, $w_0 \in \mathcal{M} \setminus C$. We will show that (8.2.9) holds if $\varepsilon, \delta > 0$ are sufficiently small.

Note that (8.2.9) is equivalent to

$$\sup_{v \in C, \sigma, \tau \geq 0} E_0(\sigma v + \tau w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}) < \frac{S}{N} S^{N/sp}. \quad (8.2.14)$$

Since each $v \in C$ and $w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}$ have disjoint supports,

$$\begin{aligned} E_0(\sigma v + \tau w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}) &= \frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|(\sigma v(x) + \tau w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(x)) - (\sigma v(y) + \tau w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y))|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \\ &\quad - \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\lambda \sigma^p}{p} |v|^p + \frac{\sigma^{p_s^*}}{p_s^*} |v|^{p_s^*} \right) dx - \int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\lambda \tau^p}{p} w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}^p + \frac{\tau^{p_s^*}}{p_s^*} w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}^{p_s^*} \right) dx. \end{aligned} \quad (8.2.15)$$

Denote by I the first integral on the right-hand side and set $\alpha = N - sp > 0$.

Lemma 8.3. For $v \in C$ and $\sigma, \tau \geq 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} I &\leq \sigma^p \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy + p c_6 \delta^\alpha \right) \\ &\quad + \tau^p \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(x) - w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy + c_7 (\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} \right) \end{aligned}$$

for some constants $c_6, c_7 > 0$.

Proof. Since $\text{supp } v \subset B_{3\delta/4}^c$ and $\text{supp } w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta} \subset \overline{B_{\delta/2}}$,

$$\begin{aligned} I &\leq \sigma^p \int_{B_{\delta/2}^c \times B_{\delta/2}^c} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \\ &\quad + \tau^p \int_{B_{3\delta/4} \times B_{3\delta/4}} \frac{|w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(x) - w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \\ &\quad + 2 \int_{B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2}} \frac{|\sigma v(x) - \tau w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy =: \sigma^p I_1 + \tau^p I_2 + 2I_3. \end{aligned} \quad (8.2.16)$$

First suppose $p \geq 2$. To estimate I_3 , we use the elementary inequality

$$|a + b|^p \leq |a|^p + |b|^p + C_p (|a|^{p-1}|b| + |a||b|^{p-1}) \quad \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R}$$

for some constant $C_p > 0$. Since $v(y) = 0$ for $y \in B_{\delta/2}$ and $w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(x) = 0$ for $x \in B_{3\delta/4}^c$, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_3 &\leq \sigma^p \int_{B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2}} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\quad + \tau^p \int_{B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2}} \frac{|w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(x) - w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \\
 &\quad + C_p \left(\sigma^{p-1} \tau \int_{B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2}} \frac{|v(x)|^{p-1} w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \right. \\
 &\quad \quad \left. + \sigma \tau^{p-1} \int_{B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2}} \frac{|v(x)| w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)^{p-1}}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \right) \\
 &=: \sigma^p I_4 + \tau^p I_5 + C_p (\sigma^{p-1} \tau J_1 + \sigma \tau^{p-1} J_{p-1}), \quad (8.2.17)
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$$J_q = \int_{B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2}} \frac{|v(x)|^{p-q} w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)^q}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy, \quad q = 1, p-1.$$

Since C is bounded in $L^\infty(\Omega)$ and

$$|x - y| \geq |x| - |y| > |x| - \frac{\delta}{2} \geq |x| - \frac{2}{3}|x| = \frac{|x|}{3} \quad \forall (x, y) \in B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2},$$

we have

$$J_q \leq c_8 \int_{B_{3\delta/4}^c \times B_{\delta/2}} \frac{w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)^q}{|x|^{N+sp}} dx dy = c_9 \delta^{-sp} \int_{B_{\delta/2}} w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)^q dy \quad (8.2.18)$$

for some constants $c_8, c_9 > 0$. By Mosconi et al. [145, Lemma 2.7], $|u_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}|_{p_s^*}$ is bounded away from zero and hence

$$\int_{B_{\delta/2}} w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)^q dy \leq c_{10} \int_{B_{\delta/2}} u_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)^q dy \quad (8.2.19)$$

for some constant $c_{10} > 0$. Noting that $u_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta} \leq u_\varepsilon$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_{B_{\delta/2}} u_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}(y)^q dy &\leq \int_{B_{\delta/2}} u_\varepsilon(y)^q dy = \varepsilon^{-\alpha q/p} \int_{B_{\delta/2}} U\left(\frac{|y|}{\varepsilon}\right)^q dy \\
 &= \varepsilon^{N-\alpha q/p} \int_{B_{\delta/2\varepsilon}} U(|y|)^q dy. \quad (8.2.20)
 \end{aligned}$$

When $q < N(p-1)/\alpha$, (8.2.10) gives

$$\int_{B_{\delta/2\varepsilon}} U(|y|)^q dy \leq c_{11} (\delta/\varepsilon)^{N-\alpha q/(p-1)} \quad (8.2.21)$$

for some constant $c_{11} > 0$, in particular, (8.2.21) holds for $q = 1$ when $p > 2N/(N+s)$ and for $q = p-1$. Combining (8.2.18)–(8.2.21) gives

$$J_q \leq c_{12} \delta^{\alpha(p-q-1)/(p-1)} \varepsilon^{\alpha q/p(p-1)}$$

for some constant $c_{12} > 0$. So

$$\sigma^{p-q} \tau^q J_q \leq c_{12} (\delta^\alpha \sigma^p)^{1-q/p} ((\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} \tau^p)^{q/p} \leq c_{13} \delta^\alpha \sigma^p + c_{14} (\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} \tau^p$$

for some constants $c_{13}, c_{14} > 0$ by Young's inequality. Combining this with (8.2.16) and (8.2.17), and noting that

$$I_1+2I_4 = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy, \quad I_2+2I_5 = \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}(x) - w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy,$$

we get the desired conclusion in this case.

If $1 < p < 2$, we use the elementary inequality

$$|a + b|^p \leq |a|^p + |b|^p + p|a||b|^{p-1} \quad \forall a, b \in \mathbb{R}$$

to get

$$I_3 \leq \sigma^p I_4 + \tau^p I_5 + p \sigma \tau^{p-1} J_{p-1}$$

and proceed as above. \square

By (8.2.15) and Lemma 8.3,

$$E_0(\sigma v + \tau w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}) \leq E_0(\sigma v) + c_6 \delta^\alpha \sigma^p + E_0(\tau w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}) + \frac{c_7}{p} (\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} \tau^p. \quad (8.2.22)$$

Since $C \subset \Psi^{\lambda_k + c_1 \delta^\alpha}$ by Lemma 8.2,

$$\begin{aligned} E_0(\sigma v) + c_6 \delta^\alpha \sigma^p &\leq \sigma^p \left(\frac{1}{p} \int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|v(x) - v(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy - \frac{\lambda}{p} \int_{\Omega} |v|^p dx + c_6 \delta^\alpha \right) \\ &= \sigma^p \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{\Psi(v)} + c_6 \delta^\alpha \right) \leq \sigma^p \left(1 - \frac{\lambda}{\lambda_k + c_1 \delta^\alpha} + c_6 \delta^\alpha \right) \leq 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8.2.23)$$

if $\delta > 0$ is sufficiently small. By (8.2.11),

$$\begin{aligned} E_0(\tau w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}) + \frac{c_7}{p} (\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} \tau^p &= \frac{\tau^p}{p} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}(x) - w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \lambda \int_{\Omega} w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}^p dx + c_7 (\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} \right) - \frac{\tau^{p_s^*}}{p_s^*} \\ &\leq \frac{s}{N} \left(\int_{\mathbb{R}^{2N}} \frac{|w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}(x) - w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}(y)|^p}{|x - y|^{N+sp}} dx dy - \lambda \int_{\Omega} w_{\varepsilon,\delta/2\theta}^p dx + c_7 (\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} \right)^{N/sp}. \end{aligned} \quad (8.2.24)$$

Combining (8.2.22)–(8.2.24) with (8.2.12) and (8.2.13) gives

$$\sup_{v \in C, \sigma, \tau \geq 0} E_0(\sigma v + \tau w_{\varepsilon, \delta/2\theta}) \leq \begin{cases} \frac{s}{N} (S + c_{15} (\varepsilon/\delta)^{\alpha/(p-1)} - \lambda c_{16} \varepsilon^{sp})^{N/sp} & \text{if } N > sp^2 \\ \frac{s}{N} (S + c_{15} (\varepsilon/\delta)^{sp} - \lambda c_{16} \varepsilon^{sp} |\log(\varepsilon/\delta)|)^{N/sp} & \text{if } N = sp^2 \end{cases}$$

for some constants $c_{15}, c_{16} > 0$, and (8.2.14) follows from this for sufficiently small $\varepsilon > 0$. \square

PART III

**New existence results for some
relativistic equations with singular
terms**

Szulkin's critical point theory

In this last part of the thesis, we investigate the existence of T -periodic solutions of the relativistic Lorentz force equation

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1 - |q'|^2}} \right)' = E(t, q) + q' \times B(t, q) \quad (9.0.1)$$

where

$$E = -\nabla_q V - \frac{\partial W}{\partial t}, \quad B = \text{curl}_q W,$$

and of the relativistic pendulum-type equation

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1 - (q')^2}} \right)' + q = G'(q) + h(t), \quad (9.0.2)$$

with $V : [0, T] \times (\mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{0\}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, $W : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$, $G : \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $h \in L^1(0, T)$.

Before getting into details and reveal the assumptions on the involved functions, we focus formerly on the relativistic nature of our equations, which turns out on their left hand side and involves the relativistic momentum introduced by Poincaré in [156], with the velocity of light in the vacuum and the charge-to-mass ratio normalized to one, for simplicity.

The presence of the relativistic momentum makes very difficult the study of the dynamics of these equations, which e.g. for (9.0.1) are limited to the identification of exact solutions for particular cases of simple electromagnetic fields (uniform and static fields [123], circular, linear or elliptically polarized electromagnetic waves [1, 17, 173] and other variants).

One of the main reasons of the lack of qualitative results is that a neat and rigorous variational approach was not available.

It is well known that (9.0.1) is formally the Euler–Lagrange equation of the relativistic Lagrangian

$$\mathcal{L}(t, q, q') = 1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'|^2} + q' \cdot W(t, q) - V(t, q)$$

(see [102]). More precisely, observe that the second part of right hand side of the previous equation

$$L(t, q, q') = q' \cdot W(t, q) - V(t, q), \quad (t, q, q') \in [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3$$

is a smooth function that accounts for the effect of the fields on the particle, while the term $1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'|^2}$ is only defined for $|q'| \leq 1$ and it is not differentiable. This means that the corresponding action functional

$$\mathcal{I}(q) := \int_0^T \mathcal{L}(t, q, q') dt$$

is not of class C^1 and the classical critical point theory [12, 160] is not applicable. This lack of regularity has been a serious obstacle for the adequate development of a proper critical point theory for equation (9.0.1) for many years.

The best fitting theory to the problems which we study here, is that one developed by Szulkin in [178] which concerns energy functionals of the form $\Psi + \mathcal{F}$ with Ψ being an $\overline{\mathbb{R}}$ -valued, proper, convex and lower semicontinuous functional and \mathcal{F} being of class C^1 . We briefly recall in the following its main features.

Let E be a real Banach space and let \mathcal{I} be a functional on E such that

$$\mathcal{I} = \Psi + \mathcal{F}, \tag{9.0.3}$$

where $\mathcal{F} \in C^1(E, \mathbb{R})$ and $\Psi : (-\infty, +\infty] \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is proper, convex and lower semicontinuous. We define $\text{dom}(\Psi)$ be the effective domain of Ψ , i.e.

$$\text{dom}(\Psi) = \{u \in E : \Psi(u) < +\infty\}.$$

and the subdifferential of Ψ at u is the set

$$\partial\Psi(u) = \{u^* \in E^* : (u^*, v - u) \leq \Psi(v) - \Psi(u) \text{ for all } v \in \text{dom}(\Psi)\}.$$

The elements u^* are the subgradients at u . If Ψ is Gâteaux differentiable at $u \in E$, thus $\partial\Psi(u) = \Psi'(u)$.

Definition 9.1. A point $u \in E$ is said to be a critical point of the functional \mathcal{I} if

$$-\mathcal{F}'(u) \in \partial\Psi(u)$$

or, equivalently, if $u \in \text{dom}(\Psi)$ and satisfies the inequality

$$\langle \mathcal{F}'(u), v - u \rangle + \Psi(v) - \Psi(u) \geq 0 \quad \forall v \in E.$$

As in the classical (smooth) case, in order to have minimax theorems a compactness condition (the well known Palais-Smale condition) is needed. For functionals as in (9.0.3), Szulkin developed the Palais Smale condition as follows.

Definition 9.2. We say that $(u_n)_n$ is a $(PS)_c$ sequence for \mathcal{I} in (9.0.3) if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow +\infty} \mathcal{I}(u_n) = c \in \mathbb{R}$$

and there exists $\varepsilon_n > 0$ with $\varepsilon_n \rightarrow 0$ such that

$$\langle \mathcal{F}'(u_n), v - u_n \rangle + \Psi(v) - \Psi(u_n) \geq -\varepsilon_n \|v - u_n\|_E \quad \forall v \in E.$$

By using these features, Szulkin has proved a suitable version of the Mountain Pass theorem for nonsmooth functionals (see [178, Theorem 3.2]), but also other results concerning the existence of multiple critical points for even functions (see [178, Theorems 4.3, 4.4]).

In our case, the presence of a magnetic field and singular terms (a singular electric field in the case of (9.0.1) and a singular potential in (9.0.2)) require some shrewdness. In fact, as we are forced to define the action functional in the Sobolev space of the functions such that each component is Lipschitz with periodic boundary conditions, we cannot expect the convergence in this space of a subsequence of every Palais–Smale sequence. Thus, Szulkin's critical point theory is not directly applicable.

In [18] a Mountain Pass Theorem without compactness conditions is given for the Szulkin critical point theory [178]. We give here an even more general version which will be useful to handle functionals having singularities. Our abstract result relies upon the idea developed in [9] to address the study of a relativistic spherical pendulum. In particular, it will be essential to impose for the action functional \mathcal{I} that $\mathcal{I}(q_n)$ blows up when $\{q_n\}$ converges uniformly to a function which “touches” the singular set of \mathcal{I} (see (9.0.4) below and compare with Lemma 5.1 in [9]).

This new result is contained in [CS9].

Theorem 9.1. Assume that Λ is an open subset of a Banach space E and that the functional \mathcal{I} is the sum of two functionals $\mathcal{I} = \Psi + \mathcal{F}$ where

(i) $\Psi : E \rightarrow (-\infty, +\infty]$ is a convex and proper functional with a closed domain $\text{Dom } \Psi := \{v \in E : \Psi(v) < \infty\}$ in E and Ψ is continuous in $\text{Dom } \Psi$.

(ii) $\mathcal{F} : \Lambda \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is a C^1 -functional.

Assume also that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = +\infty, \tag{9.0.4}$$

for every sequence $\{q_n\} \subset \Lambda$ whose distance $\text{dist}(q_n, E \setminus \Lambda)$ is converging to zero. Let also K be a compact metric space, $K_0 \subset K$ a closed subset and $\gamma_0 : K_0 \rightarrow \Lambda$ a continuous map. Consider the set

$$\Gamma_\Lambda = \{\gamma : K \rightarrow \Lambda : \gamma \text{ is continuous and } \gamma|_{K_0} = \gamma_0\}.$$

If

$$c_1 := \sup_{t \in K_0} \mathcal{I}(\gamma_0(t)) < c := \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma_\Lambda} \sup_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)) < \infty, \tag{9.0.5}$$

then, for every $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\gamma \in \Gamma_\Lambda$ such that

$$c \leq \max_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \quad (9.0.6)$$

there exist $\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon \in \Gamma_\Lambda$ and $q_\varepsilon \in \bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(K) \subset E$ satisfying

$$c \leq \max_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t)) \leq \max_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2},$$

$$\max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t) - \gamma(t)\| \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon},$$

$$c - \varepsilon \leq \mathcal{I}(q_\varepsilon) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2},$$

and

$$\Psi(\varphi) - \Psi(q_\varepsilon) + \mathcal{F}'(q_\varepsilon)[\varphi - q_\varepsilon] \geq -\sqrt{\varepsilon}\|\varphi - q_\varepsilon\| \quad \text{for all } \varphi \in E.$$

Remark 9.1. Notice that the continuity of Ψ in its closed domain implies that Ψ is lower semicontinuous in E .

Proof. Let Γ be defined as

$$\Gamma = \{\gamma : K \rightarrow E : \gamma \text{ is continuous and } \gamma|_{K_0} = \gamma_0\},$$

which is a complete metric space endowed with the uniform distance

$$d_\Gamma(\gamma_1, \gamma_2) = \max_{t \in K} \|\gamma_1(t) - \gamma_2(t)\|, \quad (\gamma_1, \gamma_2 \in \Gamma).$$

Since Λ is open in E and K is compact, the set $\Gamma_\Lambda = \{\gamma \in \Gamma : \gamma(t) \in \Lambda\}$ is open in Γ . Consider the functional $\Upsilon : \Gamma_\Lambda \rightarrow (-\infty, +\infty]$ given by

$$\Upsilon(\gamma) = \sup_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)), \quad (\gamma \in \Gamma_\Lambda).$$

Observe that every γ in the domain of Υ , that is, verifying $\Upsilon(\gamma) < +\infty$, satisfies that $\gamma(t) \in \text{Dom } \Psi$ for every $t \in K$. Hence, the continuity of Ψ in its closed domain implies that $\mathcal{I} \circ \gamma$ is continuous in the compact K and we have

$$\Upsilon(\gamma) = \max_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)).$$

By (9.0.5) the functional Υ is proper and bounded from below by c_1 . Fix $\varepsilon > 0$ that, without loss of generality, can be assumed less than $c - c_1$. Let $\gamma \in \Gamma_\Lambda$ satisfying (9.0.6). For $0 < \mu < \mu_0 := d_\Gamma(\gamma, \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_\Lambda)$, we consider the set

$$\mathcal{N}_\mu := \{\eta \in \Gamma : d_\Gamma(\eta, \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_\Lambda) \geq \mu\},$$

which clearly contains γ . By (9.0.5) and (9.0.6) we have

$$c \leq c_{\delta_0} := \inf_{\bar{\gamma} \in \mathcal{N}_\mu} \sup_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\bar{\gamma}(t)) \leq \max_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2},$$

i.e.,

$$c \leq c_{\delta_0} := \inf_{\bar{\gamma} \in \mathcal{N}_\mu} \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}) \leq \Upsilon(\gamma) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2},$$

Taking into account that \mathcal{N}_μ is closed in the complete metric space Γ , we obtain that it is also a complete metric space. In addition, Υ is lower semicontinuous in \mathcal{N}_μ by [178, Lemma 3.1]. Applying the Ekeland variational principle [99], we deduce from the above inequality that there exists $\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu} \in \mathcal{N}_\mu$ satisfying

$$c \leq c_{\delta_0} \leq \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu}) \leq \Upsilon(\gamma) \leq c + \frac{\varepsilon}{2}, \quad (9.0.7)$$

$$d_\Gamma(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu}, \gamma) = \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu}(t) - \gamma(t)\| \leq \sqrt{\varepsilon},$$

and

$$\Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu}) < \Upsilon(\vartheta) + \sqrt{\varepsilon} d_\Gamma(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu}, \vartheta) \quad \text{for all } \vartheta \in \mathcal{N}_\mu. \quad (9.0.8)$$

We claim that there exists $\mu \in (0, \mu_0)$ such that $\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu} \in \overset{\circ}{\mathcal{N}}_\mu$ (i.e., $d_\Gamma(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu}, \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_\Lambda) < \mu$). Indeed, assume by contradiction that

$$d_\Gamma(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu}, \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_\Lambda) = \mu, \quad \forall \mu \in (0, \mu_0).$$

In this case, it is possible to choose sequences $\{\mu_n\} \subset (0, \mu_0)$ and $\{\eta_n\} \subset \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_\Lambda$ satisfying

$$d_\Gamma(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}, \eta_n) = \max_{t \in K} \|\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}(t) - \eta_n(t)\| = \mu_n \xrightarrow{(n \rightarrow \infty)} 0.$$

Since $\eta_n \in \Gamma \setminus \Gamma_\Lambda$, there exists $t_n \in K$ such that $\eta_n(t_n) \in E \setminus \Lambda$ and using that $\|\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}(t_n) - \eta_n(t_n)\| \leq d_\Gamma(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}, \eta_n)$, we infer from the above convergence to zero that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \|\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}(t_n) - \eta_n(t_n)\| = 0,$$

and by assumption (9.0.4) that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}(t_n)) = +\infty.$$

By the inequality $\mathcal{I}(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}(t_n)) \leq \max_{t \in K} \mathcal{I}(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}(t)) = \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n})$, it follows that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu_n}) = +\infty,$$

contradicting (9.0.7). The claim has been proved and thus there exists $\mu \in (0, \mu_0)$ such that $\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu} \in \overset{\circ}{\mathcal{N}}_\mu$. In the sequel we fix this constant μ and we denote $\bar{\gamma}_{\varepsilon, \mu} = \bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon$. We conclude the proof by showing the existence of $t_\varepsilon \in \mathcal{T} := \{t \in K : \mathcal{I}(\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t)) \geq c - \varepsilon\}$ such that, if $q_\varepsilon = \bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t_\varepsilon)$, then

$$\Psi(\varphi) - \Psi(q_\varepsilon) + \mathcal{F}'(q_\varepsilon)[\varphi - q_\varepsilon] \geq -\sqrt{\varepsilon} \|\varphi - q_\varepsilon\| \quad \text{for all } \varphi \in E.$$

Indeed, assume by contradiction that for every $t \in \mathcal{T}$ there exists $\varphi_t \in E \setminus \{\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t)\}$ such that

$$\Psi(\varphi_t) - \Psi(\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t)) + \mathcal{F}'(\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t))[\varphi_t - \bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t)] < -\sqrt{\varepsilon}\|\varphi_t - \bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon(t)\|.$$

We can repeat the argument in the proof of Theorem 1 in Section 2 of [18] to deduce for every sufficiently small $\delta > 0$ the existence of $\gamma^* \in \Gamma$ such that

$$d_\Gamma(\gamma^*, \bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon) \leq \delta,$$

and

$$\Upsilon(\gamma^*) < \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon) - \delta\sqrt{\varepsilon} \leq \Upsilon(\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon) - d_\Gamma(\gamma^*, \bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon)\sqrt{\varepsilon}.$$

The first inequality allows to choose $\delta > 0$ such that $\gamma^* \in \mathcal{N}_\mu$ (remind that $\bar{\gamma}_\varepsilon \in \overset{\circ}{\mathcal{N}}_\mu$) and then the second inequality contradicts (9.0.8) and completes the proof. \square

Relativistic Lorentz force equation with a singular electric potential

In this chapter, we address the study of the relativistic Lorentz force equation

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1-|q'|^2}} \right)' = E(t, q) + q' \times B(t, q). \quad (10.0.1)$$

where the electric and magnetic fields, respectively E and B , are given by

$$E = -\nabla_q V - \frac{\partial W}{\partial t}, \quad B = \text{curl}_q W, \quad (10.0.2)$$

with $V : [0, T] \times (\mathbb{R}^3 \setminus \{0\}) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ and $W : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ two C^1 -functions.

As pointed out in Chapter 9, the presence of the relativistic momentum makes the study of the dynamics of these equations very challenging.

For that reason, a rigorous mathematical variational approach for its study was developed only recently in [18, 19] (see also [36] for the case $B \equiv 0$) where the maps V and W are assumed to be of class C^1 . On the other hand, the relevant cases including configurations of electric fields coming from the physical models and consisting of singular electric potential, had remained open.

An early result concerning these singular models was achieved recently in [107] via a topological argument. In that work, the authors consider the case that the electric field E is a sufficiently large L^1 -perturbation of a Coulomb electric potential, or more specifically, $E(t, q) = -\nabla V(q) - h(t)$ with $h \in L^1([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$. The potential V is assumed to be singular at zero and, for some $\gamma \geq 1$, $c > 0$, satisfies the inequality $q \cdot \nabla V(q) \leq -c/|q|^\gamma$ if $|q|$ is small enough. On the other hand, the magnetic field B is supposed to be bounded with a singularity at zero of lower order than the singularity $|q|^{-\gamma-1}$. Applying a global continuation theorem, the existence of a T periodic solution is guaranteed only when the mean value \bar{h} of h is greater than the supremum of

$C(t) := \limsup_{|q| \rightarrow \infty} |B(t, q)|$. However, this result clearly fails if e.g., h is identically zero. Also, we emphasize that the problem to address the study of Lorentz force equation by employing a variational approach when V is singular at a point, had still remained open.

In this chapter we develop the variational framework needed to address equation (10.0.1) and other relativistic singular problems as well, establishing the landmark for future investigations related on these topics and filling the mentioned gaps. To be more precise, we show not only that equation (10.0.1) can be studied using a variational approach even when the electric field E is singular, widening the range of possible choices of V and covering the case untreated in [18, 19]; but also, we prove that the topological argument carried on in [107] can be employed in such a way to handle other kinds of relativistic problems in which appears a singular term (see Section 11.2).

The results presented in this chapter are contained in [CS9].

10.1 The compactness condition

We denote by $W^{1,\infty}(0, T)$ the space of all Lipschitz functions in $[0, T]$ (or equivalently the absolutely continuous functions in $[0, T]$ with bounded derivatives) and we consider the Banach space

$$E = W_T^{1,\infty} = [W^{1,\infty}(0, T)]^3$$

endowed with the norm $\|\cdot\|$ defined from the usual norm $\|\cdot\|_\infty$ of $[L^\infty(0, T)]^3$ as

$$\|q\| = \|q\|_\infty + \|q'\|_\infty \quad (q \in W^{1,\infty}).$$

We consider also the subspace E of all T -periodic vector functions $q \in W^{1,\infty}$ (i.e. $q \in W^{1,\infty}$ such that $q(0) = q(T)$). Let also \mathcal{K} be the convex and closed set given by

$$\mathcal{K} = \{q \in E : \|q'\|_\infty \leq 1\},$$

and

$$\Lambda = \{q \in E : q(t) \neq 0, \forall t \in [0, T]\}, \quad \mathcal{K}_\Lambda = \mathcal{K} \cap \Lambda.$$

Following [18] the Lagrangian action $\mathcal{I} : \Lambda \rightarrow (-\infty, +\infty]$ associated to the problem of the existence of T -periodic solutions of the Lorentz force equation (10.0.1) is given by

$$\mathcal{I}(q) = \Psi(q) + \mathcal{F}(q), \quad q \in \Lambda.$$

where the functionals Ψ and \mathcal{F} are defined by

$$\Psi(q) = \begin{cases} \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'|^2}] dt, & \text{if } q \in \mathcal{K}, \\ +\infty, & \text{if } q \in E \setminus \mathcal{K}, \end{cases}$$

$$\mathcal{F}(q) := \int_0^T [q' \cdot W(t, q) - V(t, q)] dt, \quad \forall q \in \Lambda.$$

Since Ψ is a proper convex function which is continuous in its domain \mathcal{K} (similar proof to that of Lemma 2 in Section 3 of [18]) and \mathcal{F} is a function of class C^1 in \mathcal{K}_Λ , Szulkin's critical point theory from [178] is applicable for \mathcal{I} . We specialize Definition 9.1 to our setting.

Definition 10.1. A function $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ is a critical point of \mathcal{I} if

$$\Psi(\varphi) - \Psi(q) + \mathcal{F}'(q)[\varphi - q] \geq 0 \quad \text{for all } \varphi \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda,$$

or, equivalently, for $\mathcal{E} : [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3 \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^3$ given by

$$\mathcal{E}(t, q, p) = (p \cdot D_{q_1} W(t, q), p \cdot D_{q_2} W(t, q), p \cdot D_{q_3} W(t, q)), \quad \forall (t, q, p) \in [0, T] \times \mathbb{R}^3 \times \mathbb{R}^3,$$

if

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^T [\sqrt{1 - |q'|^2} - \sqrt{1 - |\varphi'|^2}] dt + \int_0^T [\mathcal{E}(t, q, q') - \nabla_q V(t, q)] \cdot (\varphi - q) dt \\ & \quad + \int_0^T W(t, q) \cdot (\varphi' - q') dt \geq 0, \quad \text{for all } \varphi \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda. \end{aligned}$$

By a similar argument to this one in Theorem 2 of Section 3 in [18], we have that the critical points $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} are just the T -periodic solutions of (10.0.1).

The following lemma will be essential to control the singularity of V at $q = 0$.

Lemma 10.1. Assume that W is bounded and V satisfies the following hypotheses:

(V_0) There exists $c_0 > 0$ such that

$$\limsup_{q \rightarrow 0} V(t, q)|q| \leq -c_0 < 0.$$

If a sequence $\{q_n\}$ in \mathcal{K}_Λ converges uniformly to some q on the boundary of Λ in E , then

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt = -\infty \quad \text{and} \quad \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = +\infty.$$

Remark 10.1. A sufficient condition for (V_0) is that there exist $\alpha > 1$ and $c_1 > 0$ such that $\limsup_{q \rightarrow 0} V(t, q)|q|^\alpha \leq -c_1 < 0$.

Proof. Since $\{q_n\} \subset \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ is bounded in $C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$ and W is bounded, the first and second integrals of

$$\mathcal{I}(q_n) = \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'_n|^2}] dt + \int_0^T W(t, q_n) \cdot \tilde{q}'_n dt - \int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt$$

are bounded. Hence to prove the lemma, it suffices to show that $\int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt$ converges to $-\infty$.

Let q be on the boundary of Λ in E ; i.e., such that there exists $t_0 \in [0, T]$ satisfying $q(t_0) = 0$. By the hypothesis (V_0) , there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that

$$V(t, q) \leq -\frac{c_0}{|q|} \text{ for } 0 < |q| \leq \varepsilon_0.$$

Let $t_0 \in [0, T]$ be such that $q(t_0) = 0$. Two cases can occur: either $q \equiv 0$, or (up to a change of the zero t_0 by other zero) we can assume that there exists $t_1 \in (t_0, T]$ such that $q(t_0) = 0 < |q(t)| \leq \varepsilon_0$, for every $t \in (t_0, t_1]$.

In the first case, $q \equiv 0$, we have $|q_n(t)| \leq \varepsilon_0$ for every $t \in [0, T]$ provided that n is large enough. Thus, the above hypothesis implies

$$\int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt \leq -\int_0^T \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt, \text{ for } n \text{ large enough.}$$

By Fatou lemma, we deduce

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt \leq -\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt \leq -\int_0^T \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt = -\infty,$$

which shows that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt = -\infty$$

and the lemma is proved in this case.

In the second case, observe that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt &= \left\{ \int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} + \int_{|q_n| > \varepsilon_0} \right\} V(t, q_n) dt \\ &\leq -\int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt + \int_{|q_n| > \varepsilon_0} V(t, q_n) dt. \end{aligned}$$

Using $V(t, \xi)$ is bounded from above for $t \in [0, T]$ and $\varepsilon_0 < |\xi| \leq \sup_n \|q_n\|_\infty < \infty$, we have

$$\int_{|q_n| > \varepsilon_0} V(t, q_n) dt$$

is also bounded from above for all n . Therefore, to conclude the proof it suffices to show that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt = \infty.$$

In order to prove it, since $\|q'_n\|_\infty \leq 1$, we note that

$$\int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt \geq \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt \geq \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \frac{q_n q'_n}{|q_n|^2} dt = \log |q_n(t_1)| - \log |q_n(t_0)|.$$

Consequently, using that $q_n(t_1)$ converges to $q(t_1) \neq 0$ and $q_n(t_0)$ to $q(t_0) = 0$, we deduce that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \log |q_n(t_1)| - \log |q_n(t_0)| = \infty,$$

and the proof is concluded. \square

Remark 10.2. Observe that, as a consequence of the above lemma, the functional \mathcal{I} satisfies the condition (9.0.4) of Theorem 9.1. Indeed, let $\{q_n\} \subset E$ be a sequence satisfying $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \text{dist}(q_n, E \setminus \Lambda) = 0$ and assume by contradiction that condition (9.0.4) does not hold true. Then, up to a subsequence, we can suppose that $\{\mathcal{I}(q_n)\}$ is bounded from above. In particular, $q_n \in K_\Lambda$. By using this and choosing $p_n \in E \setminus \Lambda$ such that $\|q_n - p_n\| = \text{dist}(q_n, E \setminus \Lambda)$ we get the uniform boundedness of p'_n in $[0, T]$, which together to the fact that each p_n vanishes at some point in $[0, T]$, implies that the sequence $\{p_n\}$ is bounded in E . By the compact embedding of E into the continuous functions in $[0, T]$ we can extract a subsequence $\{p_{n_k}\}$ which uniformly converges in $[0, T]$ to some function q which vanishes at some point of $[0, T]$. The convergence to zero of $\|q_n - p_n\|$ gives also the uniform convergence of $\{q_{n_k}\}$ to q in $[0, T]$. By the previous lemma we obtain the convergence of $\{\mathcal{I}(q_{n_k})\}$ to infinity contradicting the boundedness from above of the sequence $\{\mathcal{I}(q_n)\}$.

In the incoming results we will use this direct sum decomposition

$$E = \bar{E} \oplus \tilde{E}, \quad q = \bar{q} + \tilde{q}, \quad \bar{q} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T q dt, \quad \tilde{q} = q - \bar{q}.$$

Lemma 10.2 (Palais-Smale condition). *Assume in addition to (V_0) that V and W satisfy also*

$$(V_\infty) \quad \lim_{|q| \rightarrow \infty} |V(t, q)| + |\nabla_q V(t, q)| = 0 \text{ uniformly in } t \in [0, T],$$

$$(W_\infty) \quad \lim_{|q| \rightarrow \infty} |W(t, q)| + |D_{q_1} W(t, q)| + |D_{q_2} W(t, q)| + |D_{q_3} W(t, q)| = 0 \text{ uniformly in } t \in [0, T].$$

If $\{\varepsilon_n\}$ is a sequence of positive numbers converging to zero and $\{q_n\}$ is a sequence in \mathcal{K}_Λ satisfying that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = c \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \tag{10.1.1}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^T [\sqrt{1 - |q'_n|^2} - \sqrt{1 - |\varphi'|^2}] dt + \int_0^T [\mathcal{E}(t, q_n, q'_n) - \nabla_q V(t, q_n)] \cdot (\varphi - q_n) dt \\ & + \int_0^T W(t, q_n) \cdot (\varphi' - q'_n) dt \geq -\varepsilon_n \|\varphi - q_n\|, \quad \forall \varphi \in \mathcal{K}, \end{aligned} \tag{10.1.2}$$

then there exists a subsequence $\{q_{n_k}\}$ of $\{q_n\}$ converging in $C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$ to a critical point $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} with level $\mathcal{I}(q) = c$.

Proof. Let $\{q_n\}$ be a sequence satisfying (10.1.1) and (10.1.2). Since $q_n = \bar{q}_n + \tilde{q}_n$ with $\|\tilde{q}_n\| = \|\tilde{q}_n\|_\infty + \|\tilde{q}'_n\|_\infty = \|\tilde{q}_n\|_\infty + \|q'_n\|_\infty \leq T + 1$, to deduce the boundedness of $\{q_n\}$ in E it suffices to show that $\{\bar{q}_n\}$ is bounded. Suppose by contradiction that, up to a subsequence, $|\bar{q}_n|$ converges to infinity. Choosing $\varphi = \bar{q}_n$ in (10.1.2) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T [\sqrt{1 - |q'_n|^2} - 1] dt - \int_0^T [\mathcal{E}(t, q_n, q'_n) - \nabla_q V(t, q_n)] \cdot \tilde{q}_n dt \\ - \int_0^T W(t, q_n) \cdot \tilde{q}'_n dt \geq -\varepsilon_n \|\tilde{q}_n\| \geq -\varepsilon_n(T + 1). \end{aligned}$$

Since $|q_n(t)| = |\bar{q}_n + \tilde{q}_n(t)|$ converges to infinity,

$$\begin{aligned} |[\mathcal{E}(t, q_n, q'_n) - \nabla_q V(t, q_n)] \cdot \tilde{q}_n| &\leq T|\mathcal{E}(t, q_n, q'_n)| + |\nabla_q V(t, q_n)| \\ &\leq T[|D_{q_1} W(t, q_n)| + |D_{q_2} W(t, q_n)| + |D_{q_3} W(t, q_n)|] + |\nabla_q V(t, q_n)|, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$|W(t, q_n) \cdot \tilde{q}'_n| \leq |W(t, q_n)|,$$

by hypotheses (V_∞) and (W_∞) , we have

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T [\mathcal{E}(t, q_n, q'_n) - \nabla_q V(t, q_n)] \cdot \tilde{q}_n dt + \int_0^T W(t, q_n) \cdot \tilde{q}'_n dt = 0.$$

Thus,

$$\limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'_n|^2}] dt \leq \limsup_{n \rightarrow \infty} \varepsilon_n(T + 1) = 0;$$

which means (by the positiveness of the function $1 - \sqrt{1 - |s|^2}$) that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'_n|^2}] dt = 0.$$

Therefore, again by (V_∞) and (W_∞) we would obtain from (10.1.1) that

$$\begin{aligned} c = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) &= \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'_n|^2}] dt \\ &\quad + \int_0^T W(t, q_n) \cdot \tilde{q}'_n dt - \int_0^T V(t, q_n) dt = 0, \end{aligned}$$

a contradiction proving that the sequence $\{\bar{q}_n\}$ is necessarily bounded.

By the compact embedding of E into $C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$ we can assume, up to subsequences, that $q_n(t) \rightarrow q(t)$ uniformly in $[0, T]$. Since each q_n is Lipschitz with Lipschitz constant equal $\|q_n\|_\infty \leq 1$, we deduce that q is also Lipschitz with Lipschitz constant smaller or equal to one; i.e., $q \in \mathcal{K}$. By Lemma 10.1 and (10.1.1), we have

$$q(t) \neq 0, \quad \forall t \in [0, T],$$

concluding the proof. \square

10.2 Existence results

Now we employ our new abstract result (see Theorem 9.1) to derive the existence of a T -periodic solution for equation (10.0.1). In fact, the following result holds.

Theorem 10.1. *Assume the hypotheses (V_0) , (V_∞) and (W_∞) . If there exists $c_0 > 0$ such that*

$$\frac{\pi^2}{2T^2}|q|^2 - |W(t, q)| - V(t, q) \geq c_0, \quad \forall q \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (10.2.1)$$

then there exists a T -periodic solution of the Lorentz force equation (10.0.1).

Proof. Recalling that $\frac{\pi^2}{T^2}$ is the second eigenvalue of the periodic problem associated to the operator $-q''(t)$, we deduce by its variational characterization that

$$\int_0^T |\tilde{q}'|^2 dt \geq \frac{\pi^2}{T^2} \int_0^T |\tilde{q}|^2 dt, \quad \forall \tilde{q} \in \tilde{E}.$$

Thus, using this and the inequality $1 - \sqrt{1 - |p|^2} \geq \frac{1}{2}|p|^2$ for every $p \in \mathbb{R}^3$, we obtain for every $\tilde{q} \in \tilde{E} \cap \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ that

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{I}(\tilde{q}) &\geq \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T |\tilde{q}'|^2 dt + \int_0^T [\tilde{q}' \cdot W(t, \tilde{q}) - V(t, \tilde{q})] dt \\ &\geq \frac{\pi^2}{2T^2} \int_0^T |\tilde{q}|^2 dt - \int_0^T |W(t, \tilde{q})| dt - \int_0^T V(t, \tilde{q}) dt. \end{aligned}$$

The condition (10.2.1) implies then that

$$\inf_{\tilde{E}} \mathcal{I} \geq c_0 T > 0.$$

On the other hand, by (V_∞) , when $\bar{q} \in \bar{E}$ converges to infinity we have

$$\lim_{|\bar{q}| \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(\bar{q}) = - \lim_{|\bar{q}| \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T V(t, \bar{q}) dt = 0,$$

and we can choose $\rho > 0$ such that the boundary ∂B_ρ of the ball B_ρ in \bar{E} of center zero and radius ρ satisfies that

$$\sup_{\partial B_\rho} \mathcal{I} < c_0 T \leq \inf_{\bar{E}} \mathcal{I},$$

that is, \mathcal{I} verifies the geometry of the Rabinowitz's saddle point theorem [162].

Therefore, since $\dim \bar{E} < \infty$, we can apply Theorem 9.1 with K the closed ball B_ρ in \bar{E} of center zero and radius ρ , K_0 the boundary in \bar{E} of this ball and γ_0 the identity function in K_0 to deduce the existence of a sequence $\{q_n\} \subset E$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = c := \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \sup_{x \in \bar{B}_\rho} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(x)),$$

and there exists $0 < \epsilon_n \rightarrow 0$ such that

$$\Psi(\varphi) - \Psi(q_n) + \mathcal{F}'(q_n)[\varphi - q_n] \geq -\epsilon_n \|\varphi - q_n\|$$

for all positive integer n and for all $\varphi \in \text{Dom } \Psi$.

By Lemma 10.2, there exists a subsequence $\{q_{n_k}\}$ of $\{q_n\}$ converging in $C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$ to a critical point $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} with critical level $\mathcal{I}(q) = c$ \square

Observe that the periodic solution given by Theorem 10.1 can be trivial. Indeed, if for instance, V and W does not depend on t , then $q = \xi$ is a constant solution if and only if $\nabla V(\xi) = 0$. In this section we show a sufficient condition in order to obtain a second solution of (10.0.1).

Theorem 10.2. *Assume that V and W only depends on the variable q and satisfies conditions (V_0) , (V_∞) and (W_∞) . If there exists $\xi \in \mathbb{R}^3$ such that $V(\xi) < 0$, $\nabla V(\xi) = 0$ and the matrix*

$$\left(2 \frac{\partial W_j}{\partial q_i}(\xi) - \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial q_i \partial q_j}(\xi) \right)_{i,j=1,2,3} \quad (10.2.2)$$

is positive definite, then the Lorentz force equation (10.0.1) has a periodic solution which is different from the constant solution ξ .

Proof. As it has been mentioned, since V and W only depends on the variable q , the hypothesis $\nabla V(\xi) = 0$ means that $q = \xi$ is a constant (thus periodic) solution of (10.0.1). Moreover, the condition about the positive definiteness of the matrix given by (10.2.2) implies that the functional \mathcal{F} presents a strict local minimum at $q = \xi$. Since any constant is trivially a local minimum of the function Ψ , we deduce that $\mathcal{I} = \Psi + \mathcal{F}$ has a strict local minimum at $q = \xi$. In particular, there exists $r_0 > 0$ such that

$$\inf_{\|q-\xi\|=r_0} \mathcal{I}(q) > \mathcal{I}(\xi) = -V(\xi)T > 0.$$

On the other hand, by (V_∞) when the constant $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^3$ converges to infinity we have

$$\lim_{|\eta| \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(\eta) = - \lim_{|\eta| \rightarrow \infty} V(\eta)T = 0,$$

and consequently it is possible to choose $\eta \in \mathbb{R}^3$ with $\|\eta - \xi\| > r_0$ such that $\mathcal{I}(\eta) < \mathcal{I}(\xi)$.

Therefore, the functional \mathcal{I} satisfies the geometry of the Mountain Pass Theorem [12] and applying Theorem 9.1 with $K = [0, 1]$, $K_0 = \{0, 1\}$, $\gamma_0(0) = 0$, $\gamma_0(1) = \eta$ and $\Gamma = \{\gamma : [0, 1] \rightarrow E : \gamma \text{ is continuous and } \gamma(0) = 0, \gamma(1) = \eta\}$ we deduce the existence of a sequence $(q_n) \subset E$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = c := \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \sup_{t \in [0,1]} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)),$$

and there exists $0 < \epsilon_n \rightarrow 0$ such that

$$\Psi(\varphi) - \Psi(q_n) + \mathcal{F}'(q_n)[\varphi - q_n] \geq -\epsilon_n \|\varphi - q_n\|$$

for all positive integer n and for all $\varphi \in \text{Dom } \Psi$.

By Lemma 10.2, there exists a subsequence (q_{n_k}) of (q_n) converging in $C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$ to a critical point $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} with critical level $\mathcal{I}(q) = c$. Since $\mathcal{I}(q) = c \geq \inf_{\|q-\xi\|=r_0} \mathcal{I}(q) > \mathcal{I}(\xi)$, we obtain $q \neq \xi$ and the proof is concluded in this case. \square

Relativistic pendulum-type equation with a singular reaction term

This final chapter is motivated by the study of the spherical pendulum whose interest comes from the early results in [9]. Here we study of the scalar relativistic pendulum-type equation

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1-(q')^2}} \right)' + q = G'(q) + h(t), \quad (11.0.1)$$

where $h \in L^1(0, T)$ and the function G is singular at zero. Here, we employ again Theorem 9.1 to derive the existence of a T -periodic solution of (11.0.1). To be more precise, we improve the results in [9] and derive new existence results both in the case $h \not\equiv 0$ (see Theorem 11.1) and $h \equiv 0$ (see Theorem 11.2). Finally, we use the global continuation theorem to address equation (11.0.1) but assuming that there exists $c_0 > 0$ such that $G'(q)q$ is bounded from below by the function $c_0/|q|$ when q is in a neighborhood of the origin. In fact, establishing a suitable homotopic system that drives the original problem into an autonomous system, we compute the Brouwer degree of the vector field and use [63, Theorem 2] to infer the existence of a T -periodic solution for the equation (11.0.1). We point out that, in contrast with [107, Theorem 1], our existence result does not require any hypothesis on the mean value of the function h .

The results obtained in this chapter are contained in [CS9].

11.1 Periodic oscillations of a relativistic type-pendulum

We assume that the function $G : \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ satisfies the hypothesis

(G_0) there exists $c_0 > 0$ such that

$$\liminf_{s \rightarrow 0} G(s)|s| \geq c_0 > 0.$$

Remark 11.1. Observe that a sufficient condition for the hypothesis (G_0) is that there exists a constant $c_1 > 0$ such that

$$\liminf_{s \rightarrow 0} G'(s)s|s| \leq -c_1.$$

Remark 11.2. Another sufficient condition for (G_0) is that there exist $\alpha > 1$ and $c_1 > 0$ such that

$$\liminf_{s \rightarrow 0} G(s)|s|^\alpha \geq c_1.$$

Even if, contrary to the system equation (10.0.1), the equation (11.0.1) is scalar, we keep the notation q for the unknown of the equation (11.0.1). Thus, in this case, q belongs the space $E = W_T^{1,\infty}$ of all T -periodic Lipschitz functions in \mathbb{R} equipped with the norm

$$\|q\| = \|q\|_\infty + \|q'\|_\infty, \quad \forall q \in E.$$

Since the function G has a singularity at $q = 0$, we work in the subset

$$\Lambda = \{q \in E : q(t) \neq 0, \forall t \in [0, T]\}.$$

Taking

$$\mathcal{K} = \{q \in E : \|q'\|_\infty \leq 1\}, \quad \mathcal{K}_\Lambda = \mathcal{K} \cap \Lambda = \{q \in \Lambda : \|q'\|_\infty \leq 1\},$$

the functional \mathcal{I} related to problem (11.0.1) is given for every $q \in \Lambda$ by

$$\mathcal{I}(q) = \begin{cases} \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - (q')^2}] dt - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T q^2 dt + \int_0^T G(q) dt \\ \quad + \int_0^T h q dt, & \text{if } q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda; \\ +\infty, & \text{if } q \in \Lambda \setminus \mathcal{K}_\Lambda. \end{cases} \quad (11.1.1)$$

A critical point q of \mathcal{I} is a point $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - (w')^2}] dt - \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - (q')^2}] dt - \int_0^T q(w - q) dt \\ & \quad + \int_0^T G'(q)(w - q) dt + \int_0^T h(w - q) dt \geq 0, \quad \forall w \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda. \end{aligned} \quad (11.1.2)$$

Similarly to the previous section, the critical points q of \mathcal{I} in E are just the T -periodic solutions of the equation (11.0.1); i.e., satisfying $|q'(t)| < 1$ for all t , $q(0) = q(T)$ and (11.0.1) are satisfied pointwise.

We state the similar results to the Lemmas 10.1 and 10.2.

Lemma 11.1. *Assume that $h \in L^1(0, T)$ and that G satisfies the condition (G_0) . If a sequence $\{q_n\}$ in \mathcal{K}_Λ converges uniformly in $[0, T]$ to some q which vanishes at some point of $[0, T]$, then*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T G(q_n) dt = +\infty \text{ and } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = +\infty.$$

Proof. Since $\{q_n\}$ is bounded in $C([0, T])$, the first, second and fourth integrals of $\mathcal{I}(q_n)$ (\mathcal{I} is given by (11.1.1)) are bounded. Hence to prove the lemma, it suffices to show that $\int_0^T G(q_n) dt$ converges to infinity.

If q is on the boundary of Λ in E , then there exists $t_0 \in [0, T]$ satisfying $q(t_0) = 0$. By the hypothesis (G_0) , there exists $\varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that

$$G(s) \geq \frac{c_0}{|s|}, \quad \forall |s| \leq \varepsilon_0, s \neq 0.$$

Let $t_0 \in [0, T]$ be such that $q(t_0) = 0$. Two cases can occur: either $q \equiv 0$, or (up to a change of the zero t_0 by other zero) we can assume that there exists $t_1 \in (t_0, T]$ such that $q(t_0) = 0 < |q(t)| \leq \varepsilon_0$, for every $t \in (t_0, t_1]$. In the first case, $q \equiv 0$, we have $|q_n(t)| \leq \varepsilon_0$ for every $t \in [0, T]$ provided that n is large enough. Thus, the above hypothesis implies

$$\int_0^T G(q_n) dt \geq \int_0^T \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt, \text{ for } n \text{ large enough.}$$

By Fatou lemma, we deduce

$$\liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T G(q_n) dt \geq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt \geq \int_0^T \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt = +\infty,$$

which shows that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_0^T G(q_n) dt = +\infty$$

and the lemma is proved in this case.

In the second case, we have

$$\int_0^T G(q_n) dt = \int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} G(q_n) dt + \int_{|q_n| > \varepsilon_0} G(q_n) dt \geq \int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{c_0}{|q_n|} dt + \int_{|q_n| > \varepsilon_0} G(q_n) dt.$$

Using that $G(s)$ is bounded from below for $0 \leq t \leq T$ and $\varepsilon_0 < |s| \leq \sup_n \|q_n\|_\infty < \infty$, we have

$$\int_{|q_n| > \varepsilon_0} G(q_n) dt$$

is also bounded from below for all n . Therefore, to conclude the proof it suffices to show that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt = \infty.$$

In order to prove it, since $\|q'_n\|_\infty \leq 1$, we note that

$$\int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt \geq \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt \geq \int_{t_0}^{t_1} \frac{q_n q'_n}{q_n^2} dt = \log |q_n(t_1)| - \log |q_n(t_0)|.$$

Consequently, using that, as n tends to infinity, $q_n(t_1)$ converges to $q(t_1) \neq 0$ and $q_n(t_0)$ to $q(t_0) = 0$, we deduce that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \int_{|q_n| \leq \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{|q_n|} dt \geq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \log |q_n(t_1)| - \log |q_n(t_0)| = \infty,$$

and the proof is concluded. \square

Remark 11.3. As in the Remark 10.2, the above lemma implies that the functional \mathcal{I} given by (11.1.1) satisfies the condition (9.0.4) required in Theorem 9.1.

In the next results we will use this direct sum decomposition

$$E = \bar{E} \oplus \tilde{E}, \quad q = \bar{q} + \tilde{q}, \quad \bar{q} = \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T q dt, \quad \tilde{q} = q - \bar{q}. \quad (11.1.3)$$

Lemma 11.2. Assume that $h \in L^1(0, T)$ and that G satisfies the conditions (G_0) and

$$(G'_\infty) \limsup_{|s| \rightarrow \infty} |G'(s)| < \infty.$$

If $\{\varepsilon_n\}_n$ is a sequence of positive numbers converging to zero and $\{q_n\}$ is a sequence in \mathcal{K}_Λ satisfying that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = c \in \mathbb{R} \quad (11.1.4)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - (w')^2}] dt - \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - (q'_n)^2}] dt - \int_0^T q_n(w - q_n) dt \\ & + \int_0^T G'(q_n)(w - q_n) dt + \int_0^T h(w - q_n) dt \geq -\varepsilon_n \|w - q_n\|, \quad \forall w \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda, \end{aligned} \quad (11.1.5)$$

then there exists a subsequence $\{q_{n_k}\}$ of $\{q_n\}$ converging in $C([0, T], \mathbb{R})$ to a critical point $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} with level $\mathcal{I}(q) = c$.

Proof. Let $\{q_n\} \subset E$ be a sequence satisfying (11.1.4) and (11.1.5). Observe that for every $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ we have $\|\tilde{q}\|_\infty = \|q'\|_\infty \leq 1$, which together to the existence of a zero of \tilde{q} in $[0, T]$ (consequence of the zero mean value of \tilde{q}) implies that

$$\|\tilde{q}\|_\infty \leq T, \quad \|\tilde{q}\| \leq 1 + T, \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda. \quad (11.1.6)$$

Hence, in order to prove that $\{q_n\}_n$ is bounded in E , it suffices to show that $\{\bar{q}_n\}_n$ is bounded. To this aim, choosing $w = q_n + \bar{q}_n$ in (11.1.5), it follows that

$$\bar{q}_n^2 T \leq \int_0^T G'(q_n) \bar{q}_n dt + |\bar{q}_n| \|h\|_{L^1(0, T)} + \varepsilon_n |\bar{q}_n|. \quad (11.1.7)$$

This implies that the sequence $\{\bar{q}_n\}_n$ is bounded. Indeed, otherwise we can assume, up to subsequences, that $|\bar{q}_n|$ converges to ∞ . Thus, by (11.1.6), $q_n = \bar{q}_n + \tilde{q}_n$ is away from zero for large n ; that is, $s_0, n_0 \gg 0$ exist such that $|q_n| \geq s_0$ for every $n \geq n_0$. By assumption (G'_∞) , there exists $\eta > 0$ such that

$$|G'(q_n)| = |G'(\bar{q}_n + \tilde{q}_n)| \leq \eta, \quad \forall n \geq n_0.$$

By (11.1.7) we infer for every $n \geq n_0$ that

$$\bar{q}_n^2 T \leq \eta T |\bar{q}_n| + |\bar{q}_n| \|h\|_{L^1(0,T)} + \varepsilon_n |\bar{q}_n|$$

i.e. $|\bar{q}_n| \leq \eta + T^{-1} \|h\|_{L^1(0,T)} + \varepsilon_n T^{-1}$, (for every $n \geq n_0$) contradicting the convergence of $|\bar{q}_n|$ to ∞ and proving that the sequence $\{\bar{q}_n\}$, and thus the sequence $\{q_n\}$, is bounded in E .

By the compact embedding of E into $C([0, T])$ we can assume, up to subsequences, that $q_n(t) \rightarrow q(t)$ uniformly in $[0, T]$.

Since each q_n is Lipschitz with Lipschitz constant equal $\|q_n\|_\infty \leq 1$, we deduce that q is also Lipschitz with Lipschitz constant smaller or equal to one; i.e., $q \in \mathcal{K}$. By Lemma 11.1 and (11.1.4), we have

$$q(t) \neq 0, \quad \forall t \in [0, T],$$

concluding the proof. □

Theorem 11.1. *If the conditions (G_0) , (G'_∞) and*

$$(G_\infty) \quad \limsup_{|s| \rightarrow \infty} \frac{G(s)}{s} < \frac{1}{2},$$

hold true, then the equation (11.0.1) has at least a T -periodic solution.

Remark 11.4. A sufficient condition for (G'_∞) and (G_∞) is that

$$\limsup_{|s| \rightarrow \infty} |G'(s)| < \frac{1}{2}.$$

Proof. Taking into account the decomposition given by (11.1.3) and using (11.1.6) we have

$$\int_0^T \tilde{q}^2 dt \leq T^3 \quad \text{and} \quad \int_0^T h(t) \tilde{q} dt \leq \|h\|_{L^1(0,T)} \|\tilde{q}\|_\infty \leq T \|h\|_{L^1(0,T)}, \quad \forall \tilde{q} \in \tilde{E} \cap \mathcal{K}_\Lambda.$$

By this and since $1 - \sqrt{1 - s^2} \geq \frac{1}{2} s^2 \geq 0$ we deduce that the functional \mathcal{I} defined by (11.1.1) satisfies

$$\mathcal{I}(\tilde{q}) \geq -\frac{T^3}{2} + \int_0^T G(\tilde{q}) dt - T \|h\|_{L^1(0,T)}, \quad \forall \tilde{q} \in \tilde{E} \cap \mathcal{K}_\Lambda. \quad (11.1.8)$$

We claim that this inequality implies that \mathcal{I} is bounded from below over \tilde{E} . Indeed, if we take a minimizing sequence $\{\tilde{q}_n\}$ in $\tilde{E} \cap \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} ; i.e., such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(\tilde{q}_n) = \inf_{\tilde{E}} \mathcal{I} \in \mathbb{R} \cup \{-\infty\},$$

by Lemma 11.1 the accumulation points in the $C([0, T])$ -topology of the sequence $\{\tilde{q}_n\}$ can not vanish at any point of $[0, T]$. This means that there exists $\varepsilon > 0$ such that $\|\tilde{q}_n\|_\infty \geq \varepsilon$, for every n . Therefore, by using again that $\|\tilde{q}_n\|_\infty \leq T$, we obtain from (11.1.8) that

$$\mathcal{I}(\tilde{q}_n) \geq -\frac{T^3}{2} - T \sup_{\varepsilon \leq |s| \leq T} |G(s)| - T \|h\|_{L^1(0, T)}.$$

This implies that $\inf_{\tilde{E}} \mathcal{I} \in \mathbb{R}$ and the claim is proved.

On the other hand, for every $\bar{q} \in \bar{E}$ we have

$$\mathcal{I}(\bar{q}) = -\frac{T}{2} \bar{q}^2 + TG(\bar{q}) + T\bar{q} \|h\|_{L^1(0, T)},$$

and thus, by (G_∞) , we have

$$\lim_{\|\bar{q}\| \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(\bar{q}) = -\infty.$$

In consequence, we can choose $\rho > 0$ such that the boundary ∂B_ρ of the ball B_ρ in \bar{E} of center zero and radius ρ satisfies that

$$\sup_{\partial B_\rho} \mathcal{I} < \inf_{\tilde{E}} \mathcal{I},$$

that is, \mathcal{I} verifies the geometry of the Rabinowitz's saddle point theorem [161]. By Lemma 11.2 (instead of Lemma 10.2) we can repeat the argument in the proof of Theorem 10.1 to deduce the existence a subsequence (q_{n_k}) of (q_n) converging in $C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$ to a critical point $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} with critical level $\mathcal{I}(q) = c$. \square

Now we look for T -periodic solutions $q \in E$ of the equation (11.0.1) with $h \equiv 0$, i.e.,

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1 - (q')^2}} \right)' + q = G'(q) \quad (11.1.9)$$

Firstly, observe that every constant $\xi \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ verifying $\xi = G'(\xi)$ is a trivial (constant) T -periodic solution of (11.1.9). In this case, in order to find another solution we apply the Mountain Pass Theorem to the functional \mathcal{I} given by (11.1.1) with $h \equiv 0$; that is,

$$\mathcal{I}(q) = \begin{cases} \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - |q'|^2}] dt - \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T q^2 dt + \int_0^T G(q) dt, & \text{if } q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda, \\ +\infty, & \text{if } q \in \Lambda \setminus \mathcal{K}_\Lambda. \end{cases}$$

Theorem 11.2. *Assume that hypotheses (G_0) , (G_∞) and (G'_∞) hold true with the function G of class C^2 in $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$. If $\xi \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ verifies $\xi = G'(\xi)$ and $G''(\xi) > 1$, then the equation (11.1.9) has at least one T -periodic solution different from the trivial one ξ .*

Proof. Consider the functional \mathcal{F} defined for $q \in E$ by

$$\mathcal{F}(q) = -\frac{1}{2} \int_0^T q^2 dt + \int_0^T G(q) dt.$$

Observe that it is of class C^2 (because $G \in C^2$) with the first and second derivatives given for every $q, w_1, w_2 \in E$ by

$$\mathcal{F}'(q)[w_1] = - \int_0^T qw_1 dt + \int_0^T G'(q)w_1 dt$$

and

$$\mathcal{F}''(q)[w_1, w_2] = - \int_0^T w_1 w_2 dt + \int_0^T G''(q)w_1 w_2 dt.$$

In particular, the condition $\xi = G'(\xi)$ implies $q = \xi$ is a critical point of \mathcal{F} and the hypothesis $G''(\xi) > 1$ means that the second derivative of \mathcal{F} at $q = \xi$ is positive definite. Thus, \mathcal{F} has a strict local minimum at $q = \xi$. Taking into account that

$$\mathcal{I}(q) = \Psi(q) + \mathcal{F}(q), \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$$

with

$$\Psi(q) := \int_0^T [1 - \sqrt{1 - (q')^2}] dt \geq 0 (= \Psi(\xi)), \quad \forall q \in \mathcal{K},$$

we deduce that $q = \xi$ is also a strict local minimum of \mathcal{I} . Hence, there exist $\delta, r > 0$ such that

$$\mathcal{I}(q) \geq \mathcal{I}(\xi) + \delta, \quad \text{when } \|q - \xi\| = r.$$

As in the proof of Theorem 11.1, by assumption (G_∞) , for every $\bar{q} \in \bar{E}$ we have

$$\lim_{\|\bar{q}\| \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(\bar{q}) = \lim_{\|\bar{q}\| \rightarrow \infty} -\frac{T}{2} \bar{q}^2 + TG(\bar{q}) = -\infty$$

and we can choose a constant $\eta \in \bar{E}$ such that $\mathcal{I}(\eta) < \mathcal{I}(\xi)$.

In conclusion, the functional \mathcal{I} satisfies the geometry of the Mountain Pass Theorem [12] and applying Theorem 9.1 with $K = [0, 1]$, $K_0 = \{0, 1\}$, $\gamma_0(0) = \xi$, $\gamma_0(1) = \eta$ and $\Gamma = \{\gamma : [0, 1] \rightarrow E : \gamma \text{ is continuous and } \gamma(0) = \xi, \gamma(1) = \eta\}$ we deduce the existence of a sequence $(q_n) \subset E$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \mathcal{I}(q_n) = c := \inf_{\gamma \in \Gamma} \sup_{t \in [0, 1]} \mathcal{I}(\gamma(t)) > \mathcal{I}(\xi) > \mathcal{I}(\eta),$$

and a sequence $0 < \epsilon_n \rightarrow 0$ such that

$$\Psi(\varphi) - \Psi(q_n) + \mathcal{F}'(q_n)[\varphi - q_n] \geq -\epsilon_n \|\varphi - q_n\|$$

for all positive integer n and for all $\varphi \in \text{Dom } \Psi$.

By Lemma 11.2, there exists a subsequence (q_{n_k}) of (q_n) converging in $C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^3)$ to a critical point $q \in \mathcal{K}_\Lambda$ of \mathcal{I} with critical level $\mathcal{I}(q) = c$. Since $\mathcal{I}(q) = c \geq \inf_{\|q-\xi\|=r} \mathcal{I}(q) > \mathcal{I}(\xi)$, we obtain $q \neq \xi$ and the proof is finished. \square

11.2 Existence by global continuation theorem

Finally, we use the global continuation theorem to address equation (11.0.1) but assuming that there exists $c_0 > 0$ such that $G'(q)q$ is bounded from below by the function $c_0/|q|$ when q is in a neighborhood of the origin. In fact, establishing a suitable homotopic system that drives the original problem into an autonomous system, we compute the Brouwer degree of the vector field and use [63, Theorem 2] to infer the existence of a T -periodic solution for the equation (11.0.1). We point out that, in contrast with [107, Theorem 1], our existence result does not require any hypothesis on the mean value of the function h .

Consider the homotopic system

$$\left(\frac{q'}{\sqrt{1 - (q')^2}} \right)' + q = g_\lambda(q) + h_\lambda(t), \quad \lambda \in [0, 1], \quad (11.2.1)$$

with $g_\lambda(q) = \lambda G'(q) + (1 - \lambda) \frac{c_0}{q|q|}$ and $h_\lambda(t) = \lambda h(t)$. Observe that (11.2.1) turns into (11.0.1) when $\lambda = 1$.

By considering the position q and the momentum $p = q'/\sqrt{1 - (q')^2}$ as new coordinates (and taking into account that the inverse of $\phi(s) = s/\sqrt{1 - s^2}$ is given by $\phi^{-1}(p) = p/\sqrt{1 + p^2}$), equation (11.2.1) turns into the first order system of differential equations

$$\begin{cases} q' = \frac{p}{\sqrt{1 + p^2}} \\ p' = -q + g_\lambda(q) + h_\lambda(t), \end{cases}$$

that is,

$$(q, p)' = f_\lambda(t, (q, p)) := \left(\frac{p}{\sqrt{1 + p^2}}, -q + g_\lambda(q) + h_\lambda(t) \right).$$

Setting $x := (q, p)$ and denoting by \mathcal{N}_{f_λ} the Nemitskii operator associated to the function $f_\lambda(t, x)$, the previous problem can be written as the first order ordinary differential equation

$$x' = \mathcal{N}_{f_\lambda}(x)$$

in the Banach space $X = \{x \in C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^2) : x(0) = x(T)\}$.

If $P : X \rightarrow X$ is the projection given by

$$Px = \bar{x} := \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T x(t) dt \quad \forall x \in X,$$

then

$$x = \bar{x} + \tilde{x}, \quad \bar{x} = Px, \quad \tilde{x} := (I - P)(x), \quad \forall x \in X.$$

Note that, if $\tilde{X} := \text{Ker } P = \left\{ x \in X : \frac{1}{T} \int_0^T x(t) dt = 0 \right\}$, we can consider the operator $K : L^1([0, T], \mathbb{R}^2) \rightarrow \tilde{X}$ defining for each $g \in L^1([0, T], \mathbb{R}^2)$, the function Kg as the unique solution $\tilde{x} \in \tilde{X}$ of the equation

$$\tilde{x}'(t) = g(t).$$

Thus, using the previous notations, (11.2.1) turns into

$$x = Px + K[\mathcal{N}_{f_\lambda}(x)] =: T_\lambda x, \quad (11.2.2)$$

where

- P has a finite range,
- \mathcal{N}_{f_λ} is continuous with $\mathcal{N}_{f_\lambda}(\bar{\Omega})$ bounded in X ,
- and $K|_X : X \rightarrow C^1([0, T])$ is linear and continuous.

Thus, by the compact embedding of $C^1([0, T])$ into $C([0, T])$ (due to the Ascoli-Arzelà theorem) we have that $T_\lambda : X \rightarrow X$ is compact and we can employ [63, Theorem 2] to address problem (11.2.2). For the sake of completeness, we recall it here in our particular case.

Theorem 11.3. *Let $\Omega \subset X = \{x \in C([0, T], \mathbb{R}^2) : x(0) = x(T)\}$ be an open bounded subset and assume that the operators $T_\lambda : X \rightarrow X$ are compact on $\bar{\Omega}$. If the following conditions hold true*

- i) there is no solution $x \in \partial\Omega$ of the homotopic problem (11.2.2) for every $\lambda \in [0, 1]$;*
- ii) $\deg_B(f_0, \Omega \cap \mathbb{R}^2, 0) \neq 0$, where $\Omega \cap \mathbb{R}^2$ denotes the subset of the constant functions in Ω (observe that $T_0|_{\Omega \cap \mathbb{R}^2} = f_0$) and \deg_B denotes the Brouwer degree;*

then the problem (11.2.2) has at least a solution $x \in \Omega$. □

Remark 11.5. Observe that if condition *i)* in the previous theorem were not satisfied for $\lambda = 1$, then a (trivial) solution of (11.2.2) would exist on $\partial\Omega$.

In order to properly define the open bounded subset Ω required to apply the previous theorem, we derive some a priori bounds for the position q and the momentum $p = q'/\sqrt{1 - (q')^2}$ of every T -periodic solution $q(t)$ of (11.2.1).

Lemma 11.3. *If condition (G_∞) and*

$$(\tilde{G}_0) \liminf_{s \rightarrow 0} G'(s)s|s| > 0$$

hold true, then there exist positive constants C, c and M such that for every T -periodic solution $q(t)$ of (11.2.1) we have

- i) $\|q\|_\infty \leq C,$
- ii) $|q(t)| \geq c$ for every $t \in [0, T],$
- iii) $\left| \frac{q'}{\sqrt{1 - (q')^2}} \right| \leq M$ for every $t \in [0, T].$

Remark 11.6. Similarly to Remark 11.1, assumption (\tilde{G}_0) implies that

$$\limsup_{s \rightarrow 0} G(s)|s| < 0.$$

Proof. i) By hypothesis (G_∞) , there exists a positive constant η (independent of $\lambda \in [0, 1]$) such that

$$g_\lambda(s) \leq G'(s) + \frac{c_0}{s|s|} \leq \eta, \quad \forall |s| \geq 1.$$

Fixing $R \geq \max\{\eta + \|h\|_{L^1}/T, 1\}$ we claim that the above identity implies that for every solution q of (11.2.1) there exists at least one $t_0 \in [0, T]$ such that $q(t_0) \leq R$. Indeed, supposing by contradiction that a solution q of (11.2.1) satisfies $q(t) > R (\geq 1)$ for all t , we would have

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^T g_\lambda(q(t))dt &< T\eta \leq TR - \|h\|_{L^1} \leq \left| \int_0^T q(t)dt \right| - \left| \int_0^T h_\lambda(t)dt \right| \\ &\leq \left| \int_0^T q(t)dt - \int_0^T h_\lambda(t)dt \right|. \end{aligned}$$

This inequality contradicts that choosing $v = 1$ as test function in (11.2.1), we have

$$\int_0^T g_\lambda(q(t))dt = \int_0^T q(t)dt - \int_0^T h_\lambda(t)dt.$$

Therefore, for every T -periodic solution q of (11.2.1) there is at least one $t_0 \in [0, T]$ such that $q(t_0) \leq R$. Thus

$$|q(t)| = \left| q(t_0) + \int_{t_0}^t q'(s)ds \right| < R + T,$$

i.e. every solution q of the problem (11.2.1) satisfies $\|q\|_\infty \leq R + T$ and it suffices to choose $C = R + T$ to conclude the proof of i).

ii) Choosing $v = q$ as test function in (11.2.1) we deduce that

$$-\int_0^T \frac{q'^2}{\sqrt{1-(q')^2}} dt + \int_0^T q^2(t) dt = \int_0^T g_\lambda(q(t))q(t) dt + \int_0^T h_\lambda(t)q(t) dt,$$

for every T -periodic solution of (11.2.1). Now, since

$$\int_0^T \frac{q'^2}{\sqrt{1-(q')^2}} dt \geq 0,$$

we infer that

$$\int_0^T q^2(t) dt \geq \int_0^T g_\lambda(q(t))q(t) dt + \int_0^T h_\lambda(t)q(t) dt.$$

Since assumption (\tilde{G}_0) implies that there exists $c_0, \varepsilon_0 > 0$ such that

$$G'(s)s \geq \frac{c_0}{|s|}, \quad \forall 0 < |s| \leq \varepsilon_0,$$

we have

$$g_\lambda(s)s = \lambda G'(s)s + (1-\lambda) \frac{c_0}{|s|} \geq \frac{c_0}{|s|}, \quad \forall 0 < |s| \leq \varepsilon_0, \quad \forall \lambda \in [0, 1].$$

Then, it follows that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{|q(t)| < \varepsilon_0} \frac{c_0}{|q(t)|} dt &= \int_{|q(t)| < \varepsilon_0} g_\lambda(q(t))q(t) dt \\ &\leq \int_0^T q^2(t) dt - \int_{|q(t)| > \varepsilon_0} g_\lambda(q(t))q(t) dt - \int_0^T h_\lambda(t)q(t) dt \\ &\leq \int_0^T q^2(t) dt + \left| \int_{|q(t)| > \varepsilon_0} g_\lambda(q(t))q(t) dt \right| + \left| \int_0^T h_\lambda(t)q(t) dt \right|. \end{aligned}$$

By i) we obtain the inequality

$$\int_{|q(t)| < \varepsilon_0} \frac{c_0}{|q(t)|} dt \leq C^2 T + T \max_{\varepsilon_0 < |s| < C} \left| G'(s)s + \frac{c_0}{|s|} \right| + C \|h\|_{L^1}.$$

that allows us to prove the item ii). Indeed, observe first that if the T -periodic solution $q(t)$ of (11.2.1) is always out the ball $B_{L^\infty}(0, \varepsilon_0)$ the result is proved. On the other hand, if there exists a closed interval $[t_1, t_2] \subset [0, T]$ such that

$$|q(t_1)| = \varepsilon_0 \quad \text{and} \quad |q(t)| < \varepsilon_0 \quad \forall t \in (t_1, t_2],$$

then, using that $|q'| \leq 1$, we deduce for $t \in (t_1, t_2)$ that

$$\begin{aligned} |\log |q(t)|| &= \left| \log |q(t_1)| + \int_{t_1}^t \frac{q(s)q'(s)}{q(s)^2} ds \right| \leq |\log \varepsilon_0| + \int_{t_1}^{t_2} \frac{1}{|q(s)|} ds \\ &\leq |\log \varepsilon_0| + \int_{|q(s)| < \varepsilon_0} \frac{1}{|q(s)|} ds \\ &\leq |\log \varepsilon_0| + \frac{C^2 T}{c_0} + \frac{T}{c_0} \max_{\varepsilon_0 < |s| < C} \left| G'(s)s + \frac{c_0}{|s|} \right| + \frac{C}{c_0} \|h\|_{L^1} =: \bar{c}, \end{aligned}$$

that is,

$$|q(t)| > e^{-\bar{c}},$$

and ii) is also proved in this case.

iii) Let $q(t)$ be a T -periodic solution of (11.2.1). Choosing $t_0 \in [0, T]$ such that $q'(t_0) = 0$ and using the mean value theorem, we have

$$\frac{q'(t)}{\sqrt{1 - (q'(t))^2}} = \int_{t_0}^t \left(\frac{q'(s)}{\sqrt{1 - (q'(s))^2}} \right)' ds$$

Taking again $v = 1$ as test function in (11.2.1) (as in item i)) we deduce that

$$\frac{q'(t)}{\sqrt{1 - (q'(t))^2}} = \int_{t_0}^t (-q(s) + g_\lambda(q(s)) + h_\lambda(s)) ds,$$

and item iii) holds true by i) and ii) with $M = T \max_{c < |s| < C} (|s| + |G'(s)| + \frac{c_0}{|s|^2}) + \|h\|_{L^1}$. \square

Remark 11.7. Observe that, unlike in [107], in our setting we have no conditions on \bar{h} to get the upper bound of case i) in the previous lemma.

We prove our main result.

Theorem 11.4. *If $h \in L^1(0, T)$ and the function G defined in $\mathbb{R} \setminus \{0\}$ satisfies assumptions (G_∞) and (\tilde{G}_0) , then problem (11.0.1) admits at least one T -periodic solution.*

Proof. We define the open bounded subset Ω in X as

$$\Omega := \{x = (q, p) \in X : c < |q(t)| < C, |p(t)| < M, \forall t \in [0, T]\},$$

which, by Lemma 11.3, contains each T -periodic solution of system (11.2.2). The proof will be concluded by applying Theorem 11.3 if we show that

$$\deg_B(f_0, \Omega \cap \mathbb{R}^2, 0) \neq 0,$$

where $\Omega \cap \mathbb{R}^2$ stands for the identification with constants functions and $f_0 \in C^\infty(\Omega \cap \mathbb{R}^2)$ is given by

$$f_0(x) = f_0(t, x) = f_0(t, (q, p)) = \left(\frac{p}{\sqrt{1 + p^2}}, -q + \frac{c_0}{q|q|} \right).$$

To compute this degree we observe that

$$\det \text{Jac} f_0(x) = (1 + p^2)^{-3/2} \left(-1 - \frac{2c_0}{|q|^3} \right).$$

and that the only zeroes of $f_0(x)$ are $(\pm \sqrt[3]{c_0}, 0)$ and we apply the additivity property of the degree to infer that

$$\deg_B(f_0, \Omega \cap \mathbb{R}^2, 0) = \det \text{Jac} f_0(\sqrt[3]{c_0}, 0) + \det \text{Jac} f_0(-\sqrt[3]{c_0}, 0) = -6 \neq 0,$$

and the proof is concluded. □

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